

MASSIVE BLACK HOLE BINARIES IN GASEOUS ENVIRONMENTS

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PAGE III SHOWS A BLACK HOLE BINARY EMBEDDED IN A CIRCUMBINARY ACCRETION DISC WHICH WAS COUNTERROTATING WITH THE BINARY. AT THIS STAGE OF THE SIMULATION THE ECCENTRICITY HAS REACHED A CRITICAL VALUE WHERE THE BINARY STARTS TO ALIGN ITS ANGULAR MOMENTUM VECTOR WITH THAT OF THE DISC. DUE TO THE CONSERVATION OF ANGULAR MOMENTUM THE INNER PART OF THE ORIGINALLY CO-PLANAR ACCRETION DISC DISTORTS AND IS INCLINED TOWARDS THE BINARY. (FOR DISCUSSION OF THIS EFFECT, SEE § 5)

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ABSTRACT

This thesis explores theoretical astrophysics of massive, sub-parsec *black hole binaries* (BHBs) in a gaseous environment with an additional focus on identifying potential multimessenger signatures.

First, the context of massive and supermassive BHBs in cosmological structure formation is given and observational techniques both for *electromagnetic* (EM) and *gravitational waves* (GW) are outlined. Then, the numerical methods of (i) Newtonian *smoothed particle hydrodynamics* (SPH) and (ii) thermal, optically thick *general relativistic radiation hydrodynamics* (GR-RHD) are detailed.

In the case of the GR-RHD formulation, in which stiff source terms arise, a dedicated numerical treatment in form of an *implicit explicit* (IMEX) Runge-Kutta time integrator is shown. This IMEX scheme is implemented, validated and tested in two GR codes with the aim that, once publicly released, it will be useful for the community. Also to this end, the physical limitations of the current framework's applicability are explored finding that the inclusion of radiation gives order of magnitude improvements over evolutions without radiation *even* in situations where parts of the underlying assumptions are violated. The remaining shortcomings are discussed and strategies for future improvement are listed. The astrophysical accretion scenarios employed are transonic spherical accretion and sub- and supersonic Bondi-Hoyle-Lyttleton accretion onto a single black hole of galactic size.

The secular dynamics of massive BHBs in self gravitating circumbinary accretion discs is studied at the evolutionary stage where the binary has already excavated a cavity inside the disc. Starting with prograde binary-disc systems, the torques coming from the disc-gravity and from accretion are dissected into components in both space and frequency. Alternative treatments of the thermodynamics inside the cavity are tested to check the sensitivity of the numerical results towards such idealised treatments. It is explained why there is a limiting eccentricity ϵ_{crit} , which a BHB attains during disc migration, whose existence is independent of the thermodynamical treatment of the cavity gas and independent of accretion torques.

Ongoing work on BHBs in retrograde, self gravitating discs is presented hinting at the existence of yet another limiting eccentricity: an instability is observed where the BHB instead of growing maximally eccentric to $\epsilon \sim 1$, starts tilting with respect to its disc and the angular momentum vectors of the BHB *and* the disc subsequently align.

Focussing on the observational implications of the prograde disc scenario, the residual eccentricity at band-entrance of *LISA* is calculated and found to be non-negligible. Furthermore, the expected differences in eccentricity populations produced by stellar and gaseous environments is estimated finding that eccentricity can be used together with expected spin populations as a discriminant between the two environmental histories of BHBs that are detected via GWs only.

For Pulsar Timing sources, analogous calculations are presented and moreover, co-incident electromagnetic counterparts in the X-ray are identified as realistically detectable with current and upcoming X-ray facilities. Specifically, periodic variability stemming from the highly eccentric BHB could be observed by MAXI or eROSITA, whereas a significant detection of double $\text{Fe}K\alpha$ lines requires an *Athena* like X-ray spectrometer.

These results have impact on low frequency GW data analysis, on searches for supermassive BHBs, on the development of more realistic numerical treatments of relativistic accretion flows and some of the results on secular evolution of binaries in discs could possibly be applied to stellar and planetary migration astrophysics.

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GLOSSARY

β	cooling parameter for SPH	\mathbf{v}	velocity vector
\dot{m}	Accretion rate in Eddington units	h_{Pl}	Planck constant
ε	gravitational softening	a	BHB semi-major axis
η	radiative efficiency	AU	Astronomical Unit
γ	adiabatic index	\mathcal{AV}	artificial viscosity
κ	opacity	c	speed of light
λ_{Debye}	Debye length	\mathcal{C}_{CFL}	CFL factor
\mathcal{L}	Lagrangian functional	e	electron charge
\mathcal{Q}	heat	ϵ	BHB eccentricity
\mathfrak{M}	Chirp mass	G	Newton's gravitational constant
\mathcal{S}	spectral index	GHz	Giga Hertz
Ω	Keplerian frequency	Hz	Hertz
ρ	density	i	BHB inclination
Σ	surface density	k_{b}	Boltzmann constant
σ	cross-section (context)	keV	kilo electron Volt
σ	significance level (context)	kpc	kilo parsec
σ	velocity dispersion (context)	\mathcal{M}	Mach number
τ	optical depth (GR-RHD context)	mas	milli arc seconds
τ	timescale (context)	mHz	milli Hertz
dV	Volume element	Mpc	Mega parsec
dA	area element	nHz	nano Hertz
a	BH spin parameter	pc	parsec
c_s	sound speed	$\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$	self gravity
D	substantial derivative	yr	year
E	energy	AGN	active galactic nuclei
e	specific internal energy	BHB	black hole binary
g	plasma parameter	BHBs	black hole binaries
H	disc scale height	BLR	broad line region
h	gas enthalpy (GR-RHD context)	CFL	Courant Friedrich Lewy
h	hydrodynamical smoothing	EM	electromagnetic
m	particle mass	EoS	Equation of State
n	number density	FAP	False Alarm Probability
P	scalar pressure	FWHM	full width at half maximum
Q	Toomre parameter	GR-HD	general relativistic hydrodynamics
q	mass ratio of the BHB	GR-HD	general relativistic hydrodynamics
T	Temperature	GR-RHD	general relativistic radiation hydrodynamics
z	redshift	GW	gravitational wave
\mathbf{K}	force vector	ISCO	innermost stable circular orbit
\mathbf{L}	angular momentum vector	LISA	Laser Interferometer Space Antenna
\mathbf{p}	momentum vector	LOSVD	line of sight velocity distribution
\mathbf{r}	position vector	LTE	local thermal equilibrium
\mathbf{T}	torque vector	MBH	massive black hole
		MRI	magneto rotational instability
		NIR	near infra red
		PTA	Pulsar Timing Array
		RL	Roche lobe
		SDSS	Sloan Digital Sky Survey
		SKA	square kilometre array
		SMBH	supermassive black hole
		SNR	signal to noise ratio
		SPH	Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics
		ToA	time of arrival
		UV	ultraviolet
		VIZ	visual, optical
		VLBA	Very Long Baseline Array
		VLT	Very Large Telescope

PREFACE

Gaining a better understanding of the observational features of black holes and black hole binaries has been a long standing focus of high-energy and gravitational astrophysics. Black holes are commonly believed to be the only viable source of the extremely energetic phenomena occurring in the nuclei of massive galaxies, the so-termed *active galactic nuclei* (AGN). Multiwavelength studies from radio to γ -rays are being routinely performed on these AGN, hoping to shed light on the precise mechanisms at play. However, all *electromagnetic* (EM) radiation, due to its very nature, suffers from strong absorption and re-processing on its way from the emission within the distant galaxy to the observation on Earth. This, in combination with the fact that the wavelength of the photons naturally puts a limit on the smallest resolvable area on the Sky, greatly impedes the direct observation of the very cores of AGN. It is the task of the theorist to model both emission mechanisms and transfer processes in order to provide a correct interpretation of the observational data. However, even with the hope of ever better telescopes, direct imaging of black holes within their environment seems infeasible via photons only; with the exception of the two closest massive black holes whose silhouette might be imaged using radio interferometry. It is thus that much hope lies with another kind of telescopes that rely on "hearing" rather than on imaging: the *gravitational wave* (GW) observatories. Whenever charges are accelerated, light waves are emitted that travel through spacetime. This analogously holds true for accelerated mass: with the two distinct differences that (i) gravitational waves do not travel *through* spacetime, but are distortions of spacetime itself and thus travel *within* spacetime and (ii) there exists no negative mass making gravitational radiation quadrupolar at lowest order, i.e. there is no gravitational dipole.

motivation

Having said this and with the onset of the era of gravitational wave astronomy in mind, it is expected that heavy binaries of comparable mass will be the GW-loudest sources that there are in the Universe; in fact, a merger of two supermassive black holes emits more power in GWs during a few minutes than the entire Universe emits in light during the same time interval. These loud sources would, in principle, be the easiest to detect¹ but full parameter estimation remains challenging. Key questions arise such as: "Which parameters are of astrophysical interest?" "What absolute level of accuracy is useful?" "How can parameter degeneracies be broken?" "What is the physical uncertainty in the templates used for matched filtering?" and many more. For GW detectors, it is important to have good estimates on event rates, source parameters and signal properties. Some statistics of these parameters are inevitably influenced by the formation and evolution

¹ The paramount effort of building a sufficiently sensitive detector notwithstanding

of the binaries within their environments. Thus, understanding the various stages of binary evolution in a cosmological context is necessary in order to predict expected signal properties for the detectors on the one side. On the other side, only with the knowledge of how much astrophysics is imprinted on the GW signals will it be feasible to reconstruct exactly this information out of the signals once detected. This then allows for tests of various competing models of e.g. structure formation, galactic evolution, black hole growth and feedback etc.

main objectives The thesis thus targets two of the key holes in the current understanding of massive black holes interacting with their environment:

1. the secular evolution of a binary system within a regime lacking dominance of any strong astrophysical effect, i.e. the transition regime where dynamical friction is *no longer* and gravitational radiation is *not yet* effective
2. the dynamical importance of radiation transfer within accretion flows

structure of the thesis This thesis addresses the problem of modelling massive black holes binaries starting from an astronomical separation of less than a parsec, hereafter ``sub-pc."

The thesis is divided in two parts.

The first part comprises three chapters where I present an overview over both the relevant physics and methods employed within this thesis. I have tried to write each Chapter, Section and Subsection as much as possible as stand-alone. This means, that the same concept might be introduced and treated several times depending on the context. References to the dedicated Section are given when a quantity is used before its time. This is aimed at allowing to skip the tedious, technical Sections unless they are of particular interest.

Chapter 1 Chapter 1 starts with illustrating the current understanding of the role of massive black hole binaries within the cosmological framework of hierarchical structure formation. It then very briefly outlines the underlying theory of single black holes within the framework of *general relativity* (GR) as far as used in this thesis. Further, it introduces key concepts of accretion disc theory and gives an overview of the different stages and physical regimes of merging massive binary black holes.

Chapter 2 Chapter 2 concerns the observational side of black hole binary astrophysics. It summarizes the observational status of black hole detections and highlights the key difficulties. It sketches the basic concepts of modern astronomy relevant for black hole observations: black hole mass estimates, reverberation mapping, X-ray spectroscopy, multiwavelength campaigns and variability searches. It also briefly introduces the concept of low-frequency gravitational wave interferometry in space, having in mind the *eLISA/NGO* instrument and GW detection via Timing analysis of radio signal stemming from milli-second pulsars, the *Pulsar Timing Arrays (PTA)*. It concludes with an illustration of the prospective benefits of what is commonly referred to as *Multimessenger Astronomy*, namely the combination and correlation of GW and EM signals aimed at extracting maximal information out of the complementary observational techniques.

Chapter 3 Chapter 3 contains a detailed description of the (numerical) methods used. It first introduces the fluid equations and then elaborates on two numerical implementations of solving them: (i) The Newtonian code *GADGET-2* is described as it is modified from its publicly available version and some test cases specific to the problem addressed in

this thesis are shown. (ii) The general relativistic code ECHO is introduced, and the implementation of radiation in the optically thick regime, accompanied by the necessary improvement of the time-stepping algorithm is given in detail and several verification tests are presented.

Each Section concludes with a short statement of caveats and advantages of each approach.

So far I will have outlined the context of massive black hole binaries in astrophysical relativity and motivated the study of their interaction with gas at small scales. The tools employed for the study of both the Newtonian and the general relativistic regime have been introduced and their applicability shown.

Summary: Part I

This ends the first part of the thesis.

The second part consists of four chapters where the results of the thesis are described in an astrophysical context.

In Chapter 4 the secular evolution of black hole binaries in prograde self gravitating gaseous discs is discussed. This Chapter forms the longest part of the thesis as it studies (i) the origin of the secular evolution by dissecting the torques coming from different parts of the accretion disc (cf. § 4.1) and the influence of prescribing two different equations of state for the fluid close to the black holes, (ii) the existence of a limiting eccentricity in prograde discs (cf. § 4.2) and (iii) a model of what could be the very final state before the binary decouples from its disc and merges.

Chapter 4

After the study of prograde discs, this Chapter 5 now explores the possibility of having black hole binaries in retrograde self gravitating gaseous discs. It is compared how the secular evolution differs from that of the prograde case and there is some preliminary evidence that binaries in retrograde discs can be unstable to out-of-plane perturbations as it is found that the angular momentum vectors align after the black hole binary has reached a critical eccentricity. Caveats and uncertainties with respect to the reliability of the numerical scheme are discussed and some comparison with older work is shown.

Chapter 5

This Chapter 6 finally explores the observational implications both for EM and GW measurements that the previously found limiting eccentricity may have. For a *LISA* type experiment, the residual eccentricity in the detector window is estimated. Furthermore, it compares the expected eccentricity distributions for massive and supermassive sources for gaseous and stellar environments in the context of *eLISA/NGO* and *PTA* observations. At last, the possibility of detecting multi-messenger signals for supermassive sources in the *PTA* regime is explored.

Chapter 6

Departing from Newtonian dynamics of binaries, Chapter 7 describes the effect of including radiation pressure in accretion streams onto single black holes using general relativistic simulations. The effect of coupling of hydrodynamics to optically thick radiation is depicted using the example of Bondi-Hoyle-Littleton accretion in two dimensions. I compare several sub-sonic and super-sonic accretion flows in their evolution with and without the inclusion of the radiation field. Additionally, a comparison of an alternative equation of state is performed in order to compare luminosity estimates priorly used in literature in the context of predicting lightcurves from merging black hole binaries.

Chapter 7

At last, the summary of the thesis is presented in Chapter 8.

Summary

Notation and units

The abbreviations and notation used within this thesis are listed in the glossary on page [XI](#). Units are given in cgs, unless otherwise stated (the primary exceptions are Chapter § [3.2](#) and Chapter [7](#) which concern themselves with general relativity and thus use natural units). Vectorial quantities are denoted in boldface throughout. I assume a signature $(-, +, +, +)$ for the spacetime metric and will use Greek letters (running from 0 to 3) for four-dimensional spacetime tensor components, while Latin letters (running from 1 to 3) will be employed for three-dimensional spatial tensor components.

Potsdam, Germany, July 1, 2012
C.R.

published results

Some of the material of this thesis has already been submitted to or published in refereed journals, all of which is available on the arXiv:

- Constanze Roedig, Alberto Sesana, Massimo Dotti, Jorge Cuadra, Pau Amaro-Seoane and Francesco Haardt, *Evolution of binary black holes in self gravitating discs: dissecting the torques*, arXiv:1202.6063
- Constanze Roedig, Massimo Dotti, Alberto Sesana, Jorge Cuadra, Monica Colpi, *Limiting eccentricity of sub-pc massive black hole binaries surrounded by self-gravitating gas discs*, *MNRAS*, Volume 415, Issue 4, pp. 3033-3041, arXiv:1104.3868
- Alberto Sesana, Constanze Roedig, Mark T. Reynolds, Massimo Dotti, *Multimessenger astronomy with pulsar timing and X-ray observations of massive black hole binaries*, *MNRAS*, Volume 420, Issue 1, pp. 860-877, arXiv:1107.2927S
- Constanze Roedig and Alberto Sesana, *Origin and Implications of high eccentricities in massive black hole binaries at sub-pc scales*, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Volume 363, Issue 1, pp. 012035, arXiv:1111.3742
- Olindo Zanotti, Constanze Roedig, Luciano Rezzolla, Luca Del Zanna, *General relativistic radiation hydrodynamics of accretion flows. I: Bondi-Hoyle accretion*, *MNRAS*, Volume 417, Issue 4, pp. 2899-2915, arXiv:1105.5615
- Constanze Roedig, Olindo Zanotti, Daniela Alic *General relativistic radiation hydrodynamics of accretion flows. II: Treating stiff source terms and exploring physical limitations*, arXiv:1206.6662

ASTROPHYSICAL CONTEXT AND METHODS

ASTROPHYSICS OF MASSIVE BLACK HOLE BINARIES:

THE THEORETICAL SIDE

In the currently favoured hierarchical framework of structure formation (White & Rees, 1978), galaxies evolve through a complex sequence of merger and accretion events, and the existence of *massive black holes* (MBHs) at their centres is nowadays a well established observational fact (see Chapter 2). The growing interest in Keplerian massive *black hole binaries* (BHBs) residing in galactic nuclei has a twofold nature. From the observational side, it is crucial to understand the interplay of BHBs with their dense (stellar and gaseous) environment to predict robust signatures that may allow their identification. From the theoretical side, it is still unclear how the cavity between two well understood stages (cf. § 1.1) of BHB evolution is bridged: (i) the dynamical friction driven stage, when the two BHs spiral in the merger remnant centre down to pc separations and (ii) the final inspiral driven by *gravitational waves* (GWs), which become efficient when the two BHs are at a separation $\lesssim 10^{-2}$ pc.

This Chapter will introduce the key concepts from the theoretical side: starting at very early and very large scales, the current understanding of structure formation is outlined and the place binary black holes have therein. Going to smaller scales, I will sketch some basics of accretion disc theory as far as it is necessary for this thesis in § 1.2. Leaving the Newtonian regime, the last Section 1.3 will introduce black holes as objects of general relativity.

1.1 Hierarchical structure formation

Starting out in the early universe, in the epoch after photons freeze out during recombination, matter (that is Dark and baryonic matter) is not distributed homogeneously throughout the Universe, but with small over- and underdensities. This fact, we know from high precision observations of the cosmic microwave background (e.g. WMAP (Larson et al., 2011)). As the expansion of the Universe proceeds small substructures grow and gradually accumulate matter in ever deeper gravitational wells until these substructures finally decouple from the Hubble flow. The latter happens when the overdensity starts collapsing under selfgravity and virializes into a halo structure. First, the halos are small but they keep on accreting surrounding matter and they merge with surrounding other halos and thus ever larger and fewer halos form. This process is known as hierarchical clustering.

This halo growth can be described in a statistical fashion (Press & Schechter, 1974), so that at any redshift z a certain overdensity can be identified with a characteristic mass of

hierarchical
clustering

a collapsing halo (Barkana & Loeb, 2001). So generally, there are few heavy objects which harbour the earliest halos and many lighter objects that are relatively young.

The end of the dark ages is finally come, when the baryonic portion of a halo reaches the Jeans criterion and subsequently overcomes the thermal pressure and collapses to a proto-Galaxy. What ensues is the formation of the first stars, which depending on the chemical composition may be very inefficient, because primordial gas is basically metal free. Details of the micro and macro physics involved are not well understood, but as far as black holes (BH) are concerned, there have been three mechanisms suggested that would take place around or after this point (see Volonteri, 2010; Sesana, 2012, for reviews and references therein):

BH seeds

(i) *Population III remnants*: In the absence of metals, leftover H_2 that has not photo-dissociated, can present an effective coolant in $\sim 10^6 M_\odot$ halos at $z \approx 30$. Collapse in this case is subsonic thus no fragmentation occurs and a massive star $M > 100 M_\odot$ is formed. Poorly understood details of late stages of these hypermassive stars could lead to a direct collapse to a BH of a mass much less than the initial star (e.g. Madau & Rees, 2001; Heger et al., 2003).

(ii) *Direct collapse*: Slightly similar to the above, it might be possible to directly collapse gas within an enormous halo $\gtrsim 10^8 M_\odot$ into a black hole. The dominant cooling process here is line cooling at $\sim 8000K$ which leads to an isothermal, fragmentation-free collapse (see Sesana, 2012, for a summary of the details). However, it also requires the absence of H_2 cooling, a condition not straightforward to obtain (e.g. Dijkstra et al., 2008). During collapse of such a big structure it might additionally be expected that the gas is not entirely at rest with respect to the centre of mass, thus in absence of angular momentum transport collapse will halt. If any such rotationally supported structure should form, typical instabilities such as "bars within bars" (e.g. Shlosman et al., 1989) are invoked to provide efficient transport of angular momentum. Also transport in discs (as will be discussed in some detail but different context later) via local instability is a possible option. Numerical results have shown that masses of the order $\gtrsim 10^6 M_\odot$ can accumulate in the centre, which are then expected to eventually collapse to a Kerr black hole. How much of the initial central mass is lost during this last stage, because of e.g. winds, remains unclear. Still, this process, is the one that produces the heaviest seeds $\gtrsim 10^4 M_\odot$ at redshifts $z \lesssim 12$.

(iii) *Runaway stellar dynamics*: At high redshift, there is one more process that could lead to seed black hole formation: Stellar clusters can undergo core collapse if stars that are strongly bound become ever more strongly bound at the expense of loosely bound stars that are released from the cluster. This evaporation like effect increases the central density of the cluster progressively until stars start disrupting each other forming a massive central star which again can collapse to a black hole eventually. Whether or not this mechanism can be effective is dependent on the mass spectrum of the cluster and the metal content of the gas bound in the stars. Typical masses of the resulting seed black hole are expected to be in the range: $10^2 M_\odot \lesssim M_{\text{BH}} \lesssim 10^4 M_\odot$ (e.g. Begelman & Rees, 1978; Devecchi & Volonteri, 2009).

BH growth

Having identified several possibilities for forming seeds, it is still necessary to "feed" the black holes to grow them so they fit the currently observed mass spectrum. The most massive black holes known today (cf. Chapter 2) are heavier than $\gtrsim 10^6 M_\odot$, some exceeding $M_{\text{BH}} \gtrsim 10^9 M_\odot$ ¹. In principle, massive BHs can feed in three ways (cf. Sesana, 2012):

¹ As a side note, it may be mentioned that astrophysical black holes never evaporate due to Hawking radiation to any significant degree and thus can only gain, never lose, mass

- They can merge with other MBHs
- They can disrupt and subsequently accrete small compact objects, stars and gas clouds
- They can accrete from large discs surrounding them following galaxy mergers or supplied via intragalactic filaments

Due to evidence of few, very massive BHs at high redshift $z \approx 7$ (Fan et al., 2006; Jiang et al., 2008; Willott et al., 2010), the process of mass growth must be quite rapid. If only mergers between MBHs amongst each other are considered, it follows an extremely and unrealistically high merger rate in order to produce BHs $\gtrsim 10^9 M_\odot$ at $z \gtrsim 7$.

complication: very massive BH at high redshift

Coherent accretion from a large disc provides means of rapid mass growth; however, coherent accretion also implies the increase of the BH spin due to conservation of angular momentum. When the spin a of the BH is increased, however, the radiative efficiency η is increased, which is why the amount of mass that can accrete at Eddington luminosity is significantly suppressed. The challenge for theorists in producing MBH evolution models is to match the observed luminosity function of quasars. Since merging alone cannot provide nearly enough mass growth and invoking accretion at rate \dot{M} implies an observed luminosity $L = \dot{M}\eta c^2 / (f_{\text{bol}}(1 - \eta))$ ¹ combined with a spin-up that increases η , some radiatively inefficient accretion flows need to be considered for those supermassive BH at high redshift. How precisely this can be achieved still remains an open problem.

Putting these few problematic objects aside for the moment, the general, successful picture of MBH evolution is that of a tree-like merging of galaxies where each merger entails the migration of the massive, central BHs to the new common centre thereby disturbing and funnelling parts of the galactic gas and/or stars in their wake towards an accumulation around themselves in a large, cold circumnuclear disc and/or a dense distribution of stars.

As first described in Begelman et al. (1980), the migration of black holes during and after a galaxy merger may be divided into three stages:

the three stages of MBH migration

1. *The dynamical friction stage:* The first and rather well understood stage is when both black holes are very far apart and each feels only the diffuse gravitational pull of the new *center of mass* (CoM) of the newly formed galaxy. While both BHs sink towards this CoM, stars, gas and dark matter act as brakes; they are gravitationally focussed in the wake of the passing, respective BH and thus slow it down. This process is known as "dynamical friction" and its timescale is set by the density of the ambient background. Neglecting self-gravity of the background and assuming a purely collisionless background (i.e. only stars and dark matter) of uniform density ρ_\star and velocity dispersion σ , the force acting on the individual BH of velocity \mathbf{v} is (Chandrasekhar, 1943):

stellar backgrounds

$$^* \mathbf{K}_{\text{DF}} = -4\pi \ln(\Lambda) G^2 M_{\text{BH}}^2 \rho_\star \left[\text{erf}\left(\frac{v}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}\right) - \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{v}{\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{v^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)\right) \right] \frac{\mathbf{v}}{v^3} \quad (1.1)$$

The Coulomb logarithm encodes the non-locality of the drag $\ln(\Lambda) \approx \ln(b_{\text{max}}/b_{\text{min}})$ with the minimal impact parameter given by large angle scattering, $b_{\text{min}} = v^2/G M_{\text{BH}}$, and the maximum impact parameter being about the size of the background system (Colpi & Dotti, 2011). Eq. (1.1) clearly illustrates the braking effect the background has on the BH, but it is too simplified for a good timescale estimate, especially because the system is not collisionless. It is more adequate to describe the system statistically and

¹ f_{bol} is a bolometric correction factor

sum over all N (uncorrelated) two-body interactions using Green functions to evaluate the force (e.g. Colpi et al., 1999; Kandrup, 1981):

$$\begin{aligned} {}^*K_{\text{DF}}^i &= G^2 M_{\text{BH}}^2 \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \int d^3\mathbf{r} d^3\mathbf{p} \frac{\partial f}{\partial p^j} T^{ji} \\ &= G^2 M_{\text{BH}}^2 \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \int d^3\mathbf{r} d^3\mathbf{p} \frac{\partial f}{\partial p^j} N m_*^2 \frac{r_{\text{BH}}^j(t') - r^j}{|\mathbf{r}_{\text{BH}}(t') - \mathbf{r}|^3} \frac{r_{\text{BH}}^i(t) - r^i(t-t')}{|\mathbf{r}_{\text{BH}}(t) - \mathbf{r}(t-t')|^3} \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

Even though only linear, this approach is very powerful as it accounts for arbitrarily inhomogeneous backgrounds. A typical timescale for a massive BH to sink to the centre of an isothermal sphere with dispersion σ is about 10^8 yr:

$${}^*\tau_{\text{DF}} = 5 \times 10^8 \left(\frac{5}{\ln(M_{\text{halo}}/M_{\text{BH}})} \right) \left(\frac{r_{\text{circ}}}{300 \text{ pc}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{v_{\text{circ}}}{\sqrt{2} 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}} \right) \left(\frac{10^6 M_{\odot}}{M_{\text{BH}}} \right) \eta^{0.4} \text{ yr}. \quad (1.3)$$

gaseous
backgrounds

The situation may then be additionally complicated by the presence of gas¹, which has been dubbed the scenario of a "wet merger". First, the dynamical friction due to a homogeneous fluid of density ρ_{gas} can be written down (Colpi & Dotti, 2011):

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{DF}} = \begin{cases} -4\pi G^2 M_{\text{BH}}^2 \rho_{\text{gas}} \left(\frac{b_{\text{max}}}{b_{\text{min}}} \frac{\sqrt{\mathcal{M}^2 - 1}}{\mathcal{M}} \right) \frac{\mathbf{v}}{v^3}, & \mathcal{M} > 1 \\ -\frac{4}{3} \pi G^2 M_{\text{BH}}^2 \rho_{\text{gas}} \mathcal{M}^3 \frac{\mathbf{v}}{v^3}, & \mathcal{M} < 1 \end{cases} \quad (1.4)$$

where \mathcal{M} is the Mach number (see § 3). If the BH additionally accretes in a Bondi-Hoyle fashion (see Chapter 7 for a discussion of this kind of accretion flow), then an additional force term arises that is proportional to the accretion rate:

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{BHL}} \leq -4\pi G^2 M_{\text{BH}}^2 \frac{\rho_{\text{gas}}}{v^3 (1 + \mathcal{M}^{-2})^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (1.5)$$

Thus, for comparable ambient densities, gas dynamical friction tends to be more effective and leads to shorter timescales. However, the picture is more complicated in reality, due to non-linear effects such as self-gravity, shocks, cooling, dynamical feedback by the BHs etc, which is why the problem is typically addressed numerically.

2. *The binary hardening stage:* When the BHs reach a separation of roughly about one parsec (depending on their combined mass), they become bound to each other in a Keplerian orbit. At this point they can no longer retain their own environment, but begin to share a mutual one. In the case of a stellar background, this happens when the mass of stars enclosed within the binary is equal to the mass of the binary itself. Now, the interaction must be treated as a star scattering of a bound binary, i.e. a three body interaction, rather than the, much easier, two body interaction considered in the previous stage. This process is much less effective in carrying away energy and angular momentum, which led to emergence of the "last parsec problem" (Milosavljević & Merritt, 2003), which states that a binary would stall at these separations because it does not have enough stars to interact with within a Hubble

¹ The presence of gas is optional, e.g. it might not play any role in gas poor environments such as giant ellipticals

BHs form a bound
binary

time. Later studies were able to solve this problem by using rotating and triaxial stellar background distributions (Khan et al., 2011; Preto et al., 2011; Gualandris & Merritt, 2012), which are expected to form naturally from galaxy mergers (Berczik et al., 2006). In the case of a gaseous disc, the pairing occurs when the enclosed disc mass equals that of the binary. The transition is often accompanied by the excavation of a central low density region, the so-called "cavity"¹.

3. *The gravitational wave stage:* At a separation of $\lesssim 10^{-2}$ pc the BH evolution is completely dominated by the emission of gravitational waves and from here onwards there is no doubt that the binary will coalesce. The orbit, if it was eccentric will circularize during the inspiral and the semi-major axis will shrink. The evolution of the orbital elements can be calculated with *Post-Newtonian* (PN) equation of motion using expansions of a certain order. PN holds well for roughly equal mass binaries up to shortly before the final merger itself (e.g. Futamase & Itoh, 2007).

As mentioned above, MBHB are expected to live in either stellar and/or gaseous environments. So far the two environments cannot be treated fully coupled, but on their own both dense stellar systems and gaseous discs have been shown to be effective in extracting the binary energy and angular momentum (see, e.g., Escala et al., 2005; Dotti et al., 2007; Cuadra et al., 2009; Khan et al., 2011; Preto et al., 2011), possibly driving the system to final coalescence (an extensive discussion on the fate of sub-parsec BHBs can be found in Dotti et al., 2012). Scenarios involving cold gas are particular appealing not only because they might produce distinctive observational signatures, but also because cold gas dominates the baryon content in most galaxies at redshifts higher than one, providing a natural reservoir of energy and angular momentum to drive the BHB towards coalescence. As the gaseous and stellar mass content inside the BH orbit continues to decrease in response to the hardening of the binary, further inspiral is believed to be controlled by the action of either three-body scattering of individual stars and/or the interaction of the binary with a circumbinary gaseous disc (e.g. Merritt & Milosavljević, 2005; Armitage & Natarajan, 2002).

general BHB evolution in stellar or gaseous environments

Numerical simulations of wet mergers (e.g., Mihos & Hernquist, 1996; Mayer et al., 2007) have led to the following picture for the post merger evolution. Cold gas is funnelled to the central ≈ 100 parsecs by gravitational instabilities, where it forms a puffed, rotationally supported circumnuclear disc. Disc like structures are actually observed in ULIRGs which are thought to be gas rich post-merger star-forming galaxies (e.g., Sanders & Mirabel, 1996; Downes & Solomon, 1998; Davies et al., 2004a,b; Greve et al., 2009). The circumnuclear disc retains memory of the angular momentum of the galaxy orbit and will settle in the merger orbital plane. The two nuclear BHs will settle on the same plane and will efficiently spiral to sub- pc scales owing to dynamical friction against the massive circumnuclear disc (Dotti et al., 2007), eventually opening a cavity (or hollow) in the gas distribution (Goldreich & Tremaine, 1980; Artymowicz & Lubow, 1996). The subsequent evolution of the system is determined by the efficiency of energy and angular momentum transfer between the BHB and its outer circumbinary disc.

specification to gaseous environments

The following discussion will now focus on the details used in this thesis, on how BHB population statistics can be obtained and how we assume to couple the three evolutionary stages together.

specific population models used

¹ Assuming not too unequal mass binaries and a thin disc

1.1.1 Cosmological coalescence rate

supermassive
catalogues

In the following paragraph, I outline how the merger or coalescence rates for MBHBs are obtained: To construct the SMBHB cosmological coalescence rate, the procedure described in [Sesana et al. \(2009\)](#), § 2 is followed: In few words, catalogues of merging galaxies are extracted from the semi-analytical model of [Bertone et al. \(2007\)](#) applied to the Millennium run ([Springel et al., 2005](#)). Then a central MBH is associated with each merging galaxy in the constructed catalogue. Adopting the recent fit to the $M - \sigma$ relation given by [Gültekin et al. \(2009\)](#) (cf. Chapter 2), and considering accretion to be efficient onto both MBHBs *before* the final coalescence of the binary allows to obtain a catalogue of all the mergers occurring in the $(500/h \text{ Mpc})^3$ comoving volume of the simulation, labelled by MBH masses and redshift. From this, the cosmic merger rate, $d^4N/(dM_1 dM_2 dz dt_r)$, is numerically generated by weighting each event with the observable comoving volume shell at every redshift. We use these catalogues for studying Pulsar Timing sources in Chapter 6.

When we talk about potentially distinctive electromagnetic signatures, we require all MBHBs to evolve in geometrically thin discs. Although adhoc, we find that most of the merging galaxy pairs extracted from the Millennium run involve at least one massive, gas rich, spiral galaxy. Significant inflows of cold gas are therefore expected in the remnant nuclei ([Mihos & Hernquist, 1996](#)), feeding the circumbinary disc.

massive catalogues

For constructing coalescence rates for MBHBs, a different route is taken because the Millennium run does not yet provide the mass resolution for $M_{\text{BH}} < 10^7 M_{\odot}$: Here we use the population of merging MBHBs predicted by a standard MBH cosmic evolution model where MBHBs grow by merger and accretion. As BH seeds, the light remnants of PopIII stars [Madau & Rees \(2001\)](#) (see item (i) above in § 1.1) are assumed. To be specific, the model "LE" from [Arun et al. \(2009\)](#) is used. It should be stressed here that in this model, MBHBs were assumed to instantly coalesce after a dynamical friction timescale from the pairing of the two galaxies hosting the two MBHBs: none of the dynamical evolution models is implemented self consistently in deriving the MBHB population. We therefore end up with a single MBHB population to which we can apply different dynamical evolution models a posteriori. These are used in Chapter 6 for *eLISA/NGO* sources.

1.1.2 MBH binaries in stellar environment

This paragraph introduces the timescales and physics playing a role for BHB evolution in a stellar background. Combined with the next paragraph 1.1.3, this will contain all that is necessary for a posteriori coupling a single MBHB population to assumed dynamical models.

In dense stellar environments, the MBHB evolution is basically driven by three body interactions with individual stars ([Mikkola & Valtonen, 1992](#); [Quinlan, 1996](#); [Sesana et al., 2006](#); [Sesana, 2010](#)). To get a sense of the general picture, it is useful to consider the interactions between the stars and the binary one by one, as uncorrelated events, even though secular effects may also play a role (see, e.g., [Meiron & Laor \(2011\)](#)). At the moment of pairing at sub-pc separations, the MBHB is expected to be surrounded by a dense stellar distribution of stars. If a is the MBHB semimajor axis, three body interactions with stars approaching the binary centre of mass within a result in superelastic scattering, usually followed by the ejection of the stars. These stars carry away energy and angular momentum, causing the binary to shrink. The efficiency of this mechanism depends on several environmental factors, such as the details of the stellar distribution and the

effectiveness of relaxation mechanisms. In this thesis, the interest is on the evolution of eccentricity and semimajor axis.

Assessing the eccentricity evolution is not straightforward, because it depends on a combination of energy (E) and angular momentum (L) exchange during the scattering: $\Delta\epsilon \propto c_i\Delta E + c_j\Delta L$, where the two c coefficients depend on the property of the MBHB. Let us consider, for simplicity, a bound star orbiting the MBHB at a given semimajor axis a_* . The orbital energy that can be extracted in the scattering is $\propto a_*^{-1}$, whereas the angular momentum of the orbit is proportional to $\sqrt{a_*}$. It follows that $\Delta\epsilon \propto -c_i a_*^{-1} + c_j \sqrt{a_*}$ (Sesana et al., 2008). If a_* is small enough, then the first term dominates and the binary circularizes; vice versa, if a_* is large enough, then the second term dominates, and the binary eccentricity grows. This behaviour has to be expected, since stars with large a_* have large angular momentum but just little energy, and the opposite is true for stars with small a_* . It turns out that the transition point is at $a_* \approx a$, i.e., stars within the binary orbit on average promote circularisation, whereas stars outside the binary orbit make the binary grow eccentric. Heuristically this can be interpreted as follows. Let us consider a MBHB with $M_2 \ll M_1$ and a given non-zero eccentricity. Such a binary spends most of its period near its apocenter, so in the case $a_* > a$ the probability of a close star-binary encounter (and subsequent star ejection) is maximal there. In the unequal mass case, the star is ejected following a series of close encounters with M_2 . In such interactions the star gets a small 'kick' and the velocity of M_2 decreases. As this velocity is perpendicular to the MBH position vector close to the apocenter, the secondary is forced on a more radial orbit. On the contrary, a star with $a_* < a$ "feels" the secondary hole when this approaches the primary at a distance $< a$. At that point, the interaction with the star is unlikely to occur close to the pericenter of the MBHB orbit (because the time spent by the binary at the pericenter is very small), and typically also extracts a large radial component from the velocity of the secondary black hole, hence causing circularisation. Considering the collective effect of the stellar distribution, the evolution of the orbital eccentricity is therefore governed by the relative weight of stars inside and outside a . The steeper is the stellar cusp, the less effective is the eccentricity growth. As a general trend, quasi circular-equal mass MBHBs experience just a mild eccentricity growth, while systems which are already eccentric at the moment of pairing, or with mass ratio significantly lower than 1, can evolve up to $\epsilon > 0.9$ (Sesana, 2010). Such a trend has been observed in several numerical studies (Milosavljević & Merritt, 2001a; Merritt et al., 2007; Matsubayashi et al., 2007; Amaro-Seoane et al., 2009).

The above argument is strictly valid for isotropic stellar distributions. The evolution of the binary eccentricity can be extremely different for non isotropic systems. For example, Sesana et al. (2011) demonstrated that in a rotating stellar system, the eccentricity evolution of unequal MBHBs is dramatically affected by the level of co/counter rotation of the stellar distribution with respect to the binary, with corotating distributions promoting circularisation rather than eccentricity growth. This is because, as a simple consequence of angular momentum conservation during the ejection process, stars counterrotating with the binary tend to extract a lot of angular momentum from the MBHB, causing the eccentricity growth, whereas corotating stars do not. Nonetheless, most of the simulations involving rotating bulges (Berczik et al., 2006; Berentzen et al., 2009), or merging systems (Khan et al., 2011; Preto et al., 2011) find quite eccentric binaries at the moment of pairing (ranging from 0.4 to 0.8), and the subsequent evolution leads to a general eccentricity growth, in good agreement of what predicted for an isotropic stellar distribution. This may be because the binary evolution is mostly driven by loss cone refilling of unbound stars on almost radial orbits, with negligible initial angular momentum. On the other hand, Gualandris & Merritt (2012) find milder eccentricity evolutions, along the lines of what

3-body scattering

transition point

relative mass in-
and outside the
binarynon-isotropic
stellar
backgroundsevolution mainly
driven by loss cone
refilling?

is expected for a rotating stellar remnant. The eccentricity evolution of MBHBs in stellar environments is still a largely open issue, but a significant eccentricity seem to be a general outcome of the models.

In a star dominated system, assuming a full loss cone (Sesana, 2010) the MBHB hardening timescale is given by

time scale
estimate for stellar
environments

$$\tau_h = 2.89 \times 10^6 \text{ yr } \sigma_{100} M_8^{-1} \rho_5^{-1} \alpha_3^{-1} H_{15}^{-1}, \quad (1.6)$$

where $\sigma_{100} = \sigma/100 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ pc}^{-3}$ is the stellar velocity dispersion, $\rho_5 = \rho/10^5 M_\odot$ the stellar density at the binary influence radius (see Sesana (2010), for details) and $H_{15} = H/15$ the dimensionless hardening rate (Quinlan, 1996). Note that the combined M_8^{-1} and α_3^{-1} scaling implies that τ_h is independent on the MBHB mass. By equating τ_h to the characteristic timescale for GW inspiral, τ_{gw} Eq. (1.9), we can get the separation at which the stellar environment loses all influence and the BHB inspirals due to GWs only.

1.1.3 MBH binaries in circumbinary discs

As just done for stars, this paragraph now introduces the timescales and sub-regimes needed for describing BHB evolution in gaseous discs:

We assume that MBHBs evolve in geometrically thin circumbinary accretion discs (see next § 1.2 for details).

The gravitational interaction of the massive BH binary with the gaseous disc is believed to be of foremost importance to assess not only its observability on sub-parsec scale, but also its fate. If a viscous disc is present, Lindblad resonances can cause BH migration down to the gravitational wave (GW) inspiral domain (e.g. Goldreich & Tremaine, 1980; Papaloizou & Pringle, 1977). Following this proposal, a number of studies have modelled BH migration in Keplerian, geometrically thin α -discs (Ivanov et al., 1999; Gould & Rix, 2000; Armitage & Natarajan, 2002; Haiman et al., 2009; Lodato et al., 2009).

notation

Before entering the dynamics in detail, we define all the quantities used for describing the MBHB-disc system. The MBHB has total mass $M = M_1 + M_2$ ($M_1 > M_2$), mass ratio $q = M_1/M_2$, symmetric binary mass ratio $q_s = 4q/(1+q^2)$, semimajor axis a , rest-frame orbital Keplerian frequency $f_{k,r}$, and eccentricity e . The thin disc is described in terms of the α_{SS} viscosity parameter, the accretion rate \dot{M} and the accreted matter/radiation conversion efficiency η . As discussed at some length in Chapter 4, we define δ to be the relative size of the cavity to the binary semimajor axis, and we take a fiducial value $\delta = 2$. Expressions are given in units of $M_8 = M/10^8 M_\odot$, $\alpha_{0.3} = \alpha/0.3$, $\eta_{0.1} = \eta/0.1$ and $\dot{m}_{0.3} = \dot{m}/0.3$, where $\dot{m} = \dot{M}/\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}}$ is the accretion rate normalized to the Eddington rate¹. In the following, subscripts

Eddington limit

¹ An MBH accreting at a rate \dot{M} , generates a luminosity $L = \eta \dot{M} c^2$, where η is the radiation conversion efficiency of the accreted matter. Steady state accretion can be sustained as long as the radiation pressure exerted the photons emitted in the accretion process is smaller than the gravitational binding energy of the accreting material. If the contrary is true, radiation pressure blows away the reservoir of gas, suppressing the accretion process. The Eddington accretion rate \dot{M}_{Edd} is the maximum possible accretion rate corresponding to a luminosity (called Eddington luminosity L_{Edd}) that exactly counter-balance the gravity of the accreting material. We caution that the Eddington limit derivation assumes spherical symmetry of the accretion flow, and does not strictly hold for disc-like accretion due to fact that large fractions of the emitted photons may escape vertically without interacting with the inflowing matter. It has been, however, confirmed by observations that accretion-powered quasars shine close to this limit, and we thus take it as a robust reference value. For $\eta = 0.1$, L_{Edd} corresponds to $\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}} \approx 2.5 M_8 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

'X' to ``a'' refer to lengths given in units of $10^X R_s$ where $R_s = 2GM/c^2$ is the Schwarzschild radius associated to the total mass of the binary.

The picture we adopt for the MBHB evolution is the following. At separations relevant to this thesis ($a < 0.03$ pc), the binary has already excavated a cavity (see, e.g. [Artymowicz & Lubow, 1994](#)) in the circumbinary accretion disc. Both viscous torques exerted by the disc ([Goldreich & Tremaine, 1980](#)) and GW emission ([Peters & Mathews, 1963](#)) dissipate the binary binding energy causing its orbital decay. The secondary MBH is, in general, more massive than the local disc and the problem is analogous to secondary-dominated Type-II migration in planetary dynamics. A self-consistent solution to this problem was provided by [Syer & Clarke \(1995\)](#), (see their original paper and [Haiman et al. \(2009\)](#) and [Kocsis & Sesana \(2011\)](#) for a detailed discussion in the context of MBHB evolution). Such a solution applies only to discs with decreasing surface density as a function of the radius. Standard α -discs ([Shakura & Sunyaev, 1973](#)), with viscosity proportional to the total pressure, meet such a requirement only in the gas pressure dominated zone, but not in the inner radiation pressure dominated zone. β -discs, with viscosity proportional to the gas pressure only, fulfil this condition at all radii. We therefore assume β -discs as our fiducial disc model for describing the binary-disc migration ([Haiman et al., 2009](#)). The quantities relevant to the practical computation of the (S)MBHB population and the relevant timescales in the system are:

standard
evolutionary
picture

analytical disc
models

(i) the viscous timescale

$$\tau_v = 6.09 \times 10^5 \text{ yr } \alpha_{0.3}^{-4/5} \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{0.3}}{\eta_{0.1}} \right)^{-2/5} M_8^{6/5} \delta^{7/5} a_3^{7/5}; \quad (1.7)$$

(ii) the migration timescale

$$\tau_m = 2.09 \times 10^6 \text{ yr } \alpha_{0.3}^{-1/2} \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{0.3}}{\eta_{0.1}} \right)^{-5/8} M_8^{3/4} q_s^{3/8} \delta^{7/8} a_3^{7/8}; \quad (1.8)$$

(iii) the GW shrinking timescale

$$\tau_{\text{GW}} = 7.84 \times 10^7 \text{ yr } M_8 q_s^{-1} a_3^4 F(\epsilon)^{-1}, \quad (1.9)$$

where

$$F(\epsilon) = (1 - \epsilon^2)^{-7/2} \left(1 + \frac{73}{24} \epsilon^2 + \frac{37}{96} \epsilon^4 \right). \quad (1.10)$$

These timescales define two characteristic binary separations. Equating τ_m to τ_{gw} we get the decoupling separation

decoupling

$$a_3^{\text{dec}} = 0.31 \alpha_{0.3}^{-4/25} \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{0.3}}{\eta_{0.1}} \right)^{-1/5} M_8^{-2/25} q_s^{11/25} \delta^{7/25} F(\epsilon)^{8/25}, \quad (1.11)$$

which is the separation below which the GW driven migration is faster than the gas driven migration, and the binary evolution is dictated by GW emission only. This is the relevant separation that has to be considered when computing the frequency distribution of inspiralling MBHBs. Equating τ_v to τ_{gw} we get the 'disc freezing' (or detachment) separation

disc freezing

$$a_3^{\text{fr}} = 0.22 \alpha_{0.3}^{-4/13} \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{0.3}}{\eta_{0.1}} \right)^{-2/13} M_8^{1/13} q_s^{4/13} \delta^{7/13} F(\epsilon)^{5/13}, \quad (1.12)$$

below which the binary shrinking timescale is faster than the viscous inward diffusion of the inner edge of the disc. After this point, the disc can no longer follow the binary, and it is

basically 'frozen' during the quick subsequent inspiral leading to the MBHB coalescence. This latter characteristic radius discriminates between binaries attached to their discs and binaries detached from their discs, and it has to be considered in computing the population of 'observable systems'. In general $a^{\text{fr}} < a^{\text{dec}}$, defining three different phases relevant to our study:

three relevant phases

- phaseI, $a > a^{\text{dec}}$. The binary is coupled to the disc which regulates its dynamical evolution;
- phaseII, $a^{\text{fr}} < a < a^{\text{dec}}$. The binary is dynamically decoupled from the disc and it is driven by GW emission. However, the viscous time is short enough that the disc can follow the binary in its inspiral;
- phaseIII, $a < a^{\text{fr}}$. The binary leaves the disc behind and quickly coalesces.

As will be shown in Chapters 4, during phaseI, the binary maintains a constant limiting eccentricity given by the approximate formula:

$$\epsilon_0 \approx 0.66\sqrt{\ln\delta} - 0.65 + 0.19 \quad (1.13)$$

while, after decoupling, in phaseII and III, the eccentricity can be numerically computed by solving the implicit equation

$$\frac{f_{k,r}}{f_{\text{dec}}} = \left\{ \frac{1 - \epsilon_{\text{dec}}^2}{1 - \epsilon^2} \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_{\text{dec}}} \right)^{\frac{12}{19}} \left[\frac{1 + \frac{121}{304}\epsilon^2}{1 + \frac{121}{304}\epsilon_{\text{dec}}^2} \right]^{\frac{870}{2299}} \right\}^{-3/2}, \quad (1.14)$$

obtained in the quadrupole approximation by coupling the GW orbital decay rate to the eccentricity decay rate (Peters & Mathews, 1963).

To compute the frequency distribution of inspiralling MBHBs, following Kocsis & Sesana (2011), we express the frequency evolution of the binary in terms of 'residence time'

putting pieces together

$$\left| \frac{dt_r}{d\ln f_{r,k}} \right| = \left| \frac{dt_r}{d\ln a} \frac{d\ln a}{d\ln f_{r,k}} \right| = \frac{2}{3} \tau_{\text{res}}. \quad (1.15)$$

In phaseI, when the binary is driven by the disc, $\tau_{\text{res}} = \tau_m$; while in phaseII and phaseIII, GW emission takes over and $\tau_{\text{res}} = \tau_{\text{gw}}$. Putting the pieces together, for any given MBHB-disc parameters, we compute a^{dec} , assuming ϵ_0 given by equation (1.13); $dt_r/d\ln f_{r,k}$ is then obtained from equation (1.15) by plugging-in equations (1.8) and (1.9), where $\epsilon(f_{k,r})$ after decoupling is numerically obtained at any frequency from equation (6.3).

These population models using both the timescales given for stars and gas will be used in Chapter 6 for obtaining the eccentricity distribution in the frequency bands, both for *eLISA* and *PTA* observations.

1.1.4 Spin evolution of BHBs during cosmic evolution

Black holes in astrophysical context can be described by only two parameters: their mass M and their angular momentum \mathbf{J} . Due to the existence of a maximally allowed angular momentum $\mathbf{J}_{\text{max}} = G M_{\text{BH}}^2/c$, typically, the dimensionless spin¹ parameter $a = |\mathbf{J}|/|\mathbf{J}_{\text{max}}|$ is used. A BH of spin $a = 0$ is called a Schwarzschild BH, whereas increasing a needs the

¹ Note, that this has nothing whatsoever to do with quantum mechanics

description via the Kerr-metric, which is why astrophysicists speak of "Kerr-ness" meaning the magnitude of a . Einstein's *general relativity* (GR) does not allow for $a \geq 1$, which is why the measurement of a is a possible test for the validity of GR, if ever there should be a source with $a > 1$ (see Chapter 2 for the currently only feasible observational method).

A BH can obtain spin from its initial collapse if the matter was rotating priorly and did not lose the angular momentum to the exterior. Once formed, it can gain and lose spin by accreting matter. Basically any accretion process apart from perfectly spherically symmetric accretion includes rotation of the matter with respect to the BH. The other way round, even if the matter is infalling radially, initial nonzero spin a of the BH can induce rotation in the gas. Regardless on the reference frame chosen, angular momentum L is exchanged between the external matter and the BH. However, baryonic matter such as gas can typically lose L (\sim radiate or otherwise dissipate), so that only a small fraction ends up altering a . Generally, there are simple pictures of how accretion affects a . Either the gas can cool effectively, so angular momentum conservation will force it into a disc which either co- or counter-aligns with the spin of the BH (see details in § 1.3). Or the gas cannot cool and forms a puffed up structure retaining a net rotation. The latter case typically leads to very inefficient accretion and little effect on a . However, whenever a disc forms, then the change of a will depend on the thinness of the disc and the amount of mass transferred. For a coherent accretion event, where a thin disc of mass $\sqrt{6} M_{\text{BH}}$ is accreted onto a Schwarzschild BH of initial mass M_{BH} , the spin-up is maximal. If the BH now wants to lose some spin, then this is difficult because its own spin will now affect its environment, making a cancellation via a counter-aligned, coherent thin disc event unlikely (King et al., 2005). To lose spin, the BH must eat the gas in small incoherent portions, because only then the counter-aligned disc (if $L_{\text{Disc}} \ll J$) scenario is possible, which is then more effective in spinning-down the BH than the co-aligned scenario is in spinning-up (cf. § 1.3).

BH spin can be significantly affected also by mergers of two BHs. The details of what initial spin configuration leads to which final BH spin are highly non-linear and must be solved using Numerical Relativity. The general trend, however, is that the final BH spin tends to be low to mildly spinning unless the initial BH spins (that is both the spins and the BHB angular momentum) were perfectly aligned prior to merger in which case the final spin is very high (Barausse & Rezzolla, 2009; Rezzolla et al., 2008).

Even though spin is not a central element of this thesis, it is indirectly important because: (i) the value of a affects the radiative efficiency of a BH and thus the amount of matter it can gain per unit time and (ii) the question of whether accretion is coherent or incoherent in situations where there is not one, single disc around one BH, but a BHB surrounded by an outer, large-scale disc and a complicated, inner part (the aforementioned cavity) can possibly be important for GW measurements, because accretion cannot only affect the single BH spin but also align spins of the two BHs relative to each other.

In the above, the key concepts of cosmological BHB evolution in the context of supermassive sources were outlined: models for initial BH seeds, their subsequent mass growth by hierarchical merging and accretion and the importance of BH spin. I separated the merger environment into either stellar or gaseous, as their combined treatment is currently still unfeasible. Specifically for the thesis, I described how population models can be obtained and which timescales are of importance in the respective environments.

how to gain spin

angular
momentum
dissipation

how to lose spin

effect of BHB
mergersrelevance of spin
for this thesis

Summary

1.2 Accretion disc theory

Whenever some gaseous structure collapses with some net rotation, the conservation of angular momentum will flatten the gas distribution around the axis of rotation. The vertical extend of the forming disc will depend on the pressure, whereas the radial configuration will be determined by the rotation. In astrophysics, disc shaped objects are common throughout the Universe, from galactic discs, accretion discs, proto-planetary discs to rings around planets. In the following, I will summarise the central points of the current understanding of accretion discs and introduce the terminology used in the thesis.

Shakura Sunyaev discs

history of
accretion discs

The idea of accretion discs is about half a century old, Salpeter was amongst the first to offer an explanation for the (then newly discovered) quasars whose enormous luminosity could not be understood. In [Salpeter \(1964\)](#), he outlines how the conversion from rest mass into radiation during the infall into a deep gravitational well of a Schwarzschild geometry can work in Bondi-Hoyle accretion flows. [Lynden-Bell \(1969\)](#) was then the first to draw the picture of an accretion process involving a differentially rotating disc that dissipates angular momentum outwards and gas swirling into a "Schwarzschild throat". Four years later, [Shakura & Sunyaev \(1973\)](#) published the milestone work on accretion discs that still today serves as a standard model. This so-called "SS-disc" will be discussed in the following.

structure
equations

To arrive at the structure equations for a disc, it is common to start from the *Euler* equations (cf. Chapter 3 for their proper introduction) and make simplifications due to the disc-geometry. In lowest order, take first a cylindrically symmetric, ($\partial_\phi \rightarrow 0$), equilibrated ($\partial_t \rightarrow 0$), flat gas distribution of density ρ , that is allowed only to move in the plane ($v_z = 0$). Then the continuity equation is then reduced to the radial r -direction:

$$\partial_r (v_r r \rho) = 0 \quad (1.16)$$

and the momentum equations¹, with the gravitational potential $\Phi(r, z)$, become:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho v_r \partial_r v_r - \frac{\rho v_\phi^2}{r} + \partial_r P &= -\rho \partial_r \Phi \\ \rho v_r \partial_r v_\phi &= 0 \\ \partial_z P &= -\rho \partial_z \Phi \end{aligned} \quad (1.17)$$

Vertically, the gravitational potential does usually not vary much, i.e. $\partial_z \Phi \ll \partial_r \Phi$, which is why the vertical structure of the disc is given by the pressure. Radially, the pressure does not vary strongly, which is why the term $\partial_r P \sim P/r \sim 0$ can often be neglected. The structure is radially supported against the gravity $\partial_r \Phi$, by rotation $v_r \ll v_\phi$.

viscous
acceleration

If there are accelerations due to viscosity \mathbf{a}^{vis} , then there arises one additional term in the angular direction a_ϕ^{vis} and the (time dependent) equations can finally be written as.

¹ $\rho(\partial_t \mathbf{v} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \cdot \mathbf{v}) + \nabla P - \rho \nabla \Phi = 0$

$$\partial_t \rho + \frac{1}{r} \partial_r (v_r r \rho) = 0 \quad (1.18)$$

$$\partial_t v_r + v_r \partial_r v_r - \frac{v_\phi^2}{r} = -\partial_r \Phi \quad (1.19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t v_\phi + v_r \partial_r v_\phi &= a_\phi^{\text{vis}} \\ \partial_z P &= -\rho \partial_z \Phi \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to see, that pressure only plays a role in the vertical direction and determines the scale height H : disc scale height H

$$H = \frac{\rho}{\frac{d\rho}{dz}} = \frac{\rho}{\frac{d\rho}{dP} \frac{dP}{dz}} = \frac{\rho}{\frac{d\rho}{dP} (-\rho \partial_z \Phi)} = -\frac{dP}{d\rho(\partial_z \Phi)} \quad (1.20)$$

Following Montesinos Armijo (2012), the total pressure may be expressed as: pressure contributions

$$\begin{aligned} P &= c_s^2 \rho + \rho \langle v_{\text{turb}}^2 \rangle + \frac{aT^4}{3} \\ &= c_s^2 \rho \left[1 + \frac{\langle v_{\text{turb}}^2 \rangle}{c_s^2} + \frac{2HaT^4}{3\Sigma c_s^2} \right] \\ &= c_s^2 \rho [1 + \mathfrak{G}^2 + \mathfrak{S}^2 H] \end{aligned} \quad (1.21)$$

where T denotes temperature, a the radiation constant, c_s the soundspeed, and v_{turb} the turbulent velocity. Additionally, the surface density of the disc, Σ has been defined as: surface density Σ

$$\Sigma(r) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \rho dz = \int_{-H(r)/2}^{H(r)/2} dz = H(r) \rho(r, z=0) \quad (1.22)$$

Introducing two more important parameters, with $\Omega = v_\phi / r$: Toomre parameter

$$Q = \frac{\Omega c_s}{\pi G \Sigma} \quad (1.23)$$

$$\mathfrak{G} = \frac{aT^4}{3\pi G \Sigma^2} \quad (1.24)$$

the scale height H can now be written down as a function of the various pressure sources¹:

$$H = -\frac{c_s}{Q\Omega} \left((1 - \mathfrak{G}) - \sqrt{(1 - \mathfrak{G})^2 + Q^2(1 + \mathfrak{G}^2)} \right) \quad (1.25)$$

First, I should note, that I will call Q the Toomre parameter, even if the proper definition involves the epicyclic frequency rather than the orbital frequency, because this thesis deals with discs that are not deviating much from Keplerian for which the two coincide. Q , then encodes the importance of self-gravity for producing local instabilities due to fragmentation. If $Q \gg 1$, the disc is stable and does not clump under its own weight. If $1 < Q \lesssim 2$, the disc is marginally stable and produces clumps, usually in the form of spiral arms which can transport energy and angular momentum. If, however, Q is smaller than unity the disc becomes unstable to local fragmentation, equivalently local gas becomes Jeans unstable and starts collapsing. Usually this marks the onset of star formation inside a disc. discussion of the most important parameters
stability towards linear perturbation

¹ The dependence on the radius has been suppressed in the notation, because all variables $c_s, \Omega, \mathfrak{G}, \Sigma, Q, H$ etc depend on r .

β gives the ratio between radiation pressure and self-gravity. It is not used anywhere in this thesis, because I either neglect radiation pressure (in the Newtonian regime) or self-gravity (in the GR regime). Neglecting radiation pressure is a strong assumption, which presents a major caveat of our studies. However, it is also a very delicate point, because radiation transfer in discs cannot be described by just one regime and solving the radiation transport equation generally is extremely difficult.

α contains the ratio between turbulent velocity and soundspeed. This parameter is linked to the viscosity if turbulence is thought to be its cause. While radiation is difficult to compute in practise, it is at least well understood in principle; the same cannot be said about viscosity in accretion discs. It is due to this lack of understanding that still today, decades after the original works, prescriptions for the viscosity sometimes seem a bit like black magic. Throughout this thesis, the only cause of viscosity is attributed to the self-gravity, however, for analytical purposes the following paragraph will outline the standard treatment of pressure related viscosity.

The standard model of Shakura and Sunyaev deals with thin discs, for which $H/r \ll 1$ and where the self gravity of the disc is negligible. The key idea here, is that viscosity is parametrised with the famous α_{SS} parameter, as follows:

standard viscosity
parametrisation

$$T_{r\phi} = \alpha_{SS} c_s^2 \rho = -\alpha_{SS} P \quad (1.26)$$

where $T_{r\phi}$ is the shear component of the viscous stress tensor all other entries of which vanish. This statement may be recast in terms of a local, kinematical shear viscosity, ν , that stems from isotropic turbulence (cf. Eq. (3.46), but note that $\alpha \neq \alpha_{SS}$):

$$\nu = \frac{1}{3} \frac{\langle v_{\text{turb}} \rangle^2}{\Omega} = \alpha_{SS} c_s H \quad (1.27)$$

In this prescription, α_{SS} may vary between zero and 1 because turbulent motion can never be supersonic and the turbulence length scale is assumed to be comparable to H (Montesinos Armijo, 2012). The success of the parametrisation lies in its success in explaining some observations, but mostly in the simplicity and its easy implementation into numerical and especially analytical work.

microphysical
nature of α_{SS} ?

It cannot be stressed enough that this α_{SS} makes no claims about the real microphysical nature of viscosity, but allows the hiding away of processes that are potentially very involved. The difficulty in finding answers to what any real viscosity could stem from, comes from the fact that above all it needs to lead to stable discs, in which specific angular momentum l is transported *outwards* and specific energy e is transported *inwards* (Lynden-Bell & Pringle, 1974):

$$\frac{d}{dr} (e(l) - l\Omega) = -rv \frac{d}{dr} \frac{v}{r} > 0 \quad (1.28)$$

MRI as a viscosity
candidate?

Almost in any modern work on SS-accretion discs the *magneto rotational instability* (MRI (Balbus & Hawley, 1991)) is named the principal candidate to explain the local viscosity. Most studies of the MRI have been done in the shearing box approximation, because global simulations can typically not resolve the turbulence sufficiently. However, general problems of the shearing box approximation are discussed clearly in Regev & Umurhan (2008), who claim that MRI relevant for discs cannot be studied in the shearing box. Additionally, Bodo et al. (2011) argue strongly that the local MRI will not be able to transport angular momentum as it produces arbitrarily small α_{SS} for increasing resolution and that “we find ourselves in a paradoxical situation in which if a solution

is astrophysically relevant it cannot properly be described by a local model, and if it can be described by a local model then it is astrophysically irrelevant". The arguments presented are largely based on estimating the resolution requirements and pointing out that most numerical works are not yet sufficiently well resolved. A possibility that remains is to include explicit resistive and/or diffusive terms in the magneto hydrodynamical equations (see, however also Käpylä & Korpi, 2011, who find non zero α_{SS} in ideal MHD). Thus, it remains more than unclear what and how viscosity can be described.

Another important practical problem of the SS model is that it does not take into account self-gravity, which especially in the context of AGN is an important property and has been observationally confirmed (see Montesinos Armijo, 2012, §3). When $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$ is included, gravitational instabilities come into play as they not only alter the rotational curve, but also do they induce additional compression and shock heating. Typical effects on the spectrum are illustrated by Fig. 1.1, which present a fit of various AGN components onto the observational data of the Seyfert I object TON S 180 (cf. next § for more discussion). Self-gravity is very difficult to treat analytically, which is one of the reasons why numerical tools are so important. In order to estimate if and how important $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$ is in a disc, the Toomre parameter Q can be approximately recast into the form:

$$Q = 2 \frac{H}{r} \frac{M_{\text{BH}}(r)}{M_{\text{Disc}}(r)} \quad (1.29)$$

which is an indicator that $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$ begins to dominate when $\frac{M_{\text{BH}}(r)}{M_{\text{Disc}}(r)} \approx \frac{H}{r}$ (Montesinos Armijo, 2012).

influence of self
gravity $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$

Fig. 1.1: MID-IR TO X-RAY SPECTRAL MODELLING OF TON S 180 - Open squares and thick striped lines are the observed data and the power-law fits described in Turner et al. (2002). Two solid lines are the spectral components of the dusty torus (left) and the non self-gravitating disc with a corona (right; $M_{\text{BH}} = 10^{6.8} M_{\odot}$, $\dot{M} = 1000L_{\text{Edd}}/c^2$, and $\alpha = 0.002$). Two dotted lines mean the spectrum (from $r_{\text{sg}} < r < r_{\text{out}}$) of the self-gravitating disc for $\gamma = -0.6$ (where $\Sigma \propto r^{\gamma}$) and $\alpha_{\text{out}} = 0.02$ (upper; fits to the data) and that of a Keplerian, standard disc (lower). Total spectra of those three components are indicated by dashed lines: thick line is the spectrum with the self-gravitating disc mentioned above, while the case with a standard disc is indicated by a lower curve. The upper dashed line exhibits a total spectrum with a different parameter set for the outer self-gravitating disc ($\gamma = 0$, $\alpha_{\text{out}} = 0.02$).

Taken from Kawaguchi et al. (2004): With friendly permission from Toshihiro Kawaguchi

Accretion discs within the unified AGN model

Having described the central aspects of accretion discs, I will now put them into context of the full picture that is believed to be the environment of an AGN.

While the accretion disc is the component that plays the major role in feeding the central black hole, it is also the component which is least important to the observational features of an AGN. In the unified AGN model, first proposed by Padovani & Urry (1991) and completed in Urry & Padovani (1995), the AGN classification depends above all other things on the angle under which it is seen. This is because the largest component is an extended *obscuring torus*¹, which, if in the line of sight, will obscure or at least reprocess most of the emission from the centre, save for hard X-rays. The torus is made of cold and slowly moving dust, thus the observer sees it in the Infra-Red, which consists mostly of re-processed emission. The next smaller component is the thermal, optically thick and geometrically thin disc itself, which is modelled as a multicolour blackbody, meaning that each disc annulus emits a blackbody spectrum with temperature depending on the radial distance from the central BH. The blackbody emission typically peaks between optical and ultraviolet.

dusty torus

thin disc

irradiated clouds

X-ray corona

Most of the luminosity and the high energy components come from the gas clouds and winds close above and below the disc. It is believed that these structures, illuminated by the central engine, are responsible for the optical broad lines, distinctive of type-I (i.e. non obscured). Deeper in the potential well, at only few Schwarzschild radii from the central BH, a hot diffuse electron plasma component has been proposed to be the source of the X-ray continuum by thermal Comptonization (Haardt & Maraschi, 1991). It has been dubbed the *X-ray corona* and is found to work very well in explaining the extended X-ray power law observed in AGN spectra. However, the exact processes at work, the detailed balance between irradiation from the central BH and the thermal disc and most of all the time dependent geometry, conversely the variability, remain uncertain. The described components are plotted in Fig. 1.1, which is a fit to observational data to a typical AGN spectrum. One component that is still missing are the narrow spectral lines, which come from much further away and are not dynamically linked to the nucleus. They are produced in cold clouds or large scale winds, irradiated from either the jet and/or the disc. The central radio jet that powers most of the non-thermal luminosity is believed to originate magnetically either from the rotation of the black hole or from the rotation of the disc and extends to far outside the galaxy.

Type II migration

When having a second massive object inside the disc, then the accretion disc is disturbed and the object migrates by gravitational torques that typically excite spiral waves that transport angular momentum. If the torques outside the location of the secondary are stronger than the inside torques then the object loses angular momentum and migrates inwards. This process is called type I migration. Drifting toward the centre, the disc mass enclosed in the binary orbit becomes smaller than the mass of the secondary, a gap in the gas distribution opens, and Type II migration ensues. The investigation of coupled disc-binary systems has a long standing tradition in the context of planetary dynamics (Goldreich & Tremaine, 1980; Lin & Papaloizou, 1986; Ward, 1997; Bryden et al., 1999; Lubow et al., 1999; Nelson et al., 2000), where the

planetary migration

¹ The name "torus" does not mean that the geometry actually is a torus, but only that the object is vertically very extended

focus usually lies on the extreme mass ratio situation, i.e., a star surrounded by a circumstellar disc, with a planetary companion embedded in it. The comparable mass case has also been extensively investigated in the context of binary star formation (Artymowicz & Lubow, 1994; Bate & Bonnell, 1997; Günther & Kley, 2002; Günther et al., 2004), where a boost of activity has been triggered by imaging of nearby young binary stars embedded in hollow circumbinary discs (Dutrey et al., 1994). More recently, the techniques adopted in these fields has been exported to the BHB case. In the last decade, several investigations were devoted to the study of comparable mass BHBs evolving in circumbinary discs exploiting a variety of analytical and numerical techniques (e.g. Ivanov et al., 1999; Armitage & Natarajan, 2002; Gould & Rix, 2000; Armitage & Natarajan, 2005; Hayasaki et al., 2007, 2008; Haiman et al., 2009; MacFadyen & Milosavljević, 2008; Hayasaki, 2009; Cuadra et al., 2009; Lodato et al., 2009; Nixon et al., 2011; Shi et al., 2011). However only few of them dedicated a special focus on the details of the dynamical disc-binary interplay. MacFadyen & Milosavljević (2008) made use of a 2D grid-based hydrodynamical simulation where they showed how the gas flowing through the cavity mediates the energy and angular momentum transfer between the disc and the BHB. Shi et al. (2011) confirmed the nature of the disc-binary interaction by means of full 3D magnetohydrodynamics simulations. However, in both studies the BHB was on a fixed circular orbit and the central region of the disc was excised from the numerical grid. What is still lacking is a global three dimensional treatment in which the black holes can freely interact with the instreaming gas. One small step in that direction is taken in this thesis and presented in Chapter 4.

comparable mass case

recent studies

1.3 Black Holes in General Relativity

In the following, I will introduce some very basics of BHs in GR as far as they will be necessary for the thesis. When dealing with black holes as an astrophysicist, it is often possible to ignore strong gravity effects as they only appear at very small distances. Nonetheless, there are times at which it is essential not to treat BHs as a Newtonian particle. Typical examples are as follows.

1. Secular frame dragging that leads to the Bardeen-Petterson effect in accretion discs, this effect is related to the spin of the BH that aligns innermost portions of a surrounding disc to the black hole angular momentum vector (Lense, 1918; Thirring, 1918; Lense & Thirring, 1918; Bardeen & Petterson, 1975),
2. Several mechanisms proposed to cause the emission of jets in AGN (e.g. Blandford & Znajek, 1977; Blandford & Payne, 1982)
3. Spectral shapes of line emission from the innermost part of an accretion disc (cf. § 2.1)
4. Whenever a second body gets close enough to be disrupted or swallowed
5. The fact that there exists a last stable orbit: this leads for example to the truncation of accretion discs.

when to use GR

The Einstein equations

In Einstein's geometric theory of gravity, finished in 1915, he describes the field equations for the curvature of spacetime as being caused by the presence of mass (Einstein, 1915b,a):

$$G = 4\pi T \tag{1.30}$$

Thus the left hand side encodes the geometry, the right hand side (i.e. the source) encodes the energy and momentum of whatever is "inside" the geometry. The above notation contains a set of coupled differential equations, which turn out to be rather difficult to solve. A rigorous introduction of GR is absolutely beyond the scope of this thesis; I refer here to standard textbooks such as [Schutz \(1985\)](#); [Chandrasekhar \(1983\)](#); [Misner et al. \(1973\)](#) or [Living Reviews in Relativity](#)¹ for specific topics. Suffice it to say that the left hand side is non-linear, that these are 10 fully coupled equations, with 6 evolution equations containing second order time derivatives plus 4 constraint equations that contain no time derivatives and that there are gauge conditions to be chosen which define the observer. It should be mentioned that there are currently no observations related to compact objects that challenge GR predictions.

Line elements for astrophysical black holes

The simplest, analytic solution to the Einstein equations was derived by Karl Schwarzschild during WWI 1915/1916 ([Schwarzschild, 1916](#))². Using spherical symmetry in vacuum, he wrote down the line element for a non rotating singularity of mass M that possesses a horizon³ at $R_S = 2M$:

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{R_S}{r}\right) dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{R_S}{r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2) \quad (1.31)$$

It took 48 more years, until the general solution for a rotating black hole was found by Roy Kerr ([Kerr, 1963](#)). The line element in **Boyer Lindquist** (BL) coordinates and (un-normalised) spin parameter a is then:

$$ds^2 = -\frac{\Delta}{\Sigma} (dt - a \sin^2\theta d\phi)^2 + \frac{\sin^2\theta}{\Sigma} \left((r^2 + a^2)d\phi - a dt \right)^2 + \frac{\Sigma}{\Delta} dr^2 + \Sigma d\theta^2 \quad (1.32)$$

where the typical abbreviations $\Delta = r^2 - 2Mr + a^2$ and $\Sigma = r^2 + a^2 \cos^2\theta$ have been used. While there are many other possible choices of coordinates, the BL coordinates has the advantage that there is only one off-diagonal component in the metric, however they suffer from a coordinate singularity at the horizon. The most important differences to a non spinning metric are that:

1. the apparent horizon shrinks $R_S = M + \sqrt{M^2 - a^2}$, which already shows why a can never exceed M
2. the *innermost stable circular orbit* (ISCO), which is the location of minimal angular momentum, does so as well⁴ ([Bardeen et al., 1972](#)):

$$r_{\text{ISCO}} = M(3 + Z_2 \mp \sqrt{(3 - Z_1)(3 + Z_1 + 2Z_2)}), \text{ where} \quad (1.33)$$

$$Z_1 = 1 + \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{M^2}\right)^{1/3} \left(\left(1 + \frac{a}{M}\right)^{1/3} + \left(1 - \frac{a}{M}\right)^{1/3} \right) \quad (1.34)$$

$$Z_2 = \sqrt{3 \frac{a^2}{M^2} + Z_1^2} \quad (1.35)$$

¹ <http://relativity.livingreviews.org>

² (for a translation of the original, see [Schwarzschild, 1999](#))

³ For my purposes it is sufficient to define as horizon the last surface from which no physical information can escape

⁴ Note, that this effect is dependent on the sign of a , the ISCO becomes larger for increasingly negative $a < 0$

3. rotating BHs possess an ergosphere, where the rotational velocity is the speed of light
4. the radiative efficiency $\eta = 1 - E_{\text{ISCO}}$ increases with increasing $|a|$ from 6% for $a = 0$ to 42% for $a = a_{\text{max}}$, because the binding energy is smaller the farther in a particle is allowed
5. rotating BHs have a smaller horizon surface area and thus a smaller cross section when moving through a fluid

Having now listed the properties of Kerr BHs relevant to this work, I refer to (e.g. [Visser, 2007](#)) for a review of the properties of this spacetime that go far beyond the current scope.

ASTROPHYSICS OF MASSIVE BLACK HOLE BINARIES:

THE OBSERVATIONAL SIDE

This Chapter gives a brief overview of the astronomical context for *black hole binaries* (BHB). I will first outline several astronomical techniques used or proposed to observe *massive black holes* (MBHs) and *massive black hole binaries* (MBHBs). Starting from low *electromagnetic* (EM) wavelengths, these are radio observations, *near infrared* (NIR), optical (VIZ), *ultraviolet* (UV), X-ray spectroscopy and imaging, their co-incident combination in multi-wavelength campaigns and dedicated reverberation mappings. Then I will list some of the currently most promising candidates of MBHBs observations and remark on how they were obtained.

Leaving the EM window behind, I will outline two concepts proposed for observing MBHBs in *gravitational waves* (GW): (i) space born interferometry at milli Hz using the *Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (LISA)* concept¹ and (ii) radio timing observations at nano Hz frequencies via the so-called *Pulsar Timing Arrays (PTA)*. Concluding, I will remark on the possible merits of combining electromagnetic and gravitational wave observations in the so-called multimessenger astronomy.

As detailed in the previous Chapter, throughout cosmic history, the formation of a large number of massive black hole binaries as they are supposed to follow from galaxy mergers, is a natural consequence of the structure formation process (Begelman et al., 1980). However *unique*, direct or indirect evidence of gravitationally bound MBHBs in galaxy centres remains elusive. The following paragraphs should serve to explain why this fact is not surprising after all, but rather the direct consequence of the limitations both of our theoretical understanding of light-emission processes around BHs and of the instrumental capabilities of past and current observatories.

2.1 Identifying single massive black holes in galactic cores

Even though this thesis is focused on *binary* black holes, I wish to emphasize that the identification of massive black holes and the measurement of their parameters is by no means an easy task. From the theoretical side, much effort is currently being undertaken

¹ Although the *LISA* mission in its *eLISA/NGO* version proposed in ESA's Cosmic Vision programme was not selected for the first launch slot, the *LISA* concept was rated to have "the highest scientific merit" and will thus live on and be re-proposed for the L2 slot in 2015

to find unique ways of telling apart single and binary black hole observations¹. However, before trying to find binaries, both expected signatures across the wave bands and the instrumental limitations must be understood for the (supposedly) more common single black holes.

In the following, I will distinguish between primary, secondary and tertiary methods. The primary ones directly measure the kinematic profile of the black hole environment and use observational data from each object itself. Secondary methods use observational data that do not directly resolve the dynamically interesting region, but require some model to translate the measured quantity (i.e. delays in emission lines) into a dynamical quantity. From primary and secondary results, global relations can be derived, which are used in tertiary methods which are thus completely indirect and assume that all galaxies of a certain type behave like the few directly observed objects of that class.

Photometric measurements

One of the earliest ideas of finding SMBHs was trying to use photometric measurements of galactic cores. Motivated by the idea, that the central density of a galaxy would be influenced by the presence of a massive object thus altering the light profile such that the increased brightness of the core in combination with having a very small core radius would be indicative of a SMBH. However, as it has been found that usually more luminous, more massive galaxies have more massive central BHs, but their cores are at the same time larger and more diffuse (Ho, 1999), it was concluded that photometric signatures *alone* cannot be used as indicators.

Stellar kinematics (*primary*)

A more rigorous approach is to directly measure the stellar dynamics surrounding a supposed compact object. The principle idea is very straightforward: Comparing high resolution measurements of the light profile $I(r)$, the rotational velocity $V(r)$ and the velocity dispersion $\sigma(r)$ with the radial variation in (enclosed) mass, as given by the first velocity moment of the collisionless Boltzmann equation²:

$$M(r) = \frac{V^2 r}{G} + \frac{\sigma_r^2 r}{G} \left[-\frac{d \ln v}{d \ln r} - \frac{d \ln \sigma_r^2}{d \ln r} - \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_\theta^2}{\sigma_r^2}\right) - \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_\phi^2}{\sigma_r^2}\right) \right] \quad (2.1)$$

with v being the density of the tracer population, the luminosity of which is assumed to be independent of radius as $M(r)/L(r) \sim M/L$ (see Kormendy & Richstone (1995) for details). The primary quantity that is measured is the velocity dispersion, which in leading order scales as $\sigma \propto \sqrt{r}$.

Alternatively, the measurements can be compared with the results of simulations of stellar orbits around SMBHs. However, there are authors that claim that indeterminacies arise from the large variety of orbital solutions that are consistent with a given mass model (Valluri et al., 2004). Other authors report that numerical models *can* reliably determine the best matches to the kinematic and photometric observations (Richstone et al., 2004) with only two free parameters: a position independent stellar mass-to-light ratio and the BH mass itself. Additionally, in order to eliminate some degeneracies in the interpretation, the full information encoded in the *line-of-sight velocity distribution* (LOSVD) of the absorption lines can be used. So will, for example, various degrees of anisotropy lead to

¹ Note, that not a single secure observation of a binary closer than 7 pc is currently available

² This equation will be formally introduced in the next Chapter 3

symmetric deviations from Gaussian line profiles, whereas rotation of the system leave measurable skewness in the LOSVD (Ho, 1999).

It seems that the community has reached a certain consensus of the goodness of the fit from observations to mass estimates: Currently about 50 SMBH masses have been safely determined in galactic cores using stellar velocity dispersions (Gültekin et al., 2009; Graham, 2008) and about the same number of candidates with less secure measurements await better data in the near future.

50 mass estimates

In our own Galaxy, additional measurements are possible due to its closeness. Individual stars around the dark object associated with Sagittarius A* were observed within few mpc using high-resolution K-band astrometric maps and their stellar proper motion were reconstructed. Coupled with large samples of stellar radial velocity measurements in the near infra-red (NIR), this technique has yielded excellent results in the galactic centre (see Genzel et al., 2010, for a recent review) and not only could the mass of the central object be determined to $4.4 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$, but also its compactness: it must be confined to 125 AU which thus requires a minimal density of $5 \times 10^{15} M_{\odot} \text{pc}^{-3}$. This result is the most convincing evidence for the existence of black holes to date: In order to explain the compactness and the stellar orbits, the least exotic scenario/theory is that this object is a black hole as general relativity describes it. Any other explanation that is consistent with the measurement needs to invoke considerably more speculative hypotheses such as a boson star or a concentration of hyperlight black holes.

MBH in Sgr A*

best evidence for BH existence

Gas kinematics

Observing and mapping the proper motion of individual stars is by far the most reliable method of determining the mass of a dark object, however this is currently only feasible at very close distances. If aiming at extra-galactic measurements, a common method is the mapping of optical emission lines and/or radio spectroscopy of water masers.

Optical / UV emission lines (primary secondary and tertiary)

One idea is to use emission lines as tracers of the bulk motion of gas around a compact object. Without assuming anything about why/how this gas would be ionized, this method focuses on measuring the shape of line profiles and their time dependence in order to infer the motion of the emitting gas. The underlying assumption is that gas settles into a Keplerian, nuclear disc around the central object and is not strongly perturbed by non-gravitational forces (such as shocks, radiation pressure or magnetic fields). By direct gas dynamical motion, there are currently about 30 measured black holes mass estimates available.

lines as tracers

30 mass estimates

As an indirect method, the enclosed mass can be calculated after deprojecting the gas cloud motion depending on the inclination towards the observer by applying the virial theorem:

virial theorem

$$M_{\text{BH}} = f \frac{r \delta v_r^2}{G} \quad (2.2)$$

Here, f is a geometry factor, r is the distance of the line emitting gas from the central object, δv_r is the line broadening due to Keplerian motion and G is the gravitational constant (Marziani & Sulentic, 2012). However, this simple formula is quite full of difficulties: (i) The gas motion must be Keplerian: several spirals have shown to exhibit

several difficulties

non-circular motions in the optically emitting ionized regions (Fillmore et al., 1986). Besides Kormendy et al. (1996) showed that the emission line rotation curve very near the centre drops significantly below circular stellar velocities, thus rendering it useless for determining the central mass. (ii) The geometry factor f is largely unknown, but it is necessary to convert an observed *full width at half maximum* (FWHM) value into a virial velocity. (iii) The line broadening δv_r must be due to Doppler broadening only, however it is sometimes hard to determine in how far δv_r is due to scattering or other effects.

Marziani & Sulentic (2012) discuss the various problems, stating that the usual accuracy of the BH mass estimates is only up to a factor 3–5, with worst cases that have a factor 10 of uncertainty. Still, many AGN have nuclear discs of typical diameters $\sim 100 - 300$ pc from which resolved spectra in the optical can be obtained: the *Sloan Digital Sky Survey* (SDSS) contains about 100000 quasars. However, a minimum *signal to noise ratio* (SNR) is required for reliable FWHM estimates and good spatial resolution of the spectral data is required to determine if the disc is indeed in circular motion or contains spiral shocks and/or warps. Additionally, increased redshift pushes the tracer lines, such as the H_β line, into the IR, so one must either use another database for the IR band (from the *Very Large Telescope* (VLT) for example) or use another broad line as virial estimator (M_{gII} , e.g.): Currently, H_β and M_{gII} are argued to be the best estimators (Marziani & Sulentic, 2012) and McLure & Dunlop (2004) have used 12698 SDSS quasars and estimated their mass thus.

Very few AGN show very broad, double peaked lines, most visible in H_α that are additionally variable on timescales of months to years (Marziani & Sulentic, 2012). These variability timescales have been related to accretion disc dynamics (Eracleous & Halpern, 2003) and some prominent sources have been monitored for more than 20 years. Accretion discs containing hot spots, spiral waves or/and non-zero ellipticity have been proposed to explain the variability (e.g. Storchi-Bergmann et al., 2003; Lewis & Eracleous, 2006). Tracing hot spots or spiral arms in the disc itself, provides means to derive its period and thus again estimate the BH mass.

Radio VLBA observations of masers (primary)

Nuclear discs around active cores seem to favour luminous 22- GHz water maser emission (Claussen & Lo, 1986) giving rise to the observational opportunity of using maser spectra obtained by high resolution *Very Long Baseline Array* (VLBA) measurements to trace maser spots in thin Keplerian discs. For the prototypical example object of this technique, NGC 4258, Miyoshi et al. (1995) found that the disc is seen almost exactly edge on and that the maser spots are tracing an inner disc edge at 4 mas and an outer edge at 8 mas. For this galaxy they measured the rotation curve to be almost perfectly Keplerian (see also Herrnstein et al., 2005), thus facilitating a reliable mass estimate of about $3.6 \cdot 10^7 M_\odot$. However, only few AGN exist in which this technique to trace the central potential works well: the intrinsic widths of the lines must be small, the spatial distribution of the emission regions not too complicated and the disc must have negligible mass compared to the central object. Currently three black hole masses have been estimated using this technique (Gültekin et al., 2009).

Reverberation mapping (secondary)

As an indirect method for inferring virial masses of black holes Blandford & McKee (1982) proposed the following concept: If the continuum output of an AGN varies on days to months

in the optical/UV, and assuming that the broad emission lines are caused (= ionized) by that central continuum and will thus vary in response, then there should be a time delay that is proportional to the distance between line-emitting gas and BH. The region in which this is concept works, is thus set by the photoionization radius from the central source, and is of the order of one parsec (Peterson, 1993). The lines emitted by that region are expected to be Doppler broadened by the bulk motion of the emitting gas clouds that orbit around the central compact object. In order to understand the exact time delay between a variation in the source and a the absorption and re-emission in the broad line, the fact that the observer is very distant and the fact that iso-delay surfaces might not be distributed in a merely spherical onion structure must be taken into account. This gives rise to a transfer function, that needs to translate the incident light curve together with a response function into an emitted light curve (Peterson, 1993). However, there are several assumptions to be made: a relationship between the observable continuum and the ionizing continuum, a geometry of the gas configuration in the *broad line region* (BLR), a fast re-processing of the incident radiation and the radial velocity of the gas.

time delay

transfer function

It has been found, that indeed there is a clear ionization stratification in the radial direction from the central object: UV and optical continua vary without detectable phase difference and a particular line may be assigned a characteristic distance from the central object. From the (assumed) Keplerian motion, the mass of the BH can again be estimated via Eq. (2.2).

Moreover, Kaspi et al. (2000) discovered a relation between the size of the broad line emitting region, the mass of the central BH and the luminosity of the central source. Also does the FWHM of the Balmer lines correlate with the luminosity, and the mass with the luminosity. This all provides means to estimate masses and BLR sizes in sources, where direct reverberation mapping is either impossible or simply too expensive. This method has also been transferred into the UV and X-ray bands (Kaspi et al., 2005), finding that the correlations have different exponents in the respective frequency bands.

tertiary estimation

Thus reverberation mapping provides a very important method of determining the slope of various correlations that allow the indirect estimation of thousands of BH masses, even though, there remain several uncertainties as to the necessary assumptions.

Black hole spins: Relativistic X-ray lines

So far, techniques for the measurement of the black hole mass have been given, now follows the only¹ currently available technique for measuring their spin parameter a .

The idea here is to measure gravitational and Doppler shifts of relativistic lines in combination with disc reflection models (Miller, 2007a) to reconstruct the gas dynamics of the inner accretion disc very close to a black hole. Theoretical catalogues for the spectral shape of certain lines are first obtained by ray-tracing an emitted line profile from a certain location around the black hole (Arnaud, 1996a, e.g.). A key point is that the magnitude of the black hole spin changes the location of the *innermost stable circular orbit* (ISCO). As the gas within this ISCO is generally assumed not to contribute to the line emission (e.g. Young et al., 1998; Brenneman & Reynolds, 2006a) and because the line profile changes significantly if the line is emitted from deeper within the gravitational potential, a measurement of the black hole spin parameter a is thus possible.

fits to models

The most prominent lines are the hard X-ray iron emission lines that stem from the irradiation of the inner accretion disc. The external X-ray source required for

irradiated disc

¹ Speaking here only of massive BHs, for stellar mass BHs, there are methods based on the spectral shape of their emission

the irradiation is either assumed to be inverse-Compton scattering of a hot, diffuse corona or, more complexly, a combination of direct synchrotron and/or synchrotron self-Comptonization from the base of a jet plus inverse-Compton from the corona. This brings about an excess peaking between 20 and 30 keV due to Compton back scattering of the disc (Miller, 2007a). In order to determine the exact spectral profile, models are most sensitive to the ionization state of the disc, the ratio between incident and reflected emission, the temperature of the disc and the angle of inclination towards the distant observer (Miller, 2007a). For AGN, the X-ray continuum is usually well described by a power-law, which means that the X-rays are produced by Comptonization, synchrotron and synchrotron-self Comptonization. These X-rays then remove K-shell electrons from iron atoms leading to the most characteristic $FeK\alpha$ and $FeK\beta$ lines which are seen as broad, skewed lines around 3 – 7keV. These lines and the background are now separately modelled and the best fits for the background and the line shape yield values of the black hole spin a .

$FeK\alpha$ line

This technique has provided good results and measured spins in about 10 cases. However, there are controversial examples like MCG-6-30-15, where some fits to *XMM-Newton* data yielded extremely rapid spin of $a = 0.989^{+0.009}_{-0.002}$ (Brenneman & Reynolds, 2006a), a high spin of $a = 0.86^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$ was found by the FEROS group also using *XMM-Newton* data (de La Calle Pérez et al., 2010a) whereas analysis of the *Suzaku* data has recently given the value of $a = 0.49^{+0.2}_{-0.12}$ (Patrick et al., 2011). These problems notwithstanding, and with a total of more than 30 candidates getting better and better constraints, this technique is becoming increasingly important for understanding the spin distribution of massive black holes and, depending on the continuum, also for constraining the width and dissipation of the jet-emitting region. However, it must be stated, that only some AGN can be studied this way, for only Seyfert type 1 objects allow for a direct view into the central engine, whereas increasing inclination leads to obscuration by the dusty torus or, in the worst case for Blazars, only the beamed emission from the jet is visible and this technique naturally fails. Another concern is the width of the X-ray spectrum required to have a high confidence fit on the background continuum wherein lies a major source of uncertainties in all the spin measurements due to degenerate fitting parameters.

inconsistent results

2.1.1 Black hole mass relations

An indirect, yet potentially extremely powerful way, of estimating black hole masses was the discovery that there exist two correlations between (i) BH mass and bulge mass and (ii) BH mass and slit averaged velocity dispersion of the hot component of the galactic host. The first has been dubbed the $M - L$ relation (e.g., Dressler (1989); Kormendy (1993); Magorrian et al. (1998); Kormendy & Richstone (1995)) and the second, tighter relation is known as the $M - \sigma$ relation (e.g., Ferrarese & Merritt (2000a); Gebhardt et al. (2000a)). Both relations are constructed using SMBH mass measurements from direct dynamical observations (i.e. stellar kinematics, gas kinematics and masers) (see Gültekin et al. (2009) for a compilation of mass measurements).

primary estimates
only

The black hole mass - bulge mass, $M_{BH} - L$ relation

Having obtained a SMBH mass measurement to some degree of certainty from a primary (in some cases complemented by a secondary) method (see above), it is rather easy to measure the bolometric luminosity of the spheroidal component of the host (\sim "bulge"). Interestingly, there exists a correlation between the mass of the central object and the mass

(=luminosity) of the bulge, which is reproduced the left panel of Fig. 2.1 from Gültekin et al. (2009). Much effort has recently been devoted to measuring the intrinsic scatter of this relation with respect to different Hubble types and different galaxy masses. I now list the most notable points on why the discovery of this relation was so important: (i) On average, one can translate from these data, that the mass contained in the BH makes up about 0.2% of the bulge mass (Magorrian et al., 1998). (ii) Additionally, in the end of the 90-ties, there was already growing evidence that almost half of all bright ($B \lesssim 12.5$) galaxies could be classified as "active" to some extent: i.e. are partially accretion powered (e.g. Filippenko, 1996). This was because it could be shown by spectroscopic studies that nonstellar nuclear activity is present in the very core (e.g. Ho et al., 1997). (iii) Thus, the $M - L$ relation was the first piece of evidence that SMBHs could be a generic component of many, perhaps most, present-day bulge-dominated galaxies. The relation showed, that SMBHs form an essential part of galactic structure, that co-evolves with the galaxy and that by measuring one component, either the SMBH or the environment, one can infer information on the other.

importance of the correlations

SMBHs as integral parts of galactic structure

Fig. 2.1: THE $M-L$ AND $M-\sigma$ RELATION FOR GALAXIES WITH DYNAMICAL MASS MEASUREMENT - The left panel shows the $M-L$ relation with the best-fit for the sample plotted as solid line: $M_{\text{BH}} = 10^{8.95} M_{\odot} (L_V / 10^{11} L_{\odot, V})^{1.11}$. On the right panel the $M-\sigma$ relation is shown with the best fit to the full sample: $M_{\text{BH}} = 10^{8.12} M_{\odot} (\sigma / 200 \text{ km s}^{-1})^{4.24}$ as solid line. The symbols indicate the method of the BH mass measurement: stellar dynamical (pentagrams), gas dynamical (circles), masers (asterisks). Arrows indicate $3\sigma_{68}$ upper limits to BH mass. The color of the error ellipse indicates the Hubble type of the host galaxy: elliptical (red), S0 (green), and spiral (blue). Squares are galaxies that were not included in the fit.

Both figures and abridged captions taken from Gültekin et al. (2009): With permission from Kayhan Gültekin

The black hole mass - stellar velocity dispersion, $M_{\text{BH}} - \sigma$ relation

The second relation has been discovered more recently (Gebhardt et al., 2000b) and strengthens the belief that SMBHs are closely tied to their environment. On the right

importance for
structure
formation models

panel of Fig 2.1, I reproduce the compilation of 49 M_{BH} measurements and 19 upper limits as published in Gültekin et al. (2009). This figure shows the BH mass versus the stellar velocity dispersion σ plus the best fit. As obvious from the figure, many more galaxies can be included here as compared to the left panel, especially also spirals, and, additionally, the intrinsic scatter is very small (with the scatter increasing with decreasing galaxy mass). It has been argued, that the velocity dispersion is the parameter that correlates best with the black hole mass (for discussion see e.g. Ferrarese & Merritt, 2000b; Merritt & Ferrarese, 2001; Marconi & Hunt, 2003; Tremaine et al., 2002; Ferrarese & Ford, 2005; Graham, 2008). It could be said, that it was the secure measurement of the M - σ that substantially solidified the cosmological picture in which massive black holes are accepted as ubiquitous across the history of the Universe. Taken together these two relations are also very useful as tests for cosmological population models and can thus help to confide or exclude certain channels of structure formation.

Other proposed correlations

vivid ongoing
discussion

There have been discussions of whether SMBH masses correlate with dark matter halo masses of galaxies (measured by the asymptotic, circular velocity V_c) or with galaxy discs. In favour of this conjecture Volonteri et al. (2011) find in their analysis that "although the black hole masses are not uniquely determined by dark matter halo mass, when considered for the current sample as a whole, the $M_{\text{BH}} - V_c$ correlation may be as strong (or as weak) as M - σ ", but this has recently been rejected (Kormendy & Bender, 2011). If untrue, this would then mean that black holes coevolve only with bulges, where the evolution of bulges is driven locally and stochastically, thus there being no correlation with disks and pseudobulges or with dark matter haloes (Kormendy et al., 2011).

GW necessary for
populating the low
mass end

The question of where and at which redshift BHs form and how they grow (cf. § 1.1 for several recent studies) remains open and there is another important question, which will be extremely difficult to answer by electromagnetic observations: whether there is a threshold, a minimum galaxy mass below this paradigm of SMBHs co-evolving with their hosts does not hold. Because lower galaxy masses imply lower luminosities and because of the sensitivity thresholds of current EM instruments, it will be one of the major tasks of milli-Hz gravitational wave observations to populate (or not) these relation diagrams for low mass galaxies and thus low mass MBHs¹.

2.2 Searching for massive black holes binaries

Shifting the focus now from single black holes to binaries, the above mentioned techniques will still remain the same essentially. It is common to discern between two types of black hole binaries: widely separated black holes that appear as double sources that can be spatially resolved and close binaries below spatial resolution of any instrument. Obviously, the criterion of what can be spatially resolved depends on the distance to the source. However, this discrimination is not (yet) terribly arbitrary, simply because there is only one confirmed BHB in the latter category, i.e. a BHB closer than ~ 10 pc.

The theory of hierarchical formation is corroborated by several observed quasar pairs at a $\lesssim 100$ kpc projected separation (see, e.g., Hennawi et al., 2006), that have begun

¹ Although, gravitational wave observations will necessarily see binaries rather than single BHs

to merge, and by few \lesssim kpc dual accreting black holes embedded in the same galaxy (Komossa et al., 2003; Fabbiano et al., 2011), where the galaxies have (supposedly) already merged. Typically, these dual, wide BHBs are found as double X-ray sources inside a galaxy, which usually show a perturbed morphology, thus indicative of a recent merger event (Dotti et al., 2012). Currently less than 20 of these wide binaries have been found, the most prominent examples being: NGC 6240; the radio galaxy 3C75; the spiral galaxy NGC 3341; the ULIRG Mrk463; the interacting galaxy COSMOS J100043.15+020637.2 ; and the quasar pair J1254+0846¹ (Dotti et al., 2012). These dual sources are in the so-called phase-I, the dynamical friction phase of the merger (c.f. Chapter 1.1).

20 wide binaries

When going to BHB separations to less than $\lesssim 10$ pc, the necessary spatial resolution is typically not available and, again, it is possible to use either spectral line features and/or interferometry to identify them. The best (and only) example for successful radio-interferometry is 0402+379, which embeds two radio loud cores at a projected separation of 7 pc (Maness et al., 2004; Rodriguez et al., 2006) at redshift $z = 0.055$. However, radio interferometry is not a good tool to perform blind searches over the entire sky, as it has a tiny field of view, it requires both BHs to be radio-active and it would only work for sources at very low redshift.

radio
interferometry

Due to this lack of evidence for close binaries, a lot of effort has been put into developing identification criteria for binary BHs that do not rely on spatial resolvability. The proposed techniques are based on photometric variability and spectroscopic signatures or any combination thereof across the EM wavebands. The last sentence is already implying one of the basic problems with all search efforts: it requires a humongous amount of effort to get timing *and* spectral data with good flux limits, good pointing statistics and both things coincident in several bands². Long data samples are only available for the brightest of objects and there is no particular reason to assume that exactly these should harbour close BHBs in their centres. Thus, it seems a bit like the "looking for the key under the street lamp" problem. The proto-typical example of a bright source is the quasar OJ287 (Sillanpaa et al., 1988) where multiwavelength data and photographic plates are available dating back to the 19th century. In the optical light curves, a 11 year periodicity has been identified. One possible interpretation, that has been suggested, is a binary black hole of high eccentricity, where the secondary black hole periodically impacts into the accretion disc of the primary and thus causes the recurring flares (Valtonen et al., 2008). However, this interpretation of the light curves is not unique and it might well be that the question of whether or not this is indeed a SMBHB will remain unanswered till pulsar timing data (cf. next §) becomes available for this source. To date, OJ287 is the only source for which photometric variability alone has been proposed as a SMBHB identification.

problematic issues

photometric
variability

With the advent of large all-sky surveys, it is desirable to search these large catalogues probing for several simple criteria that each could be indicative of a SMBHB:

blind catalogue
searches

- Doppler shifted broad lines in the VIZ/NIR³: if the shifts correspond to velocities \gtrsim few hundred km s^{-1} these lines could be interpreted as coming from the gas bound to the active companion black hole (if only one BH is active). If both BHs are active, the broad lines should be shifted apart from each other depending on the

¹ This quasar pair is formed by two galaxies that have recently begun colliding, but can still be clearly distinguished

² Taking data from one object in several bands simultaneously is usually done via dedicated *Multiwavelength* campaigns

³ Again, M_{gII} is usually used whenever the Hydrogen-Balmer lines are redshifted into the IR

inclination towards the observer. This technique was applied to the SDSS blindly¹, yielding 32 objects with peculiar spectra, nine of which could be interpreted as BHB candidates (Tsalmantza & Hogg, 2012), out of which 4 candidates were the confirmed, previously found by Komossa et al. (2008); Bogdanović et al. (2009); Dotti et al. (2009); Boroson & Lauer (2009); Shields et al. (2009); Decarli et al. (2010).

- Velocity shifts between the broad H_β line peak and the rest frame of the narrow emission lines (Eracleous et al., 2011a). This uses basically the same idea as above, but here only the H_β is selected both as narrow and broad line for direct comparison. This yielded 88 candidates in the SDSS.
- Variability of the double peaked/shifted spectral lines. If the line velocity offset oscillate periodically around the redshift of the central source then this would be a tell tale sign of a binary. However, typically the binary periods are tens to hundreds of years and thus this is not routinely possible. Still, Eracleous et al. (2011a), found variation in the line shifts in 14 out of the 88 candidates. But still further observations are needed to rule out a stochastic nature of such drifts.

criteria not unique

However, none of these criteria can be thought of as unique, not even taken together. The community is critically lacking a reliable way of identifying black hole binaries in a unique fashion. As will also be shown later in this thesis on few examples, it is unfortunately very difficult to find such a way given the current and future observational facilities.

2.3 Low frequency gravitational waves

basic idea

The following Section will now introduce the two key concepts of how GWs in the nHz-mHz regime could be detected. The basic idea is always the measurement of a relative displacement of two points in space typically using a Michelson interferometer. The two points in space would be displaced because of the (transversal) oscillations of spacetime (= GW) passing through, and thus by measuring the time variation of the interferometer signal, amplitude and phase of the GW can be reconstructed.

experimental challenges

While this is very easy in principle, the difficulty comes from the fact, that the *strain*, i.e. the fractional change in length, is typically tiny, $h_{\text{GW}} < 10^{-21}$. If the arm of the interferometer is then L meters long, this corresponds to measuring displacements of $\Delta L = h_{\text{GW}}L$, which for a typical Earth-bound detector of few km armlength is then $\Delta L < 10^{-18}\text{m}$. Comparing this to the "size" of a nucleus which is about 10^{-15}m^2 , it is clear that many other physical processes can cause displacements of the same order that are not at all related to the presence of a GW. Thus the signal is typically buried in noise³, from which it has to be filtered out. Similar to signal processing of audio signals, GW data analysis uses *matched filtering*, i.e. the data stream (containing both noise and signal) is subjected to a series of cleansing iterations where known noise is subtracted out first and then possible signal shapes, the so-called *wave forms*, are tested for.

fundamental limitation to low frequencies on Earth

When building such an interferometer on Earth, low frequencies are inaccessible because the gravity gradient noise is becoming dominant at frequencies $\nu \lesssim 1 - 10$ Hz. This noise is

¹ The original purpose of Tsalmantza & Hogg (2012) was the automatization of a new search algorithm for gravitational lenses

² The charge radius of a proton is $r_p = 0.84184(36)(56) \times 10^{-15}\text{m}$ (Miller et al., 2011; Pohl et al., 2010)

³ The noise is made up of: *seismic, environmental/human, radiation pressure, thermal, gravity gradient* and *shot* noise contributions. For space borne detectors, there is no *seismic* noise

due to the curvature of the Earth and cannot be shielded, thus presenting a fundamental limitation. However, as the wavelength of GWs is proportional to the mass of the system emitting them, it is of much scientific interest to detect GWs all across the wavebands. Thus, it is natural to propose detectors that are not limited by gravity gradient noises, which either implies to go very far underground or to go to Space:

Going underground is expensive and even at depths where the Earth becomes fluid, gradient noises will still be problematic for frequencies $\nu < 1$. The *LISA* observatory will (one day hopefully) be realized by a gigantic triangle-interferometer trailing the Earth and rotating about its own axis (cf. next § 2.3.1): it is targeted at mHz frequencies and the sources expected are massive BHs, white dwarf binaries, extreme and intermediate mass ratio inspirals and possibly cosmic strings.

Going to even lower nHz frequencies is realised by using distant astronomical objects, known as millisecond *pulsars*, as interferometer arms. These pulsars emit extremely regular pulses which can be detected by radio telescopes (cf. § 2.3.2) and GWs passing through between the pulsar and the Earth will affect the arrival time of the pulse. Pulsar timing is expected to see supermassive BHs, where here *massive* is meant to denote anything in the range $M_{\text{BH}} \in [10^4, 10^7] M_{\odot}$, whereas *supermassive* denotes anything heavier than $M_{\text{BH}} > 10^7 M_{\odot}$.

space a viable option

mass ranges

2.3.1 Gravitational waves from Space: *LISA*

This Section sketches the very principles of the *LISA* concept¹, the target sensitivity and the expected signals. For more detail see e.g. [Amaro-Seoane et al. \(2012\)](#); [Phinney \(2002\)](#); [Danzmann & Rüdiger \(2003\)](#); [Baker et al. \(2007\)](#). The following numbers are given from the *eLISA* yellow book² even though the configuration of the next *LISA*-like proposal is likely to revert back to the more sensitive, full triangle configuration. I will refer to *LISA* as the full triangle configuration, numbers reported from *eLISA* are thus to be understood as conservative.

The central idea is to have three spacecraft arranged in a triangle, in constant contact with each other via laser links. The *eLISA* concept realised only a V-shaped link-connection, where two spacecraft were unconnected and yet this configuration could still be made to perform excellently. Each spacecraft contains a very pure and regular, free falling test mass that is used as a reference frame and the outer spacecraft follows its test mass in a drag free way. Any *relative* displacement is then measured in the change of frequency in the observed laser light from its two neighbours. The latter technique is known as Doppler tracking and has already been used to get upper limits on GWs on old space missions such as CASSINI³ (e.g. [Armstrong, 2006](#), for a review). Having three spacecraft, all with reference lasers to coherently combine the incoming laser light with the reference light, allows having independent measurements of the beat signals that can be combined together if the time delay of the spacecraft relative to each other is also measured. The combination incorporating the time delay of the signals from all spacecraft then presents the entire data stream.

LISA concept

Since this experiment is carried out in Space, both seismic and gravity gradient noise that plague Earth bound detectors are absent. This presents a key advantage since it allows going to very much lower frequencies, the only limiting factor being force gradient noises

¹ Last proposed to ESA under the name *eLISA/NGO*, see <http://www.elisa-ngo.org>

² https://lisa-light.aei.mpg.de/lisa-light/pub/ScienceWorkingTeam/YellowBook/YB_reduced.pdf

³ Classical Doppler tracking sends pulses back to Earth from one spacecraft only

on the free floating test masses (this starts happening at about 10^{-3} Hz). Additionally, the armlength can be made very long $L_{\text{LISA}} = 5 \times 10^9 \text{ m}$ or $L_{\text{eLISA}} = 1 \times 10^9 \text{ m}$, which translates into much less stringent length measurements: since the resolvable strain is $h_{\text{GW}} = \Delta L/L$. Compared to Earth bound experiments, *LISA* thus only needs picometer accuracy in ΔL rather than sub-femtometer accuracy in LIGO.

triangulation

Such a huge triangle has the further advantage that it can rotate around its own axis in order to get a sense of the direction of the incoming signal. On the Earth, several detectors must be installed all over the globe to achieve source localization, not so in *LISA*: it rotates both around itself as well as around the Sun. A GW signal will thus be Doppler modulated over the period of the constellation, its measured signal shape will oscillate over time as the signal is viewed from another angle and so, similar to the human ear, *LISA* can locate the source on the sky (with a 180° degeneracy). The rotation around the Sun gives *LISA* all-sky-sensitivity, i.e. unless a source is extremely short lived, over time there cannot be a complete blind spot towards a particular source-orientation.

The bandwidth of *LISA* is very wide, spanning more than 4 octaves from 3×10^{-5} Hz to 1 Hz. Should such an instrument eventually be realised, sources not only of very different masses can be observed, but they can be followed from chirping at wider separations through merger to ringdown. This is why one may really speak of a GW-observatory here, rather than a detector. Also vastly different types of sources are expected to be in band:

expected sources

- **Wide dwarf binaries:** some WD-binaries are the so-called *verification binaries*. These are known to exist and their masses and orbital parameters are known to a sufficient degree so as to predict that they *must* emit GW in the *LISA* band, if general relativity is correct. Having known, confirmed sources might be the most important argument for a *LISA*-type experiment, especially if the Earth bound detectors should not detect anything. For the *eLISA* configuration, eight verification binaries were identified as "must see". Additionally, about 3,000 binaries should be individually resolvable.
- **Unresolved galactic background:** *LISA* will essentially not be suffering from instrumental noise in the sense that the expected strength of unresolved, continuous GWs from binaries in the Galaxy is expected to dominate the instrumental noise by a factor of a few; at frequencies $\nu \lesssim 10^{-3}$. The noise in *LISA* is thus actually GW-signal which by its own can be used to understand the population of binaries in the Milky Way.
- **Massive BHB of equal mass:** these are by far the strongest sources that exist at all. For redshift ranges $0 < z < 5$ their observable total masses are $10^5 M_\odot - 10^7 M_\odot$ and in this epoch they should be already be well established members of galactic structure. For very early epochs $5 < z < 10$, the binaries would be lighter $2 \times 10^4 M_\odot - 10^5 M_\odot$ and their observation would tell much about the rates of BH growth in the early universe, especially if it could be possible to recover their memory of earlier environment coupling. As there currently is no EM evidence to any BH further out than $z \gtrsim 7$, any detection, which is in principle possible out till $z \sim 20$ would provide great insights in the early stages of galaxy formation/clustering and the roles the BH play in it.
- **IMRIs: intermediate mass ratio inspirals** require light black holes in a mass range where no confirmed object has yet been found. Thus the detection of such a light BH is of great interest for studying BH-mass relation as mentioned above (see § 2.1.1).
- **EMRIs: extreme mass ratio inspirals** require a massive BH and a small companion, which may either be a neutron star, a white dwarf or a small BH. These source are of primary interest because only they could provide stringent tests for deviation from general relativity. An EMRI detection would improve the understanding of the stellar environment around a massive BH. EMRIs could make visible dwarf galaxies that

escape EM observations because of their faintness and furthermore populate the mass spectrum of stellar BHs. EMRIs could be measured by *LISA* out to about $z < 0.7$ yielding extremely accurate extraction of BH-mass, spin and orbital eccentricity at the plunge.

- Cosmic strings: these proposed remnants of symmetry breaking at cosmological phase transitions could form a GW background that *LISA* could detect near TeV energies.

Comparing with the uncertainties of SMBH mass measurements given in § 2.1, it should be noted that *LISA* can detect MBHBs masses with an accuracy of 0.1% – 1.0% and spins with absolute errors in the range 0.01 – 0.1. This unprecedented accuracy allows for distinction between different models of earlier evolution that may leave imprints in the final MBHB configuration, thus MBHB observations would possibly allow for reconstruction of much more parameters than just those directly encoded in the GW signal. The sensitivity curve of both *LISA*, *eLISA* and *PTA* (next §) are given in Fig. 2.2. On the left of this figure, typical sensitivity curves are shown, comparing the *LISA* and *eLISA* design. What is interesting about the red and green curves is that one can clearly see the resonances at high frequencies, where the GW wavelength fits an integer amount of times into the armlength.

accuracy

Fig. 2.2: SENSITIVITY CURVES OF *LISA*, *eLISA* AND *PTA*: OVERVIEW WITH MODELLED SOURCES - *Left*: Sensitivity of *eLISA* (averaged over all sky locations and polarisations) versus frequency: the solid red curve is obtained numerically using the simulator LISACode 2.0 (Petiteau et al., 2008) and the dashed blue curve is an analytic approximation. The sensitivity curve of *LISA* is green. Taken from Amaro-Seoane et al. (2012): With friendly permission from Antoine Petiteau

Right: The combined sensitivity curves of *PTA* (assuming SKA) and *eLISA*/*NGO* with expected, modelled signals. For *PTAs* there is a unresolved stochastic background: green squares represent the strain of each individual source, the overall signal is shown as a blue solid line, individually resolvable sources are shown as blue triangles, and unresolved background is shown as a green solid line. For *eLISA*/*NGO* individual MBHBs can be resolved at the final stage of coalescence (red lines). The source strength is depicted as the characteristic amplitude of GW signals as a function of frequency. The upper right panel shows the MBHB coalescence rate as a function of the total mass M for two representative MBH population models. The green- and red-shaded areas highlight the portion of the mass function that will be probed by *PTA* and *eLISA*/*NGO*, respectively, highlighting the complementarity of the two experiments.

Taken from Sesana (2012): With friendly permission from Alberto Sesana

MOCK data

Currently, there is (obviously) no data available, which is why several groups test their GW detection algorithms by creating MOCK data that contains simulated signals and simulated noise. From these tests it has become apparent that LISA is extremely sensitive to SMBHB parameters even though there are degeneracies between them. This enormous sensitivity will become important to this thesis in Chapters 4 and 5, where I discuss if imprints from an early epoch of evolution can survive into the GW_{LISA} regime.

2.3.2 Gravitational waves from Pulsar Timing

most stable clocks

As illustrated and discussed in the above Section, a *LISA* type experiment cannot go to arbitrarily low frequencies, which is why people use yet another concept here that does not involve *building* any interferometer experiment. Rather it uses rapidly rotating neutron stars as reference points. These so-called millisecond pulsars are the currently most stable, known clocks in the Universe. Pulsars can be observed by radio telescopes and the shape, intensity and arrival time of their pulses depend on the physics of the emission, propagation and direction. Since pulsars are explained by magnetized neutron stars that rotate around an axis that does not coincide with the magnetic axis, various difficult details of the interaction between radiation and magnetic fields in the presence of a strongly gravitating elastic object must be taken into account for the modelling¹. Unfortunately, many of these details are still not well understood today. Fortunately, however, an approximative pulsar model is usually sufficient for the purpose here, as long as the pulsars behave well (i.e. they don't "glitch").

 time of arrival
ToA

The basic idea of *pulsar timing* is to predict the *time of arrival* (ToA) of each pulse with some model that includes both pulsar parameters and propagation effects of the pulse through interstellar space and atmosphere. This expected ToA is then compared with the measured ToA of the actual pulse at the radio telescope.

timing residuals

If now a GW should be present between the Earth (\sim the radio telescope) and the pulsar, then the ToA would be affected (Sazhin, 1978). For a typical GW frequency of 10^{-8} Hz a displacement $\Delta L \sim 30\text{m}$ would give rise to a change in ToA of 10ns corresponding a strain $h_{\text{GW}} = 10^{-17}$. The changes in ToA are called timing residuals and obtaining them means monitoring many pulsars over many years, because a single residual does not make a GW detection (mostly because of the many uncertainties as to the prediction of a single pulse), rather one needs a time evolution of residuals to match against expected GW waveforms. The collection of pulsars used are called an array, which gives the name of the project: *pulsar timing array* (PTA).

To be more precise, the difference in time due to a GW can be written down in terms of geometrical functions F that depend on the orientation towards the pulsar \hat{n} and the propagation vector of the GW \hat{k} , plus an integral over the metric perturbations g that also encodes the distance to the pulsar L (Lommen, 2011):

$$g(t, L, \hat{n}, \hat{k}) = \int_0^L h_{\text{GW}} [t - (1 + \hat{k} \cdot \hat{n})(L - \lambda)] d\lambda \quad (2.3)$$

which then gives the time delay or advance τ_{GW} :

$$\tau_{\text{GW}} = F^\times g_\times + F^+ g_+ \quad (2.4)$$

 short wavelength
regime

Here $+$ and \times simply denote the two polarizations of the GW in the TT gauge. What should be noted is, that the wavelength of the GW is always much smaller than the "armlength", i.e. the distance to the pulsar L , such that PTA can be said to operate in

¹ Additionally, pulsars often live in binaries which increases the number of model parameters even more

the short wavelength regime.

In order to get a good sensitivity curve for *PTA* (cf. right panel of Fig. 2.2), it is important to have (i) many stable pulsars (ii) that spin fast enough with little timing irregularities and (iii) a radio telescope with good sensitivity. Additionally, the SNR is integrated over the entire observation time which means that detection becomes more likely the longer the radio timing data-sets are.

The reason why it is important to have as many milli second pulsars as possible is because the signal can be split up in two terms: From Eq. (2.3) one gets the signal at L , which corresponds to the "pulsar term" and the signal at 0, the so-called "Earth term". The latter now is independent of the distance to the individual pulsar and thus the timing residual from the Earth term will show the same characteristics (up to geometry) for all available pulsars. Thus the Earth terms can be correlated, which is why a *PTA* is essentially a huge interferometer (Hellings & Downs, 1983). It is important to note, that the L_i to the individual pulsars are not known better than about $\sim 10\%$ which leads to phase noise when trying to extract GWs. Thus, studies have been done where the pulsar term is completely neglected for GW analysis showing that it is still possible to extract good information both if the GW source is burst-like as well as long-lived monochromatic (e.g. Finn & Lommen, 2010; Babak & Sesana, 2012; Sesana & Vecchio, 2010).

ignoring the pulsar term

The expected sources for *PTA* are primarily monochromatic, resolved GWs from SMBHBs out to $z \sim 1$, i.e. supermassive sources that are so loud in GWs that they can be seen even though they are not yet chirping significantly. And also in band is the unresolved stochastic background from many weaker binaries.

expected sources

Currently, the *PTA* community is operating the telescopes Effelsberg, Jodrell Bank, Nançay and Westerbork for the *European Pulsar Timing Array* (EPTA, Janssen et al., 2008); the Arecibo and Green Bank telescopes are used by the North Americans (NANOGrav, Jenet, 2009); and the Parkes telescope is operated in Australia (PPTA, Manchester, 2008). All efforts are joined together in the *International Pulsar Timing Array* (IPTA, Hobbs, 2010) project, which is projected to include the future major effort *square kilometre array* (SKA, Lazio, 2009), to be built in South Africa and/or Australia. SKA would provide a huge leap in sensitivity.

operating facilities

So far, the effort has primarily produced ever better upper limits on the stochastic GW background in the frequency region $10^{-9} \lesssim \nu \lesssim 10^{-7}$ Hz. The best residuals come from the pulsar PSR J0437–4715 with an average of ~ 60 ns timing residual uncertainty¹ over 1 yr of data from Parkes. Hobbs (2010) report that in the IPTA: "Out of 37 pulsars, thirteen have expected TOA uncertainties < 250 ns, seven between 250 and 500 ns, a further nine between 500 ns and 1μ s, five between 1 and 2μ s and the remaining three $> 2 \mu$ s". The great hope lies with SKA, which would provide timing sensitivity on the level of < 100 ns for many hundred pulsars (Kramer et al., 2004).

The field of data-analysis for *PTA* is relatively young and so far usually only circular monochromatic signals or fully stochastic background are considered. As will be shown in Chapter 6, SMBHB eccentricity could play a non-negligible role for *PTA* sources and should be taken into account in future *MOCK-PTA*-data-analysis campaigns. The expected accuracy in source parameter extraction is less than for *LISA*, but mass and spin of the SMBHBs might still be measured better than with EM methods (e.g. Corbin & Cornish, 2010).

data analysis

¹ Note that a ToA is not derived from a single pulse, but averaged over several incoming pulses and then the rms is calculated

2.4 Multimessenger Astronomy

Having described both electromagnetic and gravitational wave astronomy of black holes by themselves, this short Section will outline the possible benefits astronomers may have if the two fields could be combined in what is called *Multimessenger Astronomy*¹ (see e.g. Holz & Hughes, 2005; Armitage & Natarajan, 2005; Kocsis et al., 2006; Phinney, 2009; Schnittman, 2011; Tanaka et al., 2011, and Chapter 6) . Even though GW observations alone will be an outstanding breakthrough in science, the astrophysical payouts will be greatly amplified by the coincident identification of electromagnetic counterparts. The identification of the host galaxy of a MBH binary merger will (i) improve our understanding of the nature of the galaxy hosting coalescing MBHBs (e.g. galaxy type, colours, morphology, etc.); (ii) help to reconstruct the dynamics of the merging galaxies and of their MBHs; and (iii) offer the possibility of studying accretion phenomena onto systems of known mass and spin (Sesana et al., 2012).

cosmography

First and most importantly, GW observations do not measure the redshift z , thus in order to allow studying cosmography there are only two ways: either one assumes a particular cosmological model to construct a statistical distribution of possible host galaxies in the error box given by the GW observation and fits to match for the redshift (Petiteau et al., 2011) or one directly measures a coincident EM counterpart to the GW signal. The first method has been shown to be able to constrain the equation of state of Dark Energy on equal accuracy with supernovae measurements. However, it relies on population models from merger trees and the Millennium simulation, thus there could be systematic biases.

open questions

The second method of observing EM counterparts would be the ideal situation, however, it turns out to be very difficult: To date, no unique signature has been predicted in any waveband; it is not clear *if*

- any such signature would be coincident rather than a pre- or postcurser signal
- the signature could be a negative signal viz. a dimming instead of a brightening
- the signal could be intrinsically very weak which combined with their large distance (the bulk of the *LISA* sources are likely to cluster at $3 < z < 8$ (Sesana et al., 2007)) makes a detection rather unlikely
- the error box of *LISA* contains a small enough number of possible hosts to scan the area with EM observatories in time. The estimate for *LISA* was a somewhat modest sky localization accuracy (generally $> 1 \text{ deg}^2$, Lang & Hughes, 2008) yields about order of hundred of thousands possible hosts² (Petiteau et al., 2011; Sesana et al., 2012)
- the possibility of chance confusion is non-negligible

prospective benefits

Nonetheless, the benefits of having a direct counterpart, no matter if precursor or delayed signal, would be very important for understanding EM emission close to black holes:

- models of accretion physics and AGN could be compared
- the morphology of the immediate environment of the merger host could be compared to other, "normal" hosts to test for the influence of the presence of a binary

¹ For neutron stars and supernovae this usually includes neutrino astronomy, but for black holes neutrinos are not expected to play any role

² This is particularly true for ELISA/NGO. To fit within the available budget, the proposed instrument features 4-laser links only (i.e., single Michelson interferometer), with an inevitable degradation of the distance and sky location measurements of the source.

- the merger paradigm (Begelman et al., 1980) could be verified¹
- depending on inclination and distance to the source reverberation mapping of a post-merger host could bring clarity as to how shocked the ambient gas really gets and what equation of state is necessary to describe it
- the conjecture of whether or not nuclear activity is related to merging activity could be tested

This provides a central motivation of studying black holes in gaseous environment, since only in the presence of matter can there be a distinctive EM signal. Even if some studies claim that pair production from the vacuum is sufficient to power a jet at merger (Palenzuela et al., 2010), the presence of an accretion disc is necessary to provide the magnetic field. Thus it is the aim of this thesis to study both the large scale behaviour of accretion discs around binaries as well as develop numerical methods to describe matter and radiation close to a black hole.

¹ The first stage of dynamical friction can already be counted as verified, missing are the small scale stages

METHODS

This chapter describes the two numerical tools employed in this thesis. After a general introduction, I outline in § 3.1, the concept of *Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics* (SPH) that was used for Newtonian, non-relativistic and self-gravitating systems. In § 3.2 follows a more detailed description of *General Relativistic Hydrodynamics* (GR-HD) that was used for modelling non-self-gravitating accretion flows in the immediate vicinity of a black hole. As the latter scheme was extended to include an approximate form of radiative transfer, the required improvement of the time-stepping algorithm in the form of an implicit-explicit method is detailed in § 3.2.2.

Introduction to numerical hydrodynamics

When trying to describe astrophysical gases, the first observation is that gases consist of particles that have mass, charge and possibly many internal degrees of freedom. Whenever the aim is to describe a very large number of very tiny interacting particles, one needs kinetic theory and the knowledge of position, momentum of each particle at time t . This may be formulated in terms of distribution functions F that describe the state of the system in phase-space and one eventually arrives at the *Boltzmann equation*:

origin of
hydrodynamics
equations

$$\hat{\mathcal{L}}[F] = \hat{\mathcal{C}}[F] \tag{3.1}$$

$$\partial_t F + \dot{\mathbf{x}} \partial_{\mathbf{x}} F + \dot{\mathbf{p}} \partial_{\mathbf{p}} F = \text{sources-sinks}$$

where $\hat{\mathcal{L}}$ is the Liouville operator and $\hat{\mathcal{C}}$ is the collision operator acting on the distribution function $F = F(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}, t)$ (Liboff, 1998). The full dynamics of the ensemble of particles is then given by the total time derivative of the distribution function for all the particle species α that are present: $F_\alpha(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}, t)$ whereas the collision operator includes all position, velocity and time dependent interaction terms, cross sections, both sinks and sources (also for all species present). This equation in its general form is impossible to solve for most astrophysically interesting problems, because of the huge complexity. It is also often not necessary to solve the trajectory in phase-space for each single particle. Thus, the usual approach is to describe big "chunks" of gas as one element that carries the statistical, thermodynamical quantities obtained by integrating over all particles contained within the "chunk". This leads to the common expansion of the Boltzmann equation into moments. When going to a fluid description that relies on statistical properties, the first assumption is that the underlying gas particles are dominated by collective forces and collective interactions.

plasma parameter

Additionally, this implies that the collision terms are negligible. This is usually a very good approximation when dealing with plasmas and can always be checked by working out the plasma parameter g , which is the inverse of the number of particles n within the *Debye* sphere $4\pi\lambda_{\text{Debye}}^3/3$ (Naval Research Laboratory, 2007):

$$g = \frac{3}{4\pi n \lambda_{\text{Debye}}^3} = \frac{3(4\pi n e^2)^{3/2}}{n 4\pi (k_B T)^{3/2}} = 6e^3 \sqrt{\frac{\pi n}{k_B^3 T^3}}. \quad (3.2)$$

velocity moments

If the condition $g \ll 1$ is satisfied then we may speak of a collisionless plasma, for which a fluid description is accurate.¹ When expanding into moments of velocity², each expansion of order n will include one moment of order $n + 1$. Below, the typical expansion into the zeroth (conservation of mass $\langle F, 1 \rangle$), first (conservation of momentum $\langle F, \mathbf{p} \rangle$) and second (conservation of energy $\langle F, 1/2|\mathbf{p}|^2 \rangle$) moments has been used to derive the continuity equation (0th order) where the velocity enters as a first order term, the Euler equation (1st order) where the (tensorial) pressure Π_{ij} enters as a second order term, and the energy equation (2nd order). Mathematically, this may be expressed as the vanishing of the velocity integral over a conserved quantity convolved with the collision term of the Boltzmann equation, which should be zero, because the quantity is conserved:

$$\begin{aligned} \int d^3v \left(m/mv / \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \right) \hat{C}[F] &= 0 \\ \int d^3v \left(m/mv / \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \right) \hat{L}[F] &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

For the 0th moment, this then reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \int d^3v m \partial_t F + \int d^3v m \dot{\mathbf{x}} \partial_x F + \int d^3v m \dot{v} \partial_v F &= 0 \\ \int d^3v m \partial_t F + \int d^3v m v \partial_x F + \int d^3v m \mathbf{K} \partial_v F &= 0 \\ \partial_t \int d^3v m F + \partial_x \int d^3v m v F + \int d^3v m F \partial_v \mathbf{K} &= 0 \\ \partial_t \rho + \nabla(\mathbf{v}_{\text{bulk}} \rho) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

Here, force terms have been condensed into \mathbf{K} , the third term must be integrated by parts with the force vanishing at infinity, furthermore the mass density $\rho = \int d^3v m F$ and the bulk velocity (hereafter, just velocity) $\mathbf{v}_{\text{bulk}} = \int d^3v m \mathbf{v} F$ have been used. For the other two moments, the game is the same. It is necessary to introduce the random velocity as the difference between total velocity and bulk motion: $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{v}_{\text{tot}} - \mathbf{v}_{\text{bulk}}$, whose average is zero $\int d^3v u u F = 0$. Moreover, let the conduction heat flux be introduced as $\mathbf{q} = \int d^3v \mathbf{u} 1/2 m u^2 F$ and the thermal energy density be introduced as $e = \int d^3v 1/2 m u^2 F$. This yields then five equations for thirteen unknowns. The first reduction of complexity is that typically the pressure will be assumed to be a scalar $P = \delta_{ij} \Pi_{ij}$.

closure relation

However, still closure relations are needed to connect the variables. Such closure relations are derived from the thermodynamic Hauptsatz that the entropy tends toward an extremum. As Boltzmann found, the entropy is maximized by assuming a Maxwellian form

¹ The collisionless Boltzmann equation is then called the *Vlasov equation* (Kirk et al., 1994).

² Note, that for simplicity, I assume the non-relativistic case where $v = p/m$

for the distribution function F , but the particular form of the so-called *equation of state* (EoS), which gives the pressure as function of the variables of state, can still be chosen from a variety of admissible options.

Assuming henceforth, that the gas in question does behave like a plasma, one arrives at the subject of hydrodynamics which studies only the *macroscopic* phenomena of moving fluids. It is an effective theory aimed at capturing the dynamics of a collective of microscopic particles by describing them as continua. When referring to a fluid particle (Lagrangian approach, see below) or fluid cell (Eulerian approach), any of these fluid elements are supposed to contain large numbers of particles or molecules. The description is thus of a statistical nature assigning thermodynamic quantities, such as pressure P and density ρ , to each fluid element. The state of the fluid is characterised by the latter plus the velocity field \mathbf{v} .

macroscopic
description

Common assumptions made in this field are listed in the following:

- *homogeneous* : No point in space time is preferred
- *incompressible* : The density ρ is invariable, i.e. constant throughout the volume of the fluid and throughout its motion $\text{div} \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$
- *ideal* : Point particles interact only with themselves and the boundaries and feel no external forces
- *isotropic* : No direction within space time is preferred
- *local thermal equilibrium* (LTE) : Local quantities may be described statistically, a temperature can be associated with the distribution of the particle velocities, microscopic travel times of information exchange are small compared to the dynamical time scale under study, collisions happen a lot, the fluid is in equilibrium with the radiation, photons are emitted and re-absorbed constantly
- *inviscid* : Absence of any internal friction or dissipation within the fluid; the entropy (and often also the energy) is exactly conserved

The equation of motion for a homogeneous ideal fluid in absence of an external force, is the *Euler's equation* (Euler, 1757):

fundamental
equations

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{grad}) \mathbf{v} \right) = -\mathbf{grad} P \quad (3.5)$$

where t is the coordinate time.¹ Eq. 3.5 reflects nothing more than the conservation of linear momentum within any volume dV .

The conservation of mass is expressed in the *continuity equation*: Any current density $\rho \mathbf{v}$ flowing out of its enclosing shell of area $d\mathbf{A}$ must equal the change in time of the mass enclosed within the volume V . The integral and differential form can respectively be written as:

$$\oint \rho \mathbf{v} \cdot d\mathbf{A} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int \rho dV \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \rho \text{div} \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{grad} \rho = 0 \quad (3.6)$$

The conservation of energy may generally be expressed as the substantial derivative² of the total energy being equal to the sum of heat conduction across the surface, of work

substantial
derivative

¹ Additional external forces $\rho \mathbf{K}$ acting on any unit volume may be added on the right hand side of Eq. 3.5.

² The substantial or convective derivative of any field f is given by $D_t(f) = \partial_t(f) + \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{grad} f$

being done on the surface as fluid moves across the surface, and possible contributions from sources and sinks.

$$\partial_t e + \mathbf{div} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_{\text{bulk}} e) + P \mathbf{div} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{\text{bulk}} + \mathbf{div} \cdot \mathbf{q} = \text{heating} - \text{cooling} \quad (3.7)$$

Still missing is the closure relation, or *equation of state* (EoS) for the internal energy e and the pressure P . The former is generally given by a *caloric* EoS $e = e(V, T)$, the latter by a *thermal* EoS $P = P(V, T)$.

The above are the four essential ingredients for any formalism describing fluids: the equation of motion, equation of continuity, equation of energy and equation of state. However, they may be almost arbitrarily complicated by inclusion of external fields, non-isotropy and more realistic microphysics. Usually this then involves either higher moments or non-trivial source terms on the right-hand-side of the Boltzmann equation.

Eulerian versus Lagrangian description

There exist essentially two ways of describing fluid motion, both of which are used in this thesis:

1. **Eulerian.** In this picture, the fluid velocity field $\mathbf{v}(t, x, y, z)$ is specified at all locations in space for all times t : the fluid motion is thus described by \mathbf{v} alone. The numerical discretisation is achieved by representing space-time in finite "cells" $(\Delta t, \Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z)$. The Eulerian picture commonly implies using a static or moving mesh, whereas the discretisation may be uniform, dynamically adaptive or statically non-uniform.
2. **Lagrangian.** This method follows each fluid particle along its trajectory and thus discretises not in space, but in *mass*. For a full characterisation of the motion, the fluid position field $\mathbf{r}(x, y, z)$ is specified at all times t . The particles are viewed as interpolation points or sampling points for the fluid. A mesh is sometimes not required at all or be comoving with the fluid particle.

Shocks

The phenomenon that arguably presents one of the big challenges in modelling fluids¹ are *shocks*: Any disturbance propagates at the soundspeed c_s relative to the fluid, if, however, the flow speed², v , exceeds the soundspeed, the fluid can no longer adjust to the disturbance because it cannot propagate any signals faster than c_s . The region, into which communication is not possible in the supersonic flow, is called *upstream* whereas the wake region is called *downstream*. The *Mach number* \mathcal{M} denotes the ratio between v/c_s and the region enclosed by the angle $\alpha = \arcsin(c_s/v)$ where disturbances can still propagate is called the *Mach cone*. For increasingly supersonic ($\mathcal{M} > 1$) flow the Mach cone becomes increasingly narrow ($\alpha \rightarrow 0$).

Shocks can only form if $\mathcal{M} > 1$, however, supersonic speed alone does not result in a shock, rather the relative motion between two fluid elements where one impacts on the other supersonically produces shocks. This can also be viewed from the restframe of the slower fluid element, or more generally *the obstacle*. If a supersonic fluid hits an obstacle at point x_0 , then no signal can propagate upstream from x_0 and a true discontinuity forms at x_0 . This

¹ Turbulence and contact discontinuities are other major headaches

² The speed a disturbance perceives the fluid to move relative to itself

Mach number \mathcal{M}

true discontinuity

discontinuity presents a boundary between two regions of fluid where conditions "jump"; however, the conditions like conservation of energy, momentum and matter apply also across this so-called *shock front*. It is that the differential form of the conservation laws is no longer valid and only their integral form can be used to determine the boundary conditions between the two fluid regions. Mathematically speaking, it is useful to write down the three conservation laws one-dimensionally in the direction normal to the shock front (denoted as x in this Section).

$$\partial_t \mathbf{u} + \partial_x \mathcal{F} = 0 \quad (3.8)$$

where

$$\mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \end{bmatrix} \equiv \begin{bmatrix} \rho(x,t) \\ v(x,t)\rho(x,t) \\ E(x,t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{F} \equiv \begin{bmatrix} v(x,t)\rho(x,t) \\ \rho(x,t)v(x,t)^2 + P(x,t) \\ v(x,t)(E(x,t) + P(x,t)) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.9)$$

If the shock front is perceived as an infinitesimal layer dx , then the time derivatives vanish and only the spatial terms in Eq. (3.8) need to be considered for the three jump conditions, where $E(x,t)$ is the total energy density:

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{upstream}} = \mathcal{F}_{\text{downstream}} \quad (3.10)$$

In words this means, that the current density, $\rho \mathbf{v}$, the sum of thermal and ram pressures, $\rho v^2 + P$, and that the energy flux $\mathbf{v}(E + P)$ is constant across the boundary.

These three relations are named the *Rankine-Hugoniot* conditions and they are, in principle, reversible. Cast into thermodynamic quantities, however, the third relation can be used to show that the entropy across the shock front must always increase, thus revealing the irreversible nature of shocks (Clarke & Carswell, 2003)¹. For this, we assume the flow to be perfectly adiabatic², i.e. γ to be the same on both sides of the shock³, absence of heat conduction and no mixing.

Rankine-Hugoniot conditions

First, the third line of Eq. (3.10) is divided by ρv , then the following definitions for adiabatic flows are used for algebraic manipulation:

$$P = \text{const } \rho^\gamma \quad P dV = P d\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right) = \text{const } \rho^\gamma d\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right) = \frac{1}{\gamma-1} \frac{P}{\rho} = e \quad (3.11)$$

$$E = \frac{1}{2}v^2 + e \quad c_s^2 = \gamma \frac{P}{\rho}$$

$$\frac{1}{2}v_{\text{up}}^2 + \frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1} \frac{P_{\text{up}}}{\rho_{\text{up}}} = \frac{1}{2}v_{\text{down}}^2 + \frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1} \frac{P_{\text{down}}}{\rho_{\text{down}}}$$

to arrive at

$$\frac{\rho_{\text{down}}}{\rho_{\text{up}}} = \frac{v_{\text{up}}}{v_{\text{down}}} = \frac{(\gamma+1)P_{\text{down}} + (\gamma-1)P_{\text{up}}}{(\gamma+1)P_{\text{up}} + (\gamma-1)P_{\text{down}}} \quad (3.12)$$

In the above form the third Rankine-Hugoniot Eq. (3.12) shows, that in general:

$$\frac{P_{\text{up}}}{\rho_{\text{up}}^\gamma} \neq \frac{P_{\text{down}}}{\rho_{\text{down}}^\gamma} \quad (3.13)$$

which means, that in a shock, the gas jumps from an adiabat of lower entropy to one of higher entropy (Clarke & Carswell, 2003). This is an essential observation, since it

entropy generation

¹ The assumption of an adiabatic shock ($dQ=0$) is not in contradiction with an entropy increase

² Another important assumption is that the cooling time scale is long compared the life time of the shock as well as that external forces vary much smoother than the shock width

³ γ could change e.g.if molecules dissociate thus the chemical potential change

states that the occurrence of shocks always implies the presence of *viscosity* or generally a dissipative effect. This simply reflects the physical fact that the inviscid Euler equations do not hold at discontinuities, where entropy is generated by (unmodelled) microphysics and that a flow may be well described as inviscid as long as it remains smooth, but a special treatment is necessary whenever shocks arise.

3.1 Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH)

The first technique used in this thesis for approximating fluid dynamics on a computer is of *Lagrangian* nature: Smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) in its modern form is derived from variational principals in order to achieve its excellent conservation properties. The following Section uses the collected information of the following reviews: [Monaghan \(1992, 2005\)](#); [Dolag et al. \(2008\)](#); [Rosswog \(2009\)](#); [Springel \(2010\)](#)

3.1.1 The Hydro

As stated in the previous Section, all derivatives are evaluated in a coordinate system following the moving fluid particle. This allows the expression of the equation of continuity, motion and energy by means of the substantial derivative D :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D\rho}{Dt} + \rho \mathbf{grad} \cdot \mathbf{v} &= 0 \\ \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} + \frac{\mathbf{grad} P}{\rho} &= 0 \\ \frac{De}{Dt} + P \mathbf{grad} \cdot \mathbf{v} &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

According to [Eckart \(1960\)](#) the Lagrangian \mathcal{L} and its discretisation in terms of fluid particles \mathcal{L}_{SPH} ([Springel & Hernquist, 2002](#)) is given by:

$$\mathcal{L} = \int \rho \left(\frac{\mathbf{v}^2}{2} - e \right) dV \quad \mathcal{L}_{\text{SPH}} = \sum_i \left(\frac{m_i \mathbf{v}_i^2}{2} - m_i e_i \right) \tag{3.15}$$

where m_i denotes the mass of each fluid particle. The EoS can conveniently be expressed via an entropic function A_i and the adiabatic index γ^1 :

$$P_i = A_i \rho_i^\gamma = (\gamma - 1) \rho_i e_i \tag{3.16}$$

If entropy is conserved², however, it is useful to express the specific internal energy rather than the pressure P in terms of the entropic function A_i , since A_i is then constant. Thus A_i can be used interchangeably with the specific entropy times a constant factor:

$$e_i(\rho_i) = A_i \frac{\rho_i^{\gamma-1}}{(\gamma-1)} \tag{3.17}$$

density estimate

No matter if one chooses to evolve the entropy or the energy within the scheme: knowledge

¹ Note that this assumes the absence of heat transport and restricts the treatment to adiabatic processes

² Which is true for reversible gas dynamics, see § 3.1.2 for non-reversible processes such as shocks

of the density is required. This leads to the central question of the SPH formulation: How to estimate the density ρ_i ?

Due to the fact that SPH does not require any mesh, the notion of a finite volume element is absent a priori. However, the Eq.s (3.14) are written explicitly in terms of the density ρ . Thus, it is essential to *associate* any point within the simulation volume with the fluid variables $f(\mathbf{r})$. As each fluid particle is nothing but a numerical representation of a Dirac δ , it is natural to *smooth*¹ the point particles using a convolution kernel $W(\mathbf{r}, h)$. This also introduces the characteristic length of the kernel h , the *smoothing length*, which reduces the convolution kernel to the Dirac δ in the limit $h \rightarrow 0$.

smoothing kernel

$$f(\mathbf{r})_{\text{smoothed}} = \int f(\mathbf{r}') W(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', h) d\mathbf{r}' \quad (3.18)$$

The choice of the kernel $W(\mathbf{r}, h)$ is not unique, but the following properties are very useful:

kernel properties

- The kernel should have *finite support*:
 $W(\mathbf{r}, h)$ drops to zero at a distance of $r = nh$, where the most common value for n is two.
- $W(\mathbf{r}, h)$ be symmetric.
- $W(\mathbf{r}, h)$ must be normalized to unity: $\int W(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', h) d^3\mathbf{r}' = 1$
- $W(\mathbf{r}, h)$ must be at least *twice* differentiable.
- It must approximate the Dirac δ : $\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \int f(\mathbf{r}') W(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', h) d\mathbf{r}' = f(\mathbf{r})$

For three dimensions all this can be realised by a cubic spline like, as it is used here, the following form:

$$W_{3D}\left(\frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{nh}\right) \equiv \frac{8}{\pi} \begin{cases} 1 - 6\left(\frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{nh}\right)^2 + 6\left(\frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{nh}\right)^3 & 0 \leq \frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{nh} \leq \frac{1}{2}, \\ 2\left(1 - \frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{nh}\right)^3 & \frac{1}{2} \leq \frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{nh} \leq 1, \\ 0 & \frac{|\mathbf{r}|}{nh} > 1 \end{cases} \quad (3.19)$$

Assuming knowledge of the fluid variable $f(\mathbf{r})$ in a sufficient number of spatial points r_i , and associating every point with a mass m_j and density ρ_j , the finite volume element becomes $\Delta\mathbf{r}_j = m_j/\rho_j$. Thus the integral of Eq. (3.18) can be written in a discretised form:

$$f(\mathbf{r})_{\text{smoothed}} = \sum_j \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} f_j W(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', h) \quad (3.20)$$

If the set of points are randomly distributed, Eq. (3.20) corresponds to a Monte-Carlo integration (Springel, 2010), however the more regular the distribution of points the better the accuracy of approximating the underlying function f . In an astrophysical plasma, the spacing of particles is not Poissonian (as would be expected for a true Monte-Carlo), but rather equidistant as pressure gradients constantly try to equilibrate the inter-particle distances d .

In fact, the average spacing d between the points must always be smaller than the numerical size of the SPH particle, i.e. the local smoothing length h , which introduces another key parameter of the (common) SPH formulation: the neighbours. If the kernel is of finite support, there is a finite number of points N_{ngb} that lie within the spherical

smoothing length

neighbours

¹ thus the name *Smoothed* particle hydrodynamics

constant kernel
volume

region of radius $|\mathbf{r}| = nh$ around the selected point \mathbf{r}_j . This number of neighbours is, in practise, a parameter that is chosen initially and kept constant throughout a simulation optionally allowing only for small deviations $\Delta N_{ngb}/N_{ngb} \ll 1$ ¹, whereas the smoothing length is allowed to vary. N_{ngb} must be large enough to guarantee sufficient sampling of the kernel volume and low numbers can lead to increased noise and wrong propagation speeds in the fluid. On the other hand, the computational cost scales as $\mathcal{O}(N_{ngb}N)$ which is why (i) kernels with finite support are much preferred², (ii) the minimal sufficient N_{ngb} needs to be determined from case to case depending e.g. on the problem geometry Having chosen a good value for N_{ngb} still leaves the problem of approximating $f(\mathbf{r})$ well in regions of varying density: The smoothing length h needs to be adapted as a function of position $h = h(\mathbf{r}, t)$ ³ to satisfy the (implicit) relation (Springel, 2005)⁴:

$$\frac{4\pi}{3}(nh_i)^3 \rho_i = N_{ngb} m_i = \text{constant} \quad (3.21)$$

where a constant particle mass m_i is assumed. Eq. (3.21) guarantees that the kernel volume of particle i contains a constant mass for the estimated density ρ_i . Using this so-called *gathering* approach, only knowledge of h_i is required to estimate the density ρ_i :

$$\rho_i = \sum_j^N m_j W(\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j, h_i) \quad (3.22)$$

Note, that Eq. (3.22) is obtained from Eq. (3.20) by setting $f(\mathbf{r})_{\text{smoothed}} \equiv \rho(\mathbf{r})$ ⁵. However, owing to the fact that Eq.s (3.21) and (3.22) are both functions of ρ and h , the individual h_i still have to be iteratively determined via a shooting method (e.g. a Newton-Raphson).

equation of motion

Having written down the Lagrangian \mathcal{L}_{SPH} in Eq. (3.15), the equation of motion follows from the Euler-Lagrange equation:

$$0 = \frac{D}{Dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{r}}_i} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{r}_i} \quad (3.23)$$

$$m_i \frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt} = - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j \frac{P_j}{\rho_j^2} \frac{\partial \rho_j}{\partial \mathbf{r}_i} \quad (3.24)$$

$$= - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j \frac{P_j}{\rho_j^2} \left(\nabla_i \rho_j + \frac{\partial \rho_j}{\partial h_j} \frac{\partial h_j}{\partial \mathbf{r}_i} \right) \quad (3.25)$$

$$= - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j \frac{P_j}{\rho_j^2} \left(1 + \frac{h_j}{3\rho_j} \frac{\partial \rho_j}{\partial h_j} \right)^{-1} \nabla_i \rho_j \quad (3.26)$$

$$= - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j \frac{P_j}{\rho_j^2} \left(1 + \frac{h_j}{3\rho_j} \frac{\partial \rho_j}{\partial h_j} \right)^{-1} \left(m_i \nabla_i W_{ij}(h_j) + \delta_{ij} \sum_{k=1}^N m_k \nabla_i W_{ki}(h_i) \right) \quad (3.27)$$

¹ These deviations are not necessary and may lead to energy conservation errors

² Kernels of infinite support require summation over *all* particles, i.e. $N_{ngb} = N$, yielding an $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ scaling of the algorithm

³ Note, that h is *only* a function of the coordinates, *not* of the density

⁴ This choice of adapting h is not unique, see e.g. Hernquist & Katz (1989) for the so-called *scatter* approach, corresponding to the "classic SPH" formulation rather than the "modern SPH" formulation preferred throughout this thesis

⁵ Note, that also other fields and their derivatives can be computed the same way, however multiple differentiation of the kernel W can be very noisy and is avoided if possible

where ∇_i only acts as a spatial derivative, whereas $\partial/\partial\mathbf{r}_i$ is meant to include the variation of h_i . Introducing the abbreviations:

$$W_{ij}(h) = W(|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j|, h) \quad f_j = \left(1 + \frac{h_j}{3\rho_j} \frac{\partial\rho_j}{\partial h_j}\right)^{-1} \quad (3.28)$$

yields the SPH equation of motion for inviscid, ideal fluids:

SPH equation of motion

$$\frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt} = - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j \left(f_i \frac{P_i}{\rho_i^2} \nabla_i W_{ij}(h_i) + f_j \frac{P_j}{\rho_j^2} \nabla_i W_{ij}(h_j) \right) \quad (3.29)$$

This is the only equation that needs to be solved explicitly. Energy conservation is already incorporated as Eq. 3.21 was already used in the above derivation and because the particle masses m_i stay constant. Additionally, the specific entropy is automatically conserved for reversible processes (see, however, § 3.1.2 for shock-treatment). Conservation of linear and angular momentum follows from the fact, that the Lagrangian \mathcal{L}_{SPH} used to derive the equation of motion is already translationally and rotationally invariant.

3.1.2 The artificial viscosity \mathcal{AV}

As stated above in, the occurrence of shocks implies the presence of viscosity, for otherwise the necessary entropy generation cannot be achieved. So far, the purely inviscid SPH equations were introduced, which must now be modified to account for the dissipation needed to treat shocks properly.

Instead, however, of switching from treatment of the inviscid Euler equations to the viscous Navier-Stokes equations, a much easier trick is usually employed in SPH: a numerical effect that dissipates kinetic energy into heat whenever shocks are detected, the *artificial viscosity* \mathcal{AV} . This effect needs (i) to produce the right amount of entropy and (ii) only be active at the shock itself and go to zero elsewhere.

\mathcal{AV} properties

To this end, a viscous force is added to the equation of motion Eq. (3.29) (Springel, 2010):

$$\frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt}_{\mathcal{AV}} = - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j \Pi_{ij} \nabla_i \frac{1}{2} \{W_{ij}(h_i) + W_{ij}(h_j)\} \quad (3.30)$$

Where Π_{ij} is a symmetric viscosity factor, that may for example be parametrised as (Monaghan, 1997):

$$\Pi_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{-\alpha c_{s_{ij}} \mu_{ij} + \beta \mu_{ij}^2}{\rho_{ij}} & \text{if } \mathbf{v}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{ij} < 0 \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad \mu_{ij} = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{ij}}{|\mathbf{r}_{ij}|} \quad (3.31)$$

where double indices as in $c_{s_{ij}}$ denote arithmetic means of the corresponding quantities for the two particles i and j , which here is simply the soundspeed. The parameters α and β regulate the strength of the artificial viscosity and are either chosen at the beginning of a simulation as free parameters, or evolved via a differential equation¹. This form of viscosity is largely of *bulk viscosity* type, however it does not vanish in presence of pure shear flows (Springel, 2010), thus another pre-factor is used to multiply Π_{ij} in order to reduce spurious angular momentum transport when the shear is strong (Springel, 2005):

\mathcal{AV} strength

¹ This is not the case in this thesis, rather $\alpha = \text{const}$, $\beta = 3/2\alpha$

$$f_i^{AV} = \frac{|\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}|_i}{|\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}|_i + |\nabla \times \mathbf{v}|_i} \quad (3.32)$$

so that the resulting force due to artificial viscosity reads:

$$\frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt}{}_{AV} = - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j \frac{f_i^{AV} + f_j^{AV}}{2} \Pi_{ij} \nabla_i \frac{1}{2} \{W_{ij}(h_i) + W_{ij}(h_j)\} \quad (3.33)$$

In general, this force is positive (repulsive) when two particles approach each other and attractive when they recede. However, it needs to be stressed that this viscosity is first of all a numerical trick, which is why it is so important to make it vanish as much as possible when it is not required to produce entropy at shocks. However, the AV can be associated with physical *bulk* and *shear* viscosity by means of comparing coefficients with the Navier-Stokes equation: (See Eq. (3.46) and § 3.1.6 for more discussion on the non-physical resolution scaling of the AV .)

AV as
non-conservative
force

Note, that the AV is so far the only non-conservative effect in the numerical scheme.

3.1.3 The Self-Gravity $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$

Astrophysics is probably the only area of fluid dynamics where gravity cannot be described merely as an external force. Rather the gravitational interaction of the fluid elements with each other holds key dynamical effects such as gravitational collapse, fragmentation under self-gravity and subsequent star formation; and, in general, secular dynamics of extended massive objects such as e.g. giant molecular clouds, accretion and proto-planetary discs. Thus the Lagrangian \mathcal{L}_{SPH} must be extended to include gravity as a source of potential energy, with the gravitational field being given by the sum over all massive particles $\Phi(\mathbf{r}) = G \sum_i m_i \phi(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i, \varepsilon_i)$:

$$\mathcal{L}_{SPH} = \sum_i \left(\frac{m_i \mathbf{v}_i^2}{2} - m_i e_i \right) - \frac{G}{2} \sum_{ij} m_i m_j \phi(r_{ij}, \varepsilon_j) \quad (3.34)$$

gravitational
softening
N-body sum

There are three things to be said about implementing such an additional term:

- (i) Due to the $1/r$ nature of gravity, the parameter ε must be introduced to *soften* the interaction when two particles get too close, lest the potential diverges. This *softening length* is a priori unrelated to the aforementioned smoothing length, however, in practise, they are often coupled and use the same convolution kernel W to reduce the gravitational attraction between two particles approaching closer than a given threshold distance.
- (ii) The double sum in the second term of Eq. (3.34) must be treated with a dedicated gravitational algorithm or dedicated hardware, otherwise the sum will scale as $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ even when this can be avoided¹.
- (iii) If the softening lengths are non-constant, the variation of the Lagrangian yields a second term in the force stemming from $\partial \varepsilon_i / \partial \mathbf{r}_i$ or $\partial \phi_i / \partial \varepsilon_i$.

The additional acceleration due to self-gravity can thus be written (Springel, 2010):

¹ The algorithm selected to deal with gravity is problem depended: For collisional systems, force-accuracy is required to be very high thus the direct summation cannot be avoided, however, in situations where accuracy in the self-gravity part is not so stringent, much cheaper and more efficient algorithms such as hierarchical trees can be used

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt} \text{SG} = & -G \sum_j m_j \frac{\mathbf{r}_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \frac{\partial_r \phi(r_{ij}, \varepsilon_i) + \partial_r \phi(r_{ij}, \varepsilon_j)}{2} \\ & + \frac{G}{2} \sum_j m_j \left(\frac{\varepsilon_i}{3\rho_i} f_i \sum_k m_k \partial_\varepsilon \phi(\mathbf{r}_{ik}, \varepsilon_i) \nabla_i W_{ij}(\varepsilon_i) + \frac{\varepsilon_j}{3\rho_j} f_j \sum_k m_k \partial_\varepsilon \phi(\mathbf{r}_{jk}, \varepsilon_j) \nabla_i W_{ij}(\varepsilon_j) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.35)$$

This first term is simply the symmetrised gravity term, necessary if softening at particle i is different from softening at j . The second term accounts for the adaptive softening itself and reduces to zero for constant and uniform softening ε . If ε is related to h , then its value can be determined by solving the Poisson equation (see [Springel et al., 2001](#)):

$$\nabla^2 \phi(r, \varepsilon) = 4\pi W(r, \varepsilon) \quad (3.36)$$

In this thesis SG is treated in an approximate form via a tree-code. This introduces the second non-conservative effect that affects both energy and angular momentum conservation: energy because of the approximate force expansion and angular momentum because the expansion is not rotationally invariant.

SG as
non-conservative
force

3.1.4 Convergence, Consistency and Stability

Having written down the discretised SPH equations, the implementation still requires a time integrator and a time-step criterion. The method of choice for Hamiltonian problems are symplectic integrators, such as leap-frog or Hermite polynomials, as they avoid secular build up of non-conservative integration errors¹. As a criterion determining the size of the time step, the usual *Courant Friedrich Lewy* (CFL) criterion is used:

CFL condition

$$\Delta t_i = \mathcal{C}_{\text{CFL}} \frac{h_i}{v_{\text{sig}_{ij}}} \quad (3.37)$$

where h_i is again the smoothing length and $v_{\text{sig}_{ij}} = c_i + c_j - 3\mu_{ij}$ the maximum relative signal velocity between particle i and all its j neighbours. The idea behind this criterion is that any time step of an explicit scheme must be smaller ($\mathcal{C}_{\text{CFL}} < 1$) than the local spatial resolution divided by the characteristic propagation speed of information². This criterion reflects that only causally connected areas can influence each other and this is necessary for numerical stability. Additional acceleration due to gravity can lead to the requirement of smaller time-stepping whenever relative accelerations are large, which is why the minimum of these two must be taken:

$$\Delta t_{\text{SG}} = \min \left[t_i, \frac{2\eta\varepsilon}{|\mathbf{a}_i|} \right] \quad (3.38)$$

gravitational force
accuracy

here η is an accuracy parameter specified for each simulation, ε is, as above, the gravitational softening and \mathbf{a}_i is the acceleration vector of particle i . With this choice of time-stepping the Kick-Drift-Kick version of the leap frog has been found to perform superbly and stability has been shown by [Springel \(2005\)](#). The \mathcal{C}_{CFL} value needed to guarantee stability depends on the \mathcal{AV} and particular differential equations solved. For smooth solutions a $\mathcal{C}_{\text{CFL}} < 0.8$ is often enough, however in the presence of shocks I prefer to use values $\mathcal{C}_{\text{CFL}} \leq 0.3$.

Proving consistency of SPH is somewhat tricky. This stems from the fact that the

consistency

¹ Even though the formation of shocks breaks the time-reversibility and would allow for simple Euler schemes, the gravitational forces require the upkeep of the conservation laws otherwise orbital energy is not conserved

² In absence of shocks, magnetic or photon fields that is just the soundspeed c_s

concept of *resolution* is related to the total number of particles N and the number of neighbours N_{nbg} . Simply increasing N , while keeping N_{nbg} constant can lead to convergence to an incorrect physical limit (Rasio, 2000; Springel, 2010). However, if both parameters are increased together so that the smallest resolvable scale decreases, 1D sound wave problems have indeed been shown to consistently recover the physical dispersion relation at all wavelengths.

On the other hand this might not be necessary; if the model under study tolerates errors stemming from the density estimate (which is biased if N_{nbg} is kept constant) up to few percent, then Springel (2010) argues that one may, with good conscience, only increase resolution by increasing N . Moreover, Swegle (1995) first found the *tensile instability*, i.e. that for too many neighbours the increasing danger of clumpyness or *particle pairing* arises.

Convergence has been shown for a one dimensional acoustic wave, which is kept in the linear regime, by Springel (2010). What is shown in Fig. 3.1, is the scaling of the L1 norm

Fig. 3.1: SECOND ORDER CONVERGENCE OF SPH CODE GADGET-2 - Convergence rates for a travelling sound wave in 1D, without artificial viscosity. The power law $L1 \propto N^{-2}$ is inserted in black dashed lines.

Taken from Springel (2010): With friendly permission from Volker Springel

of the velocity of each particle i , v_i :

$$L1(v) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i |v_i - v(x_i)_{analytical}| \quad (3.39)$$

for three different choices of smoothing neighbours N_{nbg} . The second order convergence is as it should be $L1 \propto N^{-2}$, as the numerical leap frog scheme and the cubic spline kernel are second order accurate (for smooth solutions). However, the effective spatial resolution is additionally increased for larger N_{nbg} ¹.

¹ The effective resolution depends also on dimensionality d , so in order to work out the convergence order, one must consider that $h \propto N^{1/d}$, thus the convergence rate is (for a fixed number of N_{nbg} and

However, as nicely the code converges in one dimension, typical issues appear in more-dimensional problems. Again, showing results obtained by Springel (2010)¹, Fig. 3.2 depicts a 2D Riemann problem for which again the $L1(v)$ error is measured against the

Fig. 3.2: LESS THAN FIRST ORDER CONVERGENCE IN 2D - *Left:* Convergence rates for a strong shock in 2D. Open circles represent the binned $L1(v)$ error, solid circles show the individual error. The expected power law $L1 \propto N^{-1}$ is inserted in black dotted lines. The measured power law $L1(v) \propto N^{-0.7}$ in dashed lines. *Right:* Velocity profile of the SPH particles (blue) and the analytic solution (black)

Taken from Springel (2010): With friendly permission from Volker Springel

analytically know solution. The right panel shows the velocity profile v_x across the shock front along the x -axis in a 100×100 resolution; the y -axis is used to add an extended second dimension, however the shock propagation is one-dimensional along x . The blue dots represent the SPH particles and the shock is widened with respect to the analytical solution, additionally there are some oscillations at the discontinuity. This noise is reflected in the convergence rates shown on the left panel, which are notably deviating from the expected $L1 \propto N^{-1}$ rate (black dotted). Open and filled circles represent different binning and averaging of the particles prior to comparison with the known solution: open circles, for which the particles are binned and averaged first, show that eliminating the intrinsic noise leads to reducing the absolute error. However the scaling is, in both cases, less than ideal: $L1(v) \propto N^{-0.7}$. The reason for this behaviour lies in the way derivatives are calculated, or, implicitly equivalent, the intrinsic re-ordering of particles in a conservative SPH formulation (Price, 2012). The employed conservative formulation causes particles to automatically re-adjust their ordering to be regular rather than randomly clumped. This leads to a "counter-noise" in any strong shock phenomenon: in the shock region, the particle ordering is forcibly non-isotropic leading to particles that, rather than remaining at their

SPH convergence
1D vs multi-D

intrinsic SPH noise

a kernel of a p order accuracy) $L1 \propto N^{-p/d}$. The order of the time-stepping scheme can usually be lower than p as long as stability is guaranteed without affecting the convergence order.

¹ Using/Showing only tests done by Volker Springel is motivated by the fact, that this thesis uses his SPH code

compressed positions, repel each other quickly after the shock front.

In general, it can be said that SPH is robust in producing principally correct results for multi dimensional problems, however, it should be noted that noise increases in the presence of strong shocks due to the higher degree of freedom in particle motion. Thus, it is important to perform problem dependent resolution studies to make sure the required accuracy for the given problem can be achieved. See also § 3.1.6 where the GADGET-2 code is tested against some known shortcomings of SPH and De Val-Borro et al. (2007) for a comparison between SPH and Eulerian codes in the context of disc-planet interaction.

3.1.5 The extended GADGET-2: SPH with black holes and β -cooling

This Section describes the public SPH code GADGET-2 employed in this thesis and the modifications implemented for modelling accretion discs around massive black hole binaries.

GADGET-2 was developed and released by Springel (2005) and its SPH implementation is in the entropy-formulation with the artificial viscosity outlined above. The self gravity is treated via a hierarchical multipole expansion, i.e. a *tree* algorithm: distant particles are grouped together into collective clumps and their gravity is evaluated by means of a single monopole¹ force. Thus instead of summing directly over all mutual particles, which for N particles leads to a $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ cost, only local neighbours are summed up directly, whereas more distant particle groups are treated as one *node* leading to the much faster $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ scaling of the gravitational force evaluation.

This, of course, comes at the cost of accuracy in the force calculated, which leads to a parameter α controlling how many nodes of the tree must be considered to keep the relative force error roughly constant:

$$\frac{GM}{r^2} \left(\frac{l}{r}\right)^2 \leq \alpha |\mathbf{a}| \quad (3.40)$$

opening angle The so-called opening angle for any node is given by its mass M , its distance r and its extension l , which compared to the total acceleration $|\mathbf{a}|$ at the last time step gives an estimate of the ratio between truncation error and the total expected force. If criterion Eq. (3.40) is satisfied, the node is considered for the force evaluation². The parameter α must be given at the start of any simulation and remains constant throughout.

The time integration is performed as described in § 3.1.4 employing a second order, symplectic Kick-Drift-Kick leap frog with adaptive time-stepping.

GADGET-2 is efficiently parallelised, however, for highly unevenly distributed mass, as is the case for black holes (BH) surrounded by a disc, the scaling quickly saturates for a given problem size N due to strong acceleration gradients encountered in the central region near the BHs. This ultimately limits the resolution to a few million particles per disc simulation³.

modifications Additionally to the publicly available standard features, I use two important ingredients:

¹ See Springel (2005) for a detailed discussion why monopole moments are sufficient and lead to a good compromise between having a more efficient algorithm that allows for more particles, while each tree force is simpler

² An additional safety criterion is that the particle at (r_1, r_2, r_3) for which the force is evaluated, lies always outside of the tree node centred at $(r_{node,1}, r_{node,2}, r_{node,3}) : |r_k - r_{node,k}| \leq 0.6l$

³ Additionally the total output size becomes prohibitively large if frequent time sampling is required as $N=10$ million gives an uncompressed binary output file of ~ 1 Gb

1. Black holes modelled as *sink particles*, the orbit of which is accurately integrated outside of the gravitational tree and which can accrete particles that cross the *sink radius* r_{sink} , i.e the numerical size of the BH
2. Effective cooling proportional to the local dynamical time-scale of the accretion disc

1. Sink Particles as black holes

Using Cuadra et al. (2006)'s implementation, a black hole particle (BH) is modelled as a Newtonian point particle of a given gravitational softening parameter ϵ and sink radius r_{sink} . First, whenever the radial distance of a neighbouring fluid particle is closer to the BH than r_{sink} , then it is marked as "to be accreted". Next, its mass m_i and linear momentum \mathbf{p}_i relative to the BH are evaluated and added to the BH:

$$\text{if } \sqrt{x_i^2 + y_i^2 + z_i^2} < r_{\text{sink}} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} M_{BH} = M_{BH} + m_i \\ \mathbf{p}_{BH} = \mathbf{p}_{BH} + \mathbf{p}_i \end{array} \right. \quad (3.41)$$

This treatment is extremely simple and as it does not discriminate between bound and unbound particles, it may be regarded as a kind of excision. For post-processing and cross-checking purposes, I store the time and all masses, positions, velocities of the particle and all BHs at any instance, r_{sink} is crossed. As will be shown in § 4.1.2, the conservation of the total angular momentum \mathbf{L} is not violated significantly using this prescription. Using such an excision is equivalent to the assumption that (i) accretion happens cylindrically symmetric with respect to the individual BH, (ii) there is no feedback and (iii) that we neglect any BH spin and evolution thereof.

momentum
conservation

For the time integration of the black holes¹ it is necessary to use direct force evaluation, as the tree method is not accurate enough to yield robust results for secular integration. Thus, the BH particles are taken out of the tree and their relative acceleration towards each other computed and added to the one coming from the surrounding gas previously calculated in the tree:

$$\mathbf{a}|_{BH,1} = \mathbf{a}|_{SPH_{tree}} - \frac{GM_{BH,2}}{(|\mathbf{r}_{BH,1} - \mathbf{r}_{BH,2}|^2 + \epsilon^2)^{3/2}} \mathbf{dr} \quad (3.42)$$

Additionally, BH particles have their own time-stepping to re-evaluate Eq. (3.42) frequently, where this time step is set to be much smaller than the tree update frequency.

2. Energy and angular momentum transport via β -cooling

A prescription, commonly used in literature, is that of a radiative cooling proportional to the local orbital time scale (Gammie, 2001; Rice et al., 2005; Nayakshin et al., 2007; Alexander et al., 2008; Cuadra et al., 2009):

$$\frac{de}{dt}|_{cool} = -\frac{e}{t_{cool}} = -\frac{e}{\beta} = -\frac{e\Omega}{\beta} = -\frac{e}{\beta} \sqrt{\frac{GM}{R^3}} \quad (3.43)$$

with e the specific internal energy of each gas particle and constant β . Purpose of adding such a cooling term are studies (e.g. Gammie, 2001) that suggest, that in cool accretion discs² cooling is the main driver of gravitational instability rather than changes in the surface density. This is because the cooling time scale is smaller than the accretion time

comparison of disc
time scales

¹ I always use *two* BHs, but one could use any number of BHs with some code adjustments

² *Cool* meaning that the discs are geometrically thin $H/R \ll 1$ and optically thick

scale for such discs:

$$t_{acc} \propto \frac{R^2}{H^2 \alpha_{SS} \Omega} \quad t_{cool} \propto \frac{1}{\alpha_{SS} \Omega} \quad (3.44)$$

with α_{SS} the Shakura-Sunyaev viscosity (c.f. § 1.2) and $\Omega = \sqrt{GM/R^2}$. Throughout this thesis, the value for β is chosen to be 10 and constant over the entire disc¹. This is motivated by the fact, that I want to study discs that do not completely fragment during their evolution, as this would require the self-consistent implementation of star-formation. However, this value for β allows the disc to form quasi-stable overdensities and spiral-arms. Additionally, together with adiabatic heating (numerical viscosity), the gas can thus dissipate and redistribute energy, an effect needed for the transport of mass and angular momentum within the disc.

3.1.6 SPH for accretion discs: parameter and resolution tests

Due to the Lagrangian nature of the scheme, SPH will perform well for problems that require resolution in dense regions and do not in voids. Resolution follows mass and thus SPH is ideally suited for self-gravitating objects that contract or even collapse under self-gravity. The code GADGET-2 was designed for cosmological simulations of structure formation and it is not a priori obvious that it would perform well for accretion discs around black holes:

I thus first detail the parameters used in the simulations presented in the thesis, noting which are sensitive and then present a short resolution study of my "standard-model" of a BHB embedded in a gaseous disc to show the validity of my approach.

"Standard model"

First, I will describe the typical accretion disc that I use around the BHB. Since I am interested in the sub- pc separation regime, I assume that the binary torque has already excavated an inner cavity in the gas distribution. I assume that the cooling rate is long relative to the dynamical time scale, preventing disc fragmentation. I consider a binary with an initial mass ratio² $q = M_2/M_1 = 1/3$ and a disc with an initial mass $M_{disc} = 0.2M$, where $M = M_1 + M_2$ is the total mass of the binary. The binary has initial eccentricity e_0 , semi-major axis a_0 , initial dynamical time $t_{dyn} = f_0^{-1} = 2\pi/\Omega_0$, where $\Omega_0 = (GM/a_0^3)^{1/2}$. Both the binary and the disc rotate in the same plane and direction³. The disc is initially axisymmetric, and extends from $2a_0$ - $5a_0$. Its initial surface density profile is given by $\Sigma(R) \propto R^{-1}$, where R is the distance to the centre of mass of the system.

Cuadra et al. (2009) modelled the evolution of low-eccentricity binaries in the system discussed above. They found that $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$ drives the initially uniformly distributed gas into a ring-like configuration located at $R \approx 3a_0$. This ring eventually collapses and later spreads again in roughly the same radial range it had in the initial conditions ($2a_0$ - $5a_0$). However, instead of having a uniform density distribution, the disc displays a clear spiral pattern. Cuadra et al. (2009) found that this configuration remains stable for at least $3000\Omega_0^{-1}$, and that during this time the binary both shrinks and gains eccentricity due to its interaction with the disc.

¹ See Rice et al. (2012) for a recent, detailed study of cooling in SPH. I thank Ken Rice for a discussion on how our current treatment could be improved in the future.

² Unless otherwise stated, subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the primary (more massive) and secondary (less massive) black hole, respectively.

³ Note that in Chapter 5, I model retrograde discs as a non-standard case

co-rotating,
selfgravitating disc

Fig. 3.3: RESOLUTION STUDY WITH 2 AND 8 MILLION PARTICLES - *Top*: short comparison of the iso05 and adia05 models with two different resolutions. *Bottom*: long comparison of the *adia10* model and a slightly eccentric model: There are differences for the different resolutions, but they appear on small time scales and do not seem to influence the long term behaviour. Note that the pink curve stops at $t = 15 \Omega_0^{-1}$, the scales are adapted to show the differences.

Bottom figure taken from Cuadra et al. (2009): With wise and gracious permission from Jorge Cuadra

Initial conditions

In this entire thesis, I skip most of the early transient evolution and start from a snapshot taken from the late stage of a previous run, where the disc has already settled into a steady-state configuration¹. I then change some physical parameters, like the disc mass M_{disc} , the number of particles N , the eccentricity ϵ , or the EoS for the gas inside the central cavity. This is always followed by a shorter relaxation phase again, which must either be excluded from the analysis or, in any case, treated with care.

Discussion of the employed numerical SPH parameters

The relevant numerical parameters are the total number of particles, the accuracy of the self-gravity, the accuracy of the time stepping for the BHB, the tree-opening criterion, the force accuracy, the number of neighbours, the value of the artificial viscosity, the courant factor, the softening and smoothing lengths for hydro and BH particles and the frequency at which the tree must be updated.

size of the black holes

The numerical size of the black hole/sink particles is given by their sink radius (see especially § 4.1.2.2) and their softening. In order to avoid spurious effects, the sink radius must be larger than the smoothing of the surrounding SPH particles and the softening must be smaller than the sink radius. For the two black holes alone, the softening must be smaller than their closest approach throughout an entire simulation (this is relevant for very high eccentricities).

SPH parameters

For the SPH particles, I need to check several requirements. Since I use accretion discs with non-negligible mass, the $S\mathcal{G}$ in the vertical direction must be resolved, i.e:

$$h/H < 0.5 \tag{3.45}$$

where h is the smoothing length and H is the disc scale height (cf. (1.20)). Note that GADGET defines $h = 2\bar{h}$, where \bar{h} is the conventional definition of SPH smoothing length (Springel, 2005). Therefore, all the numbers should be divided by two to get the resolution in the conventional SPH language.

resolution tests

Secondly, I need to resolve shocks and non-linear effects inside the disc: this can best be checked by running the same model using different resolutions. In Fig. 3.3, I am showing two particular models (iso05 and adia05 of § 4.1.2.2) using 2 and 8 million particles and plot the evolution of the semi-major axis over time: It is clear, that the two curves, respectively, are *not* exactly the same. However, this is a very short evolution: Cuadra et al. (2009) ran the same comparison for a very similar model (adia10 of § 4.1.2.2) for a much longer time and found that there are fluctuations in the evolution, but the general trend is qualitatively and quantitatively the same. His result is reproduced in the bottom panel of Fig. 3.3. All of my tests here use models that are discussed in detail in Chapter 4, and the nomenclature is the following: adia or iso denote the EoS used inside the cavity, the number following is the sink radius r_{sink} in code units, which is either 0.05 or 0.1, in particular adia10 corresponds to the circular model of Cuadra et al. (2009).

The reason that I do not repeat the long test, is that these 8 million particle runs are extremely expensive and we had no indication that the behaviour would be influenced systematically, i.e. the qualitative results of our simulations hold under both resolutions.

To further illustrate this, I also show the time-averaged torques (used in § 4.1.3) in Fig. 3.4, for the two runs adia05 and iso05 in both resolutions. While there is a difference in

¹ The very first initial data was given to me by Jorge Cuadra

Fig. 3.4: RESOLUTION STUDY WITH 2 AND 8 MILLION PARTICLES: AVERAGED TORQUES - Averaged gravitational torques from the disc onto the black holes as a function of radius from the centre of mass for two models in two resolutions: *Top panels:* high resolution, *Low panels:* low resolution, *Right:* "iso" models *Left:* "adia" models. The models iso05 and adia05 are the same as used in § 4.1.3, but averaged over a smaller interval. i8M is the high-resolution version of iso05; adia8M is the high-resolution version of adia05. In each panel the differential torque on the **primary is shown in green**, on the **secondary in red**, the **sum of the two in blue**, and the total integrated torque (black) according to Eq. (4.7). This latter is integrated starting from $r = a$ inwards and outwards.

the noise, the main features are the same in both cases for both resolutions: the location of the extrema, the height of the extrema up to small variations and also the accretion rates of the individual black holes (not shown).

As one of the main reasons for the differences between the two resolutions, the artificial viscosity comes to mind. The standard α viscosity parameter (cf. § 3.1.2) corresponds to a physical viscosity that depends linearly on the resolution, (i.e. the smoothing length h), with shear ν and bulk μ components given by:

$$\nu = \frac{1}{10} c_s h \alpha \quad \mu = \frac{5}{30} c_s h \alpha \quad (3.46)$$

where c_s is the soundspeed (Price, 2012), which is usually only marginally affected by resolution in the discs under consideration here.

The only problematic region in these discs is the central cavity: while the main disc is dense

resolution
dependence of \mathcal{AV}

cavity difficult to
resolve

Fig. 3.5: RESOLUTION STUDY WITH 2 AND 8 MILLION PARTICLES: MAPS - (*Bottom*) low-resolution model iso05 on the left, adia05 on the right. (*Top*) high-resolution model i8M on the left and adia8M right. The color encodes the smoothing length in code units inside the cavity $r < 2a$. The x -axis shows the azimuthal direction in the range $[0, 2\pi]$, the y -axis shows the radial direction in the range $[0, 2a]$, where the origin is located at the binary centre of mass.

and thus always very well resolved, the cavity can be almost completely devoid of gas in places.

This fact does not change too much by increasing the number of particles and the important question is what happens at the inner edge of the disc (numerically). The fact that the empty region itself is not well resolved is not a major problem, because it is empty anyway. However, whenever the focus lies on accretion onto the black holes, gas needs to pass from the main disc through the empty region in the form of thin streams and join with the so-called *mini-disc* structure around the individual black hole, before it gets eventually accreted. Thus, both the flux into the cavity can be influenced by bad hydro resolution and an excess of \mathcal{AV} . Also, can the accretion rate become noisy if the smoothing length of the SPH-particle is larger than the sink-radius of the BH.

In order to address the question of resolution inside the cavity, I measure the nominal resolution inside $r < 2a$ as shown in Figs 3.5, where the smoothing length h is given as a color coded map in code units for the two models again in both resolutions.

What is observed here is, in the upper part of each map, the inner rim of the main disc, whereas in the bottom there is the mini-disc region. These maps are obtained by binning h of all particles within $r + dr, \phi + d\phi$ within the height, H , wherein more than 66% of the mass at that radius is contained. This has the effect that the adia models appear to have

accreted particles

Fig. 3.6: CROSS CHECKING THE NATURE OF ACCRETED PARTICLES - Apoastron of accreted (bound) particles, assuming Keplerian orbits around the accreting BH. **Blue** histograms are for particles accreted by M_1 , **red** histograms are for particles accreted by M_2 . The vertical ticks represent the Roche lobe size r_{RL} of M_1 (**blue**) and M_2 (**red**). Solid histograms are for simulations with $r_{\text{sink}} = 0.05$ and dashed histograms are for $r_{\text{sink}} = 0.1$

much worse resolution, but it should be noted that the H is much smaller for the iso models (as is discussed in § 4.1.1). In any case, the vertical resolution for the 2 Million runs is¹: $h/H \sim 2$ in the streams, and $h/H \sim 0.3$ in the minidisks for the iso runs. In the adia runs, the streams are described with $h/H \sim 0.8$, while the minidisks are less pronounced, and have $h/H \sim 0.4$. That means, that self gravity is not resolved in the streams, but anywhere else it is. And, that the only run, in which accretion could be expected to be affected by noise is the adia05 model, as $r_{\text{sink}} \lesssim h$.

To assess the actual nature of the accreted particles, several additional checks can be done a posteriori. This is possible because I record all the properties of the accreted particles just before crossing the sink radius. From their positions and velocities, we compute their energy status with respect of the accreting BH, and their orbits in the Keplerian approximation. Referring to [Bate et al. \(1995\)](#), we check that accreted particles are bound to the accreting BH, and that they are more bound to the accreting BH than to the other hole. We computed the *Roche lobe* (RL) of each BH and the Keplerian orbit of each particle at the moment it is accreted. The instantaneous apoastron r_{apo} of the particles can then be compared to the size of the RL, r_{RL} , of the accreting BH. Results are shown in Fig. 3.6. Basically all the particles accreted by M_1 are well within the RL for both sink radii in all simulations. On the other hand, many particles accreted by M_2 are borderline with the RL when the sink radius is 0.1. However, only about 5% (iso10) run and 8% (adia10) of them would end up outside the RL of M_2 had they not been accreted. This is a small fraction, and it is consistent with the fact that the accretion with the two sink radii is basically the same

¹ Note that the standard definition of $H = c_s/\Omega$ leads to better numbers, thus the numbers stated here are conservative.

for the iso runs (cf. Tab. 4.2).

The situation is a bit more complicated for the adia runs. Many particles in the adia10 would not be accreted in the adia05 even though they are well within the M_2 RL. This can be attributed to the different hydrodynamical properties of the material around the two BHs. In the iso runs, particles circularize around the accreting BHs, form well defined dense minidisks and progressively dissipate their angular momentum by interacting with the dense medium. Particles that are in the RL will lose their angular momentum rather quickly, being eventually accreted, whether the sink radius is 0.1 or 0.05. In the adia runs, particles form a low density cloud and fail in losing quickly their angular momentum even if they are in the RL of the accreting BH. In this case, repeated three body interaction with the other BH (we can see it as a continuous tidal forcing) may eventually eject them out of the RL, and this is why we see the different accretion on M_2 in the adia runs. In this case the dynamics related to accretion is affected by the value of r_{sink} . Note, however, that particles accreted on M_1 have $r_{\text{apo}} \lesssim 0.3r_{\text{RL}}$ in the adia10 run, and most of them are also accreted in the adia05 run. Similarly, we can speculate that most of the particles accreted by M_2 in the adia05 run will be accreted for any smaller value of r_{sink} , since they also satisfy $r_{\text{apo}} \lesssim 0.3r_{\text{RL}}$. Accretion rates obtained in the adia05 run should therefore be a good approximation of the true accretion rates under the physical assumptions of the simulations (i.e., no heating by accretion feedback, no winds or similar radiation feedback effects).

numerical
accretion rates
reasonable within
current
assumptions

List of standard SPH parameters

The standard values for my discs are listed in Tab. 3.1. Apart from the global resolution N , also other parameters were tested. I tried a run with 2 different $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$ accuracies: the one listed and half its value. I found no significant differences apart from the fact that the CPU consumption was about > 5 times higher. The force accuracy is another matter: it can help with energy conservation and it is only mildly expensive. The CFL factor must be smaller than the theoretical stability prediction, but I rather use lower values and test for each model, starting at $\mathcal{C}_{\text{CFL}} = 0.3$. In fact, I often use $\mathcal{C}_{\text{CFL}} = 0.15$ for critical runs. The tree update frequency must be compared with how fast clumps of mass relocate throughout space, and choosing a value of 0.1 means that the BHB rotates a $0.1/(2\pi)^{\text{th}}$ of its orbit before the tree is updated. Since the BHB is the heaviest and at the same time fastest moving object, this parameter must be chosen smaller for eccentric BHBs. The same applies to the time step size Δt for the BHB, which should be adaptive for eccentric BHBs. I choose the time steps to be equidistant in velocity, because tests showed that this choice conserves the energy of the BHB well.

BH time stepping

The choice of the remaining parameters is standard, where only the Softening of the BHB must be smaller than the sink radius and smaller than the closest approach at apoastron.

Table 3.1: Typical SPH parameters that are used unless otherwise specified

Parameter	value	Parameter	value	Parameter	value
N	2000000	N_{nbg}	42	Softening SPH	0.001
force accuracy	0.05	\mathcal{C}_{CFL}	0.3	Softening BHB	0.01
$\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$ accuracy η	0.1	$\mathcal{A}\mathcal{V}$	1.0	Δt_{max}	0.05
tree update	0.1	Δt BHB	0.001	ratio Softening/Smoothing	0.1

SPH as the tool of choice for large scale BHB problems

Having now outlined the numerical procedure and discussed the specific application to binary black holes in large discs, I would like to conclude with a summary of why I believe, SPH is the most convenient numerical approach here:

(i) SPH is a very robust technique, i.e. it takes some effort to make SPH codes crash. While this can be dangerous and the physical validation is always required a posteriori, it is a real blessing when comparing it with the work on grid-based codes, where the choice of atmosphere and boundary conditions can destroy so much.

(ii) Conservation laws are implicit in the Lagrangian and there is no numerical dissipation other than the \mathcal{AV}^1 . This has a huge advantage over grid codes where numerical resistivity, viscosity and mass loss must be measured each time for the given choice of parameters.

(iii) SPH does not require adaptive mesh refinement because resolution will automatically be good wherever there is high density.

(iv) It does not require excision around the black hole binary as some grid codes do unless they are equipped with a moving puncture formulation. Thus for a problem, where full three dimensional, secular dynamics are needed that do not contain clear symmetries, where exact shock/rarefaction propagation is not required and where contact discontinuities do not play a role, I would always favour SPH over a grid based technique. However, it must be said, that almost each point, with the exception of robustness, that I listed as an advantage, can also be of disadvantage in other applications. The intrinsic SPH noise and its problems with some of the fluid instabilities are foremost, but much work is being put into resolving these issues. Furthermore it is hard to increase resolution in tenuous regions of the domain. Additionally, the resolution scaling of the \mathcal{AV} and generally, many of its properties are not those expected for a physical viscosity. In the presence of accreting sink particles, the resolution changes over time, because particles are swallowed. The intrinsic re-ordering of the particles makes it almost impossible to perform stringent convergence tests. These and more shortcomings of SPH can be, at least partially, alleviated given enough effort, but if one can show that they are not of importance (at least compared with the shortcomings of a comparably CPU-expensive grid code) SPH is certainly much more flexible and less tedious to work with².

3.2 General relativistic radiation hydrodynamics (GR-RHD)

This Chapter first briefly describes the governing equations of hydrodynamics in general relativity and *one* possible numerical method to treat these in conservative form in § 3.2.1. The Chapter makes heavy use of literature referring to the ECHO-code: Del Zanna et al. (2007); Zanotti et al. (2010, 2011), direct quotes from Del Zanna et al. (2007) are identified by the superscript $\mathcal{DZ07}^3$. The interaction with radiation in the optically thick regime follows the treatment first outlined by Farris et al. (2008). The ECHO-code is a non-public code and its radiation version is currently developed by Olindo Zanotti and myself. The code is also verified for GR-magnetohydrodynamics, however magnetic fields are not considered

¹ The $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{S}$ can always be treated in exact fashion, if need be

² I should note that I have never worked with a non-relativistic grid code, thus my personal impression might well be biased. In any case, this expresses only my *personal* impression after working on the specific BHB-disc problem

³ Parts of the code have not been modified at all, but I reproduce them for completeness as they were originally published

in this thesis. Although the described treatment of the fluid is not restricted to a static metric approximation¹, we assume a constant background metric in the form of the Kerr-metric throughout, as it allows significant simplifications of the equations.

3.2.1 The basic formalism

covariant form The first step from Newtonian to relativistic fluid dynamics must be recasting the governing equations into covariant form: This gives the Euler and continuity equations (corresponding to Eqs. (3.5) and (3.6)):

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla_\alpha T^{\alpha\beta} &= 0 \\ \nabla_\alpha(\rho u^\alpha) &= 0\end{aligned}\tag{3.47}$$

where ∇_α is the covariant derivative, ρ the mass density as measured comoving with the fluid of four-velocity u^α . And $T^{\alpha\beta}$ is the total energy-momentum tensor, which can be understood as the sum of the contributions from matter, electromagnetic field, radiation and possibly other interaction terms:

$$T^{\alpha\beta} = T_m^{\alpha\beta} + T_{\text{em}}^{\alpha\beta} + T_r^{\alpha\beta} + \dots\tag{3.48}$$

energy-momentum tensor I will only consider the matter contribution $T_m^{\alpha\beta}$ and the radiation contribution $T_r^{\alpha\beta}$:

$$T_m^{\alpha\beta} = \rho h u^\alpha u^\beta + P g^{\alpha\beta}\tag{3.49}$$

$$T_r^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{c} \int I_\nu N^\alpha N^\beta d\nu d\Omega,\tag{3.50}$$

ideal gas EoS where $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the static metric, $h = 1 + \varepsilon + P/\rho$, ε and P are the specific enthalpy, the specific internal energy, and the thermal pressure, respectively. The equations are closed by an equation of state (EoS), of an ideal-gas, for which the EoS is expressed as

$$P = \rho \varepsilon (\gamma - 1),\tag{3.51}$$

where γ is the (constant) adiabatic index of the gas.

The radiation quantities are $I_\nu = I_\nu(x^\alpha, N^i, \nu)$ the specific intensity² of the radiation, N^α the four-vector defining the photon propagation direction, $d\nu$ the infinitesimal frequency and $d\Omega$ the infinitesimal solid angle around the direction of propagation. The direction of propagation of the photon is defined as $N^\alpha \equiv p^\alpha / h_{\text{pl}} \nu$, where p^α is the photon four-momentum, while h_{pl} and ν are, respectively, the Planck constant and the photon frequency as measured in the comoving frame of the fluid. Since the two terms $\nu d\nu d\Omega$ and I_ν / ν^3 are relativistic invariants (Rybicki & Lightman, 1986), their product with the tensor $p^\alpha p^\beta$ is still a tensor, and indeed it provides the integrand of Eq. (3.50).

moments of radiation In the frame comoving with the fluid, the moments of the radiation field are the energy density, the radiation flux and the radiation stress tensor, which are respectively given by

$$E_r = \frac{1}{c} \int I_\nu d\nu d\Omega,\tag{3.52}$$

$$F_r^\alpha = h^\alpha_\beta \int I_\nu d\nu d\Omega N^\beta,\tag{3.53}$$

$$P_r^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{c} \int I_\nu d\nu d\Omega N^\alpha N^\beta,\tag{3.54}$$

¹ Coupling between spacetime and fluid occurs only in the source terms

² Note that I_ν is an energy flux per unit time, frequency and solid angle, so that in cgs units it has dimensions of $\text{erg cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{Hz}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1}$.

where the tensor $h^{\alpha\beta} = g^{\alpha\beta} + u^\alpha u^\beta$ projects any other tensor into the space orthogonal to u^α , namely $h^{\alpha\beta} u_\alpha = 0$. In terms of such moments the radiation energy-momentum tensor $T_r^{\alpha\beta}$ can be rewritten as (Hsieh & Spiegel, 1976)

$$T_r^{\alpha\beta} = (E_r + \mathcal{P}_r) u^\alpha u^\beta + F_r^\alpha u^\beta + u^\alpha F_r^\beta + \mathcal{P}_r g^{\alpha\beta}, \quad (3.55)$$

where E_r and \mathcal{P}_r are the radiation energy density and pressure, respectively.

As in Farris et al. (2008), the additional and strong physical assumption is made that the radiation is very close to being isotropic in the comoving frame of the fluid, thus mimicking the conditions of the optically thick regime. However, while the radiation pressure is actually set to be $\mathcal{P}_r = E_r/3$, as the isotropic assumption implies, the radiation flux is allowed to assume nonvanishing values, although with the constraint that $F_r^i/E_r \ll 1$. Hence, the radiation field is only approximately isotropic.

optically thick
regime

The full set of equations describing the dynamics of the system is thus

full set of
equations

$$\nabla_\alpha(\rho u^\alpha) = 0, \quad (3.56)$$

$$\nabla_\alpha T^{\alpha\beta} = 0, \quad (3.57)$$

$$\nabla_\alpha T_r^{\alpha\beta} = -G_r^\beta. \quad (3.58)$$

While Eqs. (3.56), and (3.57) represent the well known continuity equation and the energy momentum equation already mentioned above, Eq. (3.58) expresses the evolution of the radiation field, where G_r^α is the radiation four-force density. The latter depends on the physical interaction between matter and radiation and is therefore specific to the problem considered. In full generality this tensor is given by (Mihalas & Weibel Mihalas, 1984; Shapiro, 1996)

$$G_r^\alpha = \frac{1}{c} \int (\chi_\nu I_\nu - \eta_\nu) N^\alpha d\nu d\Omega, \quad (3.59)$$

where $\chi_\nu \equiv \chi_\nu^t + \chi_\nu^s$ and $\eta_\nu \equiv \eta_\nu^t + \eta_\nu^s$ are the total opacity and emissivity coefficients¹, each containing a thermal contribution, indicated with the superscript "t", and a scattering one, indicated with a superscript "s". In addition, it is assumed that: (i) the scattering is isotropic and coherent; (ii) the thermal emissivity and the thermal opacity coefficients are related to the Planck function \tilde{B}_ν through Kirchhoff's law $\eta_\nu^t = \tilde{B}_\nu \chi_\nu^t$; (iii) that electrons and ions are maintained at the same temperature; (iv) the opacity coefficients are independent of frequency, $\chi_\nu = \kappa_g \rho$, where κ_g is the grey-body opacity. The last assumption, in particular, prevents taking into account photoionization effects, which are therefore not considered in the analysis.

additional
assumptions

Under these conditions, which are indeed the same considered by Farris et al. (2008), the radiation four-force can be written in covariant form as

$$G_r^\alpha = \chi^t (E_r - 4\pi\tilde{B}) u^\alpha + (\chi^t + \chi^s) F_r^\alpha, \quad (3.60)$$

where $4\pi\tilde{B} = a_{\text{rad}} T^4$ is the equilibrium black-body intensity, with T the temperature of the fluid and a_{rad} the radiation constant. The temperature is estimated from the ideal-gas EoS via the expression

temperature
estimate

¹ Note that although both are referred to as "coefficients", χ_ν and η_ν have different units. The dimensions of χ_ν are cm^{-1} , while those of η_ν are $\text{erg cm}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1} \text{Hz}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1}$.

$$T = \frac{m_p P}{k_b \rho}, \quad (3.61)$$

where k_b is the Boltzmann constant and m_p the rest-mass of the proton. Two contributions to the opacity are considered in this thesis: First is the case of bremsstrahlung opacity (Rybicki & Lightman, 1986):

thermal
bremsstrahlung

$$\begin{aligned} \chi'_{br} &= 1.7 \times 10^{-25} T_K^{-7/2} Z^2 n_e n_i \text{ cm}^{-1} \\ &= 1.7 \times 10^{-25} T_K^{-7/2} \frac{\rho_{\text{cgs}}^2}{m_p^2} \text{ cm}^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.62)$$

where n_e and $n_i \simeq n_e$ are respectively the number densities of electrons and ions (protons) expressed in cgs units, while T_K is the equilibrium temperature of both electrons and protons expressed in Kelvin. Secondly, the scattering opacity is given by the Thomson scattering opacity and recalling that the Thomson cross sections of electrons and protons are: $\sigma_{T,e} = 6.6524586 \times 10^{-25} \text{ cm}^2$ and $\sigma_{T,p} = (m_e/m_p)^2 \sigma_{T,e}$ ¹, respectively. Hence, the Thomson scattering opacities of electrons and of protons are given by

$$\chi_e^s = \sigma_{T,e} n_e = \sigma_{T,e} \left(\frac{\rho}{m_p} \right) = 0.397726 \rho_{\text{cgs}} \text{ cm}^{-1}, \quad (3.63)$$

$$\chi_p^s = \sigma_{T,p} n_p = \sigma_{T,p} \left(\frac{\rho}{m_p} \right) = 1.17968 \times 10^{-7} \rho_{\text{cgs}} \text{ cm}^{-1}. \quad (3.64)$$

Thomson
scattering
optical depth

The electron-scattering opacity dominates over free-free opacity at low densities and high temperatures (Harwit, 1998), where the interaction between electrons and ions is weak. It is worth stressing that, because of the assumptions made, an incoherent process such as Compton scattering, with a cross section that is frequency dependent, cannot be consistently taken into account and it is therefore neglected. Finally, as customary, the optical thickness is defined as the line integral of the opacities between two points in the fluid

$$\tau = \int_0^L (\chi' + \chi^s) ds. \quad (3.65)$$

In practice, we approximate expression (3.65) as $\tau \simeq (\chi' + \chi^s)L$, with L being a typical length scale of the problem.

3.2.1.1 The 3 + 1 splitting of space-time

The GR-RHD equations as written down in their covariant form above are not suitable for numerical integration, where the time coordinate has to be clearly singled out.

ECHO solves the Eq.s (3.56)-(3.58), by adopting a 3 + 1 split of spacetime in which the "spacetime is foliated into non-intersecting space-like hyper-surfaces Σ_t , defined as isosurfaces of a scalar time function t^{DZ07} ." Within this approach, the metric is decomposed according to (Arnowitt et al., 1962)

$$ds^2 = -\alpha^2 dt^2 + \gamma_{ij} (dx^i + \beta^i dt)(dx^j + \beta^j dt), \quad (3.66)$$

lapse and shift

where α is the lapse function, β^i is the shift vector, γ_{ij} is the spatial metric tensor, and

¹ I refer to Appendix A.1 for a summary about the conversion between cgs and geometrized units.

$$n_\mu = -\alpha \nabla_\mu t = (-\alpha, 0_i), \quad (n_\mu n^\mu = -1), \quad (3.67)$$

"is the future-pointing time-like unit vector normal to the slices Σ_t . The observer moving with four-velocity $n^\mu = \{1/\alpha, -\beta^i/\alpha\}$ is called *Eulerian* (Smarr & York, 1978). Any vector V^μ (or similarly a tensor) may be projected in its temporal component $V^{\hat{t}} = -n_\mu V^\mu$ and spatial component $\perp V^\mu = (g^\mu_\nu + n^\mu n_\nu)V^\nu$. As a result, any spatial vector V^μ (or tensor) must necessarily have a vanishing contravariant temporal component $V^t = 0$, whereas its covariant temporal component is $V_t = g_{\mu t} V^\mu = \beta_i V^i$, in general different from zero^{DZ07}." The 3 + 1 splitting procedure just described can be applied to the vectors and tensor introduced so far to yield

$$u^\alpha = \Gamma n^\alpha + \Gamma v^\alpha, \quad (3.68)$$

$$T_m^{\alpha\beta} = W^{\alpha\beta} + S^\alpha n^\beta + n^\alpha S^\beta + U n^\alpha n^\beta, \quad (3.69)$$

$$F_r^\alpha = \alpha F_r^t n^\alpha + f_r^\alpha, \quad (3.70)$$

$$T_r^{\alpha\beta} = R_r^{\alpha\beta} + S_r^\alpha n^\beta + n^\alpha S_r^\beta + U_r n^\alpha n^\beta, \quad (3.71)$$

where all the tensors v^μ , $W^{\mu\nu}$, S^μ , f_r^μ , $R_r^{\mu\nu}$, S_r^μ correspond to the familiar three-dimensional quantities as measured by the Eulerian observers, are purely spatial, and have indices that are raised and lowered by the spatial metric γ_{ij} . In particular, the newly introduced quantities are related to the corresponding quantities in the comoving frame by

$$D \equiv \rho \Gamma, \quad (3.72)$$

$$W^{ij} \equiv \rho h \Gamma^2 v^i v^j + P \gamma^{ij}, \quad (3.73)$$

$$S^i \equiv \rho h \Gamma^2 v^i, \quad (3.74)$$

$$U \equiv \rho h \Gamma^2 - P, \quad (3.75)$$

$$R_r^{ij} \equiv \frac{4}{3} E_r \Gamma^2 v^i v^j + \Gamma (f_r^i v^j + f_r^j v^i) + \mathcal{P}_r \gamma^{ij}, \quad (3.76)$$

$$S_r^i \equiv \frac{4}{3} E_r \Gamma^2 v^i + \Gamma (\alpha F_r^t v^i + f_r^i), \quad (3.77)$$

$$U_r \equiv \frac{4}{3} E_r \Gamma^2 + 2\alpha \Gamma F_r^t - \frac{E_r}{3}. \quad (3.78)$$

A few comments about the quantities in the equations above can be useful. The vectors v^i and f_r^i are the velocity and the radiation flux, respectively, as measured by the Eulerian observers, while $\Gamma = (1 - v^2)^{-1/2} = \alpha u^t$ is the Lorentz factor of the bulk flow. In particular, the radiation flux vector is $f_r^i = F_r^i + \beta^i F_r^t$ where F_r^t is computed from the orthogonality condition $F_r^\alpha u_\alpha = 0$ and is given by

$$F_r^t = \frac{v_i F_r^i}{\alpha - \beta_i v^i} = \frac{v_i f_r^i}{\alpha}. \quad (3.79)$$

It is interesting to note that $U_r = R_r^{\alpha\beta} n_\alpha n_\beta$ is the radiation energy density as measured by the Eulerian observers, in analogy with what happens for the conserved energy density of the fluid U defined by Eq. (3.75).

3.2.1.2 High-resolution shock-capturing (HRSC) methods

The general-relativistic radiation-hydrodynamics equations are then written in the following conservative form

$$\partial_t \mathcal{U} + \partial_i \mathcal{F}^i = \mathcal{S}, \quad (3.80)$$

which is appropriate for numerical integration via standard *high-resolution shock-capturing* (HRSC) methods developed for the Euler equations. The conservative variables and the corresponding fluxes in the i -direction are respectively given by

$$\mathcal{U} \equiv \sqrt{\gamma} \begin{bmatrix} D \\ S_j \\ U \\ U_r \\ (S_r)_j \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{F}^i \equiv \sqrt{\gamma} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha v^i D - \beta^i D \\ \alpha W_j^i - \beta^i S_j \\ \alpha S^i - \beta^i U \\ \alpha S_r^i - \beta^i U_r \\ \alpha (R_r)_j^i - \beta^i (S_r)_j \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.81)$$

whereas the sources, in any stationary background metric, can be written as

$$\mathcal{S} \equiv \sqrt{\gamma} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \alpha W^{ik} \partial_j \gamma_{ik} + S_i \partial_j \beta^i - U \partial_j \alpha + \alpha (G_r)_j \\ \frac{1}{2} W^{ik} \beta^j \partial_j \gamma_{ik} + W_i^j \partial_j \beta^i - S^j \partial_j \alpha + \alpha^2 G_r^i \\ \frac{1}{2} R_r^{ik} \beta^j \partial_j \gamma_{ik} + (R_r)_i^j \partial_j \beta^i - S_r^j \partial_j \alpha - \alpha^2 G_r^i \\ \frac{1}{2} \alpha R_r^{ik} \partial_j \gamma_{ik} + (S_r)_i \partial_j \beta^i - U_r \partial_j \alpha - \alpha (G_r)_j \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.82)$$

where only purely spatial quantities are present. We note that $\sqrt{\gamma} \equiv \sqrt{-g}/\alpha$ is the determinant of the spatial metric. In the setup for two dimensional simulations presented in Chapter 7 we assume the metric given by the Kerr solution.

Discretisation and Integration

The numerical treatment for spatial and temporal components of the equations is distinctly different.

I will start describing the spatial part, where `ECHODZ07` uses a finite-difference scheme¹: The computational domain is first divided into cells (c.f § 3.2.1.3), each cell having an edge size h_i . The conservative "fluid variables" \mathcal{U}_j are defined at cell centres C with a *point value* representation, i.e that \mathcal{U}_j is the numerical approximation of the real analytical function, with an accuracy given by the order of the spatial scheme. In a conservative approach, the spatial differential operators of divergence and curl are translated numerically by making use of the Gauss and Stokes theorems, respectively. Fluid fluxes \mathcal{F}_j^i ² are calculated at cell interfaces S_i^+ .^{DZ07}

$$\frac{d}{dt} [\mathcal{U}_j]_C + \sum_i \frac{1}{h_i} ([\mathcal{F}_j^i]_{S_i^+} - [\mathcal{F}_j^i]_{S_i^-}) = [\mathcal{S}_j]_C, \quad (3.83)$$

¹ Finite-difference has the advantage over finite-volume in multi-dimensional problems that it only requires one-dimensional reconstruction methods (e.g [Shu, 1997](#))

² These so-called fluxes contain *all* variables, also the radiation, however the term *radiation flux* is reserved for the physical vector F_r introduced in § 3.2

the hat denotes that the numerical flux function was derived using a high order approximation and \pm denotes the opposite faces, or edges, with respect to the direction of derivation. This is a *semi-discrete* form, as the time derivatives remain analytical (see § 3.2.2 for the Method of Lines).

Given this discretisation and while leaving temporal component for later, the code now performs the following logic:

1. From the set of conservative variables \mathcal{U} at time t we choose *primitive* variables \mathcal{P} , so that the functions $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{P})$ and $\mathcal{F}^i = \mathcal{F}^i(\mathcal{P})$ are unique. Here we use set of primitives

$$\mathcal{P} = [\rho, \mathbf{v}, p, \mathbf{F}_r, E_r]^T \tag{3.84}$$

omitting, as they are not used, the magnetic fields, that are also implemented in the code. The inversion routines (commonly called cons-to-prim) implemented for this choice of primitive variables are the usual ones of ECHO complemented by the (analytical) inversion of the radiation quantities (Farris et al., 2008).

2. "For each direction i , ECHO reconstructs the point value approximations of the left (L) and right (R) upwind states of primitive variables, from C to S_x^\pm :" reconstruction

$$[\mathcal{P}_j^{L,R}]_{S_x^\pm} = \mathcal{R}_x^{L,R}(\{[\mathcal{P}_j]_C\}), \tag{3.85}$$

where $\mathcal{R}_x^{L,R}$ is the 1-D reconstruction routine, here named REC, applied to a stencil $\{[\mathcal{P}_j]_C\}$ of cell centred values along x . The index j runs through all fluid components^{DZ07}.

In ECHO, we have the choice of several reconstruction routines of different order. We do not employ characteristic reconstruction, but *component-wise* reconstruction¹:

For second order accuracy we use simple *Total Variation Diminishing* (TVD)-like reconstructions based on limiters (MM2 for the *MinMod*, MC2 for *Monotonized Centered*, SB2 for *SuperBee*). For higher orders we either use *Essentially Non-Oscillatory* (ENO) -like routines: CENO3 for the *Convex-ENO* scheme by Liu & Osher (1998) in third order and WENO5 for the *Weighted-ENO* fifth order scheme (Jiang, 1996). Or, we use the fifth order *Monotonicity Preserving* scheme by Suresh & Huynh (1997), MP5, which is based on interpolation built over a *fixed* 5-point stencil², followed by a filter, basically a combination of limiters to preserve monotonicity near discontinuities.

MP5 is used in all test in § 3.2.3.1, whereas for the IMEX version of the radiation code, we later use MM2 and MC2 in order to compare with WHISKY results and WENO5, as it has proven to be more robust than MP5. CENO3 has been found to work very poorly with radiation, even though, in the purely MHD version of ECHO it was found to work well. Tests have shown that CENO3 introduces non-physical asymmetries in the evolution, not found with any other limiter, thus CENO3 is never used in this thesis. Also the SB2 limiter has not been found to work well with radiation, as it is too sharp, thus strongly introducing noise at discontinuities.

discussion of limiters

3. Using the two-state reconstructed primitive variables, the upwind flux is now derived with an approximate Riemann solver. ECHO uses the HLL approximate solver (Harten et al., 1983) which is based on the knowledge of the two highest characteristic wave speeds. These are just the (absolute) maximum of the sonic speeds and the upwind flux

¹ We also tried characteristic reconstruction, but found no improvements, thus discarding it, as it is overall more expensive and less robust in the atmosphere in the presence of radiation

² ENO schemes employ adaptive stencils rather than fixed stencils

(approximate) estimate of diffusive photon propagation $\lambda_{\text{rad}} = 1/3$ for GR-RHD. " If λ_{\pm}^x are the requested speeds, calculated at both left and right states, we then define the quantities

$$a_{\pm}^x = \max\{0, \pm\lambda_{\pm}^x(\mathcal{P}^L), \pm\lambda_{\pm}^x(\mathcal{P}^R)\} \quad (3.86)$$

and the HLL upwind fluid flux function is

$$\mathcal{F}_j^x = \frac{a_+^x \mathcal{F}_j^{xL} + a_-^x \mathcal{F}_j^{xR} - a_+^x a_-^x (\mathcal{U}_j^R - \mathcal{U}_j^L)}{a_+^x + a_-^x} \quad (3.87)$$

where all quantities are calculated at S_x^+ for each component j and where $\mathcal{F}^{xL,R} = \mathcal{F}^x(\mathcal{P}^{L,R})$, $\mathcal{U}^{L,R} = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{P}^{L,R})$. ^{$\mathcal{DZ07}$}

The coefficients a_{\pm}^x are saved, since they will be needed at step 6 for the timestep definition.

fluid flux
correction

4. "The numerical fluid flux function is retrieved by means of an additional high order procedure, named DER (see the appendix of $\mathcal{DZ07}$ for details; these parts of the code were not altered) which allows one to obtain a high order approximation from the point value quantities calculated at the same intercell locations:

$$[\hat{\mathcal{F}}_j^x]_{S_x^+} = \mathcal{D}_x(\{[\mathcal{F}_j^x]_{S_x^+}\}). \quad (3.88)$$

This correction step is necessary to preserve the accuracy in the calculation of spatial partial derivatives for high order schemes, while it can be avoided for low order $r \leq 2$ schemes, for which the DER operator is just an identity.

5. The fluid flux functions are recovered for all directions i by repeating steps 2-4 and the spatial operator in Eq. (3.83) is calculated. The source terms $[\mathcal{S}]_C$ are also worked out. ^{$\mathcal{DZ07}$}
6. Time-stepping can be finally achieved (see § 3.2.2), and the whole procedure to update the set of conservative variables \mathcal{U} must be repeated for each sub-cycle.

3.2.1.3 Non-uniform stationary grid

non uniform radial
grid

The radial numerical grid is discretized by choosing N_r points from r_{\min} to r_{\max} , non-uniformly distributed according to the following scheme

$$r_i = r_{\min} + a_1 \tan(a_2 x_i), \quad (3.89)$$

$$x_i = (\tilde{r}_i - r_{\min}) / (r_{\max} - r_{\min}), \quad (3.90)$$

where $a_1 = (r_{\max} - r_{\min})/a_0$, $a_2 = \arctan a_0$, while \tilde{r}_i are the coordinate points of the uniform grid from r_{\min} to r_{\max} . In practice, the free parameter a_0 controls the extent to which the grid points of the original uniform grid are concentrated towards r_{\min} . Usually, we choose a_0 in the range $[5 - 10]$ in most of our simulations. The angular grid is taken to be uniform.

uniform angular
grid

3.2.2 Method of lines: Explicit and Implicit-Explicit (IMEX) schemes

The *method of lines* (MoL) is a scheme used for solving PDEs, for which (well-posed) initial values are given in all directions but one. The one missing direction can then be integrated forward using simple ODE integrators. We choose this missing direction to be the time direction and this Section describes the two ways, in which ECHO can solve the time-integration.

Implicit-Explicit (IMEX) Runge Kutta

stiff source terms

A relevant feature of the radiation hydrodynamics equations (3.80) is that they contain sources for the radiation field that may easily become stiff, depending on the physical conditions under consideration. When stiffness is treated by resorting to Implicit-Explicit (IMEX) Runge-Kutta schemes, as we do here, it is crucial to split the conservative variables \mathcal{U} in two subsets $\{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}\}$, with $\{\mathbf{X}\}$ containing the variables that are affected by stiffness, and $\{\mathbf{Y}\}$ containing those that are not affected by stiffness. IMEX Runge-Kutta methods are based on an implicit discretisation for the stiff terms and on an explicit one for the non-stiff terms. They have been extensively discussed in a series of papers by Pareschi & Russo (2005), while a relevant application in resistive relativistic magnetohydrodynamics has been presented by Palenzuela et al. (2009). In full generality, within the IMEX scheme the prototypical hyperbolic equations for the two sets of variables $\{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}\}$ are split as

IMEX scheme

$$\partial_t Y = F_Y(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) \quad (3.91)$$

$$\partial_t X = F_X(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) + R_X(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}), \quad (3.92)$$

where the operator F_Y contains both the first derivatives of \mathbf{Y} and possible nonstiff source terms, the operator F_X contains both the first derivatives of \mathbf{X} and possible nonstiff source terms, while the operator R_X contains the stiff source terms affecting the variables \mathbf{X} . Each Runge-Kutta sub-step of the IMEX scheme can be divided in two parts.

1. In the first part the explicit intermediate values $\{\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{Y}^*\}$ are computed as

$$\mathbf{Y}^* = \mathbf{Y}^n + \Delta t \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \tilde{a}_{ij} F_Y[\mathbf{U}^{(j)}] \quad (3.93)$$

$$\mathbf{X}^* = \mathbf{X}^n + \Delta t \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \tilde{a}_{ij} F_X[\mathbf{U}^{(j)}] + \Delta t \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_{ij} R_X[\mathbf{U}^{(j)}] \quad (3.94)$$

where it is crucial that the summation stops at $(i-1)$, in order to avoid the appearance of the implicit terms at this stage. The matrices (\tilde{a}_{ij}) and (a_{ij}) are $\nu \times \nu$ square matrices whose dimensions and values depend on the actual choice of the accuracy of the scheme and on the number of the substeps taken (Pareschi & Russo, 2005).

2. In the second part, the nonstiff variables are directly promoted to the status of sub-step Runge-Kutta variables, namely

$$\mathbf{Y}^{(i)} = \mathbf{Y}^*, \quad (3.95)$$

while the stiff variables need to be corrected as

$$\mathbf{X}^{(i)} = M(\mathbf{Y}^*) [\mathbf{X}^* + a_{ii} \Delta t \mathbf{K}_X(\mathbf{Y}^*)]. \quad (3.96)$$

The vector $\mathbf{K}_X(\mathbf{Y})$ on the right hand side of Eq. (3.96), which does not depend on the stiff variables \mathbf{X} , results from the decomposition of $R_X(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y})$ as

$$R_X(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) = A(\mathbf{Y})\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{K}_X(\mathbf{Y}) \quad (3.97)$$

while the matrix M is given by (Palenzuela et al., 2009)

inversion matrix

$$M(\mathbf{Y}^*) = [I - a_{ii} \Delta t A(\mathbf{Y}^*)]^{-1}. \quad (3.98)$$

After $\{X^{(i)}, Y^{(i)}\}$ is computed as described above for each Runge-Kutta sub-step, the final time-update is performed as

$$\mathcal{U}^{n+1} = \mathcal{U}^n + \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^v \tilde{w}_i F[\mathcal{U}^{(i)}] + \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^v w_i R[\mathcal{U}^{(i)}], \quad (3.99)$$

where \tilde{w}_i and w_i are coefficient vectors. As a default choice, we have adopted the SSP3(4,3,3) (Strong Stability Preserving of order three) IMEX Runge-Kutta scheme, where the notation SSPk(s, σ, p) is adopted to specify the order of the SSP scheme (k), the number of stages of the implicit scheme (s), the number of stages of the explicit scheme (σ), and the order of the IMEX scheme (p) (Pareschi & Russo, 2005). A tableau notation is usually adopted to express in a compact form the coefficients of the matrices a_{ij} , \tilde{a}_{ij} and of the corresponding vectors ω_i , $\tilde{\omega}_i$ as

$$\begin{array}{c|c} \tilde{c} & a_{ij} \\ \hline & \omega^T \end{array}, \quad (3.100)$$

where the index T denotes transposition¹. So, the explicit tableau of the SSP3(4,3,3) is

$$\begin{array}{c|cccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1/2 & 0 & 1/4 & 1/4 & 0 \\ \hline & 0 & 1/6 & 1/6 & 2/3 \end{array} \quad (3.101)$$

while the corresponding implicit tableau is

$$\begin{array}{c|cccc} q_1 & q_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -q_1 & q_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 - q_1 & q_1 & 0 \\ 1/2 & q_2 & q_3 & 1/2 - q_1 - q_2 - q_3 & q_1 \\ \hline & 0 & 1/6 & 1/6 & 2/3 \end{array} \quad (3.102)$$

with

$$q_1 \equiv 0.24169426078821, \quad q_2 \equiv 0.06042356519705, \quad q_3 \equiv 0.12915286960590.$$

3.2.2.1 Specification to radiation hydrodynamics

Because of the complexity of the relativistic radiation hydrodynamics equations, isolating the term (or the terms) that are responsible for the stiffness is not a trivial task, although we can certainly say that such terms are contained in the radiation four-force density G_r^α . According to the logic of the IMEX scheme just described, we identify $\{X\}$ with the radiation hydrodynamical variables $\{U_r, (S_r)_j\}$ that are affected by stiffness, and $\{Y\}$ with the purely hydrodynamical variables $\{D, S_j, U\}$, which are *not* affected by stiffness.

As highlighted above, the IMEX scheme requires that the stiff source terms R_X are decomposed as in Eq. (3.97). We therefore write the radiation four-force G_r^α in terms of the conservative variables of the radiation field. To this extent, we invert Eq. (3.77) and Eq. (3.78) to find the radiation energy density E_r and the fluxes F_r^α in terms of U_r and $(S_r)_i$ as

¹ Note that the coefficients c_i and \tilde{c}_i , which are defined as $c_i = \sum_{j=1}^i a_{ij}$ and $\tilde{c}_i = \sum_{j=1}^i \tilde{a}_{ij}$ are not used in the practical implementation of the scheme.

$$E_r = -3\Gamma^2 W \left[2(S_r)_k v^k + U_r(1/\Gamma^2 - 2) \right] \quad (3.103)$$

$$F_r^t = \frac{\Gamma}{\alpha} W \left[-4U_r(\Gamma^2 - 1) + (4\Gamma^2 - 1)(S_r)_k v^k \right] \quad (3.104)$$

$$(f_r)_i = \frac{(S_r)_i}{\Gamma} - \frac{4}{3} E_r \Gamma v_i - \alpha (F_r)^t v_i, \quad (3.105)$$

where $W = 1/(1 + 2\Gamma^2)$. In this way, and after some simple algebra, we can rewrite the radiation four force as

$$G_r^t = -\frac{\Gamma}{\alpha} \left[\chi^t a_r T^4 + U_r(2\chi^s(1 - 3W) - \chi^t) + (S_r)_k v^k (\chi^t + \chi^s(3W - 2)) \right] \quad (3.106)$$

$$(G_r)_i = -\chi^t a_r T^4 v_i \Gamma + \frac{(\chi^t + \chi^s)}{\Gamma} (S_r)_i + U_r \Gamma v_i \left[\chi^t(1 - 4W) + 2\chi^s(W - 1) \right] \\ + (S_r)_k v^k \Gamma v_i \left[\chi^t(2W - 1) + \chi^s(2 - W) \right]. \quad (3.107)$$

We notice that the right hand sides of (3.106) and (3.107) do not contain the set of variables $\{Y\}$, while they do contain the conserved variables $\{X\}$, which always appear with a multiplication factor containing either χ^t or χ^s . This is an indication that, depending on the values assumed by the opacities, such source terms may become stiff, *but only for the radiation variables*. This means that the vector of sources given by Eq. (3.82) will be split into two parts, $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_e + \mathcal{S}_i$. The first one,

$$\mathcal{S}_e \equiv \sqrt{\gamma} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \alpha W^{ik} \partial_j \gamma_{ik} + S_i \partial_j \beta^i - U \partial_j \alpha + \alpha (G_r)_j \\ \frac{1}{2} W^{ik} \beta^j \partial_j \gamma_{ik} + W_i^j \partial_j \beta^i - S^j \partial_j \alpha + \alpha^2 G_r^t \\ \frac{1}{2} R_r^{ik} \beta^j \partial_j \gamma_{ik} + (R_r)^j_i \partial_j \beta^i - S_r^j \partial_j \alpha \\ \frac{1}{2} \alpha R_r^{ik} \partial_j \gamma_{ik} + (S_r)_i \partial_j \beta^i - U_r \partial_j \alpha \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.108)$$

will be absorbed into the operators F_Y and F_X in Eq. (3.91) and Eq. (3.92), because it contains terms that do not act as stiff sources. The second part, on the other hand, which contains the genuinely stiff terms for the radiation variables $\{X\}$, is

$$\mathcal{S}_i \equiv \sqrt{\gamma} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -\alpha^2 G_r^t \\ -\alpha (G_r)_j \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.109)$$

and its non zero components are identified with the operator $R_X(X, Y)$ in Eq. (3.92). After using Eq. (3.106) and Eq. (3.107), it is possible to further decompose R_X as prescribed by Eq. (3.97) as

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\alpha^2 G_r^t \\ -\alpha(G_r)_x \\ -\alpha(G_r)_y \\ -\alpha(G_r)_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11}, A_{12}, A_{13}, A_{14} \\ A_{21}, A_{22}, A_{23}, A_{24} \\ A_{31}, A_{32}, A_{33}, A_{34} \\ A_{41}, A_{42}, A_{43}, A_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_r \\ (S_r)_x \\ (S_r)_y \\ (S_r)_z \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \alpha\Gamma\chi^t a_r T^4 \\ \alpha\Gamma\chi^t a_r T^4 v_x \\ \alpha\Gamma\chi^t a_r T^4 v_y \\ \alpha\Gamma\chi^t a_r T^4 v_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.110)$$

where, just for convenience, the spatial coordinates to $(x, y, z,)$ are given explicitly. The stiffness coefficients of the matrix $A(Y)$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{11} &= -\alpha\Gamma(\chi^t + \chi^s 4W(1 - \Gamma^2)) \\
 A_{12} &= \alpha\Gamma v^x(\chi^t + \chi^s W(1 - 4\Gamma^2)) \\
 A_{13} &= \alpha\Gamma v^y(\chi^t + \chi^s W(1 - 4\Gamma^2)) \\
 A_{14} &= \alpha\Gamma v^z(\chi^t + \chi^s W(1 - 4\Gamma^2)) \\
 A_{21} &= -\alpha\Gamma v_x [\chi^t(1 - 4W) + 2\chi^s(W - 1)] \\
 A_{22} &= -\alpha\Gamma v^x v_x [\chi^t(2W - 1) + \chi^s(2 - W)] - \alpha(\chi^t + \chi^s)/\Gamma \\
 A_{23} &= -\alpha\Gamma v^y v_x [\chi^t(2W - 1) + \chi^s(2 - W)] \\
 A_{24} &= -\alpha\Gamma v^z v_x [\chi^t(2W - 1) + \chi^s(2 - W)] \\
 A_{31} &= -\alpha\Gamma v_y [\chi^t(1 - 4W) + 2\chi^s(W - 1)] \\
 A_{32} &= -\alpha\Gamma v^x v_y [\chi^t(2W - 1) + \chi^s(2 - W)] \\
 A_{33} &= -\alpha\Gamma v^y v_y [\chi^t(2W - 1) + \chi^s(2 - W)] - \alpha(\chi^t + \chi^s)/\Gamma \\
 A_{34} &= -\alpha\Gamma v^z v_y [\chi^t(2W - 1) + \chi^s(2 - W)] \\
 A_{41} &= -\alpha\Gamma v_z [\chi^t(1 - 4W) + 2\chi^s(W - 1)] \\
 A_{42} &= -\alpha\Gamma v^x v_z [\chi^t(2W - 1) + \chi^s(2 - W)] \\
 A_{43} &= -\alpha\Gamma v^y v_z [\chi^t(2W - 1) + \chi^s(2 - W)] \\
 A_{44} &= -\alpha\Gamma v^z v_z [\chi^t(2W - 1) + \chi^s(2 - W)] - \alpha(\chi^t + \chi^s)/\Gamma,
 \end{aligned} \quad (3.111)$$

while the components of the vector K_X (the second term on the right hand side of Eq. (3.110)) do not depend on the stiff variables X , but only on the temperature T . We note that, in the actual implementation of the IMEX Runge-Kutta scheme, the correction to the explicit variables $X^{(i)}$ dictated by Eq. (3.96) is performed when the conversion from the conservative variables U to the primitive variables is performed.

Standard Runge Kutta

The second option is a "normal" Runge Kutta integration, which is given here, although standard, as it shows that the IMEX schemes used above, are compatible with their explicit counterparts¹. The algorithm is simply the explicit part of the more general Strongly Stability Preserving (SSP) scheme. Echo implements this both in second (ex-SSP2 (2, 2, 2)) and third (ex-SSP3(4, 3, 3)) order.

First, the explicit part of SSP2(2, 2, 2) is given by:

¹ In order not to waste CPU time, however, the explicit scheme is implemented separately, although it could be obtained by setting the implicit coefficients to zero

$$\mathbf{U}^{(1)} = \mathbf{U}^n \quad (3.112)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{(2)} = \mathbf{U}^n + \Delta t F(\mathbf{U}^{(1)}) \quad (3.113)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{n+1} = \mathbf{U}^n + \frac{\Delta t}{2} [F(\mathbf{U}^{(1)}) + F(\mathbf{U}^{(2)})] \quad (3.114)$$

From (3.113) we have $\Delta t F(\mathbf{U}^{(1)}) = \mathbf{U}^{(2)} - \mathbf{U}^n$, which can be replaced in (3.114) to find

$$\mathbf{U}^{n+1} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{U}^n + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{U}^{(2)} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} F(\mathbf{U}^{(2)}) \quad (3.115)$$

which is the second-order implementation in ECHO.

The third-order Runge Kutta implementation is the same as the explicit part of SSP3(4,3,3), which is:

third order

$$\mathbf{U}^{(1)} = \mathbf{U}^n \quad (3.116)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{(2)} = \mathbf{U}^n \quad (3.117)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{(3)} = \mathbf{U}^n + \Delta t F(\mathbf{U}^{(1)}) \quad (3.118)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{(4)} = \mathbf{U}^n + \Delta t \left[\frac{1}{4} F(\mathbf{U}^{(2)}) + \frac{1}{4} F(\mathbf{U}^{(3)}) \right] \quad (3.119)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{n+1} = \mathbf{U}^n + \Delta t \left[\frac{1}{6} F(\mathbf{U}^{(2)}) + \frac{1}{6} F(\mathbf{U}^{(3)}) + \frac{2}{3} F(\mathbf{U}^{(4)}) \right] \quad (3.120)$$

Again, substituting Eq.s (3.116,3.117,3.118) into Eq. (3.119) yields

$$\frac{1}{6} \Delta t F(\mathbf{U}^{(3)}) = \frac{2}{3} \mathbf{U}^{(4)} - \frac{2}{3} \mathbf{U}^n - \frac{1}{6} \Delta t F(\mathbf{U}^{(2)}) \quad (3.121)$$

which can be replaced into Eq. (3.120) to obtain the third order Runge-Kutta in ECHO:

$$\mathbf{U}^{n+1} = \frac{1}{3} \mathbf{U}^n + \frac{2}{3} \mathbf{U}^{(4)} + \frac{2}{3} \Delta t F(\mathbf{U}^{(4)}) \quad (3.122)$$

The reason for having two different orders is that typically the order of the spatial scheme is more crucial to the global accuracy than the temporal scheme, thus there are few situations in which one would like to have a second order (e.g. MC2) spatial reconstruction paired with third-order Runge-Kutta¹. Usually, we pair the second order spatial and temporal schemes together, whereas we use third order Runge-Kutta with the fifth order spatial schemes². Namely, in situations where the stiffness is very high and numerical instability becomes the dominant issue

spatial order more crucial than temporal order

3.2.3 Validation of ECHO: GR-RHD with and without IMEX

This Section describes the code validation and various numerical tests.

The purely hydrodynamic version of the ECHO code has been validated over the same

¹ Namely, in situations where the stiffness is very high and numerical instability becomes the dominant issue

² This is due to the fact that in the presence of shocks the spatial accuracy is reduced to first or second order anyway

numerical tests extensively described in [Del Zanna et al. \(2007\)](#), obtaining the same convergence properties and will not be reported here for compactness. For the radiation part of the code, on the other hand, there are only a few analytic or semi-analytic tests that can be adopted, as we discuss below.

First, the code is validated in the non-stiff regime using a purely explicit Runge-Kutta second order scheme in § 3.2.3.1, denoted as GR-RHD-RK. Then, in § 3.2.3.2, tests are performed to show the improvement if the IMEX method is used, denoted as GR-RHD-IMEX. Additionally, ECHO-IMEX is compared against a fully relativistic GR-(M)HD code WHISKY-IMEX, into which our radiation treatment has been ported.

3.2.3.1 GR-RHD-RK: shock-tubes and spherical accretion

Shock-tube problems

Considering a flat spacetime, we have followed [Farris et al. \(2008\)](#), who proposed and solved four shock-tube tests in which nonlinear radiation-hydrodynamic waves propagate. The initial states of these tests are reported in Table 3.2 and are chosen in such a way that the discontinuity front at $x = 0$ remains stationary, namely it has zero velocity with respect to the Eulerian observer of the code. The values of the fluxes, not reported in Table 3.2, are chosen to be two orders of magnitude smaller than the energy density of the radiation field. In these tests local thermodynamic equilibrium is assumed at both ends $x = \pm X$, with $X = 20$, and this is obtained by adopting a fictitious value of the radiation constant a_{rad} , namely $a_{\text{rad}} = E_{r,L}/T_L^4$, which is then used to compute $E_{r,R} = a_{\text{rad}}T_R^4$ (here the indices L and R indicate the "left" and "right" states, respectively). The scattering opacity κ_g^s is set to zero in all of the tests, while the value of the thermal opacity κ_g^t is reported in Table 3.2. This is justified, because only the bremsstrahlung opacity is a function of the fluid variables whereas the scattering opacity is a pure number.

Each test is evolved in time until stationarity is reached. The semi-analytic solution that is used for comparison with the numerical one has been obtained following the strategy by [Farris et al. \(2008\)](#), and it implies the solution of the following system of ordinary differential equations

$$d_x \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{P}),$$

where

$$\mathbf{P} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho \\ P \\ u^x \\ E_r \\ F_r^x \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{U} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho u^x \\ T^{0x} \\ T^{xx} \\ T_r^{0x} \\ T_r^{xx} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{S} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -G_r^0 \\ -G_r^x \end{pmatrix}.$$

Fig.s 3.10 and 3.8 show the comparison of the numerical solution with respect to the semi-analytic one in the four cases considered, which correspond, respectively, to the propagation of a nonrelativistic strong shock, of a mildly relativistic strong shock, of a highly relativistic wave and of a radiation pressure dominated mildly relativistic wave. In particular, Fig. 3.10 reports the solution for the tests 1 and 2, which contain a true discontinuity represented by a shock front, while tests 3 and 4 have continuous configurations and are shown in Fig. 3.8.

The tests have been performed with $N = 800$ uniformly spaced grid points using the MP5 slope limiter described in [Del Zanna et al. \(2007\)](#) and a HLL Riemann solver. Unlike [Farris et al. \(2008\)](#), we have not boosted the solution. This results in a more stringent test for the code to maintain stationarity and it also explains why the profiles

scattering opacity
set to zero

shock properties

Fig. 3.7: DISCONTINUOUS SHOCK TUBE TEST OF GR-RHD-RK - Solution of the test 1 (*left panel*) and 2 (*right panel*) as reported in Table 3.2. From top to bottom the panels report the rest-mass density, the velocity, the radiation energy density and the radiation flux.

Fig. 3.8: CONTINUOUS SHOCK TUBE TEST OF GR-RHD-RK - Solution of the test 3 (*left panel*) and 4 (*right panel*) as reported in Table 3.2. From top to bottom the panels report the rest-mass density, the velocity, the radiation energy density and the radiation flux.

Table 3.2: Description of the initial states in the shock-tube tests with radiation field. The different columns refer respectively to: the test considered, the radiation constant, the adiabatic index and the thermal opacity. Also reported are the rest-mass density, pressure, velocity and radiation energy density in the “left” (L) and “right” (R) states.

Model	γ	a_{rad}	κ_g^t	ρ_L	P_L	u_L^x	$E_{r,L}$	ρ_R	P_R	u_R^x	$E_{r,R}$
1	5/3	1.234×10^{10}	0.4	1.0	3.0×10^{-5}	0.015	1.0×10^{-8}	2.4	1.61×10^{-4}	6.25×10^{-3}	2.51×10^{-7}
2	5/3	7.812×10^4	0.2	1.0	4.0×10^{-3}	0.25	2.0×10^{-5}	3.11	0.04512	0.0804	3.46×10^{-3}
3	2	1.543×10^{-7}	0.3	1.0	60.0	10.0	2.0	8.0	2.34×10^3	1.25	1.14×10^3
4	5/3	1.388×10^8	0.08	1.0	6.0×10^{-3}	0.69	0.18	3.65	3.59×10^{-2}	0.189	1.3

of the vector quantities, namely the velocity and the radiation flux, do not match those shown by [Farris et al. \(2008\)](#). The numerical solution is almost indistinguishable from the semi-analytic one in all of the profiles reported in the figures, thus proving the ability of the code in handling different physical regimes of the radiation field within an optically-thick approximation.

Spherical accretion test

As an intermediate step between a purely numerical test and a physical application, we consider the spherical transonic accretion onto a non-rotating black hole in the presence of an isotropic radiation field. This problem has been studied in great detail by several people and groups over the years. In the optically thick regime, the stationary solution was investigated under different approximations and by focusing on different emission mechanisms by [Maraschi et al. \(1974\)](#), [Kafka & Mészáros \(1976\)](#), [Vitello \(1978\)](#), [Gillman & Stellingwerf \(1980\)](#), [Flammang \(1982\)](#), [Nobili et al. \(1991\)](#). The time dependent solution, on the other hand, was considered by [Gilden & Wheeler \(1980\)](#) and [Zampieri et al. \(1996\)](#). The latter, in particular, via a Lagrangian code solved the radiation transfer equations using the projected symmetric trace-free (PSTF) moment formalism ([Thorne, 1981](#)), truncated at the first two moment equations. Because of the limiting approximations assumed, and in particular because of the lack of Comptonization effects, the analysis should not be regarded as an attempt to improve with respect to the above mentioned works, but rather as a preliminary study in view of further developments.

limiting approximations

Our initial conditions are given by the fluid spherically symmetric transonic solution of [Michel \(1972\)](#), which is stationary in the absence of a radiation field. The free parameters of the fluid solution are the adiabatic index γ , the critical radius r_c and the rest mass density at the critical radius ρ_c . We choose $\gamma = 4/3$ and $\rho_c = 9.88 \times 10^{-9}$ cgs for all of the models, while we change r_c between $r_c = 800$ and $r_c = 7000$ in order to control the accretion rate. The test is performed in Kerr-Schild coordinates with $1.0 < r < 1000$ using $N = 3200$ radial grid points. The evolution is stopped when stationarity in the L_2 -norms of all of the variables has been reached, which may require a final time as long as $t = 400000$ in code units. The scheme employed is the MC limiter at second order of global accuracy. The initial radiation field is initialized to a negligible energy density, while radiation fluxes are set to zero. Special attention has to be paid to the boundary conditions at the outer radial grid point, for which we have followed closely the discussion presented by [Nobili et al. \(1991\)](#). In particular, zeroth order extrapolation (copy of variables) is adopted for the gas pressure and for the density. This guarantees that the temperature has zero gradient. At the same time we want to make sure that at large radii the radiation field streams radially, namely

boundary conditions

Fig. 3.9: SPHERICAL ACCRETION TEST FOR GR-RHD - Luminosity versus accretion rate, both reported in Eddington units, in the spherical accretion test. Filled black circles refer to values extracted at constant radii. Open blue circles refer to values at constant optical thickness. Red stars are from stationary configurations as computed by Nobili et al. (1991).

Data of Nobili et al. (1991) thankfully provided by Luca Zampieri

that $E \propto f^r \propto r^{-2}$. This translates into the condition

$$\frac{d \ln E}{d \ln r} = -2, \quad (3.123)$$

which can be easily implemented. Finally, we fix the accretion rate at the outer boundary to the value possessed by the initial configuration. At the inner radial boundary, on the other hand, zeroth order extrapolation is adopted for all of the variables. The evolution is performed considering both the contribution of the bremsstrahlung opacity and of the Thomson scattering opacity for electrons. Note that during the evolution the radiation flux remains typically two orders of magnitude smaller than the radiation energy, thus maintaining the code in the physical regime that it can handle. After an initial relaxation, the system converges to a different stationary configuration characterized by a steady, non zero radiation flux. The solution is optically thick in all of the models for $r \leq 100$, while it becomes optically thin at large radii. From the radiation flux the luminosity is computed as $L = 4\pi r^2 f^r$.

Fig. 3.9 reports the results of our simulation tests in the diagram $(\dot{M}/\dot{M}_{Edd}, L/L_{Edd})$, where the luminosity is computed at $r = 100$. Although our data resemble the high luminosity branch reported in Fig. 1 by Nobili et al. (1991), a close comparison with their results is not really possible, since Comptonization, bound-bound transitions and free-bound transitions are not taken into account in our analysis. In particular, the absence of pre-heating effects does not allow us to verify the onset of strong thermal instabilities producing hydrodynamic shock waves that propagate outward, as reported by Zampieri et al. (1996). In spite of this, the test performed here is very relevant. In fact, by using an entirely different procedure with respect to Nobili et al. (1991) and Zampieri et al. (1996), it confirms the existence of a high luminosity branch in the diagram

luminosity
computation

comparison with
other work

$(\dot{M}/\dot{M}_{Edd,L}/L/L_{Edd})$, which corresponds to the optically thick regime. A more extended analysis of this problem, by including additional contributions to the opacity, a consistent treatment of the Comptonization and the effect of a spinning black hole is deferred to future work.

3.2.3.2 GR-RHD-IMEX: shock-tubes and spherical accretion in the stiff regime

In the above Section, we had considered a number of shock-tube tests in which nonlinear radiation-hydrodynamic waves propagate. We now repeat two of these shock-tubes with increased stiffness. First, it should be noted, that the values for the opacity considered in this Section cannot be handled with the non-IMEX version of the code unless CFL-values of $C_{CFL} \ll 0.01$ are chosen.

Fig. 3.10: SHOCK TUBE TEST WITH GR-RHD-IMEX - Solution of the test No. 1 with stiffness parameter $\kappa = 25$ (left panel) and $\kappa = 0.7$ (right panel). From top to bottom the panels report the rest-mass density, the velocity, the radiation energy density and the radiation flux. In both cases 800 grid-points have been used with $C_{CFL} = 0.25$. The tests are performed with the WHISKY code, employing TVD reconstruction and minmod limiter.

increasing stiffness

The fact, that the new version of the code can deal with these regimes at all, is an improvement. However, we also note that increasing the opacity by hand in order to achieve arbitrarily high stiffness is not feasible, as the radiation fluxes at the shock front start to diverge and thus bring the code into a regime, where all the fundamental assumptions (made in § 3.2.3) most prominently that $F_r^i/E_r \ll 1$ are violated. Thus, after the shock-tubes, we concentrate more again on the spherical accretion test, which provides smooth solutions that can be tuned to very high stiffness without departing from the physical regime the code can handle.

Shock tubes

In Eq. (3.2.3.1) U_1 , U_2 and U_3 are constant in x , while only T_r^{0x} and T_r^{xx} need to be solved for. Thus, these tests can be used to monitor the ability of the code in dealing with the stiff regime, by simply increasing the thermal opacity κ_g^t (the scattering opacity κ_g^s is set to zero as above). When this is done, the semi-analytic solution of the ODE system (3.2.3.1) can be obtained after adopting an ODE solver for stiff systems (Press et al., 1992). The initial states of the three tests that we have considered are reported in Table 3.3 and are chosen in such a way that the discontinuity front at $x = 0$ remains stationary. Note that tests No. 1 and 2 in Tab. 3.3 are the same of tests No. 3 and 4 in Tab. 3.2, apart for the value of κ_g^t , which controls the stiffness of the problem. After setting 800 grid-points in the x direction, we have increased the value of κ_g^t to the maximum value affordable by the numerical scheme, while keeping the CFL parameter unchanged and equal to 0.25. For example, κ_g^t has been increased from 0.3 to 3.0 in test No. 1, and from 0.08 to 0.55 in test No. 2. Each test is evolved in time until stationarity is reached.

Table 3.3: DESCRIPTION OF THE INITIAL DATA - in the shock-tube tests with radiation field. The different columns refer respectively to: the test considered, the radiation constant, the adiabatic index and the thermal opacity. Also reported are the rest-mass density, pressure, velocity and radiation energy density in the "left" (L) and "right" (R) states.

Model	γ	a_{rad}	κ_g^t	ρ_L	P_L	u_L^x	$E_{r,L}$	ρ_R	P_R	u_R^x	$E_{r,R}$
1	2	1.543×10^{-7}	25	1.0	60.0	10.0	2.0	8.0	2.34×10^3	1.25	1.14×10^3
2	5/3	1.388×10^8	0.7	1.0	6.0×10^{-3}	0.69	0.18	3.65	3.59×10^{-2}	0.189	1.3
3	2	1.543×10^{-7}	1000	1.0	60.0	1.25	2.0	1.0	60.0	1.10	2.0

Fig. 3.10 shows the comparison of the numerical solution with respect to the semi-analytic one in the two cases considered, which correspond, respectively, to the propagation of a highly relativistic wave and of a radiation pressure dominated mildly relativistic wave. Besides a typical smearing at the shock front itself, the exact solution is reproduced well. The small noise that is created from the initial conditions leaves the grid soon and the solution settles down to stationarity.

Fig. 3.11 shows the comparison of the numerical solution of a two-sided, highly relativistic, stiff shock wave, using two codes. The WHISKY¹ code is a modification of the WHISKYMHD code (Giacomazzo & Rezzolla, 2007), which implements the general relativistic resistive magnetohydrodynamics formalism (GRRMHD) (Dionysopoulou et al., 2012). We use the numerical methods provided by the original WHISKY code (Baiotti et al., 2003), namely an HLLC approximate Riemann solver and a second order TVD slope limiter method for the reconstruction of the primitives. The infrastructure as well as the solution of the Einstein equations is provided by the Cactus Computational Toolkit (Löffler et al., 2012). The GR-RHD equations were implemented in WhiskyR and in order to deal with the stiffness of the source terms, we modified the MoL thorn, as part of Einstein Toolkit², which allows the choice between second or third-order IMEX Runge-Kutta integration in time.

This additional shock tube problem, test No. 3, is somewhat peculiar as it has equal left and right states in all quantities save for the velocity. In this case, two shock waves propagates

comparison of
ECHO versus
WHISKY

extremely high
stiffness

¹ www.whiskycode.org

² The Einstein Toolkit: A Community Computational Infrastructure for Relativistic Astrophysics

Fig. 3.11: CROSS VERIFICATION SHOCK TUBE USING GR-RHD-IMEX - The two codes ECHO and WHISKY have been used to obtain the numerical solution of the test No. 3 at time $t = 15$. From top to bottom the panels report the rest-mass density, the velocity and the radiation energy density. In both cases 800 grid-points have been used with $C_{CFL} = 0.25$, MC reconstruction and RKIMEX2.

in opposite direction, no stationary solution is obtained, but a much higher value of κ_g^t can be used, namely $\kappa_g^t = 1000$. Both codes agree very well and there is no sign of spurious noise.

Spherical accretion

thermal test

In order to test the improvement with the IMEX scheme for thermal radiation, shock tubes are not particularly useful, because at shocks, the fluid is never in local thermal equilibrium with the radiation. Thus the stronger the shock, the more we violate the assumption underlying our radiation treatment. This is why we test for stability in regions of very high stiffness using the smooth solution that we know from spherical accretion onto a black hole. In this §, we offer an additional demonstration of the usefulness of our scheme, by assuming unphysically large cross-sections.

The initial conditions are again given by the fluid spherically symmetric transonic solution of Michel (1972) and all parameters that are not explicitly mentioned, remain the same as in § 3.2.3.1. This test is aimed at showing the ability of the numerical scheme in handling the stiff regime, so we have considered an unphysical set-up with $\rho_c = 0.02$, $r_c = 8.0$, and a high uniform value of the thermal opacity, $\kappa_g^t = 10^{15}$. The test is performed in Boyer-Lindquist coordinates with $2.5 < r < 200$ using $N = 300$ radial grid points. The SSP3-IMEX scheme has been adopted, with the MC limiter for the spatial reconstruction. The left panel of Figure 3.12 shows the profiles of the rest-mass density, of the radial velocity and of the radiation energy density (from top to bottom) at time $t = 1000$.

confirming the identification of the stiff terms

Because we do not have an analytical solution to compare with in this case, we simply state that the RK-version of the code could never have evolved this problem without the solution "exploding". The fact, that the solution is smooth and the code can handle arbitrary

Fig. 3.12: SPHERICAL ACCRETION AND CONSISTENCY USING GR-RHD-IMEX - (Left) Numerical solution at time $t = 1000$. From top to bottom the panels report the rest-mass density, the velocity, the radiation energy density. An artificial $\kappa_g^d = 1.0 \times 10^{15}$ has been adopted to highlight the ability of the code in treating the stiff regime. $N_r = 300$ grid-points have been used with $\mathcal{C}_{\text{CFL}} = 0.2$, MC reconstruction and SSP3-IMEX. (Right) Time evolution of a perturbed BHL model with $v_{\text{inf}} = 0.18$ and $c_{s,\infty} = 0.07$ (model p.V18.cs07 of Chapter 7) with the **IMEX** (solid line) and with the **non-IMEX** version of the code (dashed line). The lower panel shows the light curve, whereas we plot the accretion rate on the top. All curves are shown in Eddington units.

values of κ_g^d confirms that we have isolated the stiffness terms properly and that the implementation is, in fact, stable.

Consistency test

In order to confirm that the new code is producing consistent solutions, we compare a numerical solution obtained by the old and new version of ECHO of a numerically stressful Bondy Hoyle Lyttleton model (this is properly introduced in Chapter 7). We chose the model the highest Mach number (model p.V18.cs07) and compute both accretion rate and luminosity with the both versions of ECHO. The RK-version had stability problems after the shock reversal ($t \sim 1.4 \times 10^4 M$) and it was impossible to evolve the model further without reducing the \mathcal{C}_{CFL} to values smaller than $\mathcal{C}_{\text{CFL}} \leq 0.01$. As shown in the right panel of Fig. 3.12, the IMEX version reproduces the light curves and the accretion rates obtained with the purely explicit version of the code. Moreover, by using the IMEX scheme, it is now possible to extend the evolution to later times without reducing the CFL number. As a result, this test confirms, firstly, that the new scheme is verified also in a non-trivial two-dimensional application and, secondly, that the use of the IMEX offers clear advantages in terms of computational resources.

2D verification

GR-RHD-IMEX as an important tool for relativistic accretion flows

After this extensive description of our GR-RHD scheme, I would like to summarise the (current) advantages and caveats:

The assumption of LTE is a strong one and so is the assumption of isotropic radiation. We know that these can only be strictly valid in weakly dynamical, dense regions. As I will show in the second part of the thesis, the applicability can be slightly stretched towards dynamical systems of moderate density. There, some problems arise, but, on the other hand, it is shown that the radiation field still has a very significant, while still physical, effect on the dynamics of the plasma.

The field of GR-RHD is extremely new and we had to realise that although we make such strong assumptions, numerical problems arise that are not even related to atmospheres or boundaries. Future steps, that we plan, are the transition to the optically thin regime via the variable Eddington factor approach. This will be important, as it will finally allow us to evolve systems with surfaces and atmospheres. Also will the extraction of luminosity (see Chapter 7 for discussion) be finally unique and geometry independent.

Another step, that we plan, is the inclusion of the resistive magnetic fields and coupling them to the photon field via synchrotron radiation. While the implementation of RMHD is an almost trivial step from here¹, in order for this to be sensible astrophysically, we will need to drop the assumption of thermalization.

At this stage, our scheme can give us hints on how strong a role radiation pressure plays in certain, simple applications, it allows the computation of qualitative light curves and it introduces thermal conductivity and radiation induced turbulence as sources of dissipation and viscosity in our otherwise inviscid approach.

The fact, that we chose a format of the equations that is compatible with the "big GR codes" allows the copy and paste of our scheme into a module for these codes. This is very useful for flexibility and also for cross verification. It is our hope, that the radiation modules will at some point be migrated into the public releases of the WHISKY code.²

¹ WHISKY already has the GRRMHD modules that are in compatible form to the GR-RHD module

² Currently, only the AEI internal version has been tested and verified in one-dimensional tests, but the IMEX treatment in the Method of Lines thorn will be made public with the next release of the Einstein Toolkit

PART II

RESULTS

NEWTONIAN MASSIVE BLACK HOLE BINARIES IN SELFGRAVITATING DISCS: I PROGRADE DISCS

This Chapter contains the largest parts of the results obtained during my Ph.D.. Here I describe the work on secular evolution of *black hole binaries* (BHBs) in prograde selfgravitating discs. The results will not be presented in the chronological order in which they were obtained, but rather, I will start with the detailed study of how torques from the gas can influence the orbital elements of the BHB in Section 4.1.

This study confirms earlier findings that the eccentricity is excited during the evolution, which is why in Section 4.2, we explore the secular evolution of high eccentricities in some detail. We find that there is a limiting value to the eccentricity growth which can be understood using a very simple, physical model.

More massive sources accessible via *PTAs* are expected to be observed at a later stage in their BHB-disc evolution. Our standard disc model is thus adapted to the *PTA* parameters and a syncretic approach between high resolution numerics and analytic disc models is detailed in Section 4.3.

The observational implications of the results are discussed later in Chapter 6.

4.1 Dissection of the torques

In this entire Chapter we analyse three-dimensional *smoothed particle hydrodynamics* (SPH) simulations of the evolution of massive black hole binaries residing in the central hollow (*cavity*) of massive self-gravitating circumbinary discs. This standard model is described in Chapter 1.1.3 and Chapter 3.1.6.

First of all, we perform a set of simulations adopting different thermodynamics for the gas within the cavity and for the 'numerical size' of the black holes. The global aim of this investigation is the understanding of the physical roots of the secular evolution of the binary. Thus we study the interplay between gas accretion and gravity torques in changing the binary elements (semi-major axis and eccentricity) and its total angular momentum budget. We pay special attention to the gravity torques, by analysing their physical origin and location. We show that (i) the eccentricity grows due to gravity torques from the inner edge of the disc, independently of the accretion and the adopted thermodynamics; (ii) the semi-major axis decay depends not only on the gravity torques but also on their subtle interplay with the disc-binary angular momentum transfer due to accretion; (iii) the spectral structure of the gravity torques is predominately caused by disc edge overdensities and spiral arms developing in the body of the disc and, in general, does not reflect directly

motivation

results

the period of the binary; (iv) the net gravity torque changes sign across the BHB corotation radius (positive inside vs negative outside). We quantify the relative importance of the two, which might depend on the thermodynamical properties of the instreaming gas, and is crucial in assessing the disc-binary angular momentum transfer; (v) the net torque manifests as a purely kinematic effect as it stems from the low density cavity, where the material flows in and out in highly eccentric orbits. Thus both accretion onto the black holes and the interaction with gas streams inside the cavity must be taken into account to assess the fate of the binary.

In the recent past, several studies of massive BHBs in discs have been performed numerically and analytically (Ivanov et al., 1999; Armitage & Natarajan, 2002, 2005; Hayasaki et al., 2007, 2008; MacFadyen & Milosavljević, 2008; Hayasaki, 2009; Cuadra et al., 2009; Lodato et al., 2009; Nixon et al., 2011; Shi et al., 2011). However, fully three dimensional studies remain rare and often the BHB is set to be on a fixed orbit and/or the central region of the grid is excised. MacFadyen & Milosavljević (2008) (hereinafter MM08) used a 2D-grid approach to simulate a BHB embedded in an unmagnetised, locally isothermal SS- α -disk. They measured the torques and studied the gas flow between the main disc and the BHB as far as their grid was covering into the cavity. Shi et al. (2011) (hereinafter S11) performed a three dimensional simulation of a magnetized, isothermal accretion disc while excising about twice the binary separation. Both MM08 and S11 kept the BHB on a fixed circular orbit and neglected disc self-gravity.

Our goal is to give a detailed description of the coupled disc-binary dynamics, paying particular attention to the competing effects of disc-binary gravitational torques and gas accretion onto the BHs in the evolution of the binary angular momentum budget. Thus, we *simultaneously* evolve the disc and the two BHs in a self-consistent way. This enables us to separately investigate the effect of gravitational torques coming from different disc regions and to directly link different physical mechanisms (gravitational torques and accretion) to the evolution of individual quantities describing the binary (mass, mass ratio, semi-major axis and eccentricity). Our approach allows the study of the coupled dynamics which is complementary to previous studies (MM08, S11), where the binary was modelled as a fixed forcing quadrupolar potential and the central region was excised.

However, our model still is highly idealised in terms of neglecting radiation pressure or other thermodynamical issues. Thus we check if our results are affected spuriously by varying physical and numerical prescriptions that may play a relevant role in the disc-binary energy and angular momentum exchanges. Specifically, we checked the possible dependence of our results on the 'numerical size' of the two BHs (i.e., their sink radii, see next Section), and on the adopted *equation of state* (EoS) for the gas within the central cavity.

This Section is structured as follows: we first quickly describe the numerical setup and initial conditions in § 4.1.1, then we show the importance of both accretion and gravitational torques on the binary evolution in § 4.1.2. We study in detail the origin and strength of the mutual disc-binary gravitational torques in § 4.1.3 highlighting the influence of the thermodynamics prescription. In § 4.1.4 we briefly discuss the temporal behaviour and the spatial geometry of the accretion, speculating on the evolution of the binary mass ratio and BH individual spins. Finally, we compare our results to previous work in § 4.1.5 and discuss the implications of these findings in § 4.1.6.

4.1.1 Simulations

Fig. 4.1: RELAXED MERIDIONAL SLICES OF THE DISC FOR THE *ADIA* AND *ISO* RUNS - Density maps of the disc for the *adia* (top) and *iso* (bottom) runs; the black dots indicate the BHs, the axis are in units of the binary semi-major axis a . Note that this is not an azimuthal average but a vertical slice of the disc.

The model and numerical setup used here has already been described in Chapter 3.1.6, thus I only repeat the key aspects here.

We simulate a self-gravitating gaseous disc of mass $M_d = 0.2M$ around two BHs of combined mass $M = M_1 + M_2$, mass ratio $q = M_2/M_1 = 1/3$, eccentricity e and semi-major axis a . The disc, which is co-rotating with the BHs, radially extends to about $7a$, contains a circumbinary cavity of radial size $\sim 2a$ and is numerically resolved by 2 million particles. The numerical size of each BH is denoted as r_{sink} . The gas in the disc is allowed to cool on a time scale proportional to the local dynamical time of the disc $t_{\text{dyn}} = f_0^{-1} = 2\pi/\Omega_0$, where $\Omega_0 = (GM_0/a_0^3)^{1/2}$ is the initial orbital frequency of the binary¹. To prevent it from fragmenting, we force the gas to cool slowly, setting $\beta = t_{\text{cool}}/t_{\text{dyn}} = 10$ (cf. § 3.1.5). We use two different treatments for the thermodynamics inside the cavity, denoted as *adia* and *iso*, respectively. In the *adia* runs, the gas within the cavity is allowed to both cool via the β prescription and to heat up adiabatically, as it is the remainder of the disc. In the *iso* runs, we define a threshold radius $r_{\text{cavity}} = 1.75a$, below which the gas is treated isothermally, meaning that the internal energy per unit mass is set to be $u \approx 0.14(GM/r)$.

The nomenclature of the runs and the parameters used are listed in Tab. 4.1. Each run is evolved for ≈ 90 binary orbits, and we store the output in single precision ~ 6 times per

¹ Subscripts 0 refer to the initial values of any parameter.

Fig. 4.2: DISC SCALE-HEIGHT AND DISC ECCENTRICITY - Time and azimuth-averaged values of the disc half scale-height H/r and the disc eccentricity e_{disc} as a function of radius for the different simulations.

orbit. We also closely track accretion by storing the position and velocity of the two BHs and of each accreted particle at the time the latter crosses r_{sink} . For both prescriptions (*adia* and *iso*) we show the relaxed density configurations sliced along the meridional plane in Fig. 4.1 (see also Figs. 4.8-4.9 for a face-on view) and the measured, time-averaged values for both the scale height of the disc H/r , and the eccentricity of the disc e_{disc} in Fig. 4.2. H is taken to be the height above and below the disc-orbital plane in which 70% of the mass inside the annulus $(r, r + dr)$ is found. In their bodies (i.e. at $r > 2a$), the discs may be considered thin, as shown in the upper panel of Fig. 4.2, with a maximum thickness $H/r \approx 0.2$, and quasi circular (lower panel of Fig. 4.2).

Table 4.1: INITIAL PARAMETERS AND NAMES OF THE RUNS IN UNITLENGTHS OF THE CODE.

Model	r_{sink}	Cavity EoS	Disc EoS
adia10	0.1	adiabatic+ β	adiabatic + β
iso10	0.1	isothermal	adiabatic + β
adia05	0.05	adiabatic+ β	adiabatic + β
iso05	0.05	isothermal	adiabatic + β

Unless otherwise stated, we will present all the relevant quantities in the natural units of the simulation: $G = M_0 = a_0 = 1$. It follows that also the initial circular velocity of the

binary is $V_{c,0} = 1$ and its initial period $P_0 = 2\pi$. We will then later discuss the astrophysical implications of our findings by scaling them to fiducial astrophysical BHB systems.

4.1.2 Binary evolution: causes

For each of the four runs, we measure the two primary orbital elements: eccentricity e and semi-major axis a . Their evolution is shown by the red lines in Fig. 4.3. In all four runs, we find $\dot{a}(t) < 0$ and $\dot{e}(t) > 0$. While the eccentricity evolution is largely independent on the sink radius value and the adopted EoS within the cavity, the orbital shrinking is much faster in the *adia* runs, in which the binary shrinks by 4 – 5% over 90 orbits. Conversely, in the *iso* runs, the two BHs get only about 1% closer. Linear extrapolation of such results at face value implies binary coalescence on a timescale of $\sim 2000P_0$ and $\sim 10^4P_0$ for the *adia* and the *iso* runs, respectively.

e independent of r_{sink} and EoS

Fig. 4.3: SEMIMAJOR AXIS AND ECCENTRICITY EVOLUTION FOR ALL RUNS - Semimajor axis (*top panel* in each plot) and eccentricity (*bottom panel* in each plot) evolution for all the four runs. In each panel, the red line represents the full evolution directly taken from the simulation whereas the black line is the equivalent evolution when considering the energy and angular momentum exchanges due to accreted particles only.

4.1.2.1 Angular momentum budget: gravitational torque and accretion

Being interested in the physical mechanisms driving the binary evolution, we firstly identify two distinct processes:

1. the gravitational torques exerted by the gaseous particles onto each individual BH, \mathbf{T}_G (gravity torque)
2. the accretion of instreaming particles crossing either BH sink radius, $(d\mathbf{L}/dt)_{\text{acc}}$ (accretion torque).

Conservation of the total angular momentum in the simulations implies

$$\frac{d\mathbf{L}}{dt} = \mathbf{T}_G + \frac{d\mathbf{L}}{dt}_{\text{acc}}, \quad (4.1)$$

where \mathbf{L} is the BHB orbital angular momentum vector. All vectors are computed with respect to a Cartesian reference frame centred in the BHB *centre of mass* (CoM)¹; the binary initially lies in the x - y plane with angular momentum oriented along the positive z axis. In our SPH simulations, \mathbf{T}_G can be computed at each snapshot by direct summation of individual particle torques onto each BH yielding

$$\mathbf{T}_G = \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^2 \mathbf{r}_k \times \frac{GM_k m_j (\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_k)}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_k|^3}, \quad (4.2)$$

where j runs over all N gas particles, k identifies the two BHs, \mathbf{r} are position vectors, and m and M denote particle and BH masses respectively. On the other hand, $(d\mathbf{L}/dt)_{\text{acc}}$ can be computed by assuming instantaneous linear momentum conservation of each accreted particle yielding $\Delta\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{r}_k \times m_j \mathbf{v}_j$. Here \mathbf{r}_k is the position vector of the accreting BH at the moment of swallowing the particle, and \mathbf{v}_j is the particle velocity vector. Numerically, we can evaluate the binary angular momentum change $\Delta\mathbf{L}$ at each snapshot by writing Eq. (4.1) in the form

$$\Delta\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{T}_G \Delta t + \sum_{\Delta t} \mathbf{r}_k \times m_j \mathbf{v}_j, \quad (4.3)$$

where Δt is the interval between two subsequent snapshots, and the sum runs over all the accretion events occurring in this time lapse.

We use Eq. (4.3) to assess the relative importance of gravitational torques and accretion in the evolution of the system. In Fig. 4.4, we plot the evolution of the x, y, z components of the angular momentum \mathbf{L} as directly evaluated from the positions and velocities of the two BHs stored in the simulation outputs (red), together with the relative changes due to accretion (black dotted) and gravity torques (black dashed) according to Eq. (4.3). The solid black line is the sum of the latter two which should overlap with the red line if our decomposition is sufficiently accurate and these are the only two physical processes determining the binary evolution. For comparison, in simulation units, the initial binary angular momentum is ≈ 0.18 . As explained in the caption of Fig. 4.4, we find very good agreement between the two lines. Note that in three of the runs, the overall angular momentum grows over time, even though a shrinks and e increases. This counter intuitive result is due to the dominance of accretion in the angular momentum budget, and will be explained in § 4.1.2.2 below.

As a general rule, the accretion contribution to the binary \mathbf{L} evolution (i.e., the accretion torque) is at least comparable to the effect of the gravitational torques. It is therefore also interesting to see the accretion contribution to the evolution of the binary orbital elements. Having stored all the accretion events, this can be done separately by simply evolving the binary from a_0 and e_0 only by adding one accreted particle after the other, imposing linear

¹ The binary CoM slightly wiggles around the total binary-disc CoM. As a cross check, we also computed all the relevant quantities with respect to the latter, finding no significant difference in the results.

BHB angular
momentum
growing

accretion
contribution

Fig. 4.4: BINARY ANGULAR MOMENTUM CONSISTENCY CHECK - Consistency check of the evolution of the binary angular momentum components for all the simulations. In each plot, the L_x , L_y and L_z component evolution is shown from the top to the bottom. In each panel, the dashed line is the ΔL exchange balancing the gravity torques at each time step, the dotted line is the ΔL exchange computed from the accreted particles, and the solid black line is the sum of those two. For comparison, the red line is the angular momentum evolution taken directly from the raw simulation data. The L_x and L_y components are almost constant, showing fluctuations at the 10^{-4} level. The mismatch between the red and the solid black lines here is because simulation outputs are in single precision, i.e. accurate to the fourth digit, which is the fluctuation level of the computed quantity. On the contrary, the L_z component changes up to a 10^{-2} absolute level (i.e., about 5% of the initial value), and in this case we see very good agreement between the two lines. All ΔL are in units of $[M_0 a_0 V_{c,0}]$.

momentum conservation. This "would-be" evolution of $\epsilon(t)$ and $a(t)$, accounting only for the accretion effect, is shown in black in all panels of Fig. 4.3. It is clear that $\epsilon(t)$ is mainly driven by gravitational torques, with accretion playing a negligible role. This is in line with our previous findings, where the evolution of the eccentricity was attributed mainly to the gravitational interaction between the binary and the overdensities excited by its quadrupolar potential in the inner rim of the circumbinary disc. Conversely, the $a(t)$ plots highlight the importance of accretion for the semimajor axis evolution. In the *iso05* case, the binary shrinking due to accretion is actually larger than the total one, meaning that the disc torques would force the binary to expand; an effect similar to that described by Lin & Papaloizou (2011) in the context of planetary migration in self-gravitating discs. Note that in the *adia* cases \dot{a} is dominated by the effect of the disc. This explains the match between such simulations and the Ivanov et al. (1999) analytical model based on angular momentum transport through the disc (Cuadra et al., 2009).

4.1.2.2 Dissection of the binary evolution into its components

So far, we have separated the relative contribution of gravitational torques and accretion to the binary angular momentum budget. We now investigate how the angular momentum change is distributed among the relevant binary quantities. As clearly shown in Fig. 4.4, L_x and L_y show only small fluctuations (and therefore remain small compared to L_z , since the binary initially orbits in the x - y plane). From here on, we will therefore concentrate on the dominant L_z component. The binary angular momentum is

$$L_z = \mu \sqrt{GMa(1 - \epsilon^2)}, \quad (4.4)$$

where $\mu = M_1 M_2 / M$ is the binary reduced mass. Eq. (4.4) can be differentiated to separate the contribution of each single relevant quantity to the angular momentum change:

$$\frac{\dot{L}_z}{L_z} = \frac{\dot{a}}{2a} + \frac{\dot{M}}{2M} + \frac{\dot{\mu}}{\mu} - \frac{\epsilon}{1 - \epsilon^2} \dot{\epsilon}. \quad (4.5)$$

four contributions

By directly measuring a , ϵ , M , μ from the simulation, we can evaluate each single term and decompose the L_z evolution accordingly. This is shown in Fig. 4.5 for all the four runs. Note that the sum of the four contributions (solid black line in each panel) closely matches the measured L_z evolution directly measured from the simulation (red), validating our first-order expansion.

It is worth noting that the increase of L_z is perfectly compatible with semi-major axis shrinkage and eccentricity growth. In fact, Eq. (4.5) can be inverted to obtain

$$\frac{\dot{a}}{a} = \frac{2T_z}{L_z} - \frac{\dot{M}}{M} - \frac{2\dot{\mu}}{\mu} + \frac{2\epsilon}{1 - \epsilon^2} \dot{\epsilon}, \quad (4.6)$$

reduced mass
increases

where we used the fact that $\dot{L}_z \equiv T_z$. Even if the total torque is positive, and the eccentricity grows, the binary can shrink because of the negative contribution of the M and the μ terms. In particular, as we will see below, the higher accretion onto the secondary hole results in a large increase of μ (long-dashed line in Fig. 4.5) which is the main driver of the binary angular momentum growth. Eqs. (4.5) and (4.6) highlight the importance of accretion in determining the binary temporal evolution.

Fig. 4.5: DECOMPOSITION OF THE L_z EVOLUTION FOR THE FOUR RUNS - The ΔL_z contributions stem from a (dotted), ϵ (dashed), M (dot dashed) and μ (long dashed) variations separately. The sum of the four contributions is given by the solid black line, whereas the solid red line is, as in Fig. 4.4, the angular momentum evolution taken directly from the raw simulation data. All ΔL are in units of $[M_0 a_0 V_{c,0}]$.

4.1.3 Gravitational torques

As pointed out in the previous Section, understanding secular dynamics of BHBs in gaseous environments is closely tied to studying the interplay between long distance gravitational forces, hydrodynamics and accretion. In this Section, we focus on the torques coming from the self-gravitating gaseous disc, investigating the influence of regions at different distances from the BHB.

4.1.3.1 Time averaged torque profiles

Gravitational torques exerted by the disc onto the BHB can be directly calculated at each snapshot from Eq. (4.2). It is of great interest to understand where such torques originate, and given the cylindrical nature of the problem, it is natural to investigate their azimuthally-averaged radial distribution. We take r to be the projected radial coordinate (in the x - y plane) from the binary CoM, and we define dT/dr to be the differential torque, integrated over the azimuthal coordinate and the disc height. The total average torque exerted by gas in the projected distance interval $[a, b]$ from the binary CoM is

$$\langle T_{[a,b]} \rangle = \left\langle \int_a^b \frac{dT}{dr} dr \right\rangle, \quad (4.7)$$

total average
torque

where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes temporal averaging over the entire simulation.

In Fig. 4.6, we show the time averaged differential torque acting on the binary, $\langle dT/dr \rangle$ (blue), together with its integral according to Eq. (4.7) (black). We also decompose the former in the two components acting on the primary (green) and the secondary (red) BH. All torques are null at the binary corotation radius we therefore show the total torque by integrating from this point inwards ($\langle T_{[1,0]} \rangle$, binary region) and outwards ($\langle T_{[1,\infty]} \rangle$, disc region).

Fig. 4.6: DIFFERENTIAL TORQUES dT/dr AVERAGED OVER THE ENTIRE SIMULATIONS - in units of $[GM_0^2 a_0^{-2}]$. In each panel we show the differential torque on the primary (green), on the secondary (red), the sum of the two (blue), and the total integrated torque (black) according to Eq. 4.7. This latter is integrated starting from a inwards and outwards. Notably, the inward torque is positive, whereas the outward torque is negative.

In all simulations, the local average torque shows an oscillatory behaviour with a sharp maximum at the location of the secondary BH, $r \sim 0.75$, and a deep minimum in the cavity region at $1 < r < 2$. In the body of the disc ($r > 2$) positive and negative peaks alternate, but they are shallow and almost cancel out, giving a negligible contribution to the total torque (as witnessed by the fact that the integrated torque is basically constant for $r > 2$). Note that the torque on the secondary BH is always larger than the torque on the primary, due to its proximity to the outer disc resulting in a stronger interaction. The general behaviour is qualitatively the same in the *adia* and *iso* runs. In this latter case, however, we found a much sharper negative peak at $r \approx 1.7$ followed by a smaller secondary negative bump at $r \approx 1.2$. This appears to be an artefact of the sudden change in EoS of the gas inside the cavity, at $r = 1.75$. The net result is a smaller negative $\langle T_{[1,\infty]} \rangle$ which has important consequences on the binary evolution. We see in fact that in the *iso* runs $\langle T_{[1,0]} \rangle$ and $\langle T_{[1,\infty]} \rangle$ almost cancel out, meaning that, overall, gravitational torques do not change the binary angular momentum. Conversely, in the *adia* runs $\langle T_{[1,0]} \rangle$ is much smaller (in absolute value)

large positive peak
at secondary BH

than $\langle T_{[1,\infty]} \rangle$, implying an efficient angular momentum transfer from the binary to the gas (MM08; Cuadra et al., 2009).

4.1.3.2 Spectral analysis

We now consider the torque evolution in time. We separately discuss torques coming from different disc regions by showing both the time series and their associated power spectra. The associated time series and power spectra are shown respectively in the left and right panels of Fig. 4.7, where we cut the spatial domain into the following radial annuli:

- (i) $0 < r < 10 a$: the entire domain
- (ii) $0 < r < 1 a$: the 'binary region'
- (iii) $1 a < r < 1.8 a$: the 'cavity region'
- (iv) $1.8 a < r < 2.5 a$: the 'rim region'
- (v) $2.5 a < r < 10 a$: the 'disc region'

In all the simulations, the overall torque (i), shows a clear periodic oscillation, much larger in amplitude than its average value. The power spectrum unveils several distinctive peaks, with relative amplitudes that can vary significantly for different simulations. In particular, peaks in the *iso* simulations are much sharper and better defined. This is because in the *adia* simulations the BHB shrinks significantly, resulting in a broadening of the characteristic frequencies. Moreover, as we shall see in the next section, the disc sub-structures are much better defined in the *iso* runs, giving rise to neater features.

distinctive peaks

In the binary region (ii) the torque is mostly coherent and positive. Because the torque strength in (ii) is regulated by the mass inflow, it shows periodicities that are related to the accretion flow: a disc component around $f \approx 0.25P_0^{-1}$ (corresponding to the disc peak density at $r \approx 2.5a$), the forcing frequency of the binary at $f = P_0^{-1}$, and the beat between these two at $f \approx 0.75P_0^{-1}$ (see Section 4.1.4 and Section 4.2.4). In the cavity region (iii) the torque is negative on average but strongly oscillating. Several periodicities are detectable, the most striking being a peak at $f \approx P_0^{-1}$ which appears again to be directly related to the binary period. In the rim region (iv) the torque is highly oscillating, and the strongest feature is a sharp peak at $f \approx 1.3P_0^{-1}$, whereas in the disc region (v) the only significant spectral component is at $f \approx 1.7P_0^{-1}$. As a general trend, moving from the inner region to the disc body, torques become incoherent (i.e. they average to zero) and strongly oscillating (compare the power spectra scales in the different panels of each plot).

different cuts
reveal
characteristics

4.1.3.3 Interpretation: torque origin and location in the disc

In this Section, we provide a global interpretation of the features observed both in the radial distribution of the time averaged torques and in their temporal evolution. The arguments discussed below are supported by Figs. 4.8-4.9-4.10 and by Tab. 4.2.

Origin of the positive and negative peaks

It seems natural to compare the torque radial profiles obtained by our simulations with linear theory perturbation, in which torque minima and maxima are connected to *outer Lindblad resonances* (OLRs). It is in fact tempting to associate the torque minimum at $r \approx 1.6a$ with the 2:1 OLR. We should however be careful in pushing this interpretation too far, since, as already pointed out by MM08 and S11, the assumptions of linear theory are not satisfied in this context. Most importantly, looking at the upper panels of Figs. 4.8 and 4.9, we notice that the region $r < 2a$ is almost devoid of gas, and the streams are almost

connection to
OLRs problematic

Fig. 4.7: TORQUES ON BHB IN TIME AND FREQUENCY DOMAIN - Each plot depicts the torques exerted by the disc on the BHB in the time domain (*left panels*) and in the frequency domain (*right panels*). In each plot, from the top to the bottom, pairs of panels refer to the five domains discussed in the text: total torque (i), torque exerted by the material located at $r < a$ (ii), $a < r < 1.8a$ (iii), $1.8a < r < 2.5a$ (iv) and $r > 2.5a$ (v). In each *left panel*, the red line is the raw oscillating torque, and the blue one is the torque smoothed over three periods to show the average behaviour. In the associated *right panel*, we plot the power spectrum as a function of frequency in units of the initial binary orbital frequency. All torques strongly oscillate, showing several characteristic frequencies, however, note the different scales of the panels.

Fig. 4.8: DISC DENSITY AND TORQUES OF THE *iso05* SIMULATION *Top panel:* typical instantaneous logarithmic surface mass density. *Bottom row:* combined surface torque density exerted by the disc onto the binary (*left panel*), onto the primary BH (*central panel*) and onto the secondary BH (*right panel*). All plots are in code units: $G = M_0 = a_0 = 1$.

radial. Mass fluxes reported in Tab. 4.2 clearly show that, at any radius, there are always fluxes of ingoing and outgoing mass, resulting in a steady net inward flux consistent with the accretion rate onto the two BHs. A strict OLR interpretation of the torque minimum at $r \approx 1.6a$ would instead require particles in circular orbit at that radius, experiencing a secular effect due to the phase-coherent periodic forcing of the binary; this is not what happens within the cavity region. The strongest 2:1 OLR is certainly responsible for the evacuation of the gas close to the binary and for the formation and maintenance of a cavity, however cannot be directly responsible for the coherent torque seen in the cavity region. This is also supported by the fact that MM08 and S11 find a minimum at the same location ($r \approx 1.6 - 1.7a$) for an equal mass binary, where the 2:1 resonance is absent (because of the symmetry of the forcing potential), and the location of the strongest OLR (3:2) would be at $r \approx 1.3a$. The strong negative torque in the cavity region has a purely kinematic origin: material ripped off the disc edge forms well defined streams *following* the two BHs, which are clearly distinguishable in both the surface density plots shown in Fig. 4.8 and 4.9. The

non-circular orbits

inner torque of kinematic origin

Fig. 4.9: Disc density and torques of the ADIA05 simulation *Top panel:* typical instantaneous logarithmic surface mass density. *Bottom row:* combined surface torque density exerted by the disc onto the binary (*left panel*), onto the primary BH (*central panel*) and onto the secondary BH (*right panel*). All plots are in code units: $G = M_0 = a_0 = 1$. Compared to Fig. 4.8, the features highlighted above are even more evident (especially the symmetric overdensities at the inner edge of the disc).

streams are responsible for the yellow tails following the two BHs at $\sim 1.5a$ in the torque density panels, which lead to a net negative torque. Conversely, at $r \gtrsim 2a$, we have a well defined, almost circular disc, and the torque density peaks at $r \approx 2a$ and $r \approx 2.5a$ can be identified with the loci of the strong 3:1 and 4:1 OLRs (Artymowicz & Lubow, 1994).

Our simulations also allow us to investigate the torques within the binary corotation radius at $r < a$, a region often excised in grid-based simulations (see MM08 and S11). Here we find strong positive torques on both BHs. This is because the infalling material approaches the BHs at super-Keplerian velocities, and bends in a horseshoe fashion, exerting a net positive torque in front of them. In fact, the maximum positive torque basically coincides with the location of the two BHs (sharp peak at $r \approx 0.75a$ for the secondary and a broader peak around $r \approx 0.3a$ for the primary, see Fig. 4.6). The very same

effect, in the context of planetary migration, was discussed by Lin & Papaloizou (2011).¹ Note that the positive torque is related to this 'stream bending', and not directly to the small discs of gas orbiting each BH; its magnitude is in fact similar in the *iso* and in the *adia* simulations, even though in the former, the mass in the minidisks is significantly larger as shown by the time and azimuthally averaged surface density profiles in the upper panel of Fig. 4.10.

stream bending

Table 4.2: ACCRETION RATES ONTO THE BINARY AND MASS FLUXES F - in units $M/P_0 \times 10^{-5}$ at two selected distances to the binary CoM: $r_1 = a$ and $r_2 = 1.5a$. \dot{M}_1 and \dot{M}_2 are the average accretion rates on M_1 and M_2 respectively, while \dot{M} is the sum of the two. At both selected distances, F_{in} and F_{out} represent the ingoing and outgoing fluxes, and $F_{\text{net}} = F_{\text{in}} - F_{\text{out}}$ is the net ingoing flux. All quantities have been averaged over 90 binary orbits.

Model	$r_1 = a$						$r_2 = 1.5a$			
	\dot{M}_1	\dot{M}_2	\dot{M}	$F_{\text{in}1}$	$F_{\text{out}1}$	$F_{\text{net}1}$	$F_{\text{in}2}$	$F_{\text{out}2}$	$F_{\text{net}2}$	
iso10	4.5	10.7	15.2	19.6	4.5	15.1	33.7	18.8	14.9	
iso05	4.2	9.2	13.4	19.1	5.5	13.6	31.7	18.4	13.4	
adia10	3.8	9.5	13.3	17.6	4.3	13.3	42.8	29.7	13.2	
adia05	3.2	4.6	7.8	13.5	5.8	7.7	36.0	28.4	7.6	

Disc structure and characteristic torque frequencies

The surface density profiles in Fig. 4.8 and 4.9 highlight some clear differences between the *iso* and the *adia* runs: (i) the appearance and shape of the minidisks; (ii) the amount of gas feeding the streams; (iii) the definition of the inner disc edge. In the *iso* runs, we find a large amount of gas forming mini-discs around both BHs and an almost empty cavity except for two tenuous streams connecting the outer edge to the mini-discs. The edge of the disc is quite circular and well defined. Conversely, due to the gas inside the cavity being hotter in the *adia* runs, the streaming activity is more violent with thick spirals that do not settle into well defined mini-discs, but rather form a diluted, ∞ -shaped cloud around the binary. The edge of the disc is strongly disturbed by the ripped out streams and is usually not circular. The different streaming activity is also confirmed by numbers in Tab. 4.2, where we collect the average inwards and outwards mass fluxes at $r = 1.5a$ and $r = a$. Mass fluxes are generally larger in the *adia* case. Note that this does not necessarily result in larger accretion, as outgoing fluxes are also larger in this case. Most of the material in the streams, does not end up in an accretion flow, but is accelerated back to the disc (a sort of 'slingshot') impacting on the inner edge, an effect already seen and extensively described by MM08 and S11. The amount of impacting gas is 50% larger in the *adia* case, possibly contributing to the inner edge destabilization and to the larger perturbation in the disc structure. The appearance of spirals in the disc is related to the behaviour of the Toomre Q parameter, shown in the bottom panel of Fig. 4.10, which quantifies the degree of self-gravity of a disc. Not surprisingly the disc develops a spiral pattern in the region $3a \lesssim r \lesssim 5a$, where, in fact, we find that the Toomre parameter reaches its minimum value $Q \approx 1.5$ (Cuadra et al.,

influence of EoS

inner disc edge destabilised

spiral arms at minimum Q

¹ Lin & Papaloizou (2011) found that such positive torque can in principle counter-balance the negative torque due to the disc and the tails, causing, in their case, angular momentum to be transferred to the planet, resulting in an *outwards* migration.

Fig. 4.10: DISC PROPERTIES: TOOMRE PARAMETER Q AND SURFACE DENSITY Σ - average surface density (*top panel*), and Toomre parameter Q (*bottom panel*) as a function of r . Line style denotes **iso10** (long dashed), **iso05** (dot dashed), adia10 (solid) and adia05 (dashed).

2009). The shape of the spiral arms varies much in time, and their definition is different from simulation to simulation. However, at any time we find spiral structures with 2, 3 or 4 arms, which remain confined between $3a < r < 5a$.

The disc structures highlighted above are reflected in the torques depicted in the lower panels of Fig. 4.8 and 4.9. The total torque shows a typical quadrupolar structure, which leads to rapid oscillations averaging to zero in the disc body. Conversely, as already discussed, in the inner cavity we can appreciate the yellow tails following the two BHs at $\sim 1.5a$, leading to a net negative torque.

The main peaks observed in the torque power spectra must therefore arise from the structures we just described. In particular we identified the overdensities at $r \approx 2a$ in the inner rim of the disc, and the spiral structures at $r \gtrsim 3a$ in the main body of the disc. The main torque frequencies must come from the interaction between the forcing binary quadrupolar potential and such overdensities propagating in the disc. To test this hypothesis, we mimic the situation by placing test particles in circular orbits at $r = 2a$ and $r = 3.5a$ around a circular binary. We compute the torques and show them as blue lines in Fig. 4.11. The natural frequency between a quadrupolar potential oscillating with frequency f_1 and an overdensity orbiting at frequency f_2 is the beat frequency $2f_1 - f_2$, and this is what we see in the Fourier spectrum. The beats between the binary and the particles at $r = 2a$ and at $r = 3.5a$ give rise to sharp peaks seen at $f \approx 1.35P_0^{-1}$ and $f \approx 1.7P_0^{-1}$, respectively. The fact that such peaks are much sharper in the *iso* simulations stems from two facts: (i) the binary does not significantly shrink in the *iso* runs, limiting the broadening of the spectral feature and (ii) the disc features (disc edge and spiral arms) are much more defined in this case, and the torques are well localized. This can be also

dominant torque
frequencies

Fig. 4.11: TOY MODEL FOR PERIODICITY ANALYSIS OF THE DISC - Simple test model for the periodicity generated in the outside disc, i.e. at $r > a$. In the *top panel* we show the temporal evolution of the torque, whereas in the *bottom panel* we show the Fourier transform. In each panel, the **blue** curve is obtained by placing three point masses at distance $1.6a$, $2.1a$, $3.5a$ from a circular binary, and the **red** is the torque found in the *iso10* simulation.

seen by comparing the much neater torque structure in the bottom panel of Fig. 4.8 to the blurry one of Fig. 4.9. The $f \approx P_0^{-1}$ peak of the **blue** line in Fig. 4.11 is obtained by placing a third particle at $r = 1.6a$, a separation corresponding to the maximum negative torque inside the cavity. However, Fig. 4.7 shows that the peak at $f \approx P_0^{-1}$ is stronger at $r > 1.8a$ than in the $a < r < 1.8a$ region, meaning that it must be mostly directly related to the periodicity at which the binary rips gas off the disc edge (i.e. the binary period), and not to a specific radius in the cavity. Finally, as already noticed, torques in the binary region are related to the mass fuelling the two BHs, and therefore show periodicities related to the binary ($f = P_0^{-1}$), to the inner rim of the disc ($f \approx 0.25P_0^{-1}$) and to the beat between the two ($f \approx 0.75P_0^{-1}$). Note that the latter two are much more evident in the *adia* runs, where the disc rim overdensities feeding the accretion streams are more pronounced.

toy model

4.1.4 Accretion

In Tab. 4.2 we also show the average mass accretion rates. We recall here that a particle is considered accreted when it crosses the sink radius of one of the BHs. Then both its mass and its linear momentum are added to the BH, ensuring the global conservation of both quantities. The mass accretion rate is almost independent on the sink radius in the *iso* simulation, where instreaming gas settles in well defined accretion discs progressively loosing angular momentum. Conversely, in the *adia* case, the accretion rate scales almost linearly with the sink radius, suggesting a direct relation to the BH cross section ($\sim r_{\text{sink}}$).

It is particularly interesting to compare the accretion rate to the mass flow rates. Firstly we notice that in all simulations the accretion rate and the mass flow rates at $r = a$ and $r = 1.5a$ are nearly the same, meaning that the system is in a steady state configuration. Interestingly, the mass accretion rate is $\sim 25\%$ lower than the inflow rate at $r = a$. This means that not all the material crossing $r = a$ is accreted, an assumption commonly adopted in grid simulations where the $r < a$ region is excised. Part of the gas suffers a slingshot impacting back to the disc, affecting further the disc-binary angular momentum transfer.

Fig. 4.12: ACCRETION ONTO THE TWO BHs- *Top box:* accretion rate as a function of time. The red line is the total accretion rate while the blue and black lines are the accretion rates onto the secondary and the primary respectively. *Lower box:* Fourier transform of the total accretion rate (*lower panel*) and of the torques (*upper panel*). In the *upper panel*, the green line is the total torque (highest peak normalized to 1) and the red line is the torque exerted by the material at $r < a$ (multiplied by ten).

In the top panel of Fig. 4.12 we show the temporal evolution of the accretion rate on the primary hole, \dot{M}_1 , on the secondary hole, \dot{M}_2 , and the sum of the two, \dot{M} . As already found in Cuadra et al. (2009), \dot{M}_2 is a factor ~ 2 larger than \dot{M}_1 , due to the closer interaction between the secondary BH and the disc. The relative mass growth $\delta M/M$ is therefore about six time faster for the secondary BH, implying the binary mass ratio will tend toward $q \approx 1$ if this condition persists over the entire evolution of the system. Accretion rates are strongly modulated in time, and notably, \dot{M}_2 shows a striking periodicity related to the binary orbital period, whereas \dot{M}_1 is dominated by longer timescale fluctuation, related to the overdensities developing at the inner rim of the circumbinary disc.

The Fourier transform of \dot{M} is given in the lower panel of Fig. 4.12. We observe the usual three distinctive peaks observed in the torques coming from the binary region, as shown by the central panel of the figure. It is clear that the accretion and inner-torque periodicities

mass ratio
increasing

Fig. 4.13: ACCRETED ANGULAR MOMENTUM AND COHERENCE OF ACCRETION - In the *top box* of each figure, from the top to the bottom, we show the change in the *x (top)* *y (middle)* and *z (lower)* components of the angular momentum of the binary. In the lower box of each figure we show the incoming angle of the accreted material with respect to the binary orbital plane. In each box, red lines are for the **primary BH** and blue lines are for the **secondary BH**. Note that ΔL_x and ΔL_y fluctuate around zero, as a result of the planar nature of the system, and are much smaller (by an order of magnitude) than ΔL_z , which is always positive. The accretion onto the two BHs is therefore coherent and mostly in the binary plane (more for the isothermal runs ($\theta < 5\text{deg}$) than for the adiabatic ones ($\theta \approx 10\text{deg}$)). From this, one can extrapolate the spin evolution history of the two BHs. The spins will tend to align with the binary (disc) plane if they are not already aligned in first place, and will tend to grow toward the maximum allowed value (depending on the duration of this binary-disc evolution phase).

are intimately connected, both reflecting the temporal evolution of the mass inflow in the binary region (ii).

Finally we can check the orientation of the angular momentum vector of the accreted material in the reference frame of the accreting BH. This number quantifies the level of ‘coherence’ of the accretion flow, and has important consequences for the individual BH spin evolution and the magnitude of gravitational recoil at the coalescence (Bogdanović et al., 2007; Dotti et al., 2010; Kesden et al., 2010; Volonteri et al., 2010; Lousto & Zlochower, 2011; Lousto et al., 2012). At each snapshot we therefore compute the average L_z and \mathbf{L} of the accreted particles *in the accreting BH reference frame*, and the angle $\theta = \arccos(L_z/L)$ defining the degree of misalignment with respect to the z axis. Our results are similar to what already found by Dotti et al. (2009), although in the cited study the spin evolution was studied only before the gas scouring. More specifically, an isothermal EoS leads to extremely coherent accretion flows, with fluctuations in the angular momentum direction of the mini-discs of few degrees. As shown in Fig. 4.13, in the adiabatic case, the orientation of the minidisc orbiting the secondary changes by at most ≈ 20 degrees, and has an average excursion of 7 degrees, 50% bigger than the oscillations in the primary disc. Assuming that the BH spins have efficiently aligned with the circumbinary disc before the

orientation of
angular
momentum vector

coherent accretion

opening of the cavity (Dotti et al., 2010) this implies that the efficient spin-up of the binary will continue following cavity opening.

4.1.5 Comparison with previous works

The binary evolution and torque structure have been previously investigated by MM08 and S11, as mentioned above. In particular, we can compare results regarding the average gravitational torques and the mass accretion rates. While both of them can be expressed in several ways, we find it practical to normalize these quantities to the disc mass, M_d , initial binary period, P_0 , and initial binary angular momentum magnitude, L_0 . In these units we can write:

$$\langle T_{[1,\infty]} \rangle = \Gamma_1 L_0 M_d P_0^{-1} \quad (4.8)$$

$$\dot{M} = \Gamma_2 M_d P_0^{-1} \quad (4.9)$$

Here $M_d = \pi \Sigma_p r_p^2$ is the disc mass computed using the peak surface density¹ Σ_p . In both MM08 and S11, $r_p \approx 3a$, close to what we find in our discs (see Fig. 4.10). Before proceeding with this comparison we should mention several issues that has to be considered. Firstly $L_0 = (M_0/4)(GM_0 a_0)^{1/2}$ for the circular equal mass binary simulated by MM08 and S11, whereas in our simulation with $q = 1/3$ we have $L_0 = (3M_0/16)(GM_0 a_0)^{1/2}$ (assuming a circular binary). Secondly, the concept of 'accretion rate' is somewhat ill defined in grid based simulation with an excised central region. The inner boundary of the calculation is at $r = a$ for MM08 and $r = 0.8a$ for S11, and in both cases, whatever crosses that boundary is considered accreted. As already discussed (see Tab. 4.2) $\approx 25\%$ of the mass crossing $r = a$ is accelerated back to the disc edge extracting angular momentum from the binary (an effect already seen and described extensively by MM08 and S11 for the material inflowing in the cavity but not reaching the excised region). We can therefore consider MM08 and S11 to overestimate the accretion rate by a factor of 25%. Lastly, MM08 and S11 can compute gravitational torques only for $r \gtrsim a$, outside the binary corotation radius². As shown by both studies (and independently recovered by us), gravitational torques *exerted by the disc elements on the binary* are negative in this region.

new findings
inbetween old
results

For the comparison we use the *iso05* and the *adia05* runs. In the torque computation, we find $\Gamma_1 = -3.5 \times 10^{-3}$ for the former and $\Gamma_1 = -5.3 \times 10^{-3}$ for the latter. This can be compared to -1.26×10^{-3} of MM08 and -1.8×10^{-2} of S11. Our gravity torques are a factor 3-4 larger than MM08 and a factor 4-5 smaller than S11. Concerning the accretion, we get $\Gamma_2 = 1.1 \times 10^{-3}$ for the *iso05* run and $\Gamma_2 = 6 \times 10^{-4}$ for the *adia05* run, to be compared to $\Gamma_2 = 1.2 \times 10^{-4}$ of MM08 and $\Gamma_2 = 6 \times 10^{-3}$ for S11. Our accretion rates are a factor 5-10 larger than MM08 and a factor 5-10 smaller than S11. The similar scaling between $\langle T_{[1,\infty]} \rangle$ and \dot{M} is not surprising, since, as discussed in Section 4.1.3, the former is directly linked to the streams fuelling the BHs.

4.1.6 Discussion

The evolution of BHBs in circumbinary discs remains largely an open issue. Here we carried out a detailed study of the torques acting on the BHB, including the effect of the outer disc, the mass flowing in the cavity and, for the first time, of the gas entering

¹ Note that we have a physical disc mass in our simulations, but we use this quantity to ease the comparison with MM08 and S11.

² S11 already pointed out the change of sign of the torques at $r = a$.

the BHB region and eventually accreting onto the two BHs. We paid particular attention to investigating the individual contribution of different disc regions and we aimed at separating the effect of accretion from the effect of gravitational torques. The emerging picture is far more complex than the often adopted simple assumption that resonant torques arising at the disc inner edge transfer angular momentum from the BHB to the disc, causing the orbital decay (e.g. Papaloizou & Pringle, 1977; Goldreich & Tremaine, 1980; Ivanov et al., 1999; Armitage & Natarajan, 2002; Haiman et al., 2009).

Firstly, as already pointed out by a number of authors (e.g. MM08, S11), the presence of a BHB clearing a cavity in the disc *does not* prevent gas inflows and eventual accretion onto the two BHs. Such inflowing gas has a non negligible role in defining the BHB-disc mutual evolution; it forms streams that follow the BHs, eventually exerting a net *negative* torque in the cavity region. The inflows catch-up with the BHs at a super-Keplerian speed, bend in front of them, thus exerting a net *positive* torque inside the binary corotation radius (i.e. at $r < a$). We therefore conclude that the origin of the dominating gravitational torques on the binary is purely kinematic, and can be understood without directly invoking resonances of the forcing binary potential with the disc.

net negative
torque purely
kinematic

The strong positive gravitational torque is related to the gas inflows only, and not to the formation of minidisks around the two BHs nor to the eventual accretion. This becomes clear by inspecting Figs. 4.6, 4.10 and Tab. 4.2; although there is a factor up to ten difference in the mass bound to the BHs in minidisks, and a factor of three difference in the accretion rate among the simulations, the positive torque is almost the same. This is because the gravitational torque is only related to the *inflowing* mass bending in front of the BHs, which is of the same order in all simulations. Note that different thermodynamics lead to different negative/positive torque balance. Although this might be an artefact of the sudden change of EoS in the *iso* simulations, such a balance has to be better understood in order to assess the fate of the binary.

positive torque
due to inflows

Torques exerted by gas in the main body of the disc ($r > 2a$) are instead negligible for the long term evolution of the system, since they average to zero (Fig. 4.6)¹. Local torque maxima can be associated to the 3:1 and 4:1 OLRs (Artymowicz & Lubow, 1994). Given the nature of the forcing potential, a quadrupolar torque pattern naturally develops (Figs. 4.8 and 4.9) causing a time oscillating torque (Fig. 4.7) with characteristic frequencies related to the beat between twice the binary frequency and the characteristic orbital frequencies of inhomogeneities developing in the disc in form of inner edge overdensities and spiral arms (Fig. 4.11).

main disc torques
negligible

Accretion plays an important role in the binary angular momentum budget. The binary can actually gain angular momentum even if it shrinks and its eccentricity increases. This is because accretion deposits a significant amount of angular momentum in the system by increasing its mass and mass ratio (see Eq. (4.5)). The peculiar case of *iso05* is quite interesting: here the total gravitational torque exerted by the gas is almost null (Fig. 4.6). However, the BHB-disc mutual torques are responsible for the eccentricity growth, meaning that, if angular momentum was transferred by gravitational torques only, the BHB would be forced to expand. This is what we see in the upper-right panel of Fig. 4.3, where we show that the accretion-driven shrinking is faster than the actual evolution found in the simulation. In this case, gravitational torques alone would force the BHB to *expand*, whereas accretion is responsible for the shrinkage. Although whether this happens in Nature is questionable, it highlights the complexity of the BHB-disc interplay.

accretion as
important as
gravity torque

We should, nonetheless, be careful in drawing any conclusion about accretion from our simulations. If we scale our system to the fiducial binary of Chapter 6 and set $M_1 =$

caveats

¹ Note that this region excludes the disc edge

$2.6 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ and $a_0 = 0.039$ pc, then the accretion rate we find corresponds to about $20\text{--}40\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}}$ for the secondary BH, and $4\text{--}7\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}}$ for the primary BH. In such situation, it is likely that most of the gas which is *numerically* accreted in our simulations will be expelled through outflows and winds. In this case, if the gas binds to the BHs before being expelled, it transfers its linear (and angular) momentum to the holes, even if not accreted (Nixon et al., 2011). However, its mass does not add-up to the binary, making the question of angular momentum transfer more delicate and worthy of deeper and more refined investigations.

better
 thermodynamics
 required

Our simulations allowed us to investigate different EoSs and sink radii r_{sink} . The numerical size of r_{sink} has a minor impact on the general behaviour of the system, affecting the mass bound to the BH in minidisks and the accretion rate in the *adia* case. Conversely, the adopted EoS has a major impact on the results. In the *iso* runs, tenuous streams leak from an almost circular disc edge and fuel two well defined mini-discs, whereas streaming activity is more violent in the *adia* case, with thick spirals leaking from a deeply distorted disc edge, forming a diluted, ∞ -shaped cloud around the binary. This difference in streaming activity affects both the overall structure of the outer disc and the long-term binary evolution (as mentioned above). Although the extrapolation of the results of all our four simulations would imply a fast BHB coalescence (in less than 10^7 yr, for the fiducial binary parameters considered above), the almost perfect cancellation of the net gravitational torque in the *iso* simulations suggest that more realistic models for gas thermodynamics will be necessary to make clear-cut statements on this issue.

4.2 Limiting eccentricity in prograde discs

Having found in the above that the eccentricity grows in all cases in our model, independently of the EoS employed, it is interesting to ask whether the growth will saturate at some point. We study this by simulating a sequence of binary models that differ in the initial eccentricity ϵ_0 , only. In initially low-eccentric binaries, the eccentricity increases with time, while in high-eccentric binaries ϵ declines, indicating the existence of a limiting eccentricity ϵ_{crit} that is found to fall in the interval $[0.6, 0.8]$. We also present an analytical interpretation for this saturation limit.

It should be noted, that the excitation of ϵ was already noticed and studied in Armitage & Natarajan (2005), who investigated BH orbital decay in the presence of a Keplerian α -disc in two dimensions, as well as in earlier analytical work by Goldreich & Sari (2003) in the context of type-II planet migration.

structure

In the following Section, we take on the strategy of constructing a sequence of binaries with fixed semi-major axis, BH and disc-BH mass ratios but with different initial eccentricities ϵ_0 , varying it from 0.2 to 0.8. The binaries interact with the standard self-gravitating disc of Chapter 3.1.6 changing their orbital elements. With this approach we assess whether the eccentricity growth saturates, and at which value. We present a simple analytical interpretation of our numerical results in Section 4.2.3.

4.2.1 Simulation Set-up

Our goal is to study the secular evolution of the binary-disc system, focusing in the evolution of the binary eccentricity. The ideal method would be to follow the binary from an initial, pc-scale separation, until it reaches the GW-dominated regime. Unfortunately such an approach is not feasible. The time scale for decay is $\sim 10^4 \Omega_0^{-1}$ (Cuadra et al., 2009), much longer than what we can feasibly simulate with current computational power. Moreover, as

the binary shrinks, its angular momentum is transferred to the disc. Without appropriate boundary conditions, this results in the unphysical expansion of the disc, slowing further the evolution of the system (Cuadra et al., 2009). To accomplish our goal we take an indirect approach. We run a set of simulations where the gas configuration was taken from the steady state of a previous simulation, as described above, but the binary had different initial eccentricities. The energy of the binary was conserved, i.e. its semi-major axis a was fixed, only the angular momentum of the binary was changed to accomplish the various initial eccentricities e_0 . We then extrapolate the long-term evolution of the eccentricity interpreting the results of the different runs as snapshots of the binary life taken at different ages.

lack of consistent
boundary
conditions

In the following simulations, we use what was denoted as an *iso* run above in § 4.1.3 for the cavity. The effect of this recipe is to confine the gas in the inner region to a relatively thin geometry. For all runs we use 2 million particles. The dynamics of the BHs is followed with a fixed time-step, equal to $0.01 \Omega_0^{-1}$. In the present simulations the sink radius around each BH, below which particles are accreted, is set to $0.03a_0$. A face on view of the disc surface density is shown in Fig. 4.14 in which the gas has already relaxed around a binary of $e_0 = 0.6$. It shows the typical spiral arms in the disc and the resonant streams in the inner cavity region. If this figure is compared to the quasi-circular simulations in the earlier Section, it is clear to see, how much the eccentric binary has pushed out the disc.

set-up
corresponding to
iso03

Fig. 4.14: FACE-ON VIEW OF THE CIRCUMBINARY DISC - surrounding a BH binary of initial eccentricity $e_0 = 0.6$ after 150 orbits. The gas density is colour-coded on a logarithmic scale with warmer colours corresponding to lower gas density; axes in units of the semi-major axis a . The figure shows the spiral patterns excited in the disc, the somewhat cavity surrounding the binary, and the gas inflows around the BHs. Figure made using SPLASH (Price, 2007)

Fig. 4.15: ECCENTRICITY EVOLUTION OVER 400 ORBITS - of the four standard runs, starting from $\epsilon_0 = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$ bottom to top. The initial, transient relaxation is visible at early times

4.2.2 Eccentricity evolution

As described in Section 4.2.1, we prepared four initial conditions identical but for the initial values of the binary eccentricity. In Fig. 4.15 we show the evolution of ϵ for four runs with initial eccentricities $\epsilon_0 = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$, respectively (bottom to top). The bottom panel depicts the monotonic rise of ϵ , for the run with $\epsilon_0 = 0.2$: The eccentricity increases almost linearly after the first $70 f_0^{-1}$. The run for $\epsilon_0 = 0.4$ (second panel) displays a similar behaviour, but the slope $d\epsilon/dt$ is much shallower (note the different scales in the y axes of Fig. 4.15). In the third panel, corresponding to $\epsilon_0 = 0.6$, we observe a fast increase of the eccentricity up to $\epsilon = 0.62$ within the first few orbits; afterwards the eccentricity saturates, approaching a constant with $d\epsilon/dt \sim 0^+$. The top panel refers to the run with the largest initial eccentricity explored, $\epsilon_0 = 0.8$. This time, the eccentricity exhibits a negative slope with $d^2\epsilon/dt^2$ steadily decreasing until $d\epsilon/dt \sim 0^-$.

The key result, illustrated in Fig. 4.15, is the existence of a limiting ϵ_{crit} that the BH binary approaches in its interaction with the disc. Since the runs were halted after 400 orbital cycles, we can only bracket the interval in which ϵ_{crit} lies: $\epsilon_{\text{crit}} \in [0.62, 0.78]$. The reason of this uncertainty is technical as we find that the decline of ϵ is very hard to follow numerically due to the fast expulsion of the gas out of the region where torques can still effectively interact with the BH binary - an effect that increases with the binary eccentricity, as expected. Indeed, if we define R_{cavity} as the inner location of the disc's half-maximal surface density, we find that the gas moves from an initial value of $R_{\text{cavity}} \approx 2a_0$ to a time-averaged value of $\approx 2.6a_0, 3.0a_0, 3.4a_0$, and $3.8a_0$ during the first 53 binary orbits, for the runs with an initial binary eccentricity of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8, respectively. Such an expansion of the gas is not unexpected since no outer inflow boundary conditions were implemented in our simulations. While the rate of eccentricity change is affected by the

low ϵ grows
high ϵ decays

expansion of disc
inner edge

expansion resulting from the initial orbital set-up, its long-term trend (whether it increases or decreases) is a robust conclusion from our numerical study.

Our simulations strongly suggest the existence of a saturation in the disc-driven eccentricity growth, but do not pinpoint the exact value of ϵ_{crit} . In the next section we discuss the physical reasons for this limit and analytically predict the value of ϵ_{crit} .

4.2.3 Explanation of the saturation

Fig. 4.16: CROSS CHECK RUNS WITH ALTERED SETUP - Additional high eccentricity runs where the initial semi-major axis is reduced by a factor 1.8, compared to the default runs. These short runs are used to test the emerging picture of a limiting eccentricity depending on the amount of streams present in the cavity. The difference between the two runs is the thermodynamical treatment of the gas inside the cavity. For runI this is identical to the default runs whereas in runII we suppress gaseous inflows into the cavity. *Left panel:* eccentricity versus time, for $\epsilon_0 = 0.8$. Solid line refers to runI, while dashed line to runII. *Right panel:* azimuthally averaged disc surface density as a function of R [a] in arbitrary units. Surface density is averaged over the orbits 20 – 30. Solid line refers to runI, dashed line to runII (see text for description).

The *growth* of the eccentricity, from initial values ϵ_0 below a critical eccentricity ϵ_{crit} , and the *decline* of ϵ from initial values $\epsilon_0 > \epsilon_{\text{crit}}$ call for a simple physical interpretation. The increase of the eccentricity caused by the interaction of the binary with an external disc is a known fact for very unequal binaries where the non-axisymmetric potential perturbations are small (as in the case of planetary migration, see e.g. Goldreich & Tremaine, 1980; Goldreich & Sari, 2003; Armitage & Natarajan, 2005).

Goldreich & Tremaine (1980) have shown that in the high mass-ratio limit the binary-disc transfer of angular momentum occurs secularly through torques excited in the disc by the binary at discrete Lindblad and co-rotation resonances. Damping and/or growth of ϵ thus depends on the relative importance of these opposing torques (and so on how fluid elements are distributed in the disc). Principal Lindblad resonances are known to

be responsible for opening a cavity in the disc. As a consequence of disc clearance, corotation and inner Lindblad resonances are reduced in power. This consideration led Goldreich & Sari (2003) to show that only the outer Lindblad resonances, remaining after cavity opening, cause the increase of the eccentricity for initially low eccentric binaries. As discussed in § 4.1, this holds also when OLRs cannot be used as full explanation.

For the comparable mass limit studied here ($q = 1/3$) we have a simpler explanation. An initially small ϵ increases because of the larger deceleration experienced by the secondary BH near apo-apsis with respect to peri-apsis (see e.g., Lin & Papaloizou, 1979; Artymowicz et al., 1991). The longer time spent when nearing apo-apsis, and the larger over-density excited in the disc by the hole's gravitational pull due to its immediate proximity are both conducive to a net deceleration of the hole that causes the increase of the binary eccentricity. This increase continues as long as the secondary BH has a larger angular velocity at its apo-apsis $\omega_{2,\text{apo}}$ than the fluid elements in the disc ω_{disc} . When this reverses, the density wake excited by the BH moves ahead imparting to the hole, near apo-apsis, a net tangential acceleration that tends to increase the angular momentum content of the binary, decreasing ϵ . This argument is valid if the disc and the binary angular momenta are aligned. We limit our investigation to discs corotating with the binary, as expected if they form together during a gas rich galaxy merger (Mayer et al., 2007; Dotti et al., 2009). In this case the torques on the secondary will be minimal if $\omega_{\text{disc}} = \omega_{2,\text{apo}}$. The counterrotating case will be discussed in the next Chapter 5. Approximating the binary as a purely Keplerian system and the gaseous disc to be in Keplerian motion around a mass $M_1 + M_2$ located at the system center of mass (CoM), it is easy to derive:

$$\omega_{2,\text{apo}}^2 = \frac{GM_1(1+q)}{(1+\epsilon)^2 a^3} \left(\frac{2}{1+\epsilon} - 1 \right) \quad (4.10)$$

$$\omega_{\text{disc}}^2 = \frac{G(M_1 + M_2)}{R_T^3}, \quad (4.11)$$

where we defined R_T to be the distance of the strongest torque on the binary as measured from CoM. Equating $\omega_{2,\text{apo}}^2 = \omega_{\text{disc}}^2$ yields:

$$\frac{1}{R_T^3} = \frac{1}{(1+\epsilon)^2 a^3} \left(\frac{2}{1+\epsilon} - 1 \right), \quad (4.12)$$

which can be rearranged as

$$\delta^3 = \frac{(1+\epsilon)^3}{(1-\epsilon)}, \quad (4.13)$$

fitted formula for ϵ_{crit} with $\delta = R_T/a$. Eq. (4.13) implies the existence of a limiting eccentricity ϵ_{crit} that we can infer via numerical inversion of Eq. (4.13). The expression

$$\epsilon_{\text{crit}} = 0.66 \sqrt{\ln(\delta - 0.65)} + 0.19 \quad (4.14)$$

provides an analytical fit to the result within a 2% accuracy in the range $1.8 < \delta < 4.5$, relevant to our study assuming that, in a first approximation, δ can be set equal to the inner edge of the disc, R_{cavity} . Note that in this derivation, for a fixed δ , ϵ_{crit} is independent of the binary mass ratio¹. To compare the predictions of this toy model with the simulations we need to define the inner edge of the disc. This is somewhat tricky since the disc profile is not

¹ While Artymowicz & Lubow (1994) do not find any strong dependence of the gap size on the mass ratio, see Kocsis et al. (e.g. 2012) for a more detailed study

a step function at a certain R/a . In our initial simulation the clean region within the cavity has a size of $R_{\text{cavity}} \approx 2a$. At larger distances the disc density increases reaching a maximum around $R/a \approx 2.5$. For $2 < \delta < 2.5$ we get $0.55 < \epsilon_{\text{crit}} < 0.69$ which is within the range obtained from the numerical simulations described in Section 4.2.2. Note that Eq. (4.14) depends on the specific value of δ , i.e. on how close inflows of gas can get to the binary. Even though δ can in principle be measured from our simulations, its value would also be affected by the lack of physical outer-boundary conditions. Instead, δ is usually determined equating the viscous torque in the accretion disc with the positive torque exerted by the binary (see, e.g. Eq. (15) in Artymowicz & Lubow, 1994). Artymowicz & Lubow (1994) found that the size of the cavity depends on ϵ . For $\epsilon \approx 0.6$, $q = 0.3$, disc aspect ratio $H/r = 0.03$ and a viscous parameter $\alpha = 0.1$, they predict $R_{\text{cavity}} \approx 2.9a$, corresponding to a 5:1 commensurability resonance. Using this value for δ we would obtain a larger value of $\epsilon_{\text{crit}} \approx 0.77$. Note that the interaction between the binary and the disc becomes less efficient as the disc expands whereas the gravitational pull of the tenuous gas onto the secondary at peri-apsis increases. So even in a system where the influence of the gas inside the cavity is completely negligible, it is not clear if the binary could reach such a high ϵ_{crit} on a relevant time scale.

large cavities loose influence

A direct comparison between our results and Artymowicz & Lubow (1994)'s prediction is not straightforward. Although our self gravitating disc is able to redistribute angular momentum efficiently, its total amount has to be conserved. Thus, discs hosting very eccentric binaries ($\epsilon = 0.6, 0.8$) keep on expanding after a short impulsive interaction with the binary (as discussed in Section 4.2.2). The interaction between the disc and the binary is extremely inefficient when $R_{\text{cavity}} \gtrsim 4a$ (see the two top panels in Fig. 4.15). Therefore, although a larger R_{cavity} , in first approximation, implies a larger δ implying a larger ϵ_{crit} , it also results in longer timescales for the eccentricity evolution.

The feeding of a BH binary forming in a gas rich galaxy merger can be a very dynamic process, and the interaction with a single circumbinary disc could be too idealized a picture. Larger scale simulations show episodic gas inflows due to the dynamical evolution of the nucleus of the remnant (see e.g. Escala, 2006; Hopkins & Quataert, 2010). In this scenario the binary can still interact with a disc and excavate a cavity, but the size of it would be time dependent (as in the simulations presented here) and would also depend on the angular momentum distribution of the inflowing streams, resulting in a range of ϵ_{crit} .

realistic outer feeding required

4.2.3.1 Testing the emerging picture

Eq. (4.14) shows that ϵ_{crit} depends on the location of the strongest torque δ and thus, in first approximation, on the size of the cavity R_{cavity} . In order to cross-check our results, we performed two additional simulations of the $\epsilon_0 = 0.8$ case, in which $a(1 + \epsilon)$ was kept fixed, reducing the semi-major axis by a factor 1/1.8, thus increasing the *relative* cavity size R_{cavity} by 80%. These runs simulate a situation where the infalling material stays at a large distance from the eccentric binary and does not reach $R_{\text{cavity}} \approx 2.5a$, typical for the low eccentricity cases presented above.

The analysis performed in the previous section only accounts for the pull of the disc when the secondary is at apo-apsis, neglecting torques exerted by the infalling material forming mini-accretion discs around the two BHs. For low ϵ_0 , this approximation works well, because the separation of the two BHs is always much larger than the size of the inner mini-discs. However, in the high ϵ_0 , small a case tested here, the secondary BH, at each peri-apsis passage, experiences a significant drag onto the inflowing mass accumulating around the primary. Such drag causes the circularization of the orbit. Therefore, the secular evolution of the binary is determined by two factors: i) the distance of the cavity from the

torque from mini-disc

secondary BH at apo-apsis, and ii) the amount of inflowing gas through the cavity onto the primary BH.

In order to separate the two effects we set two simulations with identical initial conditions as described above. In runI, we keep exactly the thermodynamics employed in our fiducial runs (the *iso* model), that allow a stable accretion mini-disc to form around the primary hole; in runII the gas inside the cavity evolves with the β -cooling enabled just as in the rest of the disc (the *adia* model), and can be heated by adiabatic compression. This suppresses the gaseous inflows into the cavity and prevents the gas from forming a significant circumprimary disc. As shown in the left panel of Fig. 4.16, runI experiences a substantial steady decline in ϵ , whereas in runII, after a slight initial reduction, the eccentricity stays more or less constant. Such a result confirms our understanding of the dynamics of the system. In runI the secondary encounters the high density region formed around the primary at each peri-apsis passage and is slightly decelerated onto a more circular orbit. In runII, after a short initial relaxation phase, there is not enough gas in the center to cause further circularization (compare the two central densities in the right panel of Fig. 4.16); on the other hand, the cavity is large enough for the disc-binary interaction to be weak and, therefore, the eccentricity growth to be very inefficient. Thus, the predicted limiting eccentricity $\epsilon_{\text{crit}} \approx 0.88$ expected for $\delta = 3.5$ (approximately the size of the cavity in these close-separation simulations) can not be achieved.

4.2.4 Periodically modulated accretion flows

Previous works (cf. Cuadra et al., 2009) have shown a mild periodicity in the accretion rate in the case of quasi circular binaries. As this might be relevant for possible observational signatures, we thus investigate periodicities residing in the accretion flows onto the two BHs, wherefore we first scale our BHB-disc model to an astrophysical system.

Fig. 4.17 shows the evolution of the accretion rate \dot{M}_1 and \dot{M}_2 onto each hole, for the four runs with $\epsilon_0 = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$. In order to interpret our results we consider the binary to have a total mass $M = 3.5 \times 10^6 M_\odot$, typical for expected *LISA* detections, and an initial semi-major axis $a_0 = 0.038$ pc. Under this assumption, for a radiative efficiency of 0.1, the Eddington limit would correspond to accretion rates $\dot{M}_{1,E} = 0.06 M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$ and $\dot{M}_{2,E} = 0.02 M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$. Fig. 4.17 shows that this limit is fulfilled for the two high eccentricity runs only, whereas for the low- ϵ runs the BHs accrete at super Eddington rates¹. The accretion rates drop significantly in the runs with initially higher eccentricity, owing to the expansion of the cavity size with time (as discussed in Section 4.2.2).

Fig. 4.18 shows the power spectra of the accretion rates \dot{M} onto the two BHs. The frequency f (on the x -axis) is in units of the binary orbital frequency f_0 , and the power spectral density in arbitrary units. A clear periodicity emerges at the orbital frequency f_0 , indicating a modulation of the inflow rate, induced by the orbital motion (Artymowicz & Lubow, 1996; Hayasaki et al., 2008). Note that smearing of the peaks at $\sim f_0$, in Fig. 4.18, for $\epsilon_0 = 0.2$ and 0.4, is due to the few-percent shrinking of the semi-major axis, and therefore also of the orbital period, during the evolution. As the binary eccentricity increases, the second and third harmonics of the orbital frequency increase in power and become visible. In the inlay of each panel the power spectrum associated to the total mass transfer rate onto the binary is plotted in the frequency range $0.1 f_0 < f < 1.0 f_0$ to illustrate the presence of other characteristic features at: (i) the frequency associated to the rotation of the fluid in the dense part of the disc: $f_{\text{disc}}/f_0 = (a_0/r_{\text{disc}})^{3/2}$; (ii) the

¹ As already mentioned, this can occur as we neglect any radiative feedback and because disc accretion is not necessarily Eddington limited

rescale to fiducial
values

power spectrum
dominated by
orbital frequency

Fig. 4.17: MASS ACCRETION RATES FOR MASSIVE DISCS - onto the BHs, for the runs with initial $e_0 = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$ (bottom to top). Dashed (red) line refers to the primary BH, solid (blue) line to the lighter secondary hole.

beat frequency, i.e. the difference between the binary and the disc rotation frequencies: $f_{\text{beat}}/f_0 = 1 - (a_0/r_{\text{disc}})^{3/2}$. Here r_{disc} denotes the radial distance where the disc surface density has its maximum. Since the disc has a broad density profile, we consider the two values r_- and r_+ defined by the *full width half maximum* (FWHM) of the density and use those to estimate the expected disc and beat frequency intervals (enclosed by the two pairs of thick black lines in the inset of Fig. 4.18). As expected, we observe broad features consistent with the predicted frequency ranges. Signatures of the disc are always visible in these plots, with a complex line structure mirroring the over-densities in its spiral arms. The beat is very distinct in the $e_0 = 0.8$ run, marginally visible the other runs. We further notice that the significance of the peak¹ in the power spectrum, at the binary orbital frequency f_0 , is weaker for low-eccentric binaries ($e_0 = 0.2$) than for binaries with higher eccentricities. Thus, a periodic signal is indeed expected to be a distinctive signature of eccentric massive BH binaries.

The presence of periodicities in the accretion flows opens interesting prospects for monitoring sub-parsec BH eccentric binaries in circumbinary discs. Our fiducial system has $M = 3.5 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ and an initial semi-major axis $a_0 = 0.038$ pc corresponding to an orbital period of 348 years, exceeding a human lifetime. Since the binary fingerprints in the accretion rates are related to the dynamical time, we can extrapolate our results to smaller

peak strength
increases with e

¹ We utilize the normalized Lomb-Scargle periodogram here, wherein the significance of each peak is directly given by the false-alarm probability (FAP) (Scargle, 1982). Since the number of independent frequencies is the same for all four runs, the FAP scales identically for all runs, thus the relative height translates into significance. For our runs, a peak needs to exceed a height of 12 in order to have a FAP of 0.01

Fig. 4.18: POWER SPECTRUM OF THE ACCRETION RATE - (in arbitrary units) onto the primary (blue) and secondary (red) BHs. Frequencies are in units of the initial binary orbital frequency f_0 . The inlays show zoom-ins of the power spectra, in the frequency range $0.1-1f_0$ computed summing the accretion rate from the two BHs (pink). The expected intervals for the disc and the beat frequencies are marked by the thick vertical black lines, as labelled in the Figure.

periods as long as the disc and the binary are dynamically coupled (see Chapter 6). For a binary with $M = 3.5 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ and $q = 1/3$, binary-disc coupling may survive down to much shorter periods of ~ 1 month, making the observation of such periodicities astrophysically feasible. The interval of modulation $\Delta(\dot{M})$ from our runs is at the level of: $\Delta(\dot{M}) \in [10, 50]\%$ for $e_0 = 0.2$, $\in [40, 100]\%$ for 0.4, $\in [40, 90]\%$ for 0.6, and $\in [10, 50]\%$ for 0.8. Assuming a luminosity proportional to the time dependent accretion rate, a periodic monitoring of such sources will allow to construct the light curve for several years. An amplitude modulation of up to 100% over 10-to-100 cycles will thus be easily identifiable. This is addressed in detail and in view of current observational facilities in Chapter 6.

4.2.5 Summary and Conclusions

So far, we explored the dynamics of sub-pc BH binaries interacting with a circumbinary gaseous disc after they have excavated a cavity in the surface density distribution. We ran a sequence of numerical models that differ only in the initial binary eccentricity e_0 . Our aim was to study the evolution of the eccentricity in order to answer the following question: does the eccentricity continue to grow up to $e \rightarrow 1$ so that BH binaries in such discs reach the GW domain on a nearly zero angular momentum orbit, or does e saturate, and if so, at which value?

The key finding is that ϵ converges to a limiting value ϵ_{crit} . Binaries that start with low eccentricities ($\epsilon_0 < \epsilon_{\text{crit}}$) increase ϵ up to ϵ_{crit} , whereas binaries that start with high eccentricities ($\epsilon_0 > \epsilon_{\text{crit}}$) display the opposite behaviour, i.e. their eccentricity declines with time approaching ϵ_{crit} . Saturation arises due to the opposing action of the gravitational drag experienced by the lighter, secondary BH in its motion near apo-apsis. For low eccentricity orbits, the secondary BH excites a density wake which lags behind the BH at apo-apsis, causing its deceleration (and so a rise of ϵ). The opposite occurs for a highly eccentric orbit: the secondary moves more slowly than the disc (i.e. its angular frequency is smaller than the angular frequency of the adjacent fluid elements) and the density wake moves ahead of the BH path, causing a net acceleration. Additionally, gas in the mini-discs can act as a brake, when the BHs pass through it at peri-centre. Using this simple analytical argument, the limiting eccentricity is independent on the binary mass ratio, but is a function of the location δ of the inner rim of the disc from the system center of mass. For the range of values $2 < \delta < 2.5$, this argument predicts $0.55 < \epsilon_{\text{crit}} < 0.79$, consistent with our numerical findings. The larger the cavity size, the higher ϵ_{crit} , the longer is the time scale on which this limit is attained. The expectation is that BH binaries, immersed in circumbinary discs, maintain a large eccentricity throughout the migration process. Although in this study we have focused on BH binaries, the evolution of proto-stellar binaries occurs in a similar geometry (e.g., [Bate & Bonnell, 1997](#); [Artymowicz & Lubow, 1994](#)) and share much of the same physics. Thus, our results are likely relevant for the interpretation of the observed distribution of binary star eccentricities (e.g., [Pourbaix et al., 2004](#)).

BH maintain high ϵ until decoupling

4.3 Standard model for a *PTA* binary

LISA sources are typically distant ($z > 1$), light ($M_{\text{BH}} < 10^7 M_{\odot}$) and as long as they are still coupled to their discs, they have relatively long orbital periods (hundreds of years). On the other hand, *PTA* sources are nearby, heavy and have periods of years. As will be shown later, the black holes will likely still be contact with the disc-gas at their evolutionary stage at which they are visible to *PTAs*. This makes them ideal candidates for multimessenger astronomy, especially because their EM signals could be visible because of their brightness and closeness.

In this Section, we model the dynamics of the prototypical *PTA*-MBHB surrounded by a circumbinary thin accretion disc with much higher resolution than previously done. We use a syncretic approach, combining analytical accretion disc models to high resolution SPH simulations. The former provide the global set-up of the system, the latter are necessary to gather a better insight of the dynamics of the torqued material streaming through the inner edge of the circumbinary disc to form minidisks. The findings of this Section will be used for deriving possible observational consequences in Chapter 6.

As always, we model the MBHB of a total mass $M = M_1 + M_2$ surrounded by a thin Keplerian gaseous disc of mass M_d . However, this time the relative mass of the disc to the MBHB must be rescaled to be much lower as we model a much later stage of the coupled disc-binary evolution. We set primary mass $M_1 = 2.6 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$, mass ratio $q = M_2/M_1 = 0.35$ and semimajor axis $a_0 = 0.012$ pc, consistent with the typical range of source parameters calculated for a *PTA* MBHB population (see Fig. 6.5 in Section 6.3). Following the results of the previous Section, we set the the initial binary eccentricity to a value $\epsilon_0 = 0.6$. The resulting period is $P = f_0^{-1} = 2\pi/\Omega_0 \approx 6$ years (f_0 is the orbital frequency).

rescaling to different masses

truncated β -disc

Although Newtonian simulations are in principle scale-free, the expected properties of the circumbinary disc depend on the assumed mass and semimajor axis of the binary. We therefore need to work out an *a priori* scaling of the SPH simulation. A truncated circumbinary β -disc has mass (Haiman et al., 2009)

$$M_d = 8.63 \times 10^4 M_\odot \alpha_{0.3}^{-4/5} \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{0.3}}{\eta_{0.1}} \right)^{7/10} M_8^{11/5} (R_{\text{out}}^{5/4} - R_{\text{in}}^{5/4}), \quad (4.15)$$

where two limiting radii of the disc, R_{in} and R_{out} , are expressed in units of $10^3 R_S$ and, in our simulation, correspond to $R_{\text{in}} \gtrsim 2a_0$ and $R_{\text{out}} = 10a_0$, respectively. Plugging in our default disc model ($\alpha_{0.3} = \dot{m}_{0.3} = \eta_{0.1} = 1$) and the binary parameters assumed above, we obtain $R_{\text{in}} \approx 0.6$, $R_{\text{out}} \approx 3$ and $M_d \approx 5 \times 10^6 M_\odot \approx 1.5 \times 10^{-2} M$. Comparing the viscous timescale of the binary to the GW driven orbital decay (Eq.s (1.7) and (1.9), in Section 1.1.3), we find that the MBHB is still attached to the circumbinary disc, and we can study the dynamics in the Newtonian approximation, neglecting relativistic effects.

4.3.1 Numerical realisation

 necessity of high
resolution

As initial condition, we use the binary outlined in the previous Section surrounded by an 8 million particle circumbinary disc, and let it relax over 9 orbits. The integration time-step for the binary is set equal to $0.01 \Omega_0^{-1}$. We use the *iso* approach, i.e. we assume that the small amount of gas present in the inner cavity ($r \lesssim 1.75a$) is isothermal, and the cooling parameter $\beta = t_{\text{cool}}/t_{\text{dyn}} = 10$. The softening for the particles is adaptive with a minimum of $0.001 a_0$, while the MBHs are not softened¹. The sink radius is set to $0.005 a_0$, which corresponds to $\approx 6R_S$ for the secondary MBH. The necessity of such a high resolution is given by the high mass ratio between holes and discs. Furthermore, we need to be able to resolve sub-Eddington accretion rates onto the black holes, which is $\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}} = 8 M_\odot/\text{yr}$, thus we need to have single particles that are some factor smaller than this. In our choice of units, the mass of a particle is $M_{\text{SPH}} = 0.79 M_\odot$, resulting in $M_d = 1.58 \times 10^{-2} M$. To ease comparison with similar previous work by Hayasaki et al. (2007), the scale height H of the disc is defined as the half thickness at which the density decreases by a factor of $e^{-1/2}$, giving an aspect ratio of the disc of $H/r \in [0.026, 0.013]$ for $3a_0 < r < 6a_0$. The radial structure of this geometrically thin disc is well resolved at all times since the azimuthally averaged smoothing length h is always much smaller than r ; for $3.6a_0 < r < 6a_0$, we find $h/r \in [0.0117, 0.0106]$. The vertical structure is only marginally resolved, with $h/H \in [0.756, 0.824]$. The gravitational stability of the disc can be assessed via the Toomre parameter Q (see Chapter 1). The bulk of the disc (starting from the edge of the cavity extending to where the disc-density drops to one half of the maximum disc-density), located within $a_0 < r/a_0 < 7$, has $Q \in [7.0, 3.8]$. During the numerical evolution Q oscillates around these values with up to 70 % due to small compression waves spiralling out through the disc. The median sound speed of the disk is $c_s \sim 0.0043c$, corresponding to a rather cold disk with $T \sim 10^4 \text{K}$. Note that it has been shown (Lodato & Rice, 2004, 2005) that for moderately high β (as is our case) resonant heating of small scale clumps will keep a disc from fragmenting even if $Q < 1$ via self-regulation. The stability of our disc is thus guaranteed for the whole simulation and well that.

thin, cold disc

¹ Note that this does not introduce any artificial effect in the computation of the gravitational forces, since the MBHs are modelled as sink particles with sink radius larger than the typical softening of the gas particles.

4.3.2 Variable inflows and minidisc formation

As we already observed for the less resolved case in Section 4.2.4, gravitational torques, acting on the inner edge of the circumbinary disc, cause periodic inflows of mass that are triggered by the secondary pulling gas out of the disc edge at each apo-apsis passage. We follow the streams down to the sink radii of the two black holes and monitor the particles that are *swallowed* by the MBHs and bin them according to the timestep when they were swallowed. An example of the forming streaming structure is given in Fig. 4.19, where we show the logarithmic column-density of the gas in the cavity¹. The inflows are well resolved, and the gas bound to each MBH is visible to form a sense of minidisks. Although our spatial resolution is limited, we can estimate a radial minidisc size of about $0.05 a_0$, well within the respective Hill radii of the two MBHs², ensuring disc stability against tidal stripping. The minidisc average density is $\rho = 2 \times 10^{-15} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, giving a total mass of $m_{\text{md}_1} \sim 3 M_\odot$ for the primary and $m_{\text{md}_2} \sim 0.5 M_\odot$ for the secondary.

The detailed structure of the inflows and their physical properties strongly depend on the disc thermodynamics; moreover, their behaviour close to the MBHs is likely to be affected by the comparable size of the sink radius, the smoothing length and the physical size of the minidisks. Nonetheless, we can consider the rate at which particles cross the sink radii of the two black holes (what we call *numerical* accretion rate) as a good proxy to the rate at which material streaming from the outside circumbinary disc feeds to inner minidisks. Such a rate is shown in Fig. 4.20 over sixty orbital periods. The orbital periodicity is quite striking, with a maximum-to-minimum ratio larger than a factor of three. The feeding rate to the cavity relaxes, reaching a quasi-steady value which is just slightly smaller (by less than 10%) than the accretion rate onto the two MBHs. We notice that the inflows occur on the MBHB orbital period, and are triggered by the secondary pulling material off the inner edge of the circumbinary disc at its apo-apsis passages. Their nature is therefore primarily gravitational, and should be weakly dependent on the exact thermodynamics of the disc. Our simulation therefore suggests that gravitational torques are effective in feeding periodically the central cavity at a rate which is a substantial fraction of the Eddington rate. This is in agreement with similar full GR hydro simulations studying the evolution of MBHBs at closer separations (Farris et al., 2011a), in which similar streams feeding the two MBHs are observed down to $\approx 10M$ ($\approx 3 \times 10^{-4}$ pc for our MBHs).

physics of
minidisks not
captured

feeding rate

4.3.3 Analytical modelling of the minidisks

As stated in the previous paragraph, the detailed behaviour of the inflows close to the MBHs is likely to be affected by the comparable size of the sink radius, the smoothing length and the physical size of the minidisks; but our simulation does not have the resolution needed to properly account for all these issues. One possible solution would be to follow Hayasaki et al. (2008) and perform a higher resolution simulation of the inner region using the inflows as boundary conditions to feed the minidisks. While this approach is potentially useful, we argue in the following, the gas dynamics on small scales strongly depends on the details of the fuelling, and in particular on the angular momentum distribution of the inflowing gas. Running a comprehensive suite of high resolution simulations would therefore be unfeasible. Here we decide to follow a different approach. We build a simple analytic parametric model for the minidisks, using the inflow

parametric
minidisc model

¹ Fig. 4.19 made using SPLASH (Price, 2007).

² The Hill radius of the smaller MBH is defined as $R_{\text{Hill}} = a(1 - \epsilon)[M_2/(3M_1)]^{1/3}$, which is $\approx 0.19a_0$ in our case.

Fig. 4.19: FACE-ON VIEW INTO THE CAVITY OF A HIGHLY RESOLVED, ECCENTRIC BINARY $e = 0.6$ - Logarithmic column density of the cavity whereing the MBHs are inserted as small black dots, the axes are in units of the semimajor axis a_0 and the density is in code units. The small tenuous structures visible around the BHs are the so-called mini-discs that steadily form and get accreted as the binary orbits. Figure made using SPLASH (Price, 2007)

dynamics as a guidance to infer their physical size. We assume that the infalling material is periodically fed from the outer disc at some given rate \dot{m} . To simplify the notation, we do not distinguish between the two MBHs; all the quantities appearing in the equations below, are intended to be specific of the MBH under consideration¹, and the results apply to both MBHs (and both attached minidisks).

The infalling material is captured in the *Roche lobe* (RL) of the i -th MBH with an average specific angular momentum \mathcal{J} with respect to that MBH. This is converted to a characteristic size of a Keplerian orbit around the MBH simply as $r_{\text{md}} = \mathcal{J}^2/GM$. If $r_{\text{md}} < 3R_S$ the inflow is radial and accretion proceeds in a Bondi-like fashion. Otherwise, the infalling material settles at a characteristic radius r_{md} around the MBH and dissipates its angular momentum through viscous processes, diffusing inwards and eventually being accreted by the two holes (a process similar to the debris fallback in tidal disruption induced accretion, Rees, 1988). The time needed for an annulus of material at radius r to be accreted is

$$\tau_{\text{acc},\alpha} = 0.31 \text{ yr } \alpha_{0.3}^{-1} \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{0.3}}{\eta_{0.1}} \right)^{-2} M_8 r_1^{7/2} \quad (4.16)$$

¹ For example, $M_8 = M_i/10^8 M_\odot$ is the mass of the i -th MBH in units of 10^8 solar masses, $\alpha_{0.3} = \alpha_i/0.3$ is the viscosity parameter of the i -th disc in units of 0.3, and so on.

Fig. 4.20: NUMERICAL ACCRETION RATE FOR A LIGHT DISC - as a function of time (see text for details). The periodicity is remarkable, as also highlighted in the upper-right zoom-in.

$$\tau_{\text{acc},\beta} = 683 \text{ yr } \alpha_{0.3}^{-4/5} \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{0.3}}{\eta_{0.1}} \right)^{-2/5} M_8^{6/5} r_1^{7/5} \quad (4.17)$$

for α and β discs respectively¹. Here r_1 is the size of the minidisc in units of $10R_S$.

If τ_{acc} is longer than the binary orbital period P , then a pair of persistent, periodically fed minidiscs is formed around the two MBH. If, conversely, τ_{acc} is shorter than P , then the streaming periodicity is reflected in episodes of periodic accretion. For α -discs, this happens for

$$r_{\text{md,max}} < 20 R_S \alpha_{0.3}^{2/7} \left(\frac{\dot{m}_{0.3}}{\eta_{0.1}} \right)^{4/7} M_8^{-2/7} P_{\text{yr}}^{2/7} \quad (4.18)$$

(P_{yr} is the MBHB period in years), while it never happens for β -discs. Fig. 4.21 shows the maximum radius $r_{\text{md,max}}$ and the corresponding maximum mass $m_{\text{md,max}}$ of an α -minidisc. For average feeding rates of $\dot{m} \approx 0.3$ (consistent with the output of our SPH simulation), maximum disc sizes are in the range 10-40 R_S .

We can compare our model to the SPH numerical implementation of Hayasaki et al. (2008). They initially build discs of the size $\lesssim 0.2a$ around the two (equal mass) MBHs. Matter is then added on eccentric orbits from moving injection points following the phase of the binary. Injected particles have much lower angular momentum than the outer edge of the minidiscs, and are consequently readily accreted by the two MBHs, in a periodic fashion corresponding to the periodicity of injection. Their very eccentric injection is consistent with our radial accretion hypothesis or with an α -minidisc with τ_{acc} shorter

¹ To sketch the situation, we describe the minidiscs as small steady accretion discs, even though the condition of stationarity of the system are not met because of the periodicity of the infalling streaming.

persistent
minidisks

then P . However, if the streams are readily accreted, it is difficult to justify the presence of the persistent, quite large minidisks they initially set around the two MBHs. Such long-lived discs requires fuelling streams with larger angular momentum (for which $\tau_{\text{acc}} > P$). [Hayasaki et al. \(2008\)](#)'s simulations show that, if the instreaming material has enough angular momentum to initially form persistent minidisks around the two MBHs, such discs are stable, even in presence of tidal interactions, and a standard, steady state analytical description is appropriate.

In our specific simulation, the average angular momentum of the particles captured by the MBHs within their respective RLs implies $r_{\text{md}} \approx 10 - 20R_S$, meaning that the accretion process must happen through viscous inspiral rather than through radial infall, disfavoured the Bondi-like accretion scenario. Moreover, $r_{\text{md}} < r_{\text{md,max}}$ for both MBHs; for α -discs, this suggests MBHB period-related periodicity in the accretion and thus in the emitted luminosity.

Fig. 4.21: CHARACTERISTIC PROPERTIES OF α -MINIDISCS - according to our analytical modelling. *Upper left panel:* maximum minidisc radius $r_{\text{md,max}}$ allowing for $t_{\text{acc},\alpha} < P$, as a function of P . **Thick-red** curves are for $\dot{m} = 0.3$ and $\alpha = 0.3$ and **thin-blue** curves are for $\dot{m} = 0.1$ $\alpha = 0.1$. Short-dashed, long-dashed and solid curves are for a MBH mass of 10^8 , $10^{8.5}$ and $10^9 M_{\odot}$ respectively. *Upper right panel:* maximum mass of the minidisks enclosed in $r_{\text{md,max}}$ as a function of P , line and color style as in the upper left panel. *Lower panel:* maximum size of the minidisks relative to a as a function of P , compared to the Roche-lobes of the two MBHs (horizontal ticks). Here we assume our default binary; long-dashed lines are for M_1 , short-dashed are for M_2 .

4.3.4 Intermediate Summary

This detailed SPH simulation of the eccentric binary-disc interaction highlighted once again the periodic streams of gas leaking from the inner edge of the circumbinary disc

through the low density central cavity, occurring on the binary and disc dynamical time scales rather than on the viscous time. The rate at which such streams feed the central binary can be a significant fraction of the Eddington accretion rate of the MBHB ($\dot{m} \approx 0.4$). The streaming periodicity was found to be extremely sharp, with a variation in the MBHB feeding rate of a factor of two-to-four. These periodic changes in the accretion rate can be considered a fingerprint of eccentric sub-parsec binaries migrating inside a circumbinary disc.

This simulation was run to generate a proxy of a light curve typical for a binary-disc system close to decoupling. So, it was also important to try to understand the formation of minidisks around the individual BHs. We do not capture the physics in the minidisks, which is why we used an analytic modelling of the minidisks, instead. For α -minidisks, our simulation results suggest a direct translation of the numerical accretion rate into light emission. On the other side, for β -minidisks the picture of persistent, steady minidisks arises. These latter would likely emit double fluorescence lines or periodic hot spots. From this point onwards, we must take the path of post-processing the information extracted from the simulation with different overlaid models. This is done in Chapter 6.

4.4 Conclusion

This Chapter studied the long term evolution of a co-rotating, selfgravitating disc around a BHB. Using three dimensional SPH simulations, we found that both accretion torques and gravity torques influence the semi-major axis shrinkage. The spectra of the torques revealed that the dominant frequencies are not related to the BHB orbital frequency, directly. We found that all dynamically relevant torques stem from the disc inner edge or the cavity region, whereas torques in the main disc average out to zero.

The BHB eccentricity was found to approach a limiting value in the interval $\epsilon_{\text{crit}} \in [0.6, 0.8]$, independently of EoS chosen or accretion torques. This limit was explained by the combination of (i) relative motion between the disc edge and the secondary at apoastron, (ii) the braking of the BHs at periastron when passing through the minidisks and (iii) by the increasing expansion of the disc that thereby looses its influence on the BHB.

With increasing eccentricity, the accretion rates showed clear periodicities related to the binary orbital frequency and beats between the disc and the BHB.

The nature of minidisk formation around the individual BHs was studied for a BHB-disc configuration likely to be observable with *PTA*. We used analytic minidisk models to show that depending on the specific angular momentum of the instreaming gas, for α models the gas will be readily accreted whereas for β models the gas forms persistent, thin minidisks over several BHB periods. A Bondi-like scenario was never found.

NEWTONIAN MASSIVE BLACK HOLE BINARIES IN SELFGRAVITATING DISCS: II RETROGRADE DISCS

So far, I considered only massive binaries in prograde discs. There remains, however, the possibility of having retrograde discs. There are several interesting comparisons to be made, even if some issues might be a bit on the academic side. A major difference to prograde discs is the absence of outer Lindblad resonances, thus the retrograde disc is expected to extend much farther inward than in the respective prograde case. This Chapter is thus devoted to study the difference of the evolution of semi-major axis and eccentricity between the two scenarios.

First in Section 5.1, I will use my standard approach of short simulations starting from various initial eccentricities to explore the behaviour.

However, due to the fact that these short simulations showed an instability at high eccentricities, a third orbital element comes into play in Section 5.2. Here, the possibility of a tilting instability is explored where the binary leaves the disc plane and aligns its rotation with that of the disc, with higher resolution and much higher time-stepping accuracy. It must be noted, that this study is still work in progress as the dynamics turned out to be far more interesting than initially expected. It will be discussed that there is the possibility that BHBs in self-gravitating retrograde discs have a limiting eccentricity and never reach $e = 1$. Instead, they tend to align with their disc and assume the co-rotating standard scenario.

5.1 Exploring the differences between prograde and retrograde

In the previous Chapter, we studied the evolution of semi-major axis and eccentricity being influenced by accretion and gravity torques. Here, for retrograde discs, we do the same in order to explore the differences. We take the usual approach of starting from identical initial conditions in which only the eccentricity is changed. In all cases, the *adia05* model is used with all parameters the same, but for the \mathbf{L}_{BHB} vector. The overview over the nomenclature used in this Chapter is given in Tab. 5.1. A small experiment is performed with the *retro* $e = 0$ run: in order to make sure that the initial conditions of the prograde *adia05* model do not introduce any spurious systematics, the cavity was filled up with gas completely. The resulting initial transient high accretion and BHB shrinkage lasted 45 orbits, when the system converged to a perfectly relaxed behaviour. There was also a physical reason in disturbing the circular run, which will be discussed below. In any case, we concluded that spurious transients if any will have left the system after ~ 50 orbits.

initial setup

Most short runs, use the usual resolution of 2 Million particles, the two extended, long runs use double that number.

Table 5.1: INITIAL PARAMETERS AND NAMES OF THE RUNS IN UNITLENGTHS OF THE CODE.

Model	r_{sink}	ϵ_0	resolution	Δt	Cavity & Disc EoS
retro $\epsilon = 0$	0.05	0.04	2 M	0.01	adiabatic + β
retro $\epsilon = 0.1$	0.05	0.10	2 M	0.01	adiabatic + β
retro $\epsilon = 0.3$	0.05	0.27	2 M	0.01	adiabatic + β
retro $\epsilon = 0.5$	0.05	0.46	2 M	0.01	adiabatic + β
retro $\epsilon = 0.8$	0.05	0.84	2 M	0.01	adiabatic + β
retro $\epsilon = 0.7$	0.05	0.55	4 M	$0.001 * \sqrt[2]{r^3}$	adiabatic + β
retro $\epsilon = 0.9$	0.04	0.92	4 M	$0.001 * \sqrt[2]{r^3}$	adiabatic + β

Critical scale height for eccentricity excitation?

low ϵ runs
critical $\epsilon \sim H/R$?

First, we plot the evolution of the relevant quantities in Fig. 5.2: the individual accretion rates \dot{M}_1, \dot{M}_2 , the inclination i^1 between the disc and binary angular momentum vectors and the inner inclination $i_{2.5}$. The inner inclination only takes disc material closer than $r \leq 2.5$ into the evaluation of L_{Disc} and serves as a tracer of precession between different disc annuli. Furthermore, we plot the semi-major axis a and the eccentricity ϵ of all low-resolution, low eccentricity runs. According to (Nixon et al., 2011) (N11), a retrograde disc should have a critical scale height, where if $\epsilon_0 < H/R$ would give the limit for a stable eccentricity evolution, i.e. $\dot{\epsilon} = 0$, whereas for higher initial ϵ_0 the evolution would grow fast and unbounded to $\epsilon = 1$ whereafter the binary coalesce. For the current models, we measure $H/R \sim 0.4^2$ which suggests that if $\epsilon_0 \lesssim 0.4$ the eccentricities should not grow. As is clear from Fig. 5.2, this is not the case: only in the "retro $\epsilon = 0$ ", the derivative $\dot{\epsilon}$ becomes very small towards the end of the simulation. Already, the case "retro $\epsilon = 0.1$ " shows a clear $\dot{\epsilon} > 0$. In N11, they show in their Fig. 4 eccentricity growth rates for a binary of mass ratio $q = 0.5$, from $\epsilon_0 \sim 0$ to $\epsilon = 0.4$ over only 40 orbits. Comparing this to our simulations clearly shows a discrepancy, as the ϵ -growth over 100 orbits is only mild. This must be attributed to the way, this study treats accretion: even though they use a $r_{\text{sink}} = 0.01$, i.e about 5 times smaller than here, they claim to see significant mass transfer from the disc onto the BHB, which we do not. This is surprising since N11 have a very light ($M_{\text{Disc}} = 10^{-2}M$) disc, which is expected to have much less influence on the BHB than a heavy disc as we have. As a preliminary conclusion, we must state that the non- $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$ case studied by Nixon et al. (2011) finds significantly different results with the $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{G}$ -case considered here. Unfortunately, no quantitative comparison is possible at this stage.

¹ Defined as $i = \arccos(\frac{\langle \mathbf{L}_{\text{BHB}}, \mathbf{L}_{\text{Disc}} \rangle}{|\mathbf{L}_{\text{BHB}}| |\mathbf{L}_{\text{Disc}}|})$

² The work by Nixon et al. (2011) only speculate about self-gravity in their argumentation, but they do use 3D-SPH simulations

Dissecting the angular momentum contributions

The inclination generally remains at (180 ± 0.1) deg, only the initially disturbed run shows some variations but there is no visible secular trend, which is why for the low-eccentricity runs we may assume the angular momentum vector \mathbf{L} to be dominated by the L_z component. Also in all cases, the semi-major axis shrinks.

Following the strategy of the previous Chapter 4.1.2.2, we again decompose the contributions to the angular momentum budget in the four components and plot them for all runs in Fig. 5.1: semi-major axis a , eccentricity, e , total mass, M and reduced mass, μ . Looking at this figure, several observations can be made:

- Top panel: the prograde and retrograde runs are very similar in $M(t)$, $a(t)$ and $e(t)$, whereas they differ significantly with respect to how much contribution comes from $\mu(t)$, where the prograde run reaches a three times larger value after ~ 90 orbits.
- All retro panels: the calculated black sum of L_z and the simulated, red curve do not match. This stems from the fact, that the retrograde runs are very sensitive to the CoM used (whereas the prograde runs were not very sensitive). If the same figure is made using not the CoM of the BHB but the global CoM, then the red and black agree in their median but the red curve becomes very wiggly. I choose the BHB-CoM because especially the BHB eccentricity is not well defined in the global CoM. The issue of the "unstable CoM" will be discussed further below.
- All retro panels: with increasing ϵ_0 the contribution from $\mu(t)$ increases until it reaches the prograde value in the "retro $\epsilon = 0.5$ " run, whereafter there seems to be a turnover to decreasing values of $\mu(t)$.
- All retro panels: the contribution of $M(t)$ is negligible relative to the other contributions, however it should be noted that the scales on the plots are different in each row: thus the absolute contribution of $M(t)$ is slightly growing with ϵ_0 . This will be discussed below
- All retro panels: the relative contribution of $a(t)$ and $e(t)$ reverses with increasing ϵ_0 . This is obvious, because e enters non-linearly in Eq. (4.5).
- All retro panels: The slope of the total $L_z(t) - L_z(0)$ evolution becomes steeper with increasing ϵ_0 : this is partially due to the increased effect of transient relaxation, and partially an obvious effect because we are measuring a fractional change of L_z which is non-linear in e (cf. Eq. (4.5)).

As far as the comparison between retrograde and prograde is concerned, I should note that the time evolution of $a(t)$ if plotted at late times *exhibit the same slopes*. It stands to reason that they only differ in the evolution of the reduced mass, i.e. the mass ratio and in the eccentricity growth. This makes sense, because in the circular case the main difference is the cavity size of the two runs, whereas the contribution of $e(t)$ is not yet important. Due to the absence of OLRs, the cavity extends down to $\delta \sim a(1 + e)$ for the retrograde case, whereas we found that in the prograde case the cavity size is about $\delta \sim 2a(1 + e)$. For an unequal mass binary, this means that the secondary will accrete more because it orbits closer to the inner edge (independently of the disc rotation). However, for the retrograde disc, the relative speed of the BHs with respect to the gas is larger, leading to a smaller effective cross section. Thus, an equal mass binary would have smaller total accretion rates in the retrograde case than in the prograde case. The eccentricity growth is faster in the prograde case for very low values of ϵ_0 , where the retrograde case remains almost circular. But as soon as the excitation of e happens at all (i.e. for values larger than $\epsilon_0 \gtrsim 0.1$), the e -growth is more efficient in the retrograde case.

effective cross
section

Fig. 5.1: DECOMPOSITION OF THE L_z EVOLUTION FOR THE SIX RUNS - The ΔL_z contributions stem from α (dotted), e (dashed), M (dot dashed) and μ (long dashed) variations separately. The sum of the four contributions is given by the solid black line, whereas the solid red line is, as in Fig. 5.4, the angular momentum evolution taken directly from the raw simulation data. All ΔL are in units of $[M_0 a_0 V_{c,0}]$.

Accretion torques

A very interesting detail is visible from the top panels of Fig. 5.2 and the top left panel of Fig. 5.5: the individual accretion rates depend strongly on the eccentricity, both in their ratio and in their total amplitude. In order to quantify this statement, in Fig. 5.3, I plot the accretion rates as function of the eccentricity ϵ . This figure should be read as follows: each color represents a different run, starting from un-relaxed initial conditions at different ϵ_0 .

1. The combined accretion rate increases with increasing ϵ , which is the opposite of what was observed for prograde discs. The explanation is straightforward: for prograde runs the cavity is forced to expand with higher ϵ due to the OLRs whereas this is not the case for retrograde runs where instead the binary pushed further and further into the disc edge and thus accretes more.
2. The ratio of secondary to primary accretion rate reaches a maximum at around $\epsilon \sim 0.5$ and declines for higher ϵ . In the prograde case, the ratio instead decreases to around

Fig. 5.2: RETROGRADE LOW ECCENTRICITY RUNS, LOW ACCURACY - the " $\epsilon = 0$ ", " $\epsilon = 0.1$ ", " $\epsilon = 0.3$ ", " $\epsilon = 0.5$ " runs, respectively. Panels show the individual accretion rates \dot{M}_1, \dot{M}_2 (multiplied by $\times 1000$), the inclination i and inner inclination $i_{2.5}$ in degrees, the semi-major axis a and the eccentricity e . Note the different scales and see text for more details.

$\dot{M}_2/\dot{M}_1 \sim 1$ only for very high $\epsilon \sim 0.8$ and there is no turnover. The reason is similar to point (1), but additionally, the fact that in the retrograde case for $\epsilon \gtrsim 0.8$ the ratio \dot{M}_2/\dot{M}_1 becomes smaller than unity is attributed that at this point the binary leaves the disc plane and starts tilting, so the gas can come closer to the primary without being swept away by the secondary, first.

This can be further understood when considering that the BH at apoastron are increasingly slow for higher ϵ . With smaller relative velocity, the effective BH cross section increases. This is true for both holes and explains the higher accretion rates. If the secondary rips out more gas from the disc than it can accrete, which would also more likely

Fig. 5.3: RATIO OF PRIMARY AND SECONDARY ACCRETION FOR RETROGRADE RUNS - (*Left*): Total accretion rate as a function of eccentricity (*Right*): Ratio between secondary and primary accretion rate \dot{M}_2/\dot{M}_1 , on the eccentricity for all counterrotating runs. All runs, but the **red** cover the same time interval. See text for details.

Fig. 5.4: SEMI MAJOR AXIS AND ECCENTRICITY EVOLUTION FOR RETROGRADE RUNS - (*Left*): Semi major axis (*top panel* in each plot) and eccentricity (*bottom panel* in each plot) evolution for four selected runs. Linestyle as Fig. 4.3. (*Right*): Comparison of the dependence of the semi-major axis evolution on the eccentricity for all counterrotating runs. All runs, but the **red** cover the same time interval. See text for details.

happen at high ϵ , then the primary will be fed both from the secondary's leftovers and the material it rips out from the disc by itself.

In order to find out, how the evolution of ϵ and a are influenced by either accretion or gravity torques, I repeat the calculation done in the previous Chapter 4.1.2, where we calculated the "would be" evolution of ϵ and a if there was only accretion. This is shown as the black line in Fig. 5.4. The first three panels show the circular to mildly eccentric "retro $\epsilon = 0$ ", "retro $\epsilon = 0.1$ ", "retro $\epsilon = 0.3$ " runs, whereas the last panel shows the highly eccentric "retro $\epsilon = 0.8$ " run where the BHB starts tilting out of the $x-y$ plane (see discussion in the next §). It is clear that accretion is not important for $\epsilon(t)$ in all four cases, which is in line with what was found for the prograde case. However, for the semi-major axis $a(t)$ accretion becomes increasingly important with higher ϵ_0 . In fact, as ϵ_0 increases the shrinking of a becomes more and more efficient. This is opposite to what happens in the prograde case (where the disc expands). In the retrograde case, the disc is pushed out by the BHB continuously impacting into it, where each push causes the BHB to shrink. It should be noted that the last panel is not showing the entire story, because for the "would be" evolution we assume that $|\mathbf{L}| \sim L_z$ which is not true any more for "retro $\epsilon = 0.8$ ", which tilts out to $i \sim 170$ deg by the end of the run.

So far, the differences between prograde and retrograde binary-disc systems have been found to be mild in all evolution variables but the eccentricity and the accretion rates. Somewhat in contrast to the expectation, the semi-major axis shrinkage is not more efficient in the retrograde setup (we only directly compared the circular case), this changes with higher ϵ_0 . The numerical accretion rates measured from the simulations would correspond to at least one order of magnitude super-Eddington, if the system were scaled to fiducial values. It was discussed in the previous Chapter, that we can currently not include any radiative feedback or wind losses, which is why these rates should really only be interpreted as a numerical mass flux into the excision region r_{sink} .

5.2 A limiting eccentricity II: the tilting instability

When looking at Fig. 5.5, second panel on the left, we find that the inclination of the BHB tilts mildly away from exact antialignment ($i = 180$). At the same time the BHB eccentricity starts saturating its growth.

In order to study this effect in more detail, we setup the additional run "retro $\epsilon = 0.7$ " with double the resolution of the default runs. We let it relax from a much lower initial $\epsilon_0 = 0.55$ and evolve over about ~ 1000 orbits to explore, if the onset of tilting is observed naturally as a secular instability. As indicators of the onset of tilting, we identify the following criteria observed in the low-resolution runs:

- the ratio of the individual accretion rates must drop below $\dot{M}_2/\dot{M}_1 < 1$
- the inner and total inclination must change from $i \sim 180$ in either direction
- the numerical drift of the total angular momentum vector \mathbf{L} must be smaller than the change in i .

Comparing with the low resolution runs, we expect this onset of tilting at an eccentricity of about $\epsilon_{\text{tilt}} \sim 0.85$. It must be noted that these evolutions are numerically very expensive, especially because I impose much smaller time steps to improve the conservation laws. Thus at the point of writing, the "retro $\epsilon = 0.7$ " run has been on the cluster for 2 months, uninterruptedly, but has not yet reached the critical value. This is why I still refer to the

low resolution "retro $\epsilon = 0.8$ " run, when I speak of the onset of tilting.

Fig. 5.5: RETROGRADE HIGH ECCENTRICITY RUN, DIFFERENT ACCURACIES - (Left) the "retro $\epsilon = 0.8$ " run, (Right) the high accuracy "retro $\epsilon = 0.7$ " run. Panels show the individual accretion rates \dot{M}_1, \dot{M}_2 ($\times 1000$), the inclination i in degrees, the semi-major axis a and the eccentricity e . See text for more details.

Explanation of the tilting

As a criterion, of when and why this effect would appear, the following simple explanation can be found: As mentioned already, the CoM of the BHB is moving with respect to the global CoM. This is not unexpected because the disc obviously impacts discontinuously onto the BHB and whenever mass is ripped out of the disc onto a BH, it is either accreted immediately or impacts back onto the disc inner edge. The appearance of minidisks is suppressed in the retrograde case, because firstly the cavity is too small to accommodate the discs and secondly because the gas angular momentum with respect to the BH is much larger than in the prograde case. So the gas is accreted mostly in the wake of the BHs in the retrograde case. Every direct disc-BHB interaction is thus much stronger than in the prograde case. It should be mentioned that the retrograde disc remains circular even if the BHB has high $\epsilon \sim 0.8$ (cf. Fig. 5.7, top panel). Thus, it can be understood that the BHB, which has increasingly small angular momentum, has less and less rotational support, feels the impacts into its disc more strongly with increasing ϵ .

In order to estimate when the perturbations from the disc-interactions become too strong for the BHB to remain in plane, we need to work out when the primary black hole starts being influenced by accretion streams *independently* from the secondary. This happens, when streams can impact onto both holes directly, i.e. when the accretion event takes places at the maximally allowed BHB pericenter (i.e. at a separation of $2a$). As the influence radius of our black holes is minimally the numerical excision radius r_{sink} , we denote the critical distance from CoM of the primary as $\Delta_{1,\text{crit}} = (2q/(1+q) - r_{\text{sink}})a$. Using simple algebra, where $\Delta_1 M_1 = \Delta_2 M_2 = \Delta_1/q$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 a(1 + \epsilon) &= \Delta_1 + \Delta_2 = \Delta_1 \left(1 + \frac{1}{q} \right) \\
 \epsilon_{\text{crit}} &= \Delta_{1,\text{crit}} \frac{q+1}{q} - 1 \\
 &= 2 - r_{\text{sink}} \frac{q+1}{q}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5.1}$$

Fig. 5.6: RETROGRADE HIGH ECCENTRICITY AND TILTING - Panels show the individual accretion rates \dot{M}_1, \dot{M}_2 ($\times 1000$), the inclination i in degrees, the semi-major axis a and the eccentricity e . See text for more details.

In the case of the "retro $\epsilon = 0.8$ " run, the criterion Eq. 5.2 predicts the BHB to become unstable at $\epsilon \sim 0.805$, in the case of the high resolution "retro $\epsilon = 0.7$ " run at $\epsilon \sim 0.816$. The fact, that Eq. 5.2 contains a numerical parameter directly leads to the question of whether this effect is physical or purely numerical. While detailed studies are not yet available, the following comments support our current interpretation:

1. A retrograde disc of $i = 180\text{deg}$ is an unstable stability configuration if $L_{\text{Disc}} \gg L_{\text{BHB}}$ as is the case here: with growing ϵ the BHB is increasingly interacting with the retrograde disc, it is not off-hand to expect perturbations that are not perfectly in-plane
2. The co-rotating case is stable attractor, there should be a threshold value of perturbation that leads the BHB to leave the retro-configuration in favour of the prograde one.

3. If the accretion disc is not perfectly cylindrically symmetric, but rather clumpy and of non-zero vertical extent, perturbations out-of-plane *and* out-of-synchronisation¹ are well possible
4. The primary BH has the dominant dynamical effect thus the moment the primary becomes perturbed and shifts only slightly out of plane, an instability, if there, would start back-reacting on the rest of the system.

The stages of tilting

We now further explore the tilting, assuming that it is a physical effect. In order to study this numerically, again the resolution both spatial and temporal must be increased. I thus take the a relaxed snapshot of "retro $\epsilon = 0.8$ " and increase the resolution by a factor of two and run the simulation with much smaller time steps that are equidistant in velocity, as listed in Tab. 5.1. Note that choosing a time stepping $\Delta t = 0.001 \sqrt{r^3} = 0.001 \sqrt{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2|^3}$ implies neglecting the total mass growth. The time evolution of this run over almost 3000 orbits is shown in Fig. 5.6. After an initial increase of ϵ there follows circularisation which again is followed by an increase in ϵ . At the same time the inclination is decreasing then saturating and oscillating until it finally decreases. The semi-major axis experiences several phases of strong shrinkage, whereas the accretion rate of the primary exceeds the secondary until very late times.

time stepping

Kozai effect

This behaviour of exchanging inclination and eccentricity is somewhat reminiscent of the Kozai effect². However, it is not straightforward to apply these few body calculations for the BHB-disc scenario studied here: a gaseous disc is not rigid body and can dissipate angular momentum; nor is the disc a well located point mass with clearly defined eccentricity and inclination in itself.

The stages that the BHB undergoes on its way towards alignment can be subdivided into the following which are supported by Fig. 5.7³:

1. *Fast circularisation*: the BHB tilts out of plane, the ϵ quickly goes down to $\epsilon \sim 0.2$, while at the same time the semi-major axis shrinks almost by a factor of two.
2. *Disc fallback I*: while the BHB has shrunk very fast *and* circularised *and* tilted out of plane, the disc had disintegrated into many annuli of various inclinations due to conservation of angular momentum. Now, however, the inner part of the gas forms a flat inner disc again. Meanwhile, the gravity torques from the precessing gaseous annuli cause the BHB eccentricity to grow. It should be noted, that the CoM of the BHB and the (inner) disc are not the same. The accretion rates are low and the semi-major axis remains almost the same.

¹ Out-of-synchronisation means that the accretion events do not happen coincidentally at the two BHs

² The Kozai effect (Kozai, 1962) is a well known, well studied phenomenon of a secular three-body interaction when a binary interacts with a perturber that is on an inclined orbit with respect to the binary plane. The perturber can then oscillate in its inclination, pericentre, longitude of ascending node and eccentricity (Takeda et al., 2008) in so-called Kozai-cycles. The perturber feels secularly torqued by the binary and starts precessing. Depending on the time-scale of this precession, the binary eccentricity can be excited. For four-body systems, i.e. a binary and two perturbers, the same effect can be found (e.g. Murray & Dermott, 1999) where now the two perturbers can additionally exchange inclination and eccentricity.

³ An animated sequence of the first 3000 orbits of this evolution is available for download at my homepage www.aei.mpg.de/~croedig/movies.html

Fig. 5.7: THE TILTING INSTABILITY: STAGES - (Top) the high accuracy "retro $\epsilon = 0.7$ " run after ~ 1000 orbits. (Lower panels) the high accuracy "retro $\epsilon = 0.9$ " run. Panels show the successive stages of the binary first tilting out of plane and then subsequently aligning with the disc. Note the spread into various annuli that the disc undergoes in the middle panels.

3. *Inner asymmetric ring collapse*: once the gas has reformed into one (inner) planar disc, the new disc-configuration has lost the formerly large BHB upkeeping the cavity size. So, at this point, it re-adjusts to the new BHB "size" and a hot, dense ring forms (cf. third panel Fig. 5.7). This ring has very low Toomre parameter, becomes extremely clumpy and the CoM of BHB and disc-ring drift even further apart. Note that the cooling in the ring depends on the local orbital timescale. The fallback of gas is accompanied by large accretion rates and thus induced semi-major axis shrinkage. The BHB eccentricity remains very high, close to the critical ϵ during this phase
4. *Circularisation II*: when finally the ring was able to cool enough for its inner part to reach the BHB, the BHB starts circularising and tilting *into* the disc. The resulting meta-stable configuration has an inclination of about $i \sim 90$ deg, is mildly eccentric, a stable semi-major axis and comparatively low accretion rates.
5. *Disc fallback II*: the initial disc has left behind some outer annuli that now start interacting with the outer part of the (inner) disc. The inner disc and the outer ring are now aligning which is accompanied by a series of precessions of the outer ring. Meanwhile the BHB increases its ϵ and stays in the same orientation while the disc tilts towards the BHB.
6. *Outer ring collapse*: Similar to stage (3), now the outer ring becomes unstable under its own gravity as it has lost too much rotational energy by aligning with the inner disc. (Most of) the outer ring collapses onto the inner disc. The accretion rates are high, but a only mildly shrinks.
7. *CoM alignment*: Once the inner disc and the BHB are the only two major pieces reformed and the inclination is below 60 deg, the BHB and its new, much more compact disc start aligning their CoMs. This is accompanied by a circularisation of the BHB again, as during the interaction the BHB pushes the disc towards one side by impacting into it.
8. *Standard ϵ -growth*: when finally the BHB and the disc have re-united their CoMs (apart from a tenuous outer ring), the excitation of ϵ similar to what was described in Chapter 4.2 starts occurring, while the inclination furthermore decreases.

conservation laws At the current state of the simulation, the BHB has an inclination of $i \sim 30$ deg, an eccentricity of about $\epsilon \sim 0.3$ and the secondary accretion rate is exceeding the primary. During this evolution, the drift of the total angular momentum vector was about 0.8 deg, and the β -cooling has induced a loss of L of about 1.2%. However, I do not trust the evolution past orbit 2600, because there appears noise in the both the total energy and the total angular momentum. It will be a future study to find out with yet another high-accuracy run, if the limiting eccentricity of the previous Chapter will be found again. However, I m confident that it will be the final state also here: from a physical point of view, the aligned state should be energetically preferred and once the disc has aligned with the BHB, it will be forced to expand its cavity analogously to the previous Chapter. Numerically, this last stage might well take another few thousand orbits, judging from the earlier experience, simply because the cavity loses its influence once it gets pushed out to its usual $\delta \sim 2a(1 + \epsilon)$ position.

The numerical problem of performing several thousands of orbits is challenging and I might argue here, that studying the entire final alignment up to $\epsilon \sim 0.6$ would be a waste of CPU time, since the physical arguments are quite strong.

As extensions of the work presented so far, I m currently interested in (i) studying the onset of the instability to make sure it is physical; (ii) analytically derive conditions for the several stages of the evolution; (iii) experiment with the cooling prescription of the disc.

The cooling, i.e. the loss of angular momentum seems to be the most crucial numerical parameter in setting the timescales for the "ring collapse" and the dissipation of the several annuli. It is my suspicion, that different choices for β and certainly, cooling prescriptions assuming entirely different thermodynamics, will alter the 8 stages identified here.

Further questions

Further basic questions, that need to be addressed in more elaborate fashion are:

1. Our explanation currently does not include any disc-parameters. However, the scale height and the Toomre parameter seem to be important parameters that are expected to contribute to the discrimination between the onset of the instability or stable evolution up to $\epsilon \sim 1$
2. Strong gravity effects have been estimated to make no numerically resolvable difference to the current model parameters over several 100 orbits. As the estimation was based on linear arguments however, this should be cross-checked with a numerical integration.

5.3 Summary

This Chapter presented preliminary results of ongoing work on retrograde selfgravitating discs surrounding a black hole binary.

First, it was found that for quasi-circular BHB disc configurations, the difference between the retrograde and prograde scenario is chiefly in the eccentricity and mass ratio evolution. The eccentricity remains close to zero in the retrograde case whereas it grows in the prograde case. The semi-major axis shrinkage was found to be the same for the circular case. However, for increasingly eccentric runs, a shrinks increasingly fast and generally faster than in the prograde scenario.

For increasingly eccentric set-ups, the growth of ϵ is more efficient in the retrograde case. Additionally, it was found that the individual accretion rates onto the two BHs grow, but that their ratio secondary over primary \dot{M}_2/\dot{M}_1 assumes a maximum at eccentricities around $\epsilon \sim 0.5$. For prograde runs, the secondary always accretes more and the total accretion rate declines with increasing ϵ .

The retrograde setup shows a relative "zitterbewegung" between the BHB centre of mass and the global centre of mass (CoM), even in circular runs. In the prograde case, this had been a very small effect only.

There are indications that the BHB eccentricity will not grow to $\epsilon \sim 1$ in the retrograde case, but that the impacts into the disc inner edge destabilize the BHB until it starts moving out of the binary-disc plane.

The details of the subsequent alignment are likely to be sensitive to the cooling prescription of the disc, but it is to be expected that the disc disintegrates into several annuli of various inclinations which precess within each other. It was observed that precession of the disintegrated disc annuli causes the BHB eccentricity to grow while the BHB CoM and the disc CoM do not overlap. There were stages wherein the multiple annuli aligned again to try form a coherent, flat disc. Due to loss of rotational support from the shrunk BHB, this was preceded by a short period of fragmentation-like behaviour where disc collapsed shortly into a dense ring, to spread out into spiral arms later. The BHB eccentricity exhibited few oscillations and it is expected that the final state will be a perfectly aligned disc-BHB system of eccentricity around $\epsilon \sim 0.6$.

Current concerns and arguments underlining the physical nature of this effect were given. It should be stressed again that this Chapter reported work in progress, in order to serve as an interesting comparison with the standard ``co-rotating" picture.

IMPLICATIONS ON OBSERVATIONS

The existence of a relatively large limiting eccentricity in a BH binary, that emerges from the migration phase, has two important observational consequences. Firstly, the possibility of triggering periodic inflows of gas onto the two BHs. This would enhance the possibility of an electromagnetic identification of a sub-parsec BH binary. Previously, we have shown that periodicities occur on the dynamical time related to the Keplerian motion of the binary (depending on the binary parameters, from months to hundreds of years) and of the inner rim of the circumbinary disc, together with the beat frequency between the two. These features should be discernible in the power spectra of active nuclei, and secondly, a feasible GW signature of a BHB, that evolved through disc migration, is a detectable residual eccentricity at the time of entrance in the GW band.

For *LISA* or *eLISA* sources, the parameter dependence of such a residual eccentricity is studied in Section 6.1. A similar extrapolation is then applied to an expected BHB population model in the short middle Section focusing on the question if the environmental history of BHBs detected only by GWs can be recovered. Here I show the expected eccentricity distributions attained during the binary-disc coupled evolution for both the *eLISA* and *PTA* window and compare it with the values that would stem from stellar environments. For *eLISA*, there is a parameter range for which the two distribution differ significantly, which may be an important key to reconstructing host environments for GW sources. For *PTA* sources, a large fraction of systems are found to be highly eccentric independently of their environment.

In the last Section, the focus lies on supermassive GW-sources, accessible to Pulsar Timing. These sources offer the realistic possibility of being observable in both GWs and EM signals. *PTA* sources are nearby and bright and additionally, the SMBHB may be detectable while still coupled to its gaseous environment, simply because of the much lower GW frequencies. We thus explore possible *Multimessenger* signals in view of current and near-future observational facilities in Section 6.3.

6.1 Observational consequences I: *LISA*

An important consequence of the existence of e_{crit} is the detectability of a significant residual eccentricity e_{LISA} by the proposed gravitational wave detector *LISA*. It is found that at the moment of entering the *LISA* frequency domain $e_{\text{LISA}} \sim 10^{-3} - 10^{-2}$; a signature of its earlier coupling with the massive circumbinary disc. These values of e_{LISA} are large

enough to influence the GW parameter extraction. The aforementioned periodicity of the accretion rate is analysed in the context of multimessenger astronomy for *PTA* sources, because the orbital periods there are much shorter and thus more likely to be observed. Note, that in principle, a very similar analysis could be carried out here for *LISA* sources, but our approach does allow us to study *LISA* sources when they actually enter the *LISA* band, which is why we focus our multimessenger analysis on *PTA* sources and refer to [Schnittman \(2011\)](#) and references therein for the various possibilities.

6.1.1 Residual eccentricity in *LISA*-observations

If the saturation eccentricity is large, then the binary may reach coalescence with some residual eccentricity, after GW emission has reduced it considerably. This issue was already discussed in [Armitage & Natarajan \(2005\)](#) as a possible discriminant between gas-driven versus stellar-driven inspiral. After detailing the procedure used for discs in this Section, the comparison to stellar dynamics is revisited in Section 6.2, using the more restrictive mission-design of *eLISA*¹.

The existence of a limiting eccentricity that is maintained during the *coupled* evolution of the disc-binary system has important consequences for the detection of the binary as GW source only in the *latest* stage of its evolution, i.e. during the last year of GW inspiral towards coalescence. Since the systems in our simulations are far from coalescence (in our fiducial rescaling $\alpha = 0.038$ pc, corresponding to $\sim 10^5$ Schwarzschild radii of the primary hole), in the following we will extrapolate our findings to much smaller scales (order of $\sim 10^3$ Schwarzschild radii) making use of the standard optically thick, geometrically thin α -disc recipe ([Shakura & Sunyaev, 1973](#)).

extrapolation to
next stage

As discussed in Chapter 4, a BHB can shrink under the action of gravitational and accretion torques coming from the instreaming material of a circumbinary disc. This holds true as long as the migration time scale τ_m is shorter than the binary GW decay time scale τ_{GW} . Since the former scales as $\propto \alpha^{7/8}$ or $\alpha^{35/16}$ for gas and radiation pressure supported discs ([Haiman et al., 2009](#)), while the latter as $\propto \alpha^4$, there will eventually be a critical separation α_{dec} below which GW emission takes over completely and the binary decouples from the disc². After decoupling, binary-disc mutual torques are ineffective and the binary evolution is driven by GWs only. GWs tend to circularize the binary, but if decoupling occurs at small α , there might not be enough room for complete orbit circularization before entering the *LISA* frequency domain. Even a residual eccentricity as small as $\epsilon \sim 10^{-4}$ may be easily detectable ([Cornish & Key, 2010](#)), and it has to be accounted for, for a trustworthy parameter estimation of the GW source ([Porter & Sesana, 2010](#)).

To estimate the residual eccentricity in the *LISA* band ϵ_{LISA} we need four ingredients:

1. the binary eccentricity at decoupling, ϵ_{dec} ;
2. the binary semi-major axis at decoupling, α_{dec} ;
3. a model for the GW decay after decoupling;
4. an estimation of f_{LISA} at which ϵ_{LISA} has to be computed.

¹ As discussed in Chapter 2, at the moment of writing this thesis, it is not clear which mission-design will be proposed to ESA for the L2. Referring to *eLISA* currently implies making more conservative statements.

² At this point, we do not distinguish between "freezing" and "decoupling", because we are interested in a much later stage

Being interested in *LISA* BH binaries, we consider systems characterized by $10^5 M_\odot < M_1 < 10^7 M_\odot$ and $0.01 < q < 1$. Item (i) is directly extracted from the simulations detailed in Chapter 4.2. We assume that, at decoupling, the binary has the limiting eccentricity e_{crit} given by Eq. (4.14).

Fig. 6.1: RESIDUAL ECCENTRICITY e_{LISA} AS A FUNCTION OF M_1 -, for different mass ratios. Each panel refers to BH binaries at different redshifts as labelled in the figure. In each panel, from bottom to top, curves are for $\log q = 0, -0.5, -1, -1.5, -2$.

Because of its small extent, the circumbinary disc assumed in our simulations is unable to transfer the binary angular momentum outwards efficiently for a prolonged time scale. It is therefore unsuitable for estimating a disc-driven binary decay rate to be compared to the GW angular momentum loss. A viable short cut to compute a_{dec} (item (ii)) is to link

viable shortcut

Fig. 6.2: RESIDUAL ECCENTRICITY ϵ_{LISA} AS A FUNCTION OF ϵ_{dec} . - Red-solid curve refers to $q = 1/3$, green-dashed curve to $q = 0.1$. In the figure the mass of the primary BH black hole is $M_1 = 2.6 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ and the redshift of the binary is $z = 1$. The shaded vertical stripe brackets the limiting eccentricity interval found in our simulations.

our disc to a standard thin accretion disc and to estimate the gas-driven migration time scale in that approximation. When scaled to physical units, our binary has $a_0 = 0.038$ pc. Following a similar strategy as given in Chapter 1.1.3, we can thus calculate the time scales and parameters relevant for our disc. For an α disc model (Haiman et al., 2009), the circumbinary disc has a mass

truncated α -disc

$$M_d = 1.26 \times 10^3 M_\odot \alpha_{0.3}^{-4/5} \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{\eta_{0.1}} \right)^{7/10} M_7^{11/5} (R_{\text{out}}^{5/4} - R_{\text{in}}^{5/4}), \quad (6.1)$$

where $\alpha_{0.3}$ is viscosity parameter normalized to 0.3, $\dot{m} = \dot{M}/\dot{M}_E$ is the accretion rate (in units of the Eddington rate), $\eta_{0.1}$ is the radiative efficiency normalized to 0.1, M_7 is the total mass of the binary in units of $10^7 M_\odot$; the two limiting radii of the disc, R_{in} and R_{out} , are expressed in units of $10^3 R_{\text{Sch}}$ (with $R_{\text{Sch}} = 2GM/c^2$) and correspond to $R_{\text{in}} = 2a_0$ and $R_{\text{out}} = 10a_0$, respectively. With this choice we infer a total disc mass $M_d \sim 0.25M$. In such a disc the time scale for migration of the secondary BH onto the primary is given by (Eq. 26a of Haiman et al. (2009))

$$\tau_m = 1.5 \times 10^5 \text{ yr } M_7^{5/8} q_s^{3/8} \bar{a}_3^{35/16}, \quad (6.2)$$

where now \bar{a}_3 is the binary semi-major axis in units of $10^3 R_{\text{Sch}}$ and $q_s = 4q/(1+q^2)$ is the symmetric binary mass ratio. I should note here, that the difference to Chapter 1.1.3 is the fact that here we use an α disc, whereas in the remainder of the thesis we use β discs. Both of these analytic models are likely to be inaccurate in reality. However, β discs models can

high uncertainty
in analytic models

be used more self-consistently without knowing where exactly radiation pressure becomes dominant. What is important to bear in mind is that there is a significant uncertainty as to how good any of these analytic disc models predict the decoupling separation. This is why we use different models and comment on how sensitive the results are.

This time scale τ_m has to be compared with the GW decay time scale τ_{GW} for an eccentric binary Eq. (1.9). The disc-binary decoupling occurs when $\tau_{\text{GW}} = \tau_m$, and this happens somewhere in the range of binary separations between $a_{\text{dec}} \sim 10^2 - 10^3 R_{\text{sch}}$, depending on the binary mass and mass ratio. From that point on the dynamics of the binary is driven by GW emission, only.

To address point (iii), we integrate the Post Newtonian equation for eccentric binaries given by [Junker & Schaefer \(1992\)](#), following the eccentricity evolution down to the last stable orbit. *LISA* will be sensitive to GWs in the frequency range $10^{-4} - 0.1$ Hz and, in general, it will be able to monitor the final year of the binary evolution with high signal-to-noise ratio. We therefore set (item (iv)) $f_{\text{LISA}} = \max[10^{-4} \text{Hz}, f(1 \text{ yr})]$, where $f(1 \text{ yr})$ is the GW frequency observed one year before the final coalescence. Note that the observed GW frequency is related to the rest-frame emitted frequency f_r as $f = f_r/(1+z)$. This means that ϵ_{LISA} , defined as the eccentricity of the BH binary at the time of entrance in the *LISA* band, depends on the source redshift. The 10^{-4} Hz cut-off in observed frequency corresponds to higher emitted frequencies as z increases; binaries at higher z will be caught closer to coalescence and will therefore show a lower residual eccentricity.

The predicted values of ϵ_{LISA} , as a function of M_1 for different q and z , are shown in Fig. 6.1. Not surprisingly, the residual eccentricity is larger for lighter binaries (i.e., for lighter M_1) and smaller mass ratios q . This is simply a consequence of the scaling with M and q_s of the frequency at decoupling, f_{dec} , and can be easily understood analytically as follows. By coupling the orbital decay rate to the eccentricity decay rate in the quadrupole approximation (sufficient for a scaling argument, [Peters & Mathews \(1963\)](#)), we get

$$\frac{f_r}{f_o} = \left\{ \frac{1 - \epsilon_o^2}{1 - e^2} \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_o} \right)^{\frac{12}{19}} \left[\frac{1 + \frac{121}{304} \epsilon^2}{1 + \frac{121}{304} \epsilon_o^2} \right]^{\frac{870}{2299}} \right\}^{-3/2}, \quad (6.3)$$

where $f_r = 2f_K$ is the frequency of the fundamental GW harmonic (in the rest-frame of the source) inferred from Kepler's law $a^3 = GM/(2\pi f_K)^2$. Eq. (6.3) allows us to compute ϵ at any given frequency f_r , once ϵ_o and f_o are provided. In our case $\epsilon_o = \epsilon_{\text{dec}} \sim 0.6$, and $f_o = f_{\text{dec}}(a_{\text{dec}})$. If we set the value $f_{\text{LISA}} = 10^{-4}$ Hz as final frequency, Eq. 6.3, in the limit of small final ϵ , gives

$$\epsilon_{\text{LISA}} \propto f_{\text{dec}}^{19/18}. \quad (6.4)$$

The identity $\tau_m = \tau_{\text{GW}}$ requires $a_{\text{dec}} \propto M^{23/29} q_s^{22/29}$. Coupling this result to Kepler's law (i.e., $a^3 \propto M f_r^{-2}$), we get $f_{\text{dec}} \propto M^{-20/29} q_s^{-33/29}$. Finally, using Eq. 6.4 we obtain

$$\epsilon_{\text{LISA}} \propto M^{-0.73} q_s^{-1.2}, \quad (6.5)$$

which is basically the M and q dependence observed in Fig. 6.1. Fig. 6.2 shows how this result depends on the binary eccentricity at decoupling. We see two interesting things: firstly, there is a maximum ϵ_{LISA} at $\epsilon_{\text{dec}} \approx 0.4$ (i.e. ϵ_{LISA} is not a monotonic function of ϵ_{dec}); secondly, as long as $0.1 < \epsilon_{\text{dec}} < 0.7$, ϵ_{LISA} changes only within a factor of ≈ 2 . This is a consequence of the t_{GW} dependence on ϵ . The higher ϵ , the faster the GW driven evolution, and the larger is a_{dec} . Even though ϵ_{dec} is larger, the binary has much more time to circularize before entering the *LISA* band, showing a smaller residual eccentricity

Post Newtonian
integration

frequency band

scaling argument

maximum residual
eccentricity

ϵ_{LISA} . We note that the exact value of ϵ_{LISA} depends on the disc properties. It is, however, interesting that a small ϵ_{LISA} can be associated both to a fairly circular $\epsilon_{\text{dec}} \approx 0.05$ binary or to a binary with $\epsilon_{\text{dec}} > 0.95$.

These results obviously depend on the assumed disc parameters. Both a lower \dot{m} and a lower α would increase τ_{m} , resulting in a larger a_{dec} and, in turn, in a smaller ϵ_{LISA} . On the other hand, if the BHs have large spins, the radiative efficiency η may be up to a factor of 3 larger, acting in the opposite direction. It is however worth to keep in mind that $\tau_{\text{GW}} \propto a^4$. A change of a factor of 10 on τ_{m} will therefore result in a change of about $\sim 1.8 a_{\text{dec}}$, eventually influencing ϵ_{LISA} only by a factor of two. We can therefore consider our results robust and only mildly dependent on the details of the disc.

In the case of our setup this residual ϵ would amount to $\epsilon_{\text{LISA}} \sim 2 \times 10^{-3}$ for a coalescing source at $z = 1$, but can be as high as $\epsilon_{\text{LISA}} > 0.1$ for a lower mass, lower q binary (with $M \sim 10^5 M_{\odot}$ and $q < 0.1$) at the same redshift.

Using such extrapolation techniques, we can estimate the eccentricity distribution for all BHB throughout cosmic history, i.e., both in the *LISA* and *PTA* domain. These results can then be compared to what would be predicted by stellar dynamical evolution models.

6.2 Distinguishing between stellar and gaseous environments

So far, we were concentrated only on gaseous environments for binaries of masses in the *LISA* band. Before going to the more massive *PTA* sources and study there the possible signatures for multimessenger astronomy, we compare in this short Section, what statements can be made about the environment of a BHB with only GWs, i.e., without needing any EM counterpart.

We found in the first Section of this Chapter that the eccentricity has detectable influence for *LISA* sources. As noted before, there is currently a certain uncertainty as to which configuration of a *LISA* type experiment will be assumed in the future. This is why it can be beneficial to compare also the sensitivity of the current two configurations towards such signatures. In the following, we thus use the less sensitive *eLISA/NGO* configuration.

6.2.1 Eccentricity population of *eLISA/NGO* sources

We compare the left-over MBHB residual eccentricity stemming from either stellar driven dynamics or gas driven dynamics. The rationale behind this comparison is the possible reconstruction of the MBHB history that might be left imprinted even at these late evolutionary stage shortly before merger. We take the population of merging MBHBs discussed in Chapter 1 and apply different dynamical evolution models to determine the residual eccentricity. For each mechanism (gas/star) we consider two scenarios (efficient/inefficient)¹, to give an idea of the expected eccentricity range. The models are the following

1. gas-efficient: $\alpha = 0.3$, $\dot{m} = 1$. The migration timescale is maximized for this high values of the disc parameters, and the decoupling occurs in the very late stage of the MBHB evolution;

¹ The stellar eccentricity distribution used for comparison here has been derived using the evolution models by [Sesana \(2010\)](#) as discussed in Chapter 1, which reproduce the general trends of several N-body simulations (e.g. [Khan et al., 2011](#); [Preto et al., 2011](#))

Fig. 6.3: ECCENTRICITY POPULATION OF MBHBs DETECTABLE BY *eLISA/NGO* - expected in stellar and gaseous environments. The *solid* histograms represent the efficient models whereas the *dashed* histograms are for the inefficient models.

2. gas-inefficient: $\alpha = 0.1$, $m = 0.1$. Decoupling occurs at much larger (factor 3-to-5) separations, and MBHBs have much more room to circularize;
3. stars-efficient: $p(\epsilon_i) \propto \epsilon$. Initial eccentricities are taken according to a thermal probability density function [Preto et al. \(2011\)](#);
4. stars-inefficient: $\epsilon_i = 0$. Binaries are initially circular, a condition that minimizes the effectiveness of eccentricity growth.

Results are shown in Fig. 6.3, where we plot the residual eccentricity of all sources detected with $\text{SNR} > 8$, when they enter in the *ELISA/NGO* band¹. In general, MBHBs evolving in gaseous environments are expected to retain a larger eccentricity, with a distribution tail possibly extending to $\epsilon \sim 0.5$. Residual eccentricities are mostly in the $10^{-4} - 10^{-2}$ range, and are generally lower for star driven systems. Note that the distribution predicted by the star-efficient model just overlaps to the one predicted by the gas-inefficient one. Therefore, apart from those two extreme cases, the distributions predicted by the two families of models are generally distinct, especially at the high ϵ tail. A sufficient source detection statistics should allow discrimination between gas and star driven dynamics. Especially, in combination with the fact that also the spin distribution is expected to be different for the two environment (e.g. [Dotti et al., 2010](#)), this result could provide valuable information of the MBHB environment.

¹ The band entrance is defined as the frequency where the strain of the source h_{GW}^2 equals the one-sided noise spectral density of the detector $S(f)$.

6.2.2 Eccentricity population of *PTA* sources

Fig. 6.4: ECCENTRICITY POPULATION OF MBHBs DETECTABLE BY *PTAs* - expected in stellar and gaseous environments. The *solid* histograms include all sources producing timing residuals above 3 ns, *dashed* histograms include all sources producing residual above 10 ns.

To investigate *PTA* sources, we instead use MBHB population models from [Kocsis & Sesana \(2011\)](#) as discussed in Chapter 1. Here we just want to highlight the fact that *PTA* sources might be very eccentric, and adequate signal processing algorithms need to be developed. We therefore use a single representative model for each mechanism. For the gas driven evolution we use $\alpha = 0.3$, $m = 0.3$; whereas for the star driven model we use $\epsilon_i = 0.1$ for all the binaries. In Fig. 6.4, we plot the eccentricity distribution of all sources contributing to the signal at timing residual level above 10ns or 3ns, which is expected to be in the reach of future *PTA* campaigns. The distributions are rather similar with more spread and higher extremal eccentricities for the stellar case. It is not clear, whether the two distributions are discernible; the figures, however, clearly suggest that a large portion of *PTA* signals would have fairly high eccentricities ($e > 0.1$).

6.3 Observational consequences II: Multimessenger astronomy with *PTA*

Several distinctive signatures of inspiralling MBHBs have been presented in the literature. Proposed scenarios range from the radio and the optical, up to the X-rays, including

variability of the optical continuum (e.g., [Haiman et al., 2009](#)), spectral shifts in the broad line emission ([Begelman et al., 1980](#); [Eracleous et al., 2011b](#); [Tsalmantza et al., 2011](#)), peculiar flux ratios between optical/UV broad emission lines ([Montuori et al., 2011](#)), precessing or X-shaped jets ([Liu, 2004](#); [Lobanov & Roland, 2005](#)), periodic outbursts ([Sillanpaa et al., 1988](#)), and astrometric measurement of the source motion ([Sudou et al., 2003](#)). We identify here a number of possible characteristic signatures and we concentrate our investigation on two particularly promising scenarios in the high energy domain, namely, the detection of X-ray periodic variability and of double broad $K\alpha$ iron lines. For both scenarios, we quantify the population of potentially observable sources, and the joint detection prospects with future X-ray observatories and *PTAs*.

As a standard example for a *PTA* MBHB inside a thin disc, we use the numerical system supported by the analytic minidisc models discussed in Chapter 4.3. In this Section, we first model and describe in detail the MBHB population relevant to *PTA* observations in § 6.3.1. In § 6.3.4, we model the emitted spectrum, identifying possible characteristic signatures, and thereafter § 6.3.6 and 6.3.7 are devoted to periodic variability and double broad $K\alpha$ lines, respectively.

6.3.1 Pulsar timing observability

Having outlined the strategy of obtaining SMBHB catalogues in Chapter 1, we focus here on MBHBs potentially observable with ongoing and forthcoming *PTAs*. At the leading order, an eccentric MBHB radiates GWs in the whole spectrum of harmonics $f_{r,n} = n f_{r,k}$ ($n = 1, 2, \dots$). The sky-polarization averaged amplitude observed at a frequency $f_n = f_{r,n}/(1+z)$ at comoving distance d is given by ([Finn & Thorne, 2000](#))

GW from eccentric MBHBs

$$h_n(f_n) = 2\sqrt{\frac{32}{5}} \frac{\mathfrak{M}^{5/3}}{nd} (2\pi f_{r,k})^{2/3} \sqrt{g(n, \epsilon)} \quad (6.6)$$

where $\mathfrak{M} = M_1^{3/5} M_2^{3/5} / (M_1 + M_2)^{1/5}$ is the chirp mass of the system and $g(n, \epsilon)$ is a combination of Bessel functions that quantifies the relative power radiated in each single harmonic (see [Amaro-Seoane et al., 2010](#), for a detailed description). If we observe for a time T_{obs} , the relevant detectable amplitude of each harmonic is approximately

timing residual per harmonic

$$h_{\text{obs},n} = h_n \sqrt{T_{\text{obs}} f_n}, \quad (6.7)$$

where $\sqrt{T_{\text{obs}} f_n}$ is simply the number of cycles completed by the n -th harmonic in the observation time. The timing residuals are defined as integrals of the GW during the observation time. As detailed in [Sesana et al. \(2009\)](#), each harmonic induces an average timing residual of the order:

$$\delta t_{\text{gw}}(f_n) = \sqrt{\frac{8}{15}} \frac{h_{\text{obs},n}}{2\pi f_n}, \quad (6.8)$$

where $\sqrt{8/15}$ is the average 'antenna beam pattern', i.e. the average of the signal performed over all possible source-pulsar relative orientations. The total residual can then be assumed to be of the order:

total residual

$$\delta t_{\text{gw}} = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta t_{\text{gw}}^2(f_n) \right)^{1/2}. \quad (6.9)$$

In observations with *PTAs*, radio-pulsars are monitored weekly for total periods of several years ([Hobbs, 2011](#)). Assuming a repeated observation in uniform Δt time intervals

for a total time T_{obs} , the maximum and minimum resolvable frequencies are $f_{\text{max}} = 1/(2\Delta t) \approx 10^{-6}\text{Hz}$, corresponding to the Nyquist frequency, and $f_{\text{min}} = 1/T_{\text{obs}} \approx 3 \times 10^{-9}\text{Hz}$ for a 10 yr observation time. We are therefore interested only in MBHBs producing a significant residual in this frequency window.

Monte Carlo
samples

Coupling the cosmological coalescence rate to the detailed binary evolution (see Chapter 1.1.1) we numerically obtain a distribution $d^4N/(dM_1dM_2dzd\ln f_{r,k})$ so that $\int d^4N/(dM_1dM_2dzd\ln f_{r,k})$ in the appropriate mass, redshift and frequency ranges, give the average number of sources observable in the Universe taking an ideal snapshot of the whole sky at any time. To quantify the population of relevant *PTA*-MBHBs, we generate Monte Carlo samples of MBHBs according to such distribution assuming $f_{r,k} > 10^{-10}\text{Hz}$, $M_1 \& M_2 > 10^7 M_{\odot}$ and $z < 3$. For each MBHB we then compute the average timing residual in the observed frequency range $[f_{\text{min}}, f_{\text{max}}]$ according to Eq. (6.9), and we keep only those binaries producing a residual larger than 0.1ns.

6.3.2 Description of the *PTA*-MBHB population

In our default model, we assume that MBHBs evolve according to the scheme described in Chapter 1.1.3. We consider β -discs, with viscosity proportional to gas pressure only and a viscosity parameter $\alpha = 0.3$, $m = 0.3$ (see, e.g., Kollmeier et al., 2006; Labita et al., 2009) and efficiency $\eta = 0.1$ (appropriate for not-to-mildly rotating black holes). All the relevant features of the resulting *PTA*-MBHB population, averaged over 100 Monte Carlo realisations, are shown in Fig. 6.5.

source parameter
range

Typical *PTA* sources are very massive ($M > 10^8$), cosmologically nearby ($z < 2$) binaries¹. Mass ratios are in the range 0.1-1, with a long tail extending to 10^{-3} . Given the significant eccentricities, orbital periods contributing to the *PTA* signals extend up to > 100 years. For the range of masses involved, this corresponds to a broad distribution in orbital semimajor axis in the range $30 - 10^3 R_S$ and circular velocities peaked around 10^4km s^{-1} (if the systems were on circular orbits). Typical coalescence times (τ_c , defined as the integral of Eq. (1.15) from the restframe binary frequency to coalescence) are between $10^4 - 10^6$ years (bottom left panel); *PTA*-MBHBs are therefore caught in the final few hundred thousand years of their life.

resolvable sources

The bottom-central panel shows the distribution of induced residuals. Order of $\gtrsim 1000$ sources contribute to a level of 1ns or more, which can realistically be considered the ultimate goal of future *PTA* efforts. Their superposition will result in a confusion-noise-type foreground, similar to the WD-WD binary signal expected for *LISA* (see, e.g., Nelemans et al., 2001). As in this latter case, few (maybe most) of the sources contributing to the signal may be individually resolvable. Preliminary, purely frequency based, crude estimations (Sesana et al., 2009) forecast resolvability of at least $\sim 5 - 10$ sources, but many additional sources will likely be resolved using the spatial information enclosed in the array (up to $2N/7$ per frequency bin, for an array of N pulsars according to Boyle & Pen, 2010, the prescription we will use below). The bottom-right panel shows a rough estimation of the mean X-ray flux on Earth assuming that the accretion rate of the binary (fuelled by streams flowing through the cavity, see next section) is the same as the one assumed for modelling the outer circumbinary disc (i.e., $m = 0.3$ in this case) and a bolometric correction of 3% (Lusso, 2010). Given their high mass and low redshifts, *PTA*-MBHBs are quite bright, with fluxes generally above $10^{13} \text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

X-ray luminosity

In all panels, blue-solid histograms refer to sources at $a > a^{\text{ft}}$. In such systems, the gas can follow the binary during its inspiral, and strongly periodic inflows of gas feeding the

¹ (see also Lee et al., 2011, for an independent study leading to the same conclusion)

Fig. 6.5: GENERAL FEATURES OF THE TYPICAL MBHB POPULATION CONTRIBUTING AT A LEVEL OF 0.1NS OR MORE TO THE *PTA* SIGNAL IN THE $3 \times 10^{-9} - 10^{-6}$ Hz FREQUENCY WINDOW - In each panel the **blue-solid** histogram refers to sources at $a > a^{\text{fr}}$, where a^{fr} is the “disc-freezing” separation, i.e. where the disc is completely left behind by the binary. The **red-dashed** histogram refers to sources at $a < a^{\text{fr}}$ (see text for details). In the *top row*, we plot the cosmological evolution-related MBHB properties: the primary mass M_1 , mass ratio q and redshift distributions, from *the left to the right*. In the *central row* we plot MBHB properties describing the dynamics of the system: the binary semimajor axis in units of R_S , the binary period and the circular velocity V_c distributions, from *the left to the right*. In the *bottom row* we plot the coalescence time distribution (*left*), the distribution of the induced timing residuals R (*center*) and the X-flux (0.5-10 keV) assuming a bolometric correction of 3%. Distribution refers to the average over 100 Monte Carlo realisations of our default model: $\alpha = 0.3$, $m = 0.3$, $\eta = 0.1$, and ϵ_{dec} given by Eq. (1.13).

detached systems two black holes are a robust prediction of SPH simulations (Hayasaki et al., 2007, or see Chapter 4). Thus, we can safely count them in the population of *PTA*-MBHBs suitable for multimessenger astronomy observations. The dashed-red histograms, instead, track binaries at $a < a^{\text{fr}}$. For such systems, torques exerted by the binary quadrupole moment on the inner edge of the disc become smaller and smaller as the binary shrinks, losing effectiveness in driving the periodic streaming activity. Nonetheless, Tanaka et al. (2011) showed that also in this detached phase (which we labelled phaseIII) gas can efficiently leak through the cavity, feeding the central binary; moreover, residual activity related to the consumption of the fossil gas left around the two MBHBs can still be present (see, e.g., Chang et al., 2010). Therefore, detached systems should also be interesting targets for electromagnetic counterpart identification; however, we do not consider them in the following discussion, and we refer to Tanaka et al. (2011) for a comprehensive analysis of the subject.

6.3.3 Parameter dependence and caveats

α disc models The population shown in Fig. 6.5 relies on a selected MBH-host relation (Gültekin et al., 2009) and on a specific disc model (the β -disc model) with fixed parameters. Even though the qualitative features of the predicted population are robust against our particular choices, the effective number of sources and the relative population of coupled/decoupled systems are not. Both lowering α and \dot{m} result in longer migration timescales in the disc. This, on one hand, increases (up to a factor of a few) the number of *PTA*-MBHBs. However, in this case, GW emission takes over at slightly larger separations (see the weak dependence of a^{fr} on α and \dot{m} in Eq. (1.12)), and more binaries (especially with periods < 5 years) will be already detached from their discs and probably less suitable for multimessenger observations. In an α -disc, the viscosity is much larger in the radiation dominated zone, and, even though there is no self consistent solution to the binary-disc evolution, it is likely that the decoupling would happen at smaller separations. In any case, t_{ν} is surely much smaller in the radiation dominated zone for an α -disc, and the disc 'freezing' radius would certainly be smaller, allowing binaries to be in touch with their circumbinary discs for longer time and at smaller separation. In this respect, the β -disc assumption used here is likely to be conservative.

conservative estimates The impact of the chosen MBH-host relation is also mild, affecting the *PTA*-MBHB population by a factor of two-three at most. Also the binary eccentricity is not very important in terms of the population itself. In our simple model, in fact, we assume the disc migration to be independent on the binary eccentricity. A population of circular binaries will only decouple at mildly smaller values of a , slightly increasing the population of coupled systems. However, in this case, variability related to periodic streams flowing through the cavity would be highly reduced (cf. Section 4.2.4), making it difficult to recognize these systems through periodicity studies.

robust assumptions As a note of caution, we note that our models assume that *all* merging MBHBs are active in their last evolutionary stage. Under such a condition (and the assumption that systems are accreting at $\dot{m} = 0.3$), the source flux distribution shown in Fig. 6.5 accounts for $\approx 30\%$ of the soft-X AGN Log N -Log S as observed by ROSAT (Voges, 1999), meaning that one bright X-ray AGN out of three is indeed a massive binary. This, although not inconsistent with any observation, is, of course, a strong statement, that can be relaxed if $\dot{m} < 0.3$, if a certain fraction of our sources is indeed obscured, or simply if only a fraction \mathcal{F} of MBHBs is indeed active. In this latter case, it is sufficient to rescale our predictions by a factor \mathcal{F} , accounting for the fraction of active binaries. Similarly, we assumed that

all MBHBs overcome the 'last parsec problem' (Milosavljević & Merritt, 2001b); which, in the light of several recent results about both gas and stellar driven MBHB hardening (Escala et al., 2005; Berczik et al., 2006; Dotti et al., 2007; Hayasaki, 2009; Cuadra et al., 2009; Colpi et al., 2009; Khan et al., 2011; Preto et al., 2011), we consider a reasonable assumption. We will see in the following that even for $\mathcal{F} \lesssim 0.1$, the number of predicted sources is sizeable, making multimessenger astronomy with *PTA* sources an appealing prospect, worthy of deeper investigations.

6.3.4 Emitted spectrum and electromagnetic signatures

In optically thick disc theory, each disc annulus emits blackbody radiation corresponding to its particular temperature; for a standard optically thick geometrically thin disc, this is (Frank et al., 2002)

$$T(r) = \left[\frac{3GM\dot{M}f(r)}{8\pi r^3 \sigma_{\text{sb}}} \right]^{1/4}, \quad (6.10)$$

where $f(r) = (1 - 3R_s/r)^{1/2}$ (we assume a Schwarzschild black hole), and σ_{sb} is the Stephan-Boltzmann constant. The emitted luminosity at frequency ν is given by the integral over the disc extension of the blackbody radiation emitted by each annulus, i.e.

$$L_\nu = \frac{32\pi h_{\text{pl}} \nu^3}{c^2} \int_{r_{\text{in}}}^{r_{\text{out}}} \frac{r dr}{e^{h_{\text{pl}} \nu / k_{\text{b}} T(r)} - 1}, \quad (6.11)$$

where r_{in} and r_{out} are the inner and outer edges of the disc respectively, h_{pl} is the Planck constant, and k_{b} is the Boltzmann constant.

In our model, each of the discs (the circumbinary plus the two minidisks) emits a thermal component according to Eq. (6.11). We therefore infer the presence of three distinctive continuum components: (i) a thermal component peaked in the optical/IR emitted by the circumbinary discs; (ii) two thermal component peaked in the UV associated to the inner minidisks; (iii) two X-ray powerlaw associated to the tenuous hot electron plasma (corona, Galeev et al., 1979) surrounding the inner minidisks. These latter components are generated by the inverse Compton scattering of UV photons emitted by the inner radii of the minidisks against the diffuse hot plasma of electrons embedding the inner part of the discs. The up-scattered photon spectrum can be modelled as a power-law spanning the soft/hard-X domain.

disc spectral
components

For the qualitative nature of our discussion, it is sufficient to consider a flat spectrum in νL_ν (Haardt & Maraschi, 1993), normalized to give $L_{0.5-10 \text{ keV}} = 0.03 L_{\text{bol}}$ (Lusso, 2010). The general features of the predicted continuum are shown in Fig. 6.6 for two selected systems. The presence of a cavity is reflected by the characteristic double bump; the one in the IR is due to the circumbinary disc, while the one in the UV is produced by the two inner minidisks.

On top of the continuum, several sets of emission lines are also expected, as in common AGNs. In particular: (i) optical broad emission lines caused by the photoionization of the tenuous infalling material and the outer circumbinary disc ($r > 0.01 \text{ pc}$) by the inner ionizing UV source (the minidisks, $r < 10^{-3} \text{ pc}$); (ii) two 6.4 keV fluorescence iron broad emission lines (Fe $K\alpha$ lines) produced by the reflection of the up-scattered corona X-ray photons on the surface of the inner accretion minidisks at only few Schwarzschild radii (Matt et al., 1991). Moreover, several other spectral features may be present: (i) some weak optical/UV emission associated to the streaming material (Bogdanović et al., 2009; Dotti et al., 2009); (ii) X-ray hot spots related to the instreaming material shocking onto the outer edge of the inner minidisks (if $\tau_{\text{acc}} > P$, see Section 6.3.6).

emission lines

Fig. 6.6: CONTINUUM COMPONENTS OF THE EMITTED SPECTRA - In each panel we plot the thermal emission of the **circumbinary disc** (blue dot-dashed line), and of the two inner minidisks (long-dashed red line for the **primary**, short-dashed green line for the **secondary**); depending on the nature of the inflowing streams, these latter components may or may not be present. The black solid line is the resulting total continuum, where a flat X-ray emission from a putative hot corona has been added (see text). The vertical dashed line is the energy center of a typical green optical filter. The two panels refer to two fiducial systems with parameters labelled in figure. In the *upper panel*, each minidisk has size $r_{\text{md}} = 25R_S$ of the correspondent MBH; while in the *lower panel*, the size of the minidisks is $r_{\text{md}} = 15R_S$ only. We assumed our default accretion model ($\alpha = 0.3$, $\dot{m} = 0.3$, $\eta = 0.1$).

6.3.5 Characteristic signatures

Depending on the strength and angular momentum of the inflows, the features outlined above may or may not be present. We identify three different scenario:

1. $r_{\text{md}} < 3R_S$. The streams flow radially onto the two MBHs. The radiation emission of the associated Bondi-like accretion is likely to be extremely inefficient. No ionizing UV continuum and, consequently, no optical broad lines are present. In this scenario, no signatures of the existence of an accreting system may be detectable. The only guaranteed component is the continuum associated to the circumbinary disc thermal emission. If, however, the spread in specific angular momenta of the accreted matter is large compared to the angular momentum of the last stable orbit ($\Delta\mathcal{J} > R_{\text{SC}}$), then a scenario analogue to the one proposed by [Illarionov & Beloborodov \(2001\)](#) for wind-fed high mass X-ray binaries may take place. The inflowing streams collide in a caustic at few R_S and are promptly accreted in a free-fall time, forming a small scale, inviscid, radiatively efficient accretion disc ([Beloborodov & Illarionov, 2001](#); [Zalamea & Beloborodov, 2009](#)). In such models, the accreted matter/luminosity conversion efficiency ranges from 0.03 for Schwarzschild MBHs, up to 0.1 for maximally

Bondi accretion

spread of \mathcal{J} crucial

- *Periodic X-ray emission related to the periodicity of the minidisc fed through the cavity.* The outer circumbinary disc is relatively stable, and optical variability related to the streams may be overwhelmed by the outer disc continuum. Periodic variability, related to (i) periodic accretion of the minidisks, (ii) the associated varying flux of UV photons up-scattered in the corona, (iii) X-ray hotspots created by the periodic streams colliding with the minidisks, may instead be easily detectable in UV and in X-ray,
- *Double relativistic fluorescence Fe K α lines.* Such lines are a common feature in AGNs (Nandra et al., 2007; de La Calle Pérez et al., 2010b), and are produced at only few Schwarzschild radii. The line profile strongly depends on the location of the last stable orbit around the MBH (which depends on the spin magnitude) and on the disc inclination with respect to the observer. If accretion is efficient on two MBHs with different spin parameters (magnitude and/or orientation), a distinctive 'double Fe K α line' feature may be observable in the hard X spectrum of the source (see also Yu & Lu, 2001).

In the two following sections we will consider these two possibilities separately, proposing possible strategies for combining X-ray and *PTA* observations in the final discussion.

6.3.6 X-ray periodic variability

6.3.6.1 Sub-population of observable periodic sources

Being interested in variability related to the binary orbits, only a subset of the population shown in Fig. 6.5, having reasonably short periods will be suitable targets. We therefore limit our study to the systems with $P < 5$ yr. The resulting population, represented in the left plot of Fig. 6.7 for our default model, retains the mass, mass-ratio and redshift distribution of the parent one. Detached systems obviously have a period distributions extending to $P \ll 1$ yr, while binaries still attached to their discs (relevant to our investigation) are abundant at $P > 1$ yr. Assuming that a fraction of 3% of the bolometric luminosity is emitted in the X-ray¹, we can construct the LogN-LogS (i.e., the cumulative number of sources having a measured 0.5 – 10 keV flux larger than a certain value S , as a function of S) of the emitting population. This is shown in the right plot of Fig. 6.7 for both our default population (upper panel), and for an alternative model in which the smaller α viscosity and accretion rate imply an earlier detachment of the circumbinary disc. At large luminosities, such periodic binaries may add up to 5% of the observed luminous X-ray sources in the sky. The currently operating X-ray all sky monitor MAXI (Matsuoka, 2009) may already have detected a handful of them in its surveys. On the other hand, according to our default model, there might be up to 500 MBH binaries significantly contributing to the *PTA* signal, showing periodic variability on a timescale of 1 – 5 years, in the sensitivity reach of the upcoming eROSITA observatory (Predehl, 2010). We stress, once again, that our models assume that *all* merging MBH binaries are accreting in their last evolutionary phase prior to coalescence, which may be in fact likely in gas rich mergers, but nonetheless it remains an *ad hoc* assumption. If, for instance, only 10% of the merging systems is active,

¹ This picture is appropriate for hot corona reprocessing. Inviscid minidisks have matter/luminosity efficiency conversions similar to standard accretion discs ($\eta \sim 0.03 - 0.1$), and even though detailed calculation of the spectrum are not available, we may expect comparable X-ray luminosities. If the minidisks are instead steady, then X-ray luminosity emitted by shock induced hot spots may be more than an order of magnitude smaller ($10^{-3}L_{\text{Edd}}$, compared to 3% of $0.3L_{\text{Edd}}$ for corona reprocessing in our default model).

select short
periods

>100 sources for
eROSITA

Fig. 6.7: *Left plot:* properties of the PTA-MBHB population observable through periodicity, contributing at a level of 0.1ns or more to the PTA signal in the $3 \times 10^{-9} - 10^{-6}$ Hz frequency window in our default model, averaged over 100 Monte Carlo realisations. Systems with orbital periods < 5 years only were selected. From the top left to the bottom right, we plot the primary mass M_1 , mass ratio q , redshift and period distributions. *Right plot:* periodic MBHB contribution to the X-ray LogN-LogS function, assuming a bolometric correction of 3% (0.5-10 keV). The *top panel* is for our default model; the *bottom panel* is for a less optimal model ($\dot{m} = 0.1$) for which MBHB-disc decoupling occurs earlier. Vertical dotted lines depict the flux limit for a single eROSITA pointing and for the one-month sum pointings of MAXI. Dashed thin line depicts the upper end of the AGN LogN-LogS as observed by ROSAT (Voges, 1999). In both plots, linestyle as in Fig. 6.5.

the number of sources showing emission periodicity drops to 10-50, which is however still an interesting, sizeable sample.

6.3.6.2 Simulating observations: sampling and statistics

An X-ray luminosity above the instrument sensitivity is certainly not enough to identify a periodic source. The light curve has to be reconstructed with a minimum number of datapoints per orbit, for at least few orbits. In this subsection we carry a detailed statistical study of the periodicity observability. The main goal is to provide the minimum required sampling cadence an observatory must have to efficiently identify periodicities. Since astronomical time-series are always limited to a certain amount of data points, we address the problem of having a very coarse sampling rate of our light curve. We assume that the X-ray light curve mimics the numerical accretion rate of Fig. 4.20.

required cadence

The complete light curve of our simulation consists of $L = 898$ points, sampling ~ 80 orbits; each orbit is therefore sampled by ~ 11 equally spaced points. We create subsamples of this light curve by selecting a random starting zero point \bar{p} and then considering all the subsequent np points, where $n = 1, \dots, N - 1$, and $p \in [1, 2, 3]$. A stride of $p = 1$ translates into

subsampling

Fig. 6.8: DETECTION STATISTICS OF PERIODIC SOURCES - In each plot, we show histograms of the number of samples correctly identified within a certain False-Alarm-Probability (FAP). *Left panel:* statistics is constructed with 6 points per orbit over 3 orbits ($3P_0p2$, red histogram), or with 3 points per orbit over 6 orbits ($6P_0p4$, blue histogram). *Central panel:* statistics is constructed with 11 points per orbit over 3 orbits ($3P_0p1$, red histogram), or with 6 points per orbit over 6 orbits ($6P_0p2$, blue histogram). *Right panel:* statistics is constructed with 11 points per orbit over 5 orbits ($5P_0p1$, red histogram), or with 11 points per orbit over 6 orbits ($6P_0p1$, blue histogram).

taking 11 points per orbit (points $\bar{p}, \bar{p} + 1, \bar{p} + 2 \dots$), $p = 2$ means taking ~ 6 points per orbit (points $\bar{p}, \bar{p} + 2, \bar{p} + 4 \dots$) and $p = 3$ means taking ~ 4 points per orbit (points $\bar{p}, \bar{p} + 3, \bar{p} + 6 \dots$). We refer as $6P_0p1$ to a sample covering six orbits with all points included in the sampling (total of $N = 65$ points); $3P_0p2$ refers to a string of three orbits sampled every other point (total of $N = 18$ points), etc.

The reason to consider different sampling is to investigate the effect of the observation cadence. Assuming a binary with, e.g. 3 year period, $p1$ corresponds to a three month cadence, $p2$ to six months, etc. If the number of points covered by the typical subsample is N , we can draw a maximum of $\zeta = L - N$ subsamples¹. To account other possible sources of variability (AGNs are generally variable in the X-ray, [Grube et al., 2001](#)), the samples are then polluted with Gaussian noise H with a dispersion $\sigma = 10\%$ of the maximum accretion rate/luminosity of each specific sample. Each sub-sample is Fourier-transformed using the Normalized Lomb-Scargle Periodogram ([Scargle, 1982](#)) and the *False-Alarm-Probability* (FAP) of the highest detected peak is computed. After a cross-check that this highest peak corresponds to the fundamental frequency of the binary $f_0 = 1/P_0$, the FAPs of the f_0 frequency are binned logarithmically and shown in the histograms in Fig. 6.8. The left panel shows that a minimum of $\sim 15 - 20$ datapoints covering at least three orbits is needed in order to identify a decent fraction $\sim 50\%$ of the sources at a 10% false alarm probability level. Increasing the number of datapoints dramatically increases identification performances; already with ~ 30 points in the light curve we can detect most of the sources $\sim 70\%$ at a false alarm probability level of 1%.

Additionally, it is of interest, in order to crosscheck with a possible *PTA* identification of the source, to which accuracy the fundamental frequency can be recovered from the Fourier Spectra. For an observation time T , the frequency resolution bin of the observation is $1/T$. If therefore we observe a frequency f_0 , the relative accuracy of the observation is

¹ Note that the subsamples in general overlap with each other, therefore cannot be regarded as uncorrelated. However, a much longer simulation would be needed to draw a large number of uncorrelated samples, which would have been prohibitively time consuming.

$\Delta f_0/f_0 = (1/T)/f_0$. However, we can oversample the spectrum to get a better constrain on the observed frequency¹.

For the identification of any frequency we set the requirement $|f_{\text{detected}} - f_{\text{true}}|/f_{\text{true}} < 5\%$. In Fig. 6.9, we show the dependence of the number of correctly identified frequencies on the number of points available in the light curve, for different samplings (i.e., for different number of points per orbital period). We consider only frequency peaks identified at a 3σ significance or more. Note the continuity of the p2, p3 and p4 curves (six, four, and three points per orbit, respectively), meaning that, as long as we sample three or more orbits, the fraction of correctly identified systems depends strongly on the total number of points in the light curve and only mildly on the number of points per orbit (as long as this is larger than three). The discontinuity with respect to the p1 series tells us that sampling six orbits with six points per orbit is much better than sampling three orbits doubling the observation frequency. Sampling at least three orbits is a minimum identification requirement, because other sources of uncorrelated noise may wash out the significance of the periodicity if the statistics is too poor. In general, having at least $\sim 15 - 20$ points in the light curve, sampling three or more orbits, is a minimum requirement for a confident identification of the periodicity.

frequency
determination

minimal sample

Fig. 6.9: PERCENTAGE OF CORRECTLY IDENTIFIED FREQUENCIES ABOVE 3σ - within a fractional frequency error $< 5\%$, as a function of the number of points in the light curve. For each sampling (shown in different colours, see legend in figure), points from the left to the right correspond to three, four, five and six full orbits of the observed source. A 10% random Gaussian noise was added to each subsample.

¹ For all periodograms shown, we have used an oversampling factor (ofac) of 8. In evenly sampled data, we expect the analysis to be only mildly dependent on this parameter: For some choices of low ofac (< 4) in very short data sets, we observed the appearance of aliasing especially if high frequency components were not suppressed (hifac > 1 as defined in (Scargle, 1982)). We thus concluded, especially in the prospect of real unevenly sampled astrophysical data, that the high frequency noise should be suppressed using very low hifac (< 1) and at the same time using high oversampling (ofac > 4).

6.3.7 Double iron lines

6.3.7.1 Relevant source population

Spectral lines formed in relativistic accretion discs are distorted due to Doppler and relativistic effects producing a characteristic shape, which may be modelled to determine the properties of the space time around the compact object (Fabian et al., 1989; Laor, 1991). In particular, observations of supermassive black holes at the center of galaxies have revealed broad skewed lines, which have allowed constraints to be placed on the spin of the black holes (Tanaka et al., 1995; Nandra et al., 1997, 2007; Miller, 2007b; de La Calle Pérez et al., 2010b). The current status of our knowledge of relativistically broadened iron lines from AGN is summarized in Guainazzi et al. (2011).

Fig. 6.10: PROPERTIES OF THE INDIVIDUALLY RESOLVABLE *PTA*-MBHB POPULATION - assuming ten resolvable sources per frequency bin, and ten years of *PTA* observations, for our default model. All resolvable sources contributing at a level of 1ns or more to the *PTA* signal in the $3 \times 10^{-9} - 10^{-6}$ Hz frequency window are considered. From the top left to the bottom right, we plot the primary mass M_1 , mass ratio q , redshift and X-ray flux distributions. The vertical lines indicate the properties of the system studied in § 6.3.7.2. The total number of sources integrated over the blue histograms is ~ 20 . Linestyle as in Fig. 6.5.

Double relativistic Fe $K\alpha$ lines are more likely to be present in a 'steady' environment, where material rising from the accretion discs (driven by heating and vertical stratification of the accreting material, magnetic turbulence, winds, or star disc interaction) has time to shape a tenuous hot electron plasma corona. They are therefore likely to appear in situations where $\tau_{\text{acc}} > P_0$, but we do not exclude such possibility otherwise. Broad Fe $K\alpha$ lines appear to be common in AGN (Nandra et al., 2007; de La Calle Pérez et al., 2010b), yet their identification requires a large number of collected X-ray photons, i.e. deep,

deep spectroscopy

targeted, time consuming observations. It is therefore reasonable to consider only sources that may be individually resolvable in *PTA* campaigns, and consequently localized in the sky to some accuracy (Sesana & Vecchio, 2010; Corbin & Cornish, 2010).

We therefore estimate the population of sources suitable for double Fe $K\alpha$ line detection by considering individually resolvable sources only. Unfortunately, the concept of resolvability has not been deeply investigated in the *PTA* observation context (and certainly not for eccentric binaries). In the circular binary case, a rough 'one bin' rule estimate, provides ~ 10 bright resolvable binaries (Sesana et al., 2009). However, such estimate does not take into account the spatial information enclosed in the detection with an array of pulsars; two sources at different sky locations contribute differently in each pulsar, and their signals may be disentangled even if their frequencies fall in the same bin. Boyle & Pen (2010) estimated that, exploiting the spatial information enclosed in the signal, $2N/7$ sources per frequency bin would be resolvable by an array of N pulsars. For our estimate we therefore (somewhat arbitrarily) pick the ten strongest GW sources per frequency bin, and impose a further cut at 1ns (dimmer sources would not be individually detectable anyway). This leaves us with ~ 100 sources, the precise number being vastly independent on the details of the global population model, but only on the *PTA* observation time (assumed to be ten years). Such population is shown in Fig. 6.10 for our default model. Blue histograms represent MBHBs still attached to their circumbinary discs (i.e., with $a > a^{\text{fr}}$), and therefore plausibly hosting small accretion minidisks. We are left with ~ 20 bright, low redshift sources.

individually
resolvable sources

20 bright sources

Notice however, that our estimation of a^{fr} is quite conservative. In deriving it, we equated the GW shrinking time to the viscous time of an *unperturbed* disc at a radius corresponding to the inner rim of the cavity. Tanaka & Menou (2010), however, showed that the steep density gradient at the inner edge of the disc will shorten the inward diffusion timescale of the gas, causing a significant delay in the disc-binary detachment, therefore increasing the number of sources with observable minidisks. Moreover, in the β -disc picture, the consumption time of a minidisk of $\sim 30R_S$ can easily exceed 10^4 years (see Eq. (4.17)), implying that a relevant fraction of the detached systems may still be significantly accreting (Chang et al., 2010; Tanaka et al., 2011). It is in any case worth noticing that the relevant population is sizeable (maybe few-to-hundred sources) and probably mostly composed by very low redshift systems ($z < 0.2$, see lower left panel of Fig. 6.10).

minidisc
consumption time

6.3.7.2 Simulations of double $K\alpha$ line observability

We assume the iron line to be similar to that observed from the archetype MCG-6-30-15 (Tanaka et al., 1995; Brenneman & Reynolds, 2006b; Miniutti, 2007). We aim to assess the feasibility of detecting pairs of relativistic iron lines which may be emitted from the inner minidisks around the merging black holes discussed herein, and to use them to constrain the properties of the binary system, i.e., black holes spin, radial velocity, inclination etc. In order to investigate the feasibility of utilizing broad Fe $K\alpha$ emission from a binary black hole merger, spectra were simulated with XSPEC v12.6¹ (Arnaud, 1996b). We assume the availability of a next generation high throughput X-ray telescope, in comparison to current instruments, i.e., *XMM-Newton*. Specifically, we use the response matrices created for the proposed *Athena* mission concept². The current implementation envisions 2 focal plane instruments (i) the WFI a wide field CCD imager with a 25 arcmin^2 field of view, and (ii)

instrument
specification

¹ <http://heasarc.nasa.gov/xanadu/xspec/>

² <http://www.mpe.mpg.de/athena/home.php?lang=en>

line shifts
 the XMS a narrow field of view (2.4 arcmin^2) calorimeter providing high resolution spectra in the Fe $K\alpha$ region of 5eV. Hereafter, we assume that the binary system has been identified, opening the possibility to study it in high spectral resolution with the XMS.

Fig. 6.11: EXAMPLE OF A BLIND FIT MODEL TO THE SIMULATED SPECTRUM - described in §6.3.7.2. The continuum is modelled with a power-law ($\mathcal{G} \sim 1.8$). Two relativistic lines in addition to a narrow line are required to provide an accurate fit. The second relativistic line is required at greater than the 5σ confidence level as measured by a simple F-test. The residual panels indicate no lines (*bottom*), a single broad line plus Gaussian (*middle*) and 2 broad lines plus Gaussian. See text for details.

We assume a total mass of $\sim 10^9 M_{\odot}$ for the binary pair and a mass ratio of 1/3, consistent with the binary population presented in Section 6.3.7.1. A fiducial redshift of 0.1 and a bolometric luminosity of 10% L_{Edd} and an associated bolometric correction of ~ 20 (Vasudevan & Fabian, 2009; Lusso, 2010), i.e., $f_{x1} \sim 10^{-11} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $f_{x2} \sim 3 \times 10^{-11} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The parameters of our fiducial system are marked by vertical ticks in Fig. 6.10. The black hole binary is assumed to have a periodicity consistent with a velocity separation of 10^4 km s^{-1} . For simplicity, we assume the energy of the first iron line to be consistent with 6.4 keV emission at a redshift of 0.1, while the second line is blueshifted by 10^4 km s^{-1} relative to the first line.

assumptions
 In order to simulate the expected X-ray spectrum from such a system, we first make a number of simplifying assumptions. The broadband continuum emission from each accreting black hole is assumed to have a power-law shape, where the spectral index has

a value of $\mathcal{G} = 1.8$. The relativistic iron line is modelled using the `laor` line profile (Laor, 1991), where the equivalent width of the line is set to be approximately 150eV, as expected for reflection from a disc surrounding a black hole (George & Fabian, 1991). The emissivity profile of the disc is fixed at R^{-3} , and the outer radius of the emitting region is assumed to be $40 R_S$ (see §4.3.3). A narrow line consistent with Fe $K\alpha$ emission from material at much larger radii is also included. These values are consistent with current available observations (e.g., de La Calle Pérez et al., 2010b; Guainazzi et al., 2011). A more thorough and self-consistent modelling of the expected spectrum from a MBHB system, for example, including complex absorbers and self consistently calculating the continuum plus reflected emission is beyond the scope of this work (e.g., see Brenneman et al. 2011), and as such we defer a detailed analysis of this problem for future investigations.

Fig. 6.12: BEST FITS OF THE Fe $K\alpha$ LINES - *Left:* Results of the best fit model in Fig. 6.11 for binary system with spins of 0.0 & 0.9 at an inclination of 30 degrees for a random sample of 20 model realisations. *Right:* As in the figure on the left but here the black hole spins are set to 0.3 & 0.7 respectively at an inclination of 30 degrees. The coloured points indicate the results of fits initialized at the best fit values, whereas the plus & cross symbols indicate the results of the best fit blind model. Error bars (90% confidence level) are plotted on the blind model results only for clarity. The exposure time is 200ks. In both cases the lines are resolved.

The model described above was defined in `xSPEC` as `pha*((zpo+laor)+(zpo+laor)+ gauss)` fitting procedure and 200 spectra were simulated in each case, using the latest available response matrices. An example of a simulated spectrum is shown in the top panel of Fig. 6.11. The interstellar absorption component is modelled via the `pha` model; however, as we are interested in the Fe line region, modest values for the column density (i.e., $\lesssim 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) will have a negligible effect. Hence the column density was held constant in all fits and as such is not discussed further. The spectral index ν is assumed to be identical in both sources as it is inherently difficult to accurately extract both indices correctly, if the difference between them is small, due to the narrow assumed bandpass (0.5 - 10.0 keV). After each spectrum was simulated the fit & error commands were then run in order to measure the best fit parameters given the signal-to-noise (SNR) of the spectrum. This results in scatter around the defined model which is indicated in color in Fig. 6.12. This model was then removed and a new 'blind' model was defined. In this case only 2 parameters are known a priori, the redshift and the line of sight column density. Additionally the inclination of the line is fixed at the

known value. All other parameters are initialized at reasonable values given the observed spectrum. The model is first fit with only a single relativistic line and the narrow Fe $K\alpha$ line ($\text{pha}^*(\text{zpo}+\text{laor}+\text{zgauss})$). After the best fit is obtained, a second relativistic line is added to the model and the significance of this line is calculated using a simple f_{test} , e.g., see Fig. 6.11. In all cases the inclination of both lines are tied to each other, as we expect the angular momentum of each black hole to be aligned by this time in the merging process (Bogdanović et al., 2007; Dotti et al., 2010).

We focus on 2 primary cases for the spin of the merging black holes (i) $a_1 = 0.0$, $a_2 = 0.9$, and (ii) $a_1 = 0.3$, $a_2 = 0.7$. In Fig. 6.11, we plot an example best fit model to one of our simulated spectra in case (i) above. Here the inclination is 30 degrees. In Fig. 6.12, we display the results of the fit to the relativistic iron lines. The input model is in colour, whereas the subsequent blind fits are indicated by the plus and cross symbols. The exposure time in this case is 200ks. It is clear that it will be possible to resolve and constrain both Fe lines to high accuracy. Similar results are achieved for case (ii). At higher inclinations our ability to accurately recover the line parameters deteriorates as expected due to the relative narrowing of the line profile. We note that in all of the lower inclination models ($\lesssim 40$), all of the blind fits require the presence of two relativistic lines at greater than the 5σ confidence level. As we move to higher inclinations, this decreases somewhat whereby at 60 only $\sim 95\%$ of our realisations require 2 relativistic lines.

The primary uncertainty in all models is the inclination of the binary system, due to the degeneracy in the line shape with changing inclination and/or spin. If we relax the initial inclination constraint imposed above, our ability to accurately determine the line parameters is weakened. For example in case (i) above, a second line is required at $\gtrsim 5\sigma$ level on only $\sim 85\%$ of our models, while only 95% require a second line at the 3σ level. We expect, however, to get some indicative prior on the system inclination from *PTA* observations. In fact, Sesana & Vecchio (2010) showed that the GW signal analysis will enable a determination of the system inclination within a ~ 20 deg accuracy (assuming a source SNR of 10). Models were also created with additional narrow emission/absorption lines consistent with Fe XXV/XXVI. As in the case of the narrow 6.4 keV line, the exquisite resolution provided by the calorimeter in the Fe K region allows these lines to be easily resolved. We also experimented with decreasing the velocity separation of the broad line components; however, in this case the results are strongly inclination dependent. The use of a more accurate relativistic line profile model, e.g., *kerrdisk* (Brenneman & Reynolds, 2006b), would help in this case.

There are a number of caveats which should be considered when interpreting the results above. For example, even in the case of MCG-6-30-15 where long high SNR observations exist, there is uncertainty in the parameters of the observed line when modelled by different groups (Fabian et al., 2002; Reynolds et al., 2004; Brenneman & Reynolds, 2006b). In addition, complex relativistic effects (e.g., light bending, Miniutti & Fabian 2004) may render the line indistinguishable from the continuum in the absence of highly sophisticated spectral modelling (e.g., Bhayani & Nandra, 2011). Finally, we note that an alternative physical model has been proposed to explain the relativistic lines observed in numerous AGN. In this scenario, the lines are produced by a combination of non-relativistic fluorescent line emission from distant material and complex absorption by material in the inner accretion flow, e.g., for further details see the review by Turner & Miller (2009).

double line
resolved

narrow lines

uncertainties

6.3.8 Discussion and summary

The distinctive signatures of *PTA*-MBHBs highlighted above open interesting scenarios for combining pulsar timing and X-ray observations in the coming years. Even though current *PTA* efforts (PPTA, EPTA, NANOGrav) may eventually succeed in the detection challenge, multimessenger astronomy prospects are particularly promising in the context of the planned SKA. If a nominal 1ns sensitivity level will be achieved, SKA will make GW astronomy with pulsar timing possible. Several hundreds of signals emitted by the low redshift population of MBHBs will add up to form a confusion noise, on top of which some (possibly a hundred) sources will be individually resolvable and their position in the sky determined.

In this context, X-ray (but also other bands, not considered here) observations may play either a preparatory or a follow-up role. On one hand, the detection of a population of periodic X-ray sources in the present decade, may provide useful information for *PTA* observations. By the time the SKA will be online, we may have identified a catalogue of systems in the sky from which we expect to detect GW signals, being also able to give indications about the expected frequency. This may substantially facilitate the *PTA* detection and analysis pipelines, by reducing the search parameter space for specific signals. On the other hand, several resolvable sources with high SNR may be located in the sky with enough accuracy to make follow-up X-ray monitoring possible. To be conservative, according to [Sesana & Vecchio \(2010\)](#), typical *PTA* source sky location accuracy is expected to be in the order of tens of square degrees for a source SNR= 10 (but, under specific detection conditions, it can actually be an order of magnitude better, see [Corbin & Cornish, 2010](#)). According to [Fig. 6.10](#), typical masses are $> \text{few} \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$ at $z < 0.3$. Such systems should be host in massive galaxies with stellar bulges of masses $> 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ ([Gültekin et al., 2009](#)), whose number density is $\lesssim 10^{-3} \text{Mpc}^{-3}$ ([Bell et al., 2003](#)) Considering a sky location error of 10 deg^2 , the comoving volume enclosed in the error box is $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{Gpc}^3$: maybe up to few thousands candidates falls in the error-box. Since the presence of a distinctive counterpart relies on the assumption of accretion, active galaxies only should be selected, which may leave us with few dozens of candidates. Further down selection may be performed by keeping galaxies that show signatures of recent merger activity¹. If just one or at most a few systems are identified, ultra deep X-ray exposure may be used to reveal characteristic double relativistic Fe $K\alpha$ emission lines.

Such investigation will likely be possible in the next decade with future generation of pulsar timing arrays (in particular with the SKA) and X-ray observatories. Here, we quantified for the first time the population of expected sources, and their characteristic signatures, and we proposed strategy for coordinating multimessenger observations. We summarize in the following the main results:

- About a thousand MBHBs are expected to contribute to the *PTA* detectable signal in the frequency range $10^{-9} - 10^{-6} \text{ Hz}$, at a level of 1ns or more. Uncertainties in the MBHB population model and in the detailed dynamics of the contributing systems may impact such figures by a factor of a few.
- We assumed the standard picture of MBHB migration in circumbinary discs. For popular geometrically thin, optically thick discs described by typical parameters, we find that many of these *PTA* sources (order of few hundreds, 20%-to-50% of the total population, for $0.1 < \alpha < 0.3$ and $0.1 < \dot{m} < 0.3$) are coupled to their circumbinary discs,

¹ A detailed study of the statistics of candidate hosts can be found in the independent study by [Tanaka et al. \(2011\)](#), which is complementary to ours in several aspects.

making a strong case for looking to possible electromagnetic signatures rising by the disc-binary dynamical interplay.

- By modelling analytically the dynamics and the emitted spectrum of the inflow-fed minidisks forming around the two MBHs, we identified several observational features that may be distinctive of an accreting MBHB. We concentrated on the X-ray domain, by separately studying X-ray periodicity and double relativistic Fe $K\alpha$ lines.
- Assuming all merging MBHBs are accreting, we estimate about 100-500 (depending on the detailed property of the circumbinary disc) periodically variable X-ray sources with periods between one and five years. The observed flux on Earth for most of the sources is larger than $10^{-13} \text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$, within the sensitivity reach of the upcoming X-ray all sky monitor eROSITA. However, a light curve with at least 15-20 points (eROSITA will point each region of the sky at 8 different times only) is required for a statistically significant detection of such a periodicity.
- Iron line identification requires deep, targeted observations. We therefore consider as suitable candidate only those *PTA* sources that are individually resolvable, for which the sky location can be identified to some accuracy. The number of suitable targets is of the order of few tens, depending both on the ability of *PTA* of resolving sources in the sky, and on the details of the disc-MBHB decoupling and the physical nature of the minidisks.
- Assuming that the accretion flow onto each black hole is capable of generating relativistic Fe $K\alpha$ emission lines, we have demonstrated that it will in principle be feasible, via high spectral resolution observations with a next generation X-ray observatory (such as *Athena*), to identify double $K\alpha$ line features. Such features can be used to estimate the properties of the black holes, forecasting, in combination with modelling of the *PTA* signal, the possibility to constrain the space-time around the black hole to unprecedented accuracy.
- Note that we assumed *all* MBHB to be surrounded by a circumbinary disc in their late evolutionary stage, prior to merger. Even though this is likely for gas reach merging systems, it might be a too extreme assumption for the massive, low redshift sources relevant to our study. Even assuming that only 10% of the systems are surrounded by a circumbinary disc, the number of detectable sources is still interesting: about 10-50 bright, periodic X-ray sources; at least a few individually resolvable *PTA* sources showing double Fe $K\alpha$ line profiles.

6.4 Conclusions

Studying secular evolution of MBHBs and their interaction with a circumbinary disc in much detail, we have shown that the excitation of MBHB eccentricity is a robust prediction of state of the art dynamical evolution models. The same holds true also for stellar environments. In the gas dominated case, limiting eccentricity values $\epsilon_{\text{limit}} \geq 0.6$ are expected following excitation by a cold dense circumbinary disc, whereas stellar dynamics can easily produce eccentricities higher than 0.9. As a consequence, *PTA* sources, many of which are at the evolutionary stage in which the environment still plays a role in their dynamical evolution, are expected to be significantly eccentric. Many binaries producing residuals at a 10ns level (in the reach of future *PTA* campaigns) have $\epsilon > 0.1$. The impact of such high eccentricities on the *PTA* signal should be appropriately taken into account when developing dedicated data analysis algorithms. For *eLISA/NGO* sources, which have long since decoupled from their environment, we have shown the distribution of the

residual eccentricity expected for both environments. As the latter are disjoint at the high-eccentricity tail, enough GW observation statistics could distinguish among the different scenarios, providing valuable information on the environment of coalescing MBHBs. As far as multimessenger signals are concerned, we did not treat EM counterparts to *eLISA*/*NGO* events and focused on *PTA* observations. In this latter case, the EM signal is generally bright, due to the high mass and relatively small luminosity distance of the sources, making certain distinct features detectable by upcoming observatories. We have shown that counterpart identification is likely to be bias towards eccentric MBHB in periodicity searches, whereas, depending on the angular momentum of the instreaming material feeding the mini-discs, peculiar double $K\alpha$ lines might be identifiable by future hard X-ray deep spectroscopy.

Even though GW detection of MBHBs remains a challenging task for the present and future astrophysical generations, systematic pulsar timing campaigns are ongoing, and their accuracy and sensitivity will inevitably improve in the coming years. Pulsar timing will therefore provide a safe, open GW window on the low frequency Universe. The combination with electromagnetic observations, such the ones proposed here, will help exploiting GW detection capabilities at their best, providing a lot of information about the population and dynamics of MBHBs. The results presented in this Chapter are just a first step into the realm of multimessenger astronomy, hoping that investigators from both the GW and the X-ray/optical/radio communities will take the challenge so that synergetic efforts will eventually be successful.

GENERAL RELATIVISTIC RADIATIVE HYDRODYNAMICS: BONDI HOYLE LYTTLETON ACCRETION

This Chapter is focussed on general-relativistic radiation-hydrodynamics simulations of accretion flows onto black holes. While the previous Chapters dealt with large scale dynamics, this one is dedicated to smaller scales, close to a single black hole. Using the formalism introduced in Chapter 3.2, we perform simulations of accretion flows where the radiation field is treated in the optically-thick approximation, with the opacity contributed by Thomson scattering and thermal bremsstrahlung. Due to practical reasons, the previous Chapters had ignored radiation as a dynamical quantity, but here we show that on these smaller scales, we find significant differences with respect to purely hydrodynamical evolutions. In particular, once the system relaxes to a radiation-pressure dominated regime, the accretion rates become about two orders of magnitude smaller than in the purely hydrodynamical case.

The possibility of computing luminosities from the radiation fluxes is discussed and results are compared to the bremsstrahlung luminosity often used in modelling the electromagnetic counterparts to supermassive black-hole binaries.

We also show the necessity and success of the *implicit-explicit* (IMEX) treatment (as introduced in Chapter 3.2), because in many astrophysically relevant regimes the optical thickness is high and the equations become stiff. We explore the limitations of the current approach using the supersonic *Bondi Hoyle Lyttleton* (BHL) problem in two dimensions. Here we find that radiation pressure plays an important role, but also that these highly dynamical setups push our approximate treatment towards the limit of physical applicability. We thus conclude that although the current thermal, isotropic approximation to the radiation transfer is strictly valid only in equilibrated, dense setups, it does give physically reasonable improvements over the pure hydro also in set-ups that depart to some extent from equilibrium. The IMEX treatment is successful in allowing to apply our code in the entire physical parameter space.

7.1 Bondi Hoyle Lyttleton accretion in GR

The field of numerical relativistic hydrodynamics has recently seen much progress in treating astrophysical systems under more and more realistic conditions. Because of the large computational costs involved, the inclusion of multi-dimensional *general relativistic radiation hydrodynamics* (GR-RHD) has been postponed for a long time, with the remarkable exception of neutrino transport in the context of supernovae simulations

reasons for
neglecting
radiation transfer

[see [Lentz et al. \(2012\)](#) and references therein]. However, due to the increasing power of supercomputers, the situation has started changing significantly in the last few years, and the inclusion of a photon-field is no longer regarded as a remote possibility.

This delay has, however, not been due to the fact that dynamical radiation fields are not regarded as a main ingredient, rather it is the inherent difficulty of solving the radiation transfer equation¹. The cooling time-scales of a dynamical fluid may easily vary over several orders of magnitude within the computational domain. This then leads to characteristic propagation speeds for the photons in optically thin regions that are much higher than the coupled fluid/photon speeds in optically thick regions. Not only are time-scales vastly different, but also additional spatial resolution is required whenever the coupling to the photon field induces small scale instabilities and turbulence. In addition, surfaces of astrophysical structures are typically not in *local thermal equilibrium* (LTE) and can cool very efficiently, usually on much shorter timescales than the dynamical ones. This problem becomes particularly severe when performing global simulations of astrophysical systems in which the principal force is gravity. In these cases, the spatial domain must firstly be large enough to contain the entire astrophysical structure and secondly, it needs to resolve the influence of gravity². Any such multi-scale problem is numerically extremely costly and it is thus important to formulate efficient algorithms that include at least a leading order approximation to the various physics while still remaining computationally affordable.

numerical
strategies

Until a few years ago, the time dependent solution of the relativistic radiation hydrodynamics equations of accretion flows was performed in one spatial dimension only and, typically, through Lagrangian finite-difference schemes or through the so called linearised block-implicit algorithms. Starting from the pioneering works by [Gilden & Wheeler \(1980\)](#) and [Vitello \(1984\)](#), relevant results concerning spherical accretion onto black holes were obtained with a Lagrangian code by [Zampieri et al. \(1996\)](#), who were able to solve the radiation hydrodynamics equations both in the optically thin and in the optically thick regime, by means of the projected symmetric trace-free (PSTF) moment formalism introduced by [Thorne \(1981\)](#) and subsequently reformulated by [Rezzolla & Miller \(1994\)](#) for spherical flows. Such formalism provides one of the most accurate approximations to the solution of the radiation transfer equations, and, in analogy to what is done in fluid dynamics, it allows to define moments of the radiation field similarly to how density, momentum and pressure of a medium are defined as moments of the distribution function. As a result, instead of following rays, the moment equations are solved directly with an Eulerian or a Lagrangian code.³ This approach is particularly appealing in the case of an optically thick medium, characterized by a strong coupling between matter and radiation. [Farris et al. \(2008\)](#) were first to undertake the implementation of the corresponding radiation hydrodynamics equations in a general relativistic framework. A further step has been taken by [Shibata et al. \(2011\)](#), who adopted the variable Eddington factor approach of [Levermore \(1984\)](#) to solve the relativistic radiation-hydrodynamics equations both in the optically thin and in the optically thick limit. This represents a significant progress with respect to simplified treatments, where

¹ See [Pomraning \(1973\)](#) and [Mihalas & Weibel Mihalas \(1984\)](#) for a comprehensive treatment of radiation hydrodynamics and [Schweizer \(1988\)](#) for the extension to the relativistic case.

² A complementary approach, which is not covered here, is to model not a global system, but only a small, representative region e.g. a shearing box.

³ In a nonrelativistic context, recent interesting developments have been reported by [Petkova & Springel \(2009\)](#) and [Petkova & Springel \(2010\)](#), who adopted the moment formalism within the SPH Gadget code and used a variable Eddington tensor as a closure relation, following the Optically Thin Variable Eddington Tensor suggestion of [Gnedin & Abel \(2001\)](#).

effective cooling functions are introduced.

Though simplified, the BHL flow can effectively help our understanding of those compact sources accreting matter with a reduced amount of angular momentum, and is currently applied to the study of both High Mass X-ray Binaries (Hadrava & Čechura, 2012) and of the merging of supermassive black hole binaries [see Pfeiffer (2012) and references therein].

Before entering into the details of our results, it is useful to briefly review the main features of the relativistic BHL accretion as investigated through purely hydrodynamical simulations by Petrich et al. (1989); Font & Ibáñez (1998); Font et al. (1998) and Font et al. (1999). Overall, these studies have highlighted that when a homogeneous flow of matter moves non-radially towards a compact object, a shock wave will form close to the accretor. Depending on the adiabatic index and on the asymptotic Mach number¹ \mathcal{M}_∞ , the shock can either come very close to the accretor or be at a certain distance from it [see, for instance, Foglizzo et al. (2005)]. In general, for any given value of the adiabatic index, there is a minimum asymptotic Mach number above which a shock wave of conic shape, i.e., a “shock cone”, forms downstream of the accretor. On the other hand, asymptotic Mach numbers below the critical value produce a shock wave that, initially formed in the downstream region, opens progressively and reverses in the upstream region as a bow shock. More recently, two different studies have shed additional light on the physics of relativistic Bondi-Hoyle accretion flows. In the first one, Dönmez et al. (2010), reported the occurrence of the so called *flip-flop* instability of the shock cone in the relativistic regime and have also shown that quasi-periodic oscillations of sonic nature are produced in the shock cone. In the second one, Penner (2011) investigated the effects of a uniform magnetic field, finding that it produces an increase in the cone opening angle and in the mass accretion rate.

BHL model
features

recent studies

7.1.1 Initial and boundary conditions

We model an BHL accretion flow onto a black hole of galactic size with $M_{BH} = 3.6 \times 10^6 M_\odot$, that we treat in the equatorial plane, i.e., $\theta = \pi/2$. Despite the long history in literature on this type of accretion (see the review by Edgar (2004)), no stationary solution for a radiation-hydrodynamics BHL flow is known, and which could have been used as suitable initial data. As a result, we let the code converge to the nearest stationary solution after specifying the hydrodynamical solution of the BHL flow, to which we add a radiation field with uniform and small energy density E_r .

IC for radiative
BHL not available

Most of our discussion hereafter refers to accretion onto Schwarzschild black holes, although also rotating black holes will be briefly presented in § 7.1.5.1. The code solves therefore the equations in a general Kerr metric expressed in Boyer-Lindquist coordinates, so that the initial velocity field, specified in terms of an asymptotic velocity v_∞ , is given by (Font & Ibáñez, 1998)

$$v^r = \sqrt{\gamma^{rr}} v_\infty \cos \phi, \quad (7.1)$$

$$v^\phi = -\sqrt{\gamma^{\phi\phi}} v_\infty \sin \phi, \quad (7.2)$$

These relations guarantee that the velocity of the injected gas at infinity is parallel to the x -direction, while $v^2 \equiv v_i v^i = v_\infty^2$ everywhere in the flow. Other quantities that need to be

choice of
parameters

¹ The relativistic Mach number is defined as $\mathcal{M} = \Gamma v / (c_s \Gamma_s)$, where Γ and Γ_s are the Lorentz factors of the flow and of the sound speed, respectively.

Table 7.1: Initial models adopted in numerical simulation. From left to right the columns report: the name of the model, the asymptotic flow velocity v_∞ , the asymptotic sound speed $c_{s,\infty}$, the asymptotic Mach number \mathcal{M}_∞ , the initial temperature, the initial rest-mass density and the accretion radius $r_a \equiv GM/(v_\infty^2 + c_{s,\infty}^2)$. Perturbed BHL solutions are generated through injection of low pressure gas as described in the text. Each model is evolved until stationarity is reached, and in any case up until at least $t = 20000M$. The adiabatic index was set to $\gamma = 5/3$ and the black hole spin $a = 0$. The mass of the black hole is $M_{BH} = 3.6 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ and the radial grid extends from $r_{\min} = 2.1M$ to $r_{\max} = 200M$.

Model	v_∞	$c_{s,\infty}$	\mathcal{M}_∞	T [K]	ρ_∞ [cgs]	r_a [M]
V08.CS07	0.08	0.07	1.14	3.22×10^{10}	3.22×10^{-12}	88.5
V09.CS07	0.09	0.07	1.28	3.22×10^{10}	3.22×10^{-12}	76.9
V10.CS07	0.10	0.07	1.42	3.22×10^{10}	3.22×10^{-12}	67.1
V11.CS07	0.11	0.07	1.57	3.22×10^{10}	3.22×10^{-12}	58.8
V07.CS06	0.07	0.06	1.16	2.36×10^{10}	4.39×10^{-12}	117.6
V07.CS07	0.07	0.07	1.0	3.22×10^{10}	3.22×10^{-12}	102.0
V07.CS08	0.07	0.08	0.77	4.22×10^{10}	2.45×10^{-12}	88.5
V07.CS09	0.07	0.09	0.77	5.35×10^{10}	1.93×10^{-12}	76.9
p.V09.CS07	0.09	0.07	1.28	3.22×10^9	3.22×10^{-12}	76.9
p.V10.CS07	0.10	0.07	1.42	3.22×10^9	3.22×10^{-12}	67.1
p.V11.CS07	0.11	0.07	1.57	3.22×10^9	3.22×10^{-12}	58.8
p.V18.CS07	0.18	0.07	2.57	3.22×10^9	3.22×10^{-12}	26.8

set initially are: the asymptotic sound speed $c_{s,\infty}$, and the asymptotic pressure, from which the asymptotic rest-mass density ρ_∞ follows directly (see values reported in Table 7.1 for all of the models considered). For all the simulations we consider a gas of nonrelativistic electrons and hence with an adiabatic index $\gamma = 5/3$. The velocities used in our models and presented in Table 7.1 are chosen to be sufficiently high so as to open a shock cone (see details below). Any chosen v_∞ implies a restricted range of asymptotic sound speeds, if a reasonable Mach number should be considered. We remark that our models do not aim at modelling any specific astrophysical scenario, but rather at highlighting the role of the back-reaction of the radiation in an optically thick, relativistic BHL accretion flow.

Similarly, the radiation field is initialized to a value such that the radiation temperature $T_{\text{rad}} = (E_r/a_{\text{rad}})^{1/4} \approx 1.5 \times 10^5 K$. While this may seem an arbitrary choice, we have verified through a series of numerical simulations that, on long-term evolutions, the value of the obtained luminosity is not dependent of this initial choice. The computational grid consists of $N_r \times N_\phi$ numerical cells in the radial and angular directions, respectively, covering a computational domain extending from $r_{\min} = 2.1M$ to $r_{\max} = 200M$ and from $\phi_{\min} = 0$ to $\phi_{\max} = 2\pi$. For our fiducial simulation we have chosen $N_r = 1536$ and $N_\phi = 300$, but have also verified that the results are not sensitive to the resolution used or to the location of the outer boundary.

boundary
conditions

The boundary conditions in the radial direction are such that at the inner radial grid point we implement inflow boundary conditions by a simple zeroth-order extrapolation (i.e., a direct copy) of all variables. We have verified that such conditions effectively prevent inflow of matter from the region below r_{\min} . At the outer radial boundary, on the other hand, we must distinguish between the upstream region (i.e., with $\pi/2 < \phi < 3/2\pi$), and the downstream region (i.e., with $-\pi/2 < \phi < \pi/2$). In the upstream region we continuously inject matter with the initial velocity field of (7.1)-(7.2), thus reproducing

a continuous wind at large distances, while in the downstream region we use outflow boundary conditions. Finally, symmetric (i.e., periodic) boundary conditions are adopted at $\phi = 0$. The simulations using the non-IMEX code (see next paragraph) are performed with a C_{CFL} -coefficient that may vary according to the model and it is typically in the range $\sim [0.01, 0.5]$.

In addition to the "classical" BHL initial data, we will also consider a set of simulations in which the thermodynamics of the flow is slightly altered in order to reduce the temperature of the gas. We denote these models as "p-models" in Table 7.1. In essence, the perturbed BHL accretion flows are obtained by injecting gas of lower pressure than required by the stationary solution at the upwind boundary, with a proportionally reduced radiation energy density E_r (see Sect. 7.1.4 for details).

perturbed models

For the second part of this Chapter, we also use "sp-models", where the asymptotic pressure was reduced by another order of magnitude. Thus an "sp-models" is the same as an unperturbed model, save that the pressure is divided by a factor of 100.

strongly perturbed models

7.1.2 Computation of luminosity

The key new quantity that our code allows to compute is the emitted luminosity. Since the code explicitly calculates the radiation fluxes f_r^i at each time step, we use them to compute the intrinsic luminosity emitted from the optically thick region as

$$L = \int_{\Omega} f_r^i n_i dS_{opt}, \quad (7.3)$$

where S_{opt} is the surface of the volume Ω enclosing an optically thick region within the computational domain, while the scalar product $f_r^i n_i$ provides the projection of the local radiation flux onto the normal to the radiating surface. Because of the nearly isotropic assumption made for the radiation field and because of the rough spherical symmetry of the physical system under consideration, the fluxes in the angular directions are expected to be much smaller than the radial ones and to almost cancel. As a result, and for simplicity, we approximate the scalar product above as $f_r^i n_i = f_r^r$, thus computing the luminosity as

$$L = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\phi}} [\sqrt{\gamma} (f_r^r)_n \Delta\phi_n] |_{\tau=1}, \quad (7.4)$$

where $\Delta\phi_n$ is the angular size of a grid cell and we perform the surface integral at the radial position of the last optically-thick surface, i.e., where $\tau = 1$; the factor 2 accounts for both the contributions above and below the equatorial plane.

The luminosity computed in this way comprises two different contributions. The first one is an accretion-powered luminosity that it is directly proportional to the mass-accretion rate \dot{M} through a relation of the type $L_{\text{acc}} = \eta \dot{M}$, where the coefficient η expresses the efficiency of the conversion of gravitational binding energy into radiation. The main dissipative mechanism is provided by compression of the fluid when this has nonzero thermal conductivity¹. A second contribution to the total luminosity (7.4) is given by dissipative processes related to shock heating that, as we will show below, can provide a considerable contribution to the total emission.

contributions to the luminosity estimate

However, since we are dealing with inviscid non-magnetized fluids, the luminosity (7.4) obviously cannot provide the contribution coming from dissipative processes driven by

¹ See Appendix A.1.1

viscosity (of whatever origin), and that can be a significant part of the accretion-powered luminosity in a realistic accretion scenario. For comparison, in the Shakura-Sunyaev thin-disc model the main dissipative mechanism comes from the viscous stress tensor, directly proportional to the total pressure via the “alpha” parameter. Similarly, in spherical accretion, a realistic viscous fluid with nonzero bulk viscosity will produce a viscous dissipation adding to the one coming from the fluid compression. In summary: in realistic accretion scenarios one should expect that *both* thermal conductivity and viscosity act as transport coefficients of dissipative processes and lead to contributions to the emitted luminosity. In our treatment, however, only the effects of the former one can be accounted for. Hereafter, the luminosities and the accretion rates will be reported in Eddington units, i.e., $L_{\text{Edd}} = 4\pi GMm_p c / \sigma_{T,e} \simeq 1.26 \times 10^{38} (M/M_\odot) \text{ erg s}^{-1}$, $\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}} = L_{\text{Edd}}/c^2 \simeq 1.39 \times 10^{17} (M/M_\odot) \text{ g s}^{-1}$. See also (A.8) for the Eddington luminosity in the geometrized units of the code.

7.1.3 Classical BHL accretion

We start our analysis by considering the extent to which a radiation field affects the dynamics of the classical BHL flow, comparing the dynamics for very similar physical conditions. The initial models, which are the first seven reported in Table 7.1, have very high temperatures and, consequently, high thermal conductivities¹. As mentioned above, for any given value of the adiabatic index, there is a critical asymptotic Mach number $\mathcal{M}_{\infty,c}$, usually close to unity, above which a shock cone forms in the downstream region and below which the shock cone reverses in the upstream region. Our simulations indicate that, for values of the Mach number close to the critical one, the radiation effects on the dynamics are most evident. This is shown in Fig. 7.1 for model V09.CS07, where we have reported the distribution of the rest-mass density at three different times in a purely hydrodynamical evolution (left panels) and in a radiation-hydrodynamic evolution (right panels). This model, in particular, provides an example in which the radiation field prevents the reversal of the shock cone from the downstream region into the upstream region, which instead takes place in the purely hydrodynamical evolution. Since the dynamics of V09.CS07 becomes radiation-pressure dominated around $t \sim 5000M$, the explanation of this effect is simple: In such conditions the effective adiabatic index of the fluid-plus-radiation medium is smaller than that of the fluid alone [see Eq. (70.22) of [Mihalas & Weibel Mihalas \(1984\)](#)]

effective adiabatic
index γ_{eff}

$$\gamma_{\text{eff}} = \frac{5/2 + 20q + 16q^2}{(3/2 + 12q)(1 + q)}, \quad (7.5)$$

where $q = \mathcal{P}_r/P$. This fact has two important consequences. The first one, which we will discuss shortly when commenting Fig. 7.5, is to increase the rest-mass density jumps across shock fronts. The second one, is exactly to favour the generation of the shock cone downstream of the accretor, as firstly noticed by [Ruffert \(1996\)](#) and later confirmed by [Font & Ibáñez \(1998\)](#).

Comparison pure
hydro versus
radiation hydro

As clearly shown in Fig. 7.1, the radiation-hydrodynamics evolution of model V09.CS07 is remarkably different from the purely hydrodynamical one, and it can be divided in the following stages. After the shock cone has fully opened in the downstream region (top right panel of Fig. 7.1), the flow becomes radiation-pressure dominated, making the shock cone

¹ The non-IMEX version of the code does not allow to handle stiff source terms that arise in the radiation-hydrodynamics equations when the conductivity is small ([Szóke et al., 2006](#)). See § 3.2.2 for treatment of this difficulty.

Fig. 7.1: COMPARISON OF BHL DENSITY EVOLUTION IN PURE AND RADIATIVE HYDRODYNAMICS - Rest-mass density in cgs units on a logarithmic scale for model V09_CS07 in a purely hydrodynamical evolution (*left panels*) and in a radiation-hydrodynamics evolution (*right panels*). Different rows refer to different times of the evolution and white regions correspond to densities slightly below the threshold for the colour code at around $10^{-12} \text{ g/cm}^{-3}$. Note that the presence of a radiation field reduces the rest-mass density considerably near the black hole, suppressing the accretion rate.

Fig. 7.2: RATIO OF RADIATION AND GAS PRESSURE FOR THE UNPERTURBED BHL MODEL V09.CS07 - *Left Panel:* logarithm of the ratio of radiation pressure over gas pressure at early times. *Right Panel:* the same as the right panel but at later times, when stationarity had been reached.

oscillate from one side of the accretor to the other, in a way that resembles the flip-flop instability already encountered in relativistic BHL flows by [Dönmez et al. \(2010\)](#). This transient behaviour, captured in the right-middle panel of [Fig. 7.1](#), is accompanied by an outflow of matter expelled by radiation pressure beyond the computational grid. After that, the system relaxes to a stationary configuration characterized by the presence of a shock cone with a much smaller opening angle than in the hydrodynamical solution, giving rise to a "reduced" shock cone. Also shown in [Fig. 7.2](#) is the ratio between the radiation pressure and the fluid pressure, reported in the left panel for an early and fluid-pressure dominated stage of the evolution, and in the right panel for a late and radiation-pressure dominated one.

critical Mach
number

A very similar behaviour to the one discussed so far is shown in [Fig. 7.3](#) for model V10.CS07, the initial Mach number of which is only slightly larger than model V09.CS07. However, in this case the higher fluid velocity causes supercritical behaviour both in the hydrodynamical and the radiation-hydrodynamical evolution so that the shock cone remains in the downstream region. The close similarity between the dynamics of models V09.CS07 and V10.CS07 in the presence of the radiation field is also testified by the asymptotic mass accretion rate, which is $\dot{M} \simeq 13.14\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}}$ for model V09.CS07 and $\dot{M} \simeq 10.24\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}}$ for V10.CS07.

accretion rates

An information complementary to that of [Fig. 7.1 - 7.3](#) is provided by [Fig. 7.4](#), which shows the evolution of the mass accretion rate for a few selected models. For each of these models both the purely hydrodynamical evolution (red solid lines) and the radiation-hydrodynamical one (blue dashed lines) are considered. A few comments are worth making about this figure. The first one is that, once stationarity is reached, the mass accretion rates of the radiation-hydrodynamics models are significantly smaller than those of the corresponding hydrodynamics models. This result was of course expected, because of the obstructive effect of the radiation pressure. The second comment is that the reversal of the shock cone in the hydrodynamics models V09.CS07, V07.CS07, V07.CS09 and in the radiation-hydrodynamics models V07.CS07 and V07.CS09 leads to an increase of \dot{M} , as highlighted by the arrows. For the hydrodynamical version of model V09.CS07, for instance, this increase starts at $t \sim 12000M$, as reported in the top-left panel of [Fig. 7.4](#). Finally, we find that all

Fig. 7.3: COMPARISON OF BHL DENSITY EVOLUTION IN PURE AND RADIATIVE HYDRODYNAMICS - Rest-mass density in cgs units on a logarithmic scale for model V10.CS07 in a purely hydrodynamical evolution (*left panels*) and in a radiation-hydrodynamics evolution (*right panels*). Different rows refer to different times of the evolution and white regions correspond to densities slightly below the threshold for the colour code at around $10^{-12} \text{ g/cm}^{-3}$. Note that the presence of a radiation field reduces the rest-mass density considerably near the black hole, suppressing the accretion rate.

Fig. 7.4: MASS ACCRETION RATES FOR SEVERAL UNPERTURBED BHL MODELS - Evolution of the mass accretion rate in Eddington units for models V07.CS07 and V07.CS09 (*left panels*) and V09.CS07 and V10.CS07 (*right panels*).

models accrete at super-Eddington rates even when a radiation field is present¹. This is not surprising, since the Eddington limit holds strictly only in spherical symmetry, which is not fulfilled in wind-like accretion.

Fig. 7.5: COMPARISON OF THE REST-MASS DENSITY JUMP ACROSS THE SHOCK FRONT FOR MODEL V09.CS07 at time $t = 5000$ in a purely hydrodynamics evolution (**red solid line**) and in a radiation hydrodynamics evolution (**blue dashed line**). The location of the shock was re-normalized to lie at $x = 0$ and is displaced by $\Delta x \sim 0.2M$ between the two runs.

compressibility

Additional differences between the hydrodynamics and the radiation-hydrodynamics evolutions emerge after comparing the jumps experienced by the rest-mass density across a shock wave in a representative model. Such a comparison is reported in Fig. 7.5 for

¹ The fraction of matter accreted depends on the position of the shock front. When the shock forms in the downstream region, about 80% – 90% of the matter crossing the shock front is accreted by the black hole. This percentage decreases to 50 – 60%, when the matter crosses the shock front in the upstream region.

Fig. 7.6: OPTICAL THICKNESS AND RADIATIVE FLUX IN THE UNPERTURBED BHL MODEL V09.CS07 *Left Panel:* logarithm of the optical thickness for once stationarity is reached. *Right Panel:* Logarithm of the modulus of the radiative flux (in geometrized units) in the same model at the same time.

model V09.CS07, showing the variation of the rest-mass density across the shock that is produced at time $t = 5000M$ and visible in the two top panels of Fig. 7.1. The two curves have been obtained after slicing the rest-mass density along an “ x -direction” perpendicular to the shock front, and sliding the two profiles so that the shock is located at the same $x = 0$ position for both the hydrodynamical and the radiation-hydrodynamical evolution. Negative and positive values of the x -coordinate refer therefore to the unshocked and to the shocked region, respectively, while the rest-mass density has been normalized to the value in the unshocked region.

The first comment about this figure is that the density jump in the hydrodynamics evolution is slightly smaller than the value of 4 predicted by the theoretical expectation of $\rho_2/\rho_1 \sim (\gamma + 1)/(\gamma - 1)$ valid for an ideal gas EoS. This effect may be due to the presence of both numerical diffusion and tangential velocities along the shock front. The second comment is that the compression ratio across the shock increases by 3% in the transition from a hydrodynamical to a radiation-hydrodynamical evolution. This effect can again be understood by regarding the fluid in the radiation-hydrodynamics evolution as an effective fluid having a *smaller* adiabatic index, as indeed expected in the radiation-pressure dominated regime. This result is also in agreement with analytical investigations by [Guess \(1960\)](#) and [Mihalas & Weibel Mihalas \(1984\)](#) (§104).

Before computing the luminosity as described in §. 7.1.2, it is important to make sure that the physical conditions lead to an optically thick regime. Of course all of the models considered in our simulations and reported in Table 7.1 show only very limited regions where the optical thickness can be $\sim \mathcal{O}(1)$ during the evolution. As a representative example, the left panel of Fig. 7.6 shows the optical thickness when the system as relaxed to stationarity, for the same model V09.CS07 that we have extensively described so far. The right panel of Fig. 7.6, on the other hand, shows the corresponding intensity of the momentum of the radiation field. Comparing to right-bottom panel of Fig. 7.1 shows that the distribution of the radiative fluxes is correlated with the rest-mass density distribution, but also that a good portion of the radiative emission is concentrated along the shock fronts of the reduced shock cone.

The evolution of the emitted luminosity and of the mass-accretion rates are illustrated in the two panels of Fig. 7.7. More specifically, the left panel, which reports models with increasing Mach number but having the same initial temperature, shows that the

optical depth

luminosity increases with \mathcal{M}_∞

Fig. 7.7: LUMINOSITY AND MASS-ACCRETION IN CLASSICAL BHL ACCRETION FLOWS - in Eddington units: The *left panel* collects models with different initial velocities but with the same sound speed. In contrast, the *right panel* collects models with the same initial velocities but with different values for the sound speed. All simulations were evolved until they reached stationarity, and up to $t = 30000M$ at most.

Table 7.2: Mass accretion rate, luminosity and efficiency η_{BHL} as defined in Eq. (7.6) of BHL accretion in the quasi-stationary regime.

Model	\mathcal{M}_∞	$\dot{M}_{\text{acc}}/\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}}$	L/L_{Edd}	η_{BHL}
V08.CS07	1.14	17.9	3.10	0.14
V09.CS07	1.28	13.14	4.11	0.22
V10.CS07	1.42	10.24	6.18	0.36
V11.CS07	1.57	8.32	6.77	0.38
V07.CS07	1.0	27.64	1.44	0.05
V07.CS08	0.87	21.74	2.14	0.09
V07.CS09	0.77	17.44	1.91	0.10
p.V10.CS07	1.42	11.58	5.35	0.29
p.V11.CS07	1.57	8.34	7.05	0.40
p.V18.CS07	2.57	4.02	30.5	0.69

luminosity increases with \mathcal{M}_∞ and reaches stationary values of a few Eddington units. On the other hand, the right panel, which reports models with the same asymptotic velocity but different temperatures, shows that stationarity is reached on longer timescales and a correlation with the final luminosity is less robust. In all of the models shown, the first bump around $t \sim 2000M$ is due to the initial opening of the shock cone.

Our calculations allow us to derive the efficiency of the accretion flow η_{BHL} . We remark that the concept of η_{BHL} for a BHL flow, with a nonzero velocity of the matter at infinity, is not the same as in standard accretion discs, where the gas flow is supposed to start from matter at rest at infinity. Thus, we define an effective BHL luminosity efficiency η_{BHL} as

radiative efficiency

$$\eta_{\text{BHL}} = \frac{L}{\dot{M}_{\text{acc}}c^2 + \frac{1}{2}\dot{M}_{\infty}v_{\infty}^2}, \quad (7.6)$$

where the denominator takes into account a kinetic contribution to the energy flux. We report the values of $\dot{M}_{\text{acc}}/\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}}$, L/L_{Edd} and η_{BHL} in Table 7.2 for those models presenting a quasi-stationary accretion pattern. From the data reported in the Table it is possible to deduce the existence of two different regimes in a radiative BHL accretion flow. A first regime, corresponding to $\mathcal{M}_{\infty} \lesssim 1$, where the luminosity is dominated by the accretion-powered luminosity and thus proportional to \dot{M} . A second regime, corresponding to $\mathcal{M}_{\infty} \gtrsim 1$, where the luminosity is instead dominated by the emission at the shock front. In particular, by comparing the first four models that have the same initial asymptotic sound speed, we note that, as the asymptotic Mach number is increased, the accretion rates decrease. This effect is due to the reduced opening angle of the shock cone. The corresponding luminosity, on the other hand, increases, because of the enhanced dissipation at the shock front.

As a final remark we note that, as already discussed in § 7.1.2, the luminosities we have reported here can only provide lower limits on the energy efficiency η_{BHL} . We have in fact neglected not only viscous dissipative processes from the accretion flow, but also any nonthermal emission, such as inverse Compton or synchrotron radiation, which could arise from a corona developing near the black hole.

7.1.4 Perturbed Bondi-Hoyle-Lyttleton flow

As mentioned in § 7.1.1, in addition to the standard and stationary BHL flows, we have also considered initial conditions that would lead to perturbed BHL accretion patterns (tagged these as the “p-models”). The rationale behind this choice is that of investigating how the accretion flows varies when the initial conditions are no longer those ensuring a stationary flow. At the same time, this allows us to consider models that have lower temperatures and, consequently, lower thermal conductivities.

In practice, we trigger the perturbation of the BHL flow by acting on the thermodynamic conditions of the fluid in the upstream region and by producing models with values of the initial temperature that are typically one order of magnitude smaller than those in standard BHL models. Because of the perturbation introduced, the dynamics of the perturbed models is typically characterized by a very dynamical phase before quasi-stationarity is reached. However, in spite of these violent transients, the perturbation introduced does not destroy the general BHL pattern, which is recovered eventually.

Among the perturbed models, p.V09.CS07 has the minimum Mach number, and is also the only one producing a shock cone that progressively reverses into the upstream region as a bow shock. The remaining three models, which all have higher Mach numbers, develop the usual shock cone downstream of the black hole. This behaviour is reported in the four panels of Fig. 7.8, showing the evolution at different times of the rest-mass density for the model p.V10.CS07 in a radiation-hydrodynamical evolution. Note that the accretion cone, that is fully formed at time $t \sim 3000M$, is highly unstable and it goes through a rapid sequence of oscillations generating an undulated stream in the wake. Finally, the system reaches a quasi-equilibrium state characterized by a reduced shock cone similar to that already encountered in the dynamics of standard models.

The extraction of the light-curve and the computation of all remaining quantities follows the same procedure used in the standard models and we have reported the mass-accretion rates and the light-curves in the two panels of Fig. 7.9. Note that the general features in the light-curves for the standard models are also present for the perturbed models. In particular, there is an initial rise in luminosity which corresponds to the formation of the

rationale behind
perturbing the
solution

strong, transient
oscillations

Fig. 7.8: DENSITY EVOLUTION IN THE PERTURBED BHL MODEL p.V10.CS07 - Rest-mass density in cgs units on a logarithmic scale for the at four different times in a radiation-hydrodynamics evolution. The two rows refer to different times of the evolution and white regions correspond to densities slightly below the threshold for the colour code at around $10^{-12} \text{ g/cm}^{-3}$. Note that a highly dynamical transient precedes the development of a stationary flow.

shock cone. After that, between $t \sim 1000M$ and $t \sim 2000M$ depending on the model, a peak is produced in the light-curve which is due to the shock cone changing its geometry to an open cone. Interestingly, even the efficiency $\eta_{\text{BH}\mathcal{L}}$ of the perturbed models are very similar to those of the corresponding standard ones¹. For the model p.V11.CS07, for instance, $\eta_{\text{BH}\mathcal{L}} = 0.40$, to be compared with $\eta_{\text{BH}\mathcal{L}} = 0.38$ of V11.CS07 (see also the discussion in Section 7.1.5).

time evolution

We remark that the fluid temperature within $25M$ from the black hole decreases more rapidly for high Mach numbers, so that the build up of the radiation pressure is faster for the highest Mach number. It should also be noted that while all perturbed models are radiation-pressure dominated in the upstream region after $t \sim 10000M$, this regime is reached at different times by different models. Furthermore, even when radiation pressure dominates the dynamics, there could be isolated portions of the flow where the gas pressure is not completely negligible. This is the case, for instance, in the undulated downstream part of the flow, where the ratio of gas pressure to radiation pressures ratio can be as high as $P/P_r \sim 0.1$.

role of radiation pressure

The dominant role played by the radiation pressure is imprinted on the accretion rate

¹ As will be discussed in the next §, the values *really* are the same for a better choice of luminosity extraction

for the p-model p.V18.CS07, as it is clear from Fig. 7.9. This model features the lowest quasi-equilibrium accretion rate and the highest luminosity. In general, we have found that the higher the Mach number, the higher the radiation pressure, and the smaller the average density around the black hole. The perturbed model p.V18.CS07 for instance, has a rest-mass density which is a factor 100 smaller than that in model p.V09.CS07, which has the minimum Mach number among the perturbed models and the longest relaxation time (cf. Fig. 7.9). At the same time, the accretion rate of p.V09.CS07 does not show the typical decline up until $t = 20000M$, although it is radiation-pressure dominated everywhere in the numerical domain. It is possible that the behaviour of model p.V09.CS07 would change, with the mass-accretion rate decreasing and the luminosity increasing, if the evolution was carried on a much longer timescale.

Fig. 7.9: LUMINOSITY AND MASS ACCRETION - *Left Panel*: Luminosity in Eddington units for the perturbed BHL accretion flows. *Right Panel*: Mass accretion rates in Eddington units for the same models in the left panel.

7.1.5 Strongly perturbed BHL flow

In this Section, we now use the IMEX solver, for treating the numerically difficult parameter space that is inaccessible to the (much faster) explicit code. Given that the key parameter responsible for numerical difficulty had been temperature, we are in a position to show the true advantage of the IMEX here. Only now, it becomes feasible to treat astrophysical temperatures that are few orders of magnitude lower than in and as astrophysically realistic as our approach can allow at this stage (cf. Section 7.2 for more discussion). We go to some length analysing the fluid dynamics in order to point out the current limitations that our formulation of the GR-RHD equations has.

IMEX required for lower temperatures

In the following we examine the behaviour of three models, with two different initial soundspeeds $c_{s,\infty}$ and the same asymptotic velocity v_∞ . The prefix sp is used to denote "strongly perturbed" which means that the initial asymptotic pressure is lowered by two

three new models

orders of magnitude with respect to the equilibrium value.

Measured physical quantities

In addition to the primitive variables provided by the code, we calculate several physical quantities as they are: the accretion rate in Eddington units, \dot{M} , the luminosity in Eddington units, L , the radiation equivalent temperature, $T_{\text{rad}} = (E_{\text{r}}/a_{\text{rad}})^{1/4}$, the fluid temperature, T_{fluid} , the effective BHL luminosity efficiency $\eta_{\text{B}\mathcal{H}\mathcal{L}}$, the effective adiabatic index γ_{eff} , and the local Mach number \mathcal{M} :

$$\mathcal{M} = \frac{\Gamma \sqrt{v_i v^i}}{\Gamma_{c_s} c_s} \quad \text{with} \quad c_s = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma P}{h\rho}} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma P}{\rho + \frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1} P}}. \quad (7.7)$$

Table 7.3: Representative quantities of the considered models after quasi-stationary state has been reached. The columns report the model name, the average relaxed radiation temperature, the average relaxed Mach number, the average relaxed effective adiabatic index, the relaxed accretion rate and the relaxed luminosity. See text for definition of these quantities.

Name	$\langle T_{\text{rad}} \rangle [\text{K}]$	$\langle \mathcal{M} \rangle$	$\langle \gamma_{\text{eff}} \rangle$	$\dot{M}/\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}}$	L/L_{Edd}	$\eta_{\text{B}\mathcal{H}\mathcal{L}}$
V07.cs03	5.6×10^5	20.1	1.333	132	0.939	6.9×10^{-3}
sp.V07.cs03	5.6×10^5	849	1.334	135	0.943	6.8×10^{-3}
sp.V07.cs05	4.3×10^5	679	1.333	62	0.484	9.0×10^{-3}

volume weighted
averages

We measure several quantities Q as volume weighted averages over all grid elements i , thus defining the pointy brackets as

$$\langle Q \rangle = \frac{1}{\sum_i^N r_i dr_i d\phi_i} \left(\sum_i^N Q_i r_i dr_i d\phi_i \right). \quad (7.8)$$

The rate of entropy generation is measured according to Eq. (A.16), which is an appropriate approximation for a coupled photon fluid plasma in a quasi-stationarity state. Selected results are shown in Figs. 7.10 to 7.12 and summarised in Tab. 7.3.

Discussion of the luminosity extraction

When we extract the luminosity, we choose a surface of constant optical depth $\tau \gtrsim 10$. We argue this is reasonable because only if $\tau \gg 1$ the system is still in a regime where the approximation with the diffusion limit is valid. This is also realistic, when thinking of actual observations, where measurements are taken at constant¹ τ .

We generally compute the luminosity as the surface integral over outgoing radiation fluxes f_r^f according to Eq. 7.4:

$$L = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{N_\phi} [\sqrt{\gamma} (f_r^f)_n \Delta\phi_n] |_{\tau=\tau_*}, \quad (7.9)$$

¹ In the case of stars, for instance, this is usually taken as $\tau \sim 2/3$.

Fig. 7.10: 2D OPTICAL DEPTH AND FLUID TEMPERATURE OF PERTURBED MODEL *sp.V07.cs03* AND UNPERTURBED MODELS *V07.cs03* - Both models are shown at stationary state: (*Top*) $t = 7.71 \times 10^4 M$ for model *sp.V07.cs03* and (*Bottom*) $t = 5.98 \times 10^4 M$ for model *V07.cs03*.

In the above Section 7.1.3, we computed the luminosity by imposing the criterion $\tau_{\bullet} \geq 1$. However, these small values of the optical depth often correspond to an integration surface close to the boundary of the numerical domain, where spurious boundary effects may alter the results. Hence, we realised our mistake and now we have adopted a different criterion by choosing $\tau_{\bullet} \geq 10$, which guarantees that the integration surface is not placed at the outermost grid cells.

It is clear that the new extraction leads to lower luminosity which is in accordance with our expectation, since the luminosity is a surface integral containing the area of the

large uncertainties to the luminosity estimate

surface where $\tau = 10^1$. The higher the Mach number, the lower is the final density which in turn means the smaller is the area where the optical depth is high. This is strictly true for high temperatures where Thomson scattering dominates over bremsstrahlung. If the emitting region is perfectly spherical then the geometrical factor and the radial flux cancel yielding a number that is independent of the radius where it was extracted. However, the emitting surface becomes less and less spherical the more supersonic the flow. By chance, we had previously chosen the method from which the maximal luminosity resulted. This comparison is relevant for the discussion of uncertainties in luminosity-estimates in § 7.1.5.2.

BHL dynamics dominated by radiation temperature

summary of dynamics First of all, we note that the qualitative dynamics of the new BHL models are the same as those described in Section 7.1.3 and can be summarised as follows. Initially, a narrow, hot shock cone forms downstream of the accretor and the plasma is fluid-pressure dominated. Progressively, the radiation field builds up strength until the radiation pressure becomes similar to the fluid pressure. At this point, the shock cone becomes unstable, oscillating from one side of the accretor to the other, and finally reverses into the upstream domain. From now on the radiation pressure exceeds the fluid pressure, the effective adiabatic index approaches the value $\sim 4/3$ and, at the same time, the density (and correspondingly the optical depth) decreases in most parts of the numerical domain. After the upstream shock has moved out of the numerical domain and expelled a significant amount of mass, a new, low density equilibrium is formed in which there is a much smaller shock cone in the downstream region.

lower temperatures in strongly perturbed models The central improvement over the treatment in the previous Sections is shown in Fig. 7.10, where the two-dimensional maps of the fluid temperature (right) and of the optical depth (left) are reported for two different models, both of them at the final quasi-stationary state. The top panels show that for the strongly perturbed model `sp.V07.cs03` large parts of the upstream region settle down to temperatures of the order $T_{\text{fluid}} \lesssim 10^6 \text{K}$, a value which could not be reached before due to the stiffness of the equations. The corresponding unperturbed model, `V07.cs03`, shown in the bottom panels, has upstream temperatures as high as $T_{\text{fluid}} \lesssim 5 \times 10^9$, while both of the models have high optical thickness. It is important to note that at this stage of the evolution, namely after the "reversal" of the shock cone, the effective adiabatic index of all three models is very close to $4/3$, and therefore behaving like an effective photon fluid. We can understand the thermodynamics of the models better if we look at the time evolution of the averaged fluid and radiation temperatures, which are plotted in Fig. 7.11.

fluid and radiation temperature differ There are three points worth noting. First of all, for each model, the two temperatures T_{rad} and T_{fluid} differ by many orders of magnitude, suggesting that, at least globally, there is a strong deviation from thermal equilibrium within the fluid. Secondly, the fluid temperatures of the models `sp.V07.cs03` and `V07.cs03` are also very different, in spite of the dynamics being very similar (this is discussed in the next §). Finally, T_{rad} shows a smooth evolution, whereas T_{fluid} exhibits a strong dip, a reversal and heats up again afterwards. We know that at "reversal", the hot ($T_{\text{fluid}} \gg 10^{10} \text{K}$) shock cone is almost completely destroyed and because the density downstream of the accretor becomes small after "reversal", yet the pressure remains high, there forms a high temperature shock cone,

¹ We can assign error bars to our extraction method by taking the standard deviation of the mean and we find that both our estimates agree within these uncertainties.

Fig. 7.11: COMPARISON OF FLUID AND RADIATION TEMPERATURES, MACH NUMBER AND EFFICIENCY - (Left): Volume weighted averages according to Eq. (7.8) for all three BHL models `sp.V07.cs05`, `sp.V07.cs03` and `V07.cs03` as a function of time. Temperatures are given in Kelvin. (Right): Comparison of the volume weighted averages of the local Mach number $\langle \mathcal{M}_{\text{rel}} \rangle$ and the radiative efficiency $\langle \eta \rangle$ as a function of time.

as visible in the right panels of Fig. 7.10, with T_{fluid} -average being dominated by the high values within the downstream shock cone. Thus, the fluid behaves like an effective photon fluid of temperature $T_{\text{rad}} \lesssim 10^6 \text{K}$, but in the shock cone no thermalization is possible and the fluid temperature vastly exceeds the radiation temperature. In order to corroborate this conjecture, we measure the entropy generation rate $\nabla_{\nu} S^{\nu}$ (see Appendix A.1.1), which after all is one of the surest ways of determining if a shock is present. We also know, that at shocks fluids are not thermalised. $\nabla_{\nu} S^{\nu}$ is plotted in Fig. 7.12 for the two models `V07.cs03` and `sp.V07.cs03`. The entropy generation rate is maximum in the shocked region downstream of the accretor, even though the dynamics is otherwise stationary. If we compare T_{rad} and T_{fluid} in the upstream regions where $\nabla_{\nu} S^{\nu}$ is small (white regions of the Figure) then they are indeed equal. We thus conclude that the nominal temperature of these models are the radiation temperatures after the dynamics have become completely radiation dominated and $\gamma_{\text{eff}} \sim 4/3$.

$\nabla_{\nu} S^{\nu}$ as
thermalisation
tracer

To further illustrate the effects of radiation induced dynamics, we measure again the two classical parameters luminosity and the accretion rate in Eddington units. We plot the luminosity on the left panel of Fig. 7.13 and the accretion rate \dot{M} on the right; for all three models. The important aspects of this figure are that (i) the final luminosity is sub-Eddington for all cases, (ii) the models `sp.V07.cs03` and `V07.cs03` converge towards the same value, and (iii) the higher soundspeed (correspondingly the lower asymptotic Mach number \mathcal{M}_{∞}) of `sp.V07.cs05` leads to smaller luminosity.

Fig. 7.12: 2D ENTROPY GENERATION RATES FOR V07.cs03 and sp.V07.cs03 - Distribution map of $\nabla_v S^v$ for model V07.cs03 (*left panel*) at time $t = 5.98 \times 10^4 M$ and for model sp.V07.cs03 (*right panel*) at time $t = 7.71 \times 10^4 M$.

Fig. 7.13: TIME EVOLUTION OF PERTURBED BHL MODELS sp.V07.cs05, sp.V07.cs03 AND V07.cs03- (*Left panel*) luminosity L extracted at constant optical depth $\tau \geq 10$, (*Right panel*) accretion rate \dot{M} as a function of time in Eddington units.

The role of fluid temperature

It is interesting to note that the strongly perturbed model `sp.V07.cs03` converges toward the (almost) same final state in all radiation quantities as its unperturbed counterpart `V07.cs03`. This is observed in the accretion rate, \dot{M} , plotted on the right of Fig. 7.13, in the luminosity, in the radiative efficiency, η (cf. Fig. 7.11), the optical depth, τ (cf. Fig. 7.10), and the radiation temperature, T_{rad} (cf. Fig. 7.11), of these two models.

perturbation has little influence of dynamics

We could actually have observed this before, however, unfortunately, we had used a less than ideal criterion for the luminosity extraction, which obscured this fact. However, we note at this point that our luminosity estimate has large error bars, but that it serves well as a numerical tracer for comparison between the different models.

While the radiation quantities converge for the two models, the fluid influenced quantities do not: fluid temperature, Mach number and entropy generation are neither qualitatively and certainly not quantitatively the same. Thus it stands to reason that, as far as the current approach is physically valid, only the radiation temperature and the matter density (conversely, the optical depth) are of dynamical importance. However, it is somewhat worrisome that the discrepancy between T_{fluid} and T_{rad} is so large, as it implies that the assumption of LTE is only valid in a small portion of the grid (cf. the white region of Fig. 7.12 (right panel)). Again, it is known that full thermalization is very hard to accomplish in dynamical environments of moderate density. Therefore, we are currently dealing with a two component fluid that effectively behaves like a photon gas, but has regions in which T_{fluid} is 6 orders of magnitude above T_{rad} .

fluid temperature dynamically unimportant

At last, it should be noted that the less supersonic model `sp.V07.cs05` fits well into the outlined picture on all points, so does it for example show lower accretion rates. This is not surprising because the radiation pressure is lower in this case as shown by the orange curve in Fig. 7.11.

differences between the new models

Above, we argued that the two 07.03 models behave remarkably similar. There are, however, some small differences in the dynamics between the two models `sp.V07.cs03` and `V07.cs03`: the time evolution is faster for `V07.cs03` as it has higher T_{fluid} thus higher thermal conductivity (cf. Appendix A.1.1); the shock cone opening angle is smaller and the spread in local Mach number and $\nabla v S^V$ is smaller in the unperturbed case, `V07.cs03`. Without claiming any rigour, we attribute this to the much higher local Mach number encountered in the perturbed case (cf. Fig 7.11 [light blue curve](#)).

7.1.5.1 Spinning black holes

Although the results presented so far refer to Schwarzschild black holes, a number of different simulations have been performed also for spinning black holes, with dimensionless spin parameters ranging between 0 and 0.99. The interest, in these cases, was that of determining the influence that the black-hole spin may have on the flow pattern and on the emission properties, for both the classical BHL configurations and the perturbed ones.

Overall, the modifications introduced by the black-hole spin are not particularly large to deserve a dedicated discussion. More specifically, as far as the dynamics is concerned, we have confirmed that as the spin of the black hole is increased, the shock cone that may form in the downstream part of the flow is progressively wrapped (this was originally pointed out

dynamics largely unaffected by spin

by [Font et al. \(1999\)](#)). This distortion, however, is evident only in the immediate vicinity of the horizon, and typically below $r \leq 20M$. Furthermore, very minor changes has been found in the light-curves, to the point that the luminosity for a $a = 0.99$ black hole is only 3% larger than that for a $a = 0$ Schwarzschild black hole. These results suggest that if spin-related signatures in the electromagnetic emission should exist and can be extracted, these will become evident only when a more sophisticated modelling of the emission processes (e.g., through inverse Compton in a rarefied corona) will be considered. This will be part of our future work.

7.1.5.2 Impact on EM counterparts of supermassive black hole binaries

As discussed already in the previous Chapter 6, we are always interested in possible observational consequences. The current scope of the GR-RHD approach is very limited. However, we can compare our luminosity estimate in its uncertainty with other approaches reported in literature. We are well aware that the physical conditions considered here badly match those expected in realistic scenarios describing the merger of a massive BHB.

standard
post-processing

A common approximation made in numerical simulations aimed at estimating the luminosity from binary black hole mergers ([Bode et al., 2010](#); [Farris et al., 2010](#); [O’Neill et al., 2009](#); [Megevand et al., 2009](#); [Zanotti et al., 2010](#); [Bode et al., 2011](#); [Farris et al., 2011b](#)), is computing the bremsstrahlung luminosity without taking the back-reaction of the radiation into account, but rather by performing a volume integral of the bremsstrahlung emissivity. First efforts to improve this treatment, but still without a proper radiation transfer, were initiated in Newtonian physics by [Corrales et al. \(2010\)](#); [Rossi et al. \(2010\)](#) by enforcing a locally isothermal evolution¹.

We have computed the bremsstrahlung-luminosity emitted in the classical BHL accretion of model V09.CS07 following the general relativistic prescription adopted by the works cited above, namely

$$L_{\text{BR}} \simeq 3 \times 10^{78} \int \left(T^{1/2} \rho^2 \Gamma \sqrt{\gamma} dV \right) \left(\frac{M_{\odot}}{M} \right) \text{ erg/s}, \quad (7.10)$$

and compared the results obtained using the estimate (7.10) with those obtained through our radiative-transfer treatment. In addition, we have also considered an alternative calculation in which an isothermal evolution is enforced, and where it is assumed that all the changes in the temperature that are due to a local compression are dissipated as radiation. This idea, has been extended to a general-relativistic context by [Zanotti et al. \(2010\)](#), and used also here for comparison.

The result of this comparison is shown in Fig.7.14, where we have reported the four light-curves computed according to the approaches just described. While this analysis is not exhaustive and has been performed in the specific scenario of an optically thick BHL accretion, it does point out that the predictions made using the simplistic estimate of the bremsstrahlung luminosity via Eq. (7.10) provide light-curves that are a factor $\gtrsim 20$ larger than those obtained with GR-RHD whereas an isothermal evolution leads to even smaller luminosities.

7.1.6 Limiting assumptions and caveats of the treatment

We should state a few words of caution as to the current shortcomings and necessary future improvements of our scheme:

¹ The model considered there was not BHL; the point here is the choice of EoS

Fig. 7.14: COMPARISON AMONG LIGHT-CURVES COMPUTED WITH DIFFERENT APPROACHES - *Solid and dotted red*: luminosity obtained with the full radiation-hydrodynamics evolution according to Eq. (7.4) at two different optical depths τ . *Dashed blue*: luminosity obtained from Eq. (7.10). *Long-dashed green*: luminosity obtained through the isothermal evolution approximation. See text for more explanations.

- The fluid is not in equilibrium with the radiation in parts of the numerical domain. In order to account for this, the assumption of LTE would have to be dropped. This is beyond the scope of the current tests.
- The optically thin regime cannot be treated which is why we plan as the next step to incorporate the variable-Eddington factor approach.
- Temperatures of order $T < 10^5 K$, as they appear in small regions of the domain, require the inclusion of bound-free opacities, which are currently not implemented.
- The only dissipative mechanism is currently thermal conductivity and radiation induced turbulence. Types of viscosity such as generated by magnetic fields would be beneficial. Coupling the current equations to MHD is a possible future step.
- Uncertainties in the luminosity computation: When an integral over the radial fluxes is performed then the result is only meaningful, if the flux scales as $1/r^2$ and the surface is spherical. Since we currently cannot extract in regions where the optical depth is low, we must trace a geometrical surface of constant τ . Thus, although our radiation flux scales as $1/r^2$ in the optically thick regions, we cannot extract an invariant observable number L which leads to high uncertainties. This also could be alleviated by incorporating the variable Eddington factor approach.

Having said this, it should also be mentioned that these tests were quite illuminating as to how sensitive these models are to small regions within the numerical domain, where stiff terms arise. It was for these patches, that we introduced the IMEX treatment. This brought us to the point where we can now apply our code to the full extent of its physical validity. The fact, that this implies a restriction to very simple tests is notwithstanding.

BHL models very sensitive to stiff terms

7.2 Summary and Conclusions

We have implemented and solved the equations of relativistic radiation hydrodynamics in the thermal, optically thick regime and on a fixed black-hole spacetime. As a first application of the new code we have considered the emission properties of a hot BHL accretion flow onto a black hole with the opacity given by Thomson scattering and thermal bremsstrahlung only. By considering different models with an ideal-gas EoS of adiabatic index $\gamma = 5/3$, and various sub-sonic and super-sonic regimes, we have found that the inclusion of radiation drastically alters the well known dynamics of BHL flows in all models considered. In particular, the system quickly enters a radiation-pressure dominated regime, characterized by mass accretion rates that, once stationarity is reached, decrease by one or two orders of magnitude with respect to the purely hydrodynamical evolution. Nevertheless, the measured accretion rates are found to be always super-Eddington and as high as $\dot{M}/\dot{M}_{\text{Edd}} \lesssim 140$. This is in agreement with the expectation that the Eddington limit should hold strictly only in spherically symmetric flows. Another observation was that the effective adiabatic index in the radiation pressure dominated regime becomes that of a photon fluid, i.e., $\gamma_{\text{eff}} \sim 4/3$ and that the radiation can prevent the reversal of the shock cone that is typical of BHL flows with low Mach numbers. The *flip-flop* instability was not observed in any of our models, only at the shock reversal did we see a short, transient behaviour somewhat reminiscent of this instability.

By computing the emitted luminosity through a surface integral over the radiative fluxes at the last optically thick surface, our approach has allowed a more self-consistent computation of the light-curves for the BHL flow, finding luminosities $L/L_{\text{Edd}} \lesssim 1$. These results have been found to be independent of the initial conditions chosen for the intensity of the radiation energy density. However, the uncertainties of the luminosity estimate are between one and two orders of magnitude.

We studied the physical applicability of the current thermal, optically thick approximation and found that in the BHL model (i) the fluid and the radiation are not in equilibrium in shocked regions, thus violating one of our basic assumptions and (ii) that the only dynamically important variables are the radiations quantities once radiation pressure exceeds fluid pressure.

We also addressed the numerical problem of stiff source terms; proposed a numerical treatment, implemented and verified it. As we chose an IMEX Runge-Kutta scheme, we needed to isolate the principal stiff parameters which were found to be the (density-weighted) opacities (cf. Chapter 3).

We then revisited the BHL accretion in 2D for an astrophysical, dynamical problem. Here, we could show that (i) the IMEX scheme allows us to evolve models with realistic choice of parameters (ii) the dynamics of the flow are significantly and physically correctly affected by the radiation pressure, yielding again comparatively low accretion rates and Eddington limited luminosities.

Thus we conclude, that the current treatment cannot yet yield truly consistent results in anything but stationary solutions. It can, however, give order of magnitude improvements over pure hydrodynamics. Equipped with our stiffness treatment, we can now apply the code in all its physically reasonable parameter space and we can go forward to dropping some of the currently limiting assumptions.

SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This thesis explored the astrophysics of massive black hole binaries in a gaseous environment. Within the context of hierarchical structure formation, it was outlined how the formation and evolution of massive black hole binaries has become an established concept. It was discussed how black holes are thought to form and grow via accretion and mergers. This modern picture of galaxies, that harbour massive black holes in their centres was then confronted with current observational evidence, evidence from *electromagnetic* (EM) measurements that confirms the existence of massive black holes and leaves little room for alternative explanations. As far as dual black holes are concerned, we currently still lack definite evidence for their evolution into closely bound binaries. It was detailed that the fundamental reason for this is the absence of both theoretical understanding of the precise signatures such a close binary would have, as well as instrumental limitations of the currently operating facilities.

As we now live in an era of physics where we expect a new window into Space to open, the concept exploring this *gravitational wave* (GW) window at the low frequencies was introduced. Especially, the potential benefits of merging information from the traditional, the EM and the future GW observations were listed.

Talking about observing massive black hole binaries from the GW perspective, implies talking about either space borne interferometry with an instrument like *LISA* or radio timing observations of millisecond pulsars using *pulsar timing arrays* (PTAs). On the EM side, signatures are expected to be across all bands. This thesis was focused on sources of masses and parameters either for *LISA* or *PTA*.

After an introduction to the numerical methods used and developed for this thesis, a detailed study of the interplay between a binary black hole and its surrounding gaseous disc was presented. The secular evolution of the binary on its way towards coalescence was studied using Newtonian, high resolution simulations. The origin of torques from the gas onto the holes and the interplay between accretion and long range gravitational torques was investigated, finding that a prograde disc will excite the eccentricity growth in the binary leading to a saturation at high values. Accretion was found to be negligible in the context of eccentricity, however, for the binary shrinkage of the semi-major axis it was found to be at least as important as the gravity torques.

Hereafter, ongoing work on retrograde discs was presented and compared to the prograde case, where the most striking difference was the appearance of an instability at very high binary eccentricities. Here, current numerical data suggests that, if the gaseous disc is significantly clumpy, a reversal from the retrograde to the prograde scenario could replace the picture of unlimited, retrograde eccentricity growth.

8. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

Focussing then on the observational implications of the prograde disc scenario, the consequence of having a high, limiting eccentricity was explored. As potentially important for *LISA* data analysis, the residual eccentricity at band-entrance was calculated and found to be non-negligible. Further, the expected eccentric source population to be seen by *LISA* was derived comparing stellar environments against gaseous environments. It was found that there is the possibility of using residual eccentricities as a discriminant between stellar and gaseous binary environments, in addition to spin-statistics. For supermassive sources, the thesis presented one of the first studies of multimessenger astronomy with *PTAs* addressing current and forthcoming instrumental constraints. It was found that especially the X-ray band could be used for finding counterparts to a GW source. We identified periodic variability and double $\text{Fe}K\alpha$ lines as two promising signatures that can be realistically targeted by MAXI, eROSITA and an *Athena* like X-ray experiment. Also for *PTA* sources, we contrasted stellar versus gas driven binary evolution scenarios with respect to the expected eccentricity population resolvable in band: mild to high eccentricities are expected for both environments. While the employed models are yet too uncertain as to safely conclude whether or not these distributions be discernible, this result has impact on *PTA* data analysis, which currently does not yet include eccentric source models.

Treating black holes as Newtonian point masses is justified only when looking at large scales. However, key ingredients in the numerical treatment of smaller scale gas dynamics around compact objects, are radiative transfer and *general relativity* (GR). It was explained why radiation is inherently difficult to include in a numerical scheme and proposed a strategy for taking at least leading order effects into account in full general relativistic hydrodynamics. Owing to the fact that the current standard formulation employed in these codes demands a special treatment in the time integration, a *strong stability preserving implicit explicit* scheme was adapted to solve the stiff, optically thick, coupled radiation hydrodynamics equations in GR. The scheme was implemented, verified and applied to spherically symmetric, transonic accretion flows. Encouraged by the good agreement of the acquired results with older, more detailed works, this thesis showed the first two dimensional global simulation of general relativistic fluid dynamics dynamically coupled to a photon field. As the problem of choice, the Bondi-Hoyle-Lyttleton accretion was studied in detail. For any EM luminosity computation, there is a clear advantage of having photon fluxes intrinsic in the numerics rather than post-processing superimposed emission models a posteriori. However, it was shown that the developed approximate treatment still has limitations such as its inability to consistently account for the essentially non-thermal nature of shocks and that these limitations lead to uncertainties when extracting EM luminosities. It was concluded that the inclusion of coupled fluid radiation dynamics is necessary and possible in full GR, but that there remains much to be improved.

Results presented in this thesis have impact on low frequency gravitational wave data analysis, on searches for supermassive black hole binaries, on the development of more realistic numerical treatments of relativistic accretion flows and some of the results on secular evolution of binaries in discs could possibly be applied to stellar and planetary migration astrophysics.

Parts of this thesis have been published in [Roedig et al. \(2011\)](#); [Sesana et al. \(2012\)](#); [Roedig & Sesana \(2012\)](#); [Zanotti et al. \(2011\)](#) or submitted in [Roedig et al. \(2012\)](#), [Roedig et al. \(2012\)](#).

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Constanze

We shall not cease from exploration,

and the end of all our exploring

will be to arrive where we started

and know the place for the first time.

T.S. Eliot

APPENDIX

A.1 Extended geometrized system of units

The definition of geometric units of time and lengths is obtained by setting the speed of light c and the gravitational constant G to pure numbers. This implies that seconds and grams of the cgs system can be written as

$$1\text{ s} = 2.997924 \times 10^{10} \left(\frac{1}{c} \right) \text{ cm} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$1\text{ g} = 7.424157 \times 10^{-29} \left(\frac{c^2}{G} \right) \text{ cm}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Within this general setup, a convenient unit of space is still required. The cm is of course a bad choice and the gravitational radius $r_g = GM/c^2$ is instead chosen. In order for this new unit to be convenient with respect to the centimeter, the mass M of the system has to be sufficiently large. From the physical value of the solar mass and from (A.2) we find the relation between the cgs units and the new unit of length r_g

$$1\text{ cm} = 6.772289 \times 10^{-6} \left(\frac{M_\odot}{M} \right) r_g, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$1\text{ s} = 2.030281 \times 10^5 \left(\frac{1}{c} \right) \left(\frac{M_\odot}{M} \right) r_g, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$1\text{ g} = 5.027854 \times 10^{-34} \left(\frac{c^2}{G} \right) \left(\frac{M_\odot}{M} \right) r_g. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

It is also useful to explicitly write the conversion of rest-mass density and luminosity between the two systems, namely

$$\rho_{\text{cgs}} = 6.1776 \times 10^{17} \left(\frac{G}{c^2} \right) \left(\frac{M_\odot}{M} \right)^2 \rho_{\text{geo}}, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$L_{\text{cgs}} = 3.6292 \times 10^{59} \left(\frac{G}{c^5} \right) L_{\text{geo}}, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where ρ_{cgs} and ρ_{geo} (as well as L_{cgs} and L_{geo}) are the pure numbers expressing the mass density (as well as the luminosity) in the cgs system and in the geometrized system, respectively. In the traditional geometrized system c and G are set equal to unity. However,

for specific physical applications where very low mass densities are encountered, the corresponding value of ρ_{geo} may become prohibitively small. For this reason, it is convenient to assume a smaller value of G , such as $G = 10^{-10}$.

In geometrized units, thus the Eddington luminosity and the Thomson scattering opacity of electrons read:

$$L_{\text{Edd}} = 3.4636 \times 10^{-22} \left(\frac{c^5}{G} \right) \left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \right), \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$\chi_e^s = 3.628 \times 10^{22} G \rho_{\text{geo}} \left(\frac{M_{\odot}}{M} \right). \quad (\text{A.9})$$

The extension of the geometrized system of units to the temperature can be obtained by setting to a pure number any physical constant containing the temperature. In this thesis we have chosen to set $m_p/k_b = 1$, where m_p is the mass of the proton, while k_b is the Boltzmann constant. In this way the temperature is a dimensionless quantity and the transformation of the temperature from the dimensionless values to Kelvin is given by

$$T_K = 1.088 \times 10^{13} T_{\text{geo}}. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

In these *extended* geometrized units the radiation constant $a_{\text{rad}} = 4\sigma/c$ becomes

$$a_{\text{rad}} = 0.191495 \left(\frac{1}{G} \right) \left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \right)^2 r_g^{-2}. \quad (\text{A.11})$$

A.1.1 Entropy generation rate

In the framework of Eckart's formulation of Relativistic Standard Irreversible Thermodynamics (Eckart, 1940), the entropy current is given by

$$S^{\mu} = s\rho u^{\mu} + \frac{q^{\mu}}{T}, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where q^{μ} is the heat flux, s is the entropy per unit mass, and T is the temperature of the fluid. The heat flux is given by the relativistic form of Fourier law, namely (Israel, 1976)

$$q_{\mu} = -\lambda T (h_{\mu}^{\nu} \nabla_{\nu} \ln T + a_{\mu}), \quad (\text{A.13})$$

where a^{μ} is the four-acceleration of the fluid, λ is the thermal conductivity and $h_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} + u_{\mu}u_{\nu}$ is the projector operator in the space orthogonal to the four-velocity u^{μ} . Under the assumption that the fluid has vanishing shear and vanishing bulk viscosity, the entropy-generation rate that follows from (A.12) and (A.13) is given by

$$T \nabla_{\mu} S^{\mu} = \frac{q^{\mu} q_{\mu}}{\lambda T}. \quad (\text{A.14})$$

We recall that the thermal conductivity is related to the opacity. For instance, the thermal conductivity computed using the ordinary diffusion approximation of stellar interiors is given by $\lambda = (4/3)a_{\text{rad}}cT^3/\chi^s$ (Schwartz, 1967). Under the assumption that the matter plus radiation fluid behaves as a single fluid with effective pressure and energy density given by $P_{\text{eff}} = P + \mathcal{P}_r$, $e_{\text{eff}} = e + E_r$, the four acceleration a_{μ} can be computed from the Euler equations as

$$a_\mu = -\frac{h_\mu^\nu \nabla_\nu P_{\text{eff}}}{e_{\text{eff}} + P_{\text{eff}}}. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

When quasi stationary configurations are reached, the terms containing time derivatives can be neglected with respect to those containing spatial derivatives, and after replacing q^μ into Eq. (A.14) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_\mu \mathcal{S}^\mu \approx & \frac{\lambda}{T^2} \left[(g^{rr} + \Gamma^2 (v^r)^2) (\partial_r T)^2 + (g^{\phi\phi} + \Gamma^2 (v^\phi - \beta^\phi / \alpha)^2) (\partial_\phi T)^2 + \right. \\ & 2\Gamma^2 v^r (v^\phi - \beta^\phi / \alpha) \partial_r T \partial_\phi T - \frac{2T}{e_{\text{eff}} + P_{\text{eff}}} \left((g^{rr} + \Gamma^2 (v^r)^2) \partial_r P_{\text{eff}} \partial_r T + \right. \\ & (g^{\phi\phi} + \Gamma^2 (v^\phi - \beta^\phi / \alpha)^2) \partial_\phi T \partial_\phi P_{\text{eff}} + \Gamma^2 v^r (v^\phi - \beta^\phi / \alpha) \partial_r P_{\text{eff}} \partial_\phi T + \\ & \left. \left. \Gamma^2 v^r (v^\phi - \beta^\phi / \alpha) \partial_\phi P_{\text{eff}} \partial_r T \right) + + \left(\frac{T}{e_{\text{eff}} + P_{\text{eff}}} \right)^2 \left((g^{rr} + \Gamma^2 (v^r)^2) (\partial_r P_{\text{eff}})^2 + \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. (g^{\phi\phi} + \Gamma^2 (v^\phi - \beta^\phi / \alpha)^2) (\partial_\phi P_{\text{eff}})^2 + 2\Gamma^2 v^r (v^\phi - \beta^\phi / \alpha) \partial_r P_{\text{eff}} \partial_\phi P_{\text{eff}} \right) \right]. \quad (\text{A.16}) \end{aligned}$$

The conversion of $\nabla_\mu \mathcal{S}^\mu$ from geometrized units to cgs units is given by

$$[\nabla_\mu \mathcal{S}^\mu]_{\text{cgs}} = 1.0353 \times 10^{31} \text{ Gc} \left(\frac{M_\odot}{M} \right)^3 [\nabla_\mu \mathcal{S}^\mu]_{\text{geo}}. \quad (\text{A.17})$$

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